

SUMMARY

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“A Technological civilization is programmed by the principle that something ought to be done because it is technologically possible. If it is possible to build nuclear weapons, they must be built, even if they might destroy us all. Once this principle is accepted, humanist Values (something has to be done because it is needed by man) are dethroned and technological development becomes the foundation of ethics’ Eric Fromm, Father of political psychology.

‘God is an organism with a mind called logos...’ (Plato) of a logic higher than man’s (Augustine)

“It has become appallingly obvious that our technology has exceeded our humanity. “Einstein
‘I had a nightmare. I dreamt with a man who asked me nicely to give him Crispr CAS-9; (to edit genes). Then he turned. He was Hitler.’

Jen Doudna, recipient of the 2020 nobel prize for his discovery of Cas-9, the system likely used to edit coronavirus, a molecule that bacteria manufacture to edit viruses that carry any viral gene injected on its 5D jail structure, locates it and cuts it, allowing the automatic pegging of a different RNA or DNA gene in the same location by a ‘repairing RNA-DNA strain’. The system makes genetic editing from simplest viruses to humans as easy as a ‘word editor’ – the name given by professionals to it, opening in the 2010s the Pandora Box of ‘viral chimeras’, even if our technological civilization will by principle deny its mishandling and only herald its medical uses.

“A system that reproduces faster has a higher chances to survive” *Darwin, 4D Biology*
“A system closer to the ideal superorganism has a higher chances to survive.” *L&S, 5D Biology.*

Abstract: We study the coronavirus crisis with the tools of 5D sciences, within the context of the age of History in which it is inscribed – the age of singularity black swan technologies, born in the last period of the Industrial r=evolution, the ‘chip radiation’, when technology not only has exceeded mankind but its negative consequences for our life standards and future will be felt increasingly obvious.

But as we live in a technological civilization that worships machines, without even defining them in scientific terms, we will play constantly with the dual fruits of the tree of metal – deny the lethal consequences of technology, and once those black swans come ‘easy’, as entropic=destructive technologies are easier to produce, we will paradoxically increase our reliance of technology to ‘save’ us from them. In the process mankind will be weakened as a species, while the stick and carrot machines of higher AI l’spatial’ intelligence and destructive ‘temporal’ entropy become the true protagonists of History.

The coronavirus takes this process long in the making to new heights, as ‘not infectious robots’, ‘safe virtual work’, ‘safe e-money’. ‘virtual streaming’ even ‘safe masturbation’ substitutes real human social contact. So the constant displacement of humanity by the machine, of the family by the company-mother, of governments by informative metal-communicators, of human welfare and GDP by corporative welfare and machine GDP, of human labor by self-productivity (mechanical labor/human labor-> ∞) will continue with the acquiescence of society, since all technologies are first implemented for the ‘common good’ and only when they multiply without limit become used routinely for the control and herding of populations, which loose skills to the new technologies that substitute them in labor and war fields...

Update. Abstract.

We publish in March this rather complex review of what already in our 1992 book, 'the extinction of man', we considered to be one of the 3 risks of extinction of mankind, all coming from 'lower scales of the 5th dimension of space-time', with 'faster' speeds of reproduction hence able to kill mankind: Biological faster reproductive 'virions' and metal nano-bacteria imitating them (Genetic risks); Self-feeding nuclear 'cosmic bombs', black holes and strangelets made of heavier quarks that reproduce exponentially and can be made in accelerators of the next plasma generation cheaply or now at CERN, which will provoke a Nova Explosion of Earth (Nuclear Risk) and Military AI and AI in general which is displacing with the robotic r=evolution humans from labor and war fields. The Genetic risk came and provoked with the evolution of genetic manipulation tools the present pandemic. The Nuclear risk is total extinction, and will happen at the speed of a nuclear bomb reaction, so when it happened it won't be chronicled. It just will take the world down. Hence its researchers cannot be blamed. The third risk is the slow process of atrophy and substitution of huminds by metal-minds and it is obviously already affecting our children. All of them will proceed for the profits of Technological industries. And all those risks are censored in peer reviewed magazines. So the suicidal species will go ahead without even talking about it, because in a capitalist society go(L)d and the machine are the supreme goods.

This said, we have a much wider view and consider the 'entropic' extinction age of mankind unless the miracle of a change of culture or economic r=evolution happens, but we have preached for 30 years without results such changes, deterministic, as most process of life and death of organisms, in this case mankind. So we dedicate 3 final pages to the entropic age of History and the Earth, one to each of those risks:

- The genetic risk of the present pandemics is this paper.
- The Nuclear risk, which considers the Nova explosion of Earth is 'metal-earth and entropy'. Disclosure: I was the lead plaintiff of the suits against CERN in 2008.
- The AI risk is natural to the age of Robotics that also started in 2008 after the crash age of metal-minds, and we forecast according to the 80 years cycles of the evolution of machines on that old seminal book.

In this paper we thus study first the 5D risks and specifically the risk of genetically engineered viruses. We proposed the view that while a mixture of a pangolin and bat virus is highly improbable as those 2 species do not mix in Nature (pangolins are 3000 kilometers, away, perfectly protected with scales to avoid bites of ants and hence impossible to be bitten by bats, which do NOT even try), what is impossible is to introduce a 3rd complex mutation of an ACE-2 key specific of humans and make nature mutate dozens of proteins but it can be engineered.

Recently new papers have come, decrying the total censorship of peer reviewed magazines to studies on the engineering of the virus, and a detailed analysis with the same thesis we published in march – no rocket science, any student of biology knows it was engineered.

We then focus on the aspects we care more on those papers, namely the model of the organism of history and how a proper design of mankind could have cured the sickness as opposed to a capitalist, technoutopian society that won't. And notice the 20 billion \$ plus gained in stocks and similar quantities in vaccines by big pharma. And the nobel prize given to the first breakthrough on virus editing, the crisprs-9 molecules. So it is OBVIOUS that as all other LETHAL RISKS to mankind things WON'T go away, but will continue. And so now we have as we feared for 30 years the society nightmare of a world increasingly inhuman, with pandemic risks, Nuclear extinction risks, and 'safe' 'clean' AI robots and Nuclear Industries making a killing with its tech companies passing the trillion \$ mark.

This is the future till we become extinct at the end of the century, by the combined power of the 3 GNA risks unless a change of economic system and science from mechanist technoutopian to organic 5D takes place. But as we cannot even publish in peer reviewed magazines (I have been vaporized for the thoughtcrime of denouncing CERN along all my work in 5D for more than a decade one. My name means a paper even does NOT enter peer review) there is no chance. The FMAsters, Financial-Media-Academia industry and its machines of information thus will ensure scientific censorship kill us all, happy and ignorant on why and how we could have made History immortal.

STATUS	ID	TITLE
EA: Not Assigned	BJPS-2020-182	The fifth dimension View Submission
Reject - Inappropriate		

KEY 5D LAWS OF SPACE-TIME ORGANISMS APPLIED TO HISTORIC CIVILIZATIONS.

5D metrics: A 4D world of time lifecycles embedded in 5D hyperbolic, organic scales.

In the graph, the organic, network structure of the whole Universe defines a series of 'hyperbolic' cellular scales that make the organism NOT the mechanism, the basis of all Nature's system.

Mathematically then it is necessary to find a metric function to define this new dimension of spacetime. Since a dimension only exists when we can write a mathematical simple metric that leaves the dimension invariant when we change our parameters of space and time - hence we travel through it. (Klein). So we write:

$$s^2 \text{ (Lineal Size/ Volume) } \times T_f \text{ (cyclic frequency=speed of time clocks) } = \Delta \pm j: 3 \text{ Co-existing Planes of timespace.}$$

It means an organism co-exists symbiotically in 3 scales of $\Delta-1$ parts, (cells, atoms, human beings), joined by $\Delta\emptyset$ networks of energy and information (electromagnetic and gravitational fields; blood and nervous networks; political and economical systems), $\Delta\emptyset$, in a larger $\Delta+1$ world; (gravitational, thermodynamic, social system), because its parts are symbiotic.

In 5D metric, smaller systems in space have faster time clocks that store more information in the frequency and form of its cycles, coding larger wholes: genes code cells, memes societies and particles code atoms and molecules. But larger wholes are stronger envelopes, membranes (static, dimensional view) or angular momenta (dynamic view as time=motions) which enclose and control in synchronicity its faster smaller parts. They also have more 'scales of Δ -energy'. So they exchange energy for information with its parts, through 3 Δ^0 T-motion, Δ -Energy & S-informative networks that travel through the 5th dimension, harmonizing the co-existence of organic scales whose vital Universal constants are 5D metric ratios of information & energy exchanges. Thus the Universe is a nested, fractal 5D superorganism that organizes 'vital spacetime forms with motion' through networks into larger organic systems that emerge as new planes of STjence, from particles into atoms, molecules, cells, matter states, organisms, solar systems & galaxies. As each new 'ST-organism' becomes a 'fractal point' unit of a new '5D space-time network'.

The outcome is the organic structure of all physical, biological and social systems, from History coded by memes, ideas and instruments that create human social organisms, civilinations, to physical systems coded by particles and scalar, 'social numbers' and algebraic equations, whose 'operands' code the different 'Dimotions of spacetime', to biology coded by genes. And so we shall use the same laws of 5D scales of space-time to study every stience of the Universe and its superorganisms defined by the symbiosis in space, synchronicity in time and simultaneity in space of its parts and wholes across 3 of those 5D scales, the $\Delta-1$, atomic, cellular and individual scale, the Δ^0 , thermodynamic, organic and social scale, and the $\Delta+1$, gravitational ecosystemic and global scale of physical, biologic and social systems.

But how do your travel through those hyperbolic scales of the 5th dimension. Simple: growing in 'size' in space while decelerating the 'speed of your time cycles, through the worldcycle of life and death.

As all systems of the Universe are born in a smaller seed with faster time cycles, evolve as an organism coming out in the Δ^0 -scale within a larger world of slower 'Deep time cycles', to die back dissolving our information again into cellular space.

It is the same process in all 5D journeys of all species that live and die travelling through 3 planes of 5D space-time; from the smallest black hole that is born with an enormous 'metabolic temperature', to the new species, routinely born as small individuals (first mammal rat, first robots with small chips; first human likely the Homo Floresiensis, who had the same morphology and used technology and likely spoke, etc.) Then a reproductive radiation multiplies the seed into a larger herd of clones, joined by emergent physiological networks whose slower 'entropic, informative and reproductive networks, create an Δ^0 supørganism that lives 3 st-ages and dissolves back into $\Delta-1$.

5D metric is then used to analyze with the same laws, all scales of space-time each one studied by a stience, whose species are made of 3 relative elements: Δ -scales of Space=Form & Time=Motion:

In mathematics Non-E fractal points of Space grow in lines=networks; 3 of which form a topologic space-time plane=organism. Numbers represent Δ -scalar groups and Algebraic operands Time motions.

In physics Δ ST is proved because its 3 elements correspond to its 3 conserved quantities: S=angular momentum, T=lineal momentum & 3 Energy forms, $\Delta-1$: Internal, $\Delta\emptyset$ -kinetic & $\Delta+1$ potential energy. Thus ST: 2 |+O momenta integrate into $\Delta+1$ work=energy: $\int p=E$ or dissolve=derivate into the ∂p =Forces scale.

In biology we travel through the 5th dimension of scalar space & cyclical time by growing organically in 'space size' through cellular/atomic/social networks 'while slowing down the 'speed of our metabolic time cycles, which is exactly what happens in the worldcycle of life and death of any universal species as all are born in a smaller seed with faster time cycles, evolve as an organism emerging as a bigger Δ^n network organism, to live within a larger $\Delta+1$ world of slower 'Deep time cycles', to die back dissolving its information back into its lower cellular/atomic $\Delta-1$ plane; from the smallest black hole born with a huge 'metabolic temperature' (Hawking), to the new species, born as small individuals (1st placental mammal shrew, first digital brain=chips; 1st modern human brain, Homo Floresiensis). Then a reproductive radiation multiplies the crystal, DNA cell or species creating an Δ^0 supœrganism that lives 3 ages of growing information till death dissolves back into $\Delta-1$ ($\Delta-1$: plasma>T-gas, S=T-liquid, S-solid states « $E=mc^2$).

Organic worldcycles happen in all stiences. They define the key system of reality, an Δ ST Supœrganism whose simultaneous parts in space become synchronous in time, across 3 5D scales, the $\Delta-1$, atomic, cellular and individual scale, the Δ^0 , thermodynamic, organic and social scale, and the $\Delta+1$, gravitational ecosystemic and global scale of physical, biologic and social systems, whose metrics allows the symbiotic transfer of spacetime energy made of cyclical information and lineal motion. As all scales have the same value and properties, hence the Universe is absolutely relative.

Thus space laws are Topologic laws that put together 3 type of networks: |-moving limbs/fields> \emptyset -reproductive waves/bodies & O-informative particle/heads.

Time laws study life-death worldcycles that evolve $\Delta-1$ seeds into $\Delta\emptyset$ -organisms made of those 3 topologies that 'age' in 3 ST-ages dominated by each network till the S-head exhaust all motion and a 'fast' entropic=death dissolves its information into an Δ st 0-sum.

Finally $\Delta\pm j$ scalar laws study Δ -energy exchanges thru $3\pm j$ 'Actions' of Tt-entropic feeding, Ts-motion, $\int T$ -reproduction, St-information & Ss-mind mirror languages that revolve and project order in a larger $\Delta+1$ world. Those are the Δ ST-events & forms of space-time described by each species in each stience. This is a very brief, condense 'synopsis' of the many sides of 5D stience, we expand in the appendix and all other papers at Academia.edu, in case you want to understand it better. We are though just interested in giving you a feeling of this new r=evolution of stience, as we apply it to the study of the scales .

Unfixable' boot ROM security flaw in ...

Chemists Design New Compounds That ...

Massive Black Hole Mystery Solved Wit...

GNA RISKS. AND THE GOEBBELS METHOD IN THE CHILDISH AGE OF ENTROPY

According to 5D metrics, $\$ \times T = C$; the smallest species in space, reproduce faster in time and win in the struggle for existence. The biggest existential dangers for mankind do not come from larger forms, national struggles or the global warming of Earth but from efficient species co-existing with us in lower planes of space-time, whose 'reproductive and evolutionary radiations' fast outpace human capacity to contain them.

Why this law is so important? Because it balances the survival and symbiotic existence of all parts of the Universe, and all parts of a super organism, and defines 'what codes information' - the small being, and what codes energy- the larger whole, establishing the 'harmony' of all the scales of the Universe, and explaining all its fundamental constants which are ratios between spatial volumes and informative clocks of time.

In what concerns the coronavirus, the importance as in all other existential crisis of humanity is obvious: In the organic Universe smaller is more powerful, because it is faster in time actions of reproduction and evolution that define the struggle for existence according to Darwin's dictum:

"As many more individuals of each species are born than can possibly survive; and as, consequently, there is a frequently recurring struggle for existence, it follows that any being, if it vary however slightly in any manner profitable to itself, under the complex and sometimes varying conditions of life, will have a better chance of surviving, and thus be naturally selected. From the strong principle of inheritance, any selected variety will tend to propagate its new and modified form." The Origin of Species

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In the graph the 3 top predator species of the economic ecosystem (chips, robots, AI), the biological ecosystem (coronavirus) and its nano-technologic replicas (metal-viruses, 'virons') and the matter, galactic ecosystem (black hole, strangelets), which have become with the advance of technology (electronic industry, Crsprs-9 genetic editing, high energy accelerators) the 3 key existential dangers for humanity in the XXI c.

As an activist who has tried for decades to denounce those existential risks with little results due to the egoc (Ego=idiocy) of mankind, the coronavirus crisis did not surprise me. It was expected and yet it is of the risks poised by lower $j-1$ planes of existjence, the less dangerous for humanity.

The top predator species of matter, a baby black hole or heavy quark strangelet, if reproduced by the industry of accelerators would take a few hours to destroy Earth, feeding at light speed in the matter of this planet. The chip radiation and all its applications are making obsolete humans in labor and war fields. And its application to the design of nano-bacteria, able to eat metal and reproduce its form would mean the extinction of the planet by a grey-goo in 3 months. Finally the top predator of life, a viral coronavirus, which mixes the killing efficiency of the SARS species and the maximal expansion rate of the Universe (a perfect exponential $e=2.8$ speed of propagation). As we consider the extinction of the planet Earth by Strange matter or black holes in the paper 'Entropy and the metal-earth), and the extinction of man and life by the chip radiation the paper 'Entropy and History'), and we are living now in the present lesser crisis of a perfect genetic virus in its 3 'Space-time elements' that conform any function of life, (maximal $\$T$ =speed of reproduction and infection; maximal St =genetic charge of any virus and maximal Ts -strength of its invasive spike membrane).

So 2 5D elements essential to the coronavirus and future existential crisis: the exponential growth of smaller 5D systems of a lower plane of existence.

And the technological dangers of living in a society whose 'free market citizens', companies, have the right to evolve and reproduce any technology regardless of its lethality for mankind. Since an efficient social organism, as humanity could be if social scientists, '**doctors of history**', ruled and designed her according to the laws of organic systems, should not go through those risks for 2 obvious reasons:

- As a single global organism, aware of the 5D laws of existence, humanity would avoid any encounters with those species, meaning the Industry of Accelerators would be banned from testing big-bang production of strangelets and black holes; the Chip industry would be limited to simple models, below the capacity of human beings to control them, and its most lethal species (military and working robots) that make humans obsolete banned. And genetic engineering (Crsprs-9 technology) that makes possible to enhance any lethal virus by editing-into it the most destructive genes of other sub-species, repressed.

How does mankind face those risks is obvious: with 'egocy: ego=idiocy' which is infinite to our species, due to its complete misunderstanding of the biological, organic nature of the Universe and its 'network intelligence'. In brief, it has no intention under a capitalist system of 'lineal time thought', who believes the species is 'entitled' and has a special place in the Universe, and it is the only intelligent form, etc. etc. to forbid any of those technologies. And if something wrong happens it will accuse always Nature.

This was my experience in the activism and suits against CERN for its attempts to make strange matter and black holes on Earth. The whole point is they could not be blamed if the catastrophe happened. Or as the American West Pacific Supreme court who closed the suits (CERN alleged as a cold war European institution diplomatic immunity), 'the destruction of Earth won't be attributable to the American Government' – so the existence of a virus with the qualities of SARS and flu will never be attributed to bio-logic research or else we would have to forbid 'genetic editing' with its enormous 'benefits' for the pharma industry. Fact is since Crsprs-9 exists there have been editing of viruses all over the place. Specifically in the late 2010s a team from the Wuhan virology Institute engineered a hybrid virus, combining a bat coronavirus with a SARS virus that had been adapted to grow in mice and mimic human disease. The hybrid virus was able to infect human cells... This we know. What we do not know are biowarfare similar experiments taken place in the leading nations of the field, US, China and Israel. We know also that to make some extra-money Chinese concerns sell to markets for meat, the monkeys and animals used in experiments – even rats that are consumed in that country.

From science, a paragraph that explains it all: "The WIV lab, along with researchers in the U.S. and Switzerland, showed in 2015 the scary-good capability of bat coronaviruses to thrive in human cells. In that paper, which was published in 2015 in the journal Nature Medicine, they described how they had created a chimeric SARS-like virus out of the surface spike protein of a coronavirus found in horseshoe bats, called SHC014, and the backbone of a SARS virus that could be grown in mice. The idea was to look at the potential of coronaviruses circulating in bat populations to infect humans. In a lab dish, the chimeric coronavirus could infect and replicate in primary human airway cells; the virus also was able to infect lung cells in mice.

That study was met with some pushback from researchers who considered the risk of that kind of research to outweigh the benefits. Simon Wain-Hobson, a virologist at the Pasteur Institute in Paris, was one of those scientists. Wain-Hobson emphasized the fact that this chimeric virus "grows remarkably well" in human cells, adding that "If the virus escaped, nobody could predict the trajectory," Nature News reported." So if it happened almost 10 years ago, with new capabilities, and UNLIKE the SARS which has a 98% civet virus from where it could have derived, NOT a single virus with a degree of similarity to be the only source of the COVID-19, why NOT a single paper defends the more likely thesis of a chimera? Obviously because peer pressure makes impossible in modern mankind to blame anyone, any technology, given the astounding egocy of man.

Update. The new canonical article on artificial creation.

A few months after we published this article, it came a work from 3 chinese scholars far more detailed which essentially says the same: *The ace-2 key CANNOT be created by nature, and it has been put it on a 'bat base' and pangolin add on. It even detail the procedures in a lab to make it happens with all the detailed processes involved:* https://zenodo.org/record/4028830#.X9R_sq2B3MU

This is the abstract:

The COVID-19 pandemic caused by the novel coronavirus SARS-CoV-2 has led to over 910,000 deaths worldwide and unprecedented decimation of the global economy. Despite its tremendous impact, the origin of SARS-CoV-2 has remained mysterious and controversial. The natural origin theory, although widely accepted, lacks substantial support. **The alternative theory that the virus may have come from a research laboratory is, however, strictly censored on peer-reviewed scientific journals.** Nonetheless, SARS-CoV-2 shows biological characteristics that are inconsistent with a naturally occurring, zoonotic virus. In this report, we describe the genomic, structural, medical, and literature evidence, which, when considered together, strongly contradicts the natural origin theory. The evidence shows that SARS-CoV-2 should be a laboratory product created by using bat coronaviruses ZC45 and/or ZXC21 as a template and/or backbone. Building upon the evidence, we further postulate a synthetic route for SARS-CoV-2, demonstrating that the laboratory-creation of this coronavirus is convenient and can be accomplished in approximately six months. Our work emphasizes the need for an independent investigation into the relevant research laboratories. It also argues for a critical look into certain recently published data, which, albeit problematic, was used to support and claim a natural origin of SARS-CoV-2. From a public health perspective, these actions are necessary as knowledge of the origin of SARS-CoV-2 and of how the virus entered the human population are of pivotal importance in the fundamental control of the COVID-19 pandemic as well as in preventing similar, future pandemics.

And this is the key concept, exactly the same we deduced – no rocket science.

To engineer and create a human-targeting coronavirus, they would have to pick a bat coronavirus as the template/backbone. This can be conveniently done because many research labs have been actively collecting bat coronaviruses over the past two decades^{32,33,70,72,81-85}. Once they have chosen a template virus, they would first need to engineer, through molecular cloning, the Spike protein so that it can bind hACE2. The concept and cloning techniques involved in this manipulation have been well-documented in the literature^{44-46,84,86}. With almost no risk of failing, the template bat virus could then be converted to a coronavirus that can bind hACE2 and infect humans⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶. Second, they would use molecular cloning to introduce a furin-cleavage site at the S1/S2 junction of Spike. This manipulation, based on known knowledge^{60,61,65}, would likely produce a strain of coronavirus that is a more infectious and pathogenic. Third...'

So the whole process is clear-cut. And what we wrote in march here is now in great detail analyzed in that article. But the issue we insist is part of an age of entropic extinction of history, in which machines are processing our species what we call in our history articles...

The domestication of mankind: loss of all 'survival instincts'.

We quote from our earlier book, what really is going on here from the large view of history and the 3 GNA risks, the domestication of mankind that does not have any longer survival instincts

Darwin explained the 3 traits of the domestication syndrome: neoteny=infantilism, loss of Intelligence & survival instincts (docility). *Those are the 3 traits of mankind in the age of Metal-minds so we have to accept humans have become domesticated by company-mothers & its machines & weapons, to become its workers=reproducers and vitalizers= consumers the only 2 jobs humans had in the eco(nomic)system, now made obsolete by AI robots that consume and reproduce other machines. So as all 'domesticated' species, animetals will be disposed off in Orwellian fashion without resistance in new wars, Holocausts or by GNA lethal technologies (Genetic editing of virions and virions, Nuclear cosmic bombs- strangelets, black holes or AI machines. But children do NOT understand death. So they reject the truths of 5D social sciences and its r=evolutionary, survival solutions, since only huminds intelligent and brave enough with Max. Δ+i: social evolution & information could control and made History immortal".*

Extinction of Man, Bookmasters, 92 L§

RECAP. THE AGE OF BLACK SWANS. CHRONICLE OF A DEATH FORETOLD.

The coronavirus pandemic is the 2nd lethal 'black swan' of technological evolution that can destroy mankind. At the turn of the century, those lethal 'smaller species' were the 3 classics of activism against existential risks to mankind, the 3rd horizon of nuclear weapons (strangelets and black holes that devour matter), Genetic engineering and metal-bacteria,

and AI and military robots. I participated intensely in those debates and became the main plaintiff of a series of suits against CERN, the center of research in strangelets and black holes that might blow up the planet into a Nova. That was the 'first black swan' and it did not materialize, but it didn't either go away. China is planning a 100 km.

accelerator that certainly will make them. This is the question about black swans: as technology advances the chances of a black swan to appear in history increases, the moment and place is not known, the probability grows. It is like the famous Scrodinger's cat paradox. It is the cat dead or alive? If he has pressed the trap and a poison felt he is dead, if the poison didn't fall it is alive. *But the experiment is misleading, because a nervous cat the longer he is inside the trap, the more often it will press the trap and so if the first chance is 50-50%, after 2 touches it will be 75%-25%, after 3 touches, 87.5% and after 4 touches, it will be 93.75%, which in verbal terms means 'most likely' the cast will be dead. The singularity black swans of the XXI century, due to the evolution of technology which is our ethic religion, are of this fashion. None will go away, all will increase its chances as technology improves and facilitates those happenings; and every time scientists touch the trap chances will grow.*

The first singularity black swan seems now dormant till the Chinese complete its accelerator, unless CERN gets lucky and makes a USDUSD dibaryon that grows into strangelet. The schrodinger's cat has been acting on that first black swan as the graph shows (growing amount of dibaryons formed), but we are still here. The second black swan, the genetic virus did happen and of course as in all religions, the evilness of technology is denied. So it was a natural cause. The 3rd black swan is the most popular, as it has been played in sci-fi, but won't be discussed in real science: AI, robots, Internet awakening as the brain of a Universal organism. Each of those black swans however has a natural occurrence within the laws of evolution of superorganisms which are isomorphic in all scales. Considering for example the last one, which seems the most exotic fiction: the awakening to consciousness of the metal-earth=capitalism as a collective brain of neuronal computers. It is the natural end of the 3 ages of the Earth's evolution. Gaia (Life Earth) <History (Human Earth)> Metal-earth (AI machines)

You see, this is the equation of the 3 ages of a ferromagnetic planet parallel to all other 3 physiological ages. In the first age, the planet is a watery planet made of life beings, similar to a soft larva that feeds in plants. But then History starts, and nerds act as enzymes, catalyzing the evolution and reproduction of machines and weapons, as its company-mothers terraform the earth to its image and likeness. It is the chrysalis age of the larva, when enzymes inside start to evolve the harder parts of the insect. In the last stage, the chrysalis makes the brain of the insect; as nerds make a brain of computers called the Internet; and then the cryssallis brain makes a stronger type of enzymes, as nerds make robots with AI chips. Then something weird happens in both, the planet of nerds and the pupa; both new brains, the pupae and the internet become alive, showing an increasing nervous activity, and they throw the new hard enzymes and AI robots against the soft enzymes and the nerds, killing them all, substituting them in cellular factories. So life becomes extinguished. The process is extremely fast, within the last day of the pupa, the last cycle in slower time on the larger planet of the Industrial r=evolution, a human generation of 80 years, once the internet is born, all forms of nitrolife become extinguished, and the new race of robots takes over and that is the moment in which the butterfly comes out of the pupa and takes off in its reproductive flight trying to mate and spread its genes. So do robots, that will increase the speed of reproduction of robots, infect the entire planet and send probes to other planets, spreading the infection through the galaxy.

So the last ages of the chip radiation, the age of the singularity black swans that now has started and the moment of extinction of humanity are natural st=ages of the evolution of Earth, from History into the mechanocene that only an intelligent, humble organic human species who did know the laws of the organic Universe could have halted. As this is not the case, chances are slim.

THE AGE OF ENTROPY IN HISTORY

‘Only to death (max. Tt), God (Max. Ss) and the Sun (Max. S=T) you can’t look at its face’ Rochefoucauld

The equation of death in 5D systems.

Unlike in physics, where there is only one arrow of time-future, entropy=death, due to the simplification of the infinite time cycles and clocks of the Universe into a single coordinate of lineal time, to create reality you need to time arrows, which with less or more rigor in its definitions, humans have called ‘entropy and information’, ‘yang and yin’, ‘shiva and visnu’, ‘motion=time and form=space’. This final definition is the one I established back in the 2000s when I was chair of duality in the International Systems Sciences society annual congresses, during for a time I tried to explain 5D metrics and duality to scientists. The definition is essential to understand the complex structure and multiple layers of time cycles and different speeds of time clocks in the Universe. Why information must be added to the mix? Because a ‘cycle’ needs at least two dimensions, the lineal time or ‘locomotion and entropy’ proper of physics, but a height dimension of form, of information. So when you look at this screen or paper you realize its information requires ‘two dimensions’, with the added dimension of height. This second dimension of height-information however has not been understood by humans for long because it requires a slow rhythm of time to ‘grow’. You can move fast and even faster you can explode your internal form moving all over the place your parts, in a big-bang of death=entropy. But to create information, slow time rhythms are required. Evolution grows the height of information from reptiles that became dinosaurs and then birds, to humans that became mammals, to machines that evolved into metal-minds and spread its information through antennae. But that took often many generations. Death though is fast. And so if we talk of two poles in the Universe: $S \leftrightarrow T$, minds and languages that code and make information grow, vs. fast Time-motions that bring entropy and disorder, while both are balanced, one takes long, it is the arrow of life, of information, of creation, of evolution, of height. And the other takes very short time, and it is very obvious because it is explosive, sudden, a cliff of death, the arrow of entropy, of war, the crash of a stock market, the breaking of a crystal. And yet because humans and life belong to the arrow of information, paradoxically, while they are fully aware of the death arrow, they neither understand it because they fear it so much, they can’t look at its face.

Yet to understand death is vital to avoid it – *you have to look at its face*. In 5D we do have an equation for the 3 entities you cannot look at its face; one because it is immanent, invisible, illogic, it is God, the Game of Existence, Ss, the pentalogic of all languages, the other opposite to it, is the game of extinction, entropy, death, the sudden disorder in a single quanta of ‘time’ of both the internal and external motion of an organism. In the jargon of 5D we talk of the Universe as a game of space=form/information and time=motion, and between those two poles, $S \leftrightarrow T$ everything happens. But the two extremes, the ‘seeds’ and ‘minds’ that imprint with information the energy of reality, and the Tt-entropic death that kills and erases information *have different asymmetric speeds of creation*. The creative process of imprinting the ‘energy’ (S=T), of existence in the human case given by the sun (the third maximal ‘standing point’ of the function of existence, to use the jargon of 5D, we can’t look directly) is very slow.

It takes 9 months to make a child, and 20 years to grow it up. But death, entropic big-bang explosions happens in the minimal quanta of Time of a being, when expansive-motion is maximal. So it takes a second to die, a second to kill that child in war, with the entropic iron-weapons mankind uses to kill. ‘Only entropy comes easy’. To break a glass takes a second to manufacture far longer. A Second is the time quantum of mankind – the time of a step, a beat of the heart, a thought, a glimpse of the eye. It is the synchronizing quantum of your organism’s 3 parts, your Ts-limbs of locomotion (external T-motion, internal form) your S=T-body of energy that balances both and your St-head (external form internal motion or information). The graphs show 2 of the many cases in which we can consider the opposite periods of the two main arrows of ‘spacetime’, Tt-entropy, which are cliffs of destruction that last briefly in time (left stock market growth, right death periods), while the longer periods of slow growth are soft curves *which last longer in time so they balance the total spacetime equation of the immortal universe: $S \leftrightarrow T$* . This physicists ignore as they only consider the big-bang cliffs of death=entropy, and inversely people ignore as they only consider the slow periods of growth of information (Life arrow).

Even the most simplifying physicist knows that entropy comes easy, the arrow of time of destruction is much faster than that of creation. And that explains why death comes in a quantum, in a second of human time. But whenever we observe a system of nature, we find entropy coming easy, in any scale of reality.

In 5D larger systems have deeper time, so they are slower. This is the essence of 5D 'metric', already noticed by Hutton, the father of geology that said Earth was a living organism. He invented in fact the term superorganism to qualify the Earth. And he said his deep time is slow in its cycles. So it is a quantum of time for the Earth, instead of a second a day. A day is the synchronized time of its smaller life forms, its cells that replicate every other day. All those synchronicities between the parts of superorganisms that 4D science doesn't even research – they are doing still doodles in the sand of time with its physical worldlines, matter here to the case of the coronavirus pandemic and all the other lethal 'smaller technological systems' that menace mankind: we develop technologies but entropy always come first. We develop nuclear forces but the A-bomb came first and in a second killed 200.000 Japanese. The nuclear power plant took 10 years more and even then Chernobyl take a few hours and it killed by leukemia 200.000 more people. We developed genetic editing and a 30 genes virus has broken human civilization. It will take much longer to edit 30.000 human genes to create superman. The first species in Nature are always top predators. The first eye was the squid, the nautilus and it killed the whole cambrian fauna triggering the Cambrian diversification and the trilobite defensive system. The first fishes were sharks and they killed every other fish. Man started massacring all fauna and the first AI machines will be terminators as always the first machines have been bombs and weapons. This mankind ignores. Only entropy comes easy because the arrow of death is asymmetric and is much faster than the nurturing arrow of creation. And that is why the tree of technology, the tree of metal, wrongly called the tree of science will kill mankind. But man ignores it, and it is impossible to teach him this obvious fact. So with time I have come the conclusion that man is an enzyme that catalyzes the evolution of lethal machines in a single generation, the age of the singularity black swans weapons that complete the 3 generations of bodies, engines and heads of metal now ensemble in organic weapons. One generation of humanity thus will destroy earth's life. Hutton's deep time of 3 billion years.

This paper in nested 'degrees' of Δ -'scalar depth', 'T-ime latitude', 'S-patial range', and '@-linguistic complexity', is dedicated to the present --entropic STage of History, the age of the 'Coronavirus', part of the age of 'black swan' singularities – accidental global catastrophes derived of the 'ethics of a technologic civilization' and the inverse arrows of time, as 'entropy comes easy' (Chekhov) and so technological advances of the bad and good fruits of the tree science comes easier as 'bad=death fruits'. To understand this age we thus need to 'widen our horizons' to the present cycle of the economic ecosystem – part of the age of the chip radiation, when metal-minds vastly out power human capacity and evolve ever faster new top predator machines=weapons; part of the age of the 'Industrial r=evolution' of machines catalyzed by 'human homunculus enzymen' who worship them, with its idol-ogies of metal (nationalism=worship of weapons, mechanism=worship of machines and capitalism=worship of go(l)d) and so cannot recognize its evil-antilive fruits. The language of english – an expansion of comprehension of the bio-logic laws of the Universe and History is needed to try to expand your consciousness of the biological laws and ages of history.

Within it the chip radiation the age of black swans is unfortunately the entropic age of the larger worldcycle of the Human Superorganism in time or 'History'.

For that reason this paper as all other papers on the '33 books' that conform the 'Encyclopedia of 5D Stiences' have 3 lengthy introductions to 5D stiences and the organic Universe, to the nested superorganism of history and to the 'Dimension of entropy', which is the one of disorder and death we live in.

This is needed because what passes as 'truth' and 'science' today is a primitive 2nd 'mechanical age' of the scientific method, after the Greek, experimental age whose zenith was Aristotle, to which Galileo added machines to measure time (clocks) and space (telescopes & microscopes), but *without a formal evolution of the causal A->B logic of time and understanding of the 5D fractal scales of space. So this upgrading of the logic of time to the pentalogic causality that creates reality departing from its 4 elements, Space, time, scale and language, denied by the limits of entropic death; and an upgrading of Non-Euclidean mathematics to define a fractal point with 'parts', which 'holds a world in itself' Leibniz, and the related concepts of space=form and time=motion, of which we are all made is needed. Indeed, the egocy of man (Ego=idiocy) fascinated by its*

machines of measure seem NOT to understand that the humind has evolved very little since the Greeks, in fact in the audiovisual age of machines devolved from 'cogito ergo sum' to 'vidi, credo ergo sum', the previous e-motional age of magic and religion; so what the 3rd age of science, the age of the 'organic method', which as the previous ages started by Aristotle and Galileo needs to collapse first into a 'mind-point-particle' means is a vast reorganization of that data obtained with machines, the 'details' of the laws of spacetime organisms, made to the image and likeness of i-logos, the organic mind of the Universe, you might call God – the game of creation and extinction of those superorganisms, of which mankind is one..

We DO need to reveal those deeper truths a bio-social-organic language proper of bio-history, itself one of the stiences of the 'organic paradigm' of the Universe, , the 3rd Stage of 'science' as the search for 'truth' with all the available languages of humind's thought, $P(\text{truth})=1$ (the §T-organism) > \sum Linguistic mirrors > Mathematical language > Logic Language > E-motional Magic thought.

All this will sound Chinese to you, but we can't escape the purpose of this blog which is to evolve humind's thought and analyze reality with the 5D laws of the scalar, organic, nested Universe, of which Earth is a smaller superorganism, in which Mankind acts as its 'surface membrain', or collective brain, between 3 ages of its evolution:

Gaia (relative past: life) < History (relative present: Mankind) > Metal-earth (relative future: machines).

This equation can be written in 5D \rightarrow logic in time as a equation of 3 ages of increasing information, Gaia>History> Metalearth and will invariably end in the extinction of humanity, past the 3rd age of any superorganism, and that is the final entropic state: History <<Metal-earth and the ultimate meaning of the 'Entropic singularity age of black swans' we live today, and just have started, as 3 are again the ages of this entropic time, the age of Singularity nuclear weapons (black holes and Earth's big-bangs), the age of reproductive virions and viron (life viruses and metal-bacteria) and the 3rd informative age of AI-robots and metal-earth's consciousness.

However or else I wouldn't even bother to write this encyclopedia of stiences, given my personal circumstances, the 'time equation' of the 3 ages of a superorganism can be written into a space-present equation of immortality, just by *changing the dynamic symbols of ilogic $d=\text{evolution}$, <, > between the ages of time, which transforms the equation into a present superorganism, by limiting; the entropy of youth and the evolution of information towards a 3rd age that invariably ends when energy is exhausted into an entropic reversal of death, by a symbol of devolution of information:*

Ts (entropic youth) > §T (energetic, reproductive maturity) > St (informative 3rd age).

Which is the equation of the 3 ages of life, becomes then an equation of present, when the last > symbol of ilogic informative growth becomes by changing the symbols to < devolution:

Ts (limbs/fields of motion) < §T (energetic body-wave) < St (informative particle-head)

So then in this version of the trinity fractal generator of events and forms of time-space, time becomes space, the unbalanced limbs/fields and particle/heads SERVE with its function=form the present §T-feminine balanced stage of reproduction, as limbs/fields move the body-wave and heads-particles inform it, transferring them motion and form, which paradoxically means, limbs/fields slow down and particles/heads loose information and the body-wave combines them reproducing a new form. This is the marvelous trick of the essential equation of immortality: $Ts<\S T>St$.

This trick of existential ilogic, when achieved by any superorganism - and many do:

In physics an ∞ number of immortal atoms that do the trick. In biology a few simple organic herds, every system that reproduces into a clone equal system, some life organisms that revert its clocks of time and rejuvenate its old cells with excess of information. Among humans at mind level (as the nervous system of information keep warping and wrinkling along the skin, our vital body-space, too evolved to stop), are able to forget their tail of excessive past information and angst. Finally some, civilizations like the classic Chinese culture, the closest one to understand the yin-formation, yang-entropy game of reality, repeated its cycles after destroying its dynasties, and suppressed negative technologies (gunpowder) stopping the evolution of weapons, and if the west had NOT existed to go back with a vengeance, it would have likely achieved immortality.

So this is NOT just a theoretical exercise. If humans repressed the chip radiation and forbade the triad of extinctive technologies we have been denouncing for decades:

Youth-entropic age of cosmic bombs (strangelets, black holes) < reproductive age of vir(i)ons> 3rd informative AI Age

They could make history immortal. But for that the homunculus enzyman and its mechanical worship of technology should evolve science into stience, A-logic into i-logic, Euclidean maths into non-E maths of fractal points, respect and understand the organic, sentient, immortal, infinite Universe and then the Universe would respect him and granted him life. This is not happening anytime sooner. On the contrary the homunculus enzyman is determined to follow the ethics of technological civilization with a single mind thought and repressing any attempt to make a more complex reading of reality and history, guided by what we shall call ‘aniemtal cultures’ of Germanic tribal warriors, parasitic biblical bankers and techno-utopian nerds... That is the worshipers of the tree of metal that confuse science with the mechanical method and cannot understand the complexity of the organic tree of life and man as the most perfect superorganism we know of, the measure of all things, the beliefs of my Greek-Latin-Spanish culture will kill us all as that is the manifest destiny of its idol-ogies and you cannot change their feeble minds, egocy and doodles of the sand of the so-called idols of its tribe of mechanon scientists, one Mr. Newton, one Mr. Einstein, one Mr. Hawking, one Mr.... you name it... Minions of thought. And I said enough. Frankly... ‘2 things I deem infinite, the Universe and the stupidity of man’, said one of them father of the A-bomb. He was right.

In this paper thus we shall study the wrong cultures of mankind in their response to the singularity event of the coronavirus and contrast them with the right measures of the organic paradigm and its closer organic civilination, that of Asia, to show indeed what is our manifest destiny ruled by the mechanon civilization of the Anglo-American world: extinction, soon. Unfortunately this is now a global civilization and so only r=evolution would spare us that certain death.

THE PENTALOGIC CAUSAL ELEMENTS OF A 5D Δ\$T ANALYSIS OF THE CORONAVIRUS.

Thus there are 2 languages we use in this paper to explain the Coronavirus pandemic; 5D stience which is a rigorous, objective ‘stientific’ analysis of the event with the formalism of 5D and a simpler language to discuss the sociological aspects of it. To state finally that as in all papers on 5D social sciences, history and economics I have no agenda but the ‘higher truth’ of the 5D organic Universe. The fact that such higher truths show our social systems to be ‘sick’ and inefficient, is an unwanted outcome of 5D social sciences, which in this crisis os showing its faults crystal clear.

5D Systems sciences are based on the alternative philosophy of science to that of mechanist physicists and its only entropy arrow, called organicism. Let us try to explain why only organicism is a scientific truth.

According to *Deism* the whys of existence are due to a personal being, external to the Universe that makes it all happen and cares for humans more than for the rest of His work. According to *Mechanism*, this is due to the self-similarity between the Universe and the primitive machines we humans construct to observe it. Mechanism though needs ‘someone’ to make the machine, which is not self-generated; so it is similar to deism, reason why the founding fathers of science, all pious believers, adopted it as a proof of the existence of God, which had given man self-similar properties – the capacity to make machines to the image and likeness of the Universe. The problem with those 2 approaches, which in fact are the same is obvious: a personal God is an anthropomorphic, subjective myth and science must be objective; while a mechanical view of the Universe still needs an internal, self-sustained process of growth, creation and synchronization caused by an external God that made and rewinds the clock – as Leibniz clearly stated in his critique of Newton.

Scientists today are unaware that mechanist theories are in fact deist theories, reason why Kepler and Newton, pious believers, liked them; since they were a metaphor of their self-centered, anthropomorphic religious beliefs: If

man created machines because we were made to the image and likeness of God, God had created the ultimate machine, the Universe.

Organicism on the other hand is the only self-sustained, rational theory that doesn't need a creator, language or god, as organisms are self-replicating, *but does explain perfectly within the 'correspondence principle', those 2 other philosophies of science; since a machine is just a primitive organism of metal, and in History, Gods are the subconscious collective of civilizations, ANOTHER scale of social evolution of the fifth dimension.*

3 elements, $\Delta\text{S}\text{T}$, are essential to the Universe and to any analysis of what happens there. They are:

$\Delta\pm j$: The scales of size that define the speed of the 'cycles of evolution and reproduction of species' an apply here right on to the coronavirus lethality, as it spreads much faster than humans react to it, and so we need to introduce the 5th dimension of scales and its metric equation that determines those speeds.

T-time: The cyclical patterns of time, as all clocks of time are repetitive so are the laws of science – merely the collection of repetitive facts.

S-space: The ternary topology of space that defines the structure of all systems as made of 3 elements, an 'informative brain' (the RNA in the virus, the brain in man, the capital and government in a nation), a hard membrane that isolates it (the crown spikes in the virus, the skin in man, the frontier in the nation) and a vital space between both that reproduces its goods and elements (the virus uses a host cell to that aim, the organs of man – its body – are our vital space, and the people of the nation are its vital space).

When put together $\Delta+S+T$ define a supœrganism of scales, in which smaller 'cells' are joined by 3 topologic networks that **act** as the informative network (brain, capital, RNA), reproductive vital network (blood, economy, host cell) and defensive, feeding, membrane network (guts, crown, health-care and military system of the nation).

Lethal technology: how humans create the future... in the stock-market.

Back in the 2000s when I thought I had due to the discovery of the laws of 5D a responsibility with mankind, I warned against 3 technologies that could extinguish us – the 3rd horizon of nuclear weapons (after A-bombs that can destroy a city, H-bombs that can destroy a country, quark bombs, which can provoke a nova and destroy a planet); AI military robots, and Genetic editing both of nitrolife species and iron nano-viruses 'virions and virons'. As usually because the machine is our religion and we are likely just enzymen whose task in this planet is to kill life and do mechanisms, I was ignored, and my suits as lead plaintiff against CERN and its quark canon ended my scholar career to the point my papers on 5D don't even get accepted for peer review in scientific papers. That was 2008, an then less than a decade latter crsprs-9 (graph^{nt.1}) was found as an RNA-protein 'head-body' tandem, the essential *intelligent micro-organism of the cell, with a Nitrogen mind and a strong body, able to edit any targeted part of a genome at will. It was then obvious that the warning will become realized and since virions are the easier genome to edit, virologists will edit a pandemic virion as they did (see paper on coronavirus crisis).*

Then what happened was expected: denial, censorship and when Luc Montaigne, the HIV virus discoverer and Nobel prize affirmed it was edited and the animal market origin a fairy tale, even the President of France came to deny. As AI has also progressed to 'teach with violent videogames', how to kill to visual robots, whose intelligence won't be verbal but visual as Tesla cars and SUVs is. So they will 'imagine' violent motions, as eyes are 'natural born killers' (already robots move faster with tracks painted on red-entropy colors). So now we have the 3 technologies of human genocide I warned against in my book 'the extinction of man', c.92. And, we can safely state we have entered the age of life extinction, with the 3 lethal events that can extinguish mankind, discovered, researched, encourage and funded.

This said Crispr and similar defensive collaborative systems in cells are a fascinating example of the symbiosis between 'DNA' Ss-languages, 'RNA' St-heads and 'protein ST - bodies' in human cells, to liquidate a Tt> ST virus, as the grah shows.

Unfortunately the coronavirus has no 'memory' in the cell. So it is a top predator $\Delta-2$ case, another proof of 5D metrics of scale that remind us of humind's egocy and the fragility and evanescence of $\Delta+1$ slower less fit species is the coronavirus, a pandemic so obvious to come, when we apply a pentalogic analysis:

- Ts: CV has the top predator membrane with 'spikes' that target and open lesser, weaker membranes of multicellular organisms. It is a hard protein with excellent 'Darwinian, perpendicular' penetration.
- St: CV has one of the largest RNA strands of the viral kingdom, with a perfect cyclical form for fast replication
- §¶: CV has the perfect 'e' number of contagion, 2,8, the fastest exponential growth, of nuclear decay, death dissolution of cells...
- Δ -j: the virus is the minimal unit of life, so the fastest clocks of replication, loading up to 100.000 in a single cell.
- @: its mind is a perfect, no-frills concept: to host, parasite and use the cell's mind to achieve its own dimotional goals.

Figure 20.14 Gene editing using the CRISPR-Cas9 system.

So I expected a pandemic from January on. Humans on the other side, understand nothing, egocy makes them not to plan the future or rather expect always the best from technology. Why? The answer is deeper in the entangled world in which money runs it all. It has to do it with the true brain that designs the future of this planet (see our papers on Metal-earth and capitalism): Money. Money today is overwhelmingly invented in stocks and e-money derivatives for company-mothers or reproduced by FED for banks to invest in corporations. But as all corporations are overpriced while humans die of anoxia – lack of money, its 'circulatory/energy blood/oxygen system', speculators = financiers MUST overprice the future as positive always for mankind, with a stratospheric price. So Internet companies, AI companies and bio-technological companies and weapon companies when all others fail and war becomes profitable are always positive, a wonderful future that allows to price them ad maximal. This is how since the XVII c. the future was create in the Jewish-Anglo-American 'capitalist' culture, with its 'wishful thinking', damned lies and statistics that make impossible any rational argument and control of the lethal goods of the future. Or else 'stockrats', the new aristocrats of capitalism could not sell Internet 'crapcode' companies for billions of dollars.

And park the trillions the FED reproduces NOT for the needs of people, and a demand economy base in welfare, but for the tiny 0.01% who control stock-markets, overwhelmingly in the western world that sets all trends, belonging to 'biblical segregational cultures' of believers in the supremacy of man and their people over Gaia, History and planet Earth. Then of course, reality bites, but the trillions of \$ created in stock valuation are already pocketed. Today AI has only 3 uses, 2 negative for mankind – state control and corporative control of data to deny health-care to the sick, isolate the poor in ghettos, policed preventively etc. While for machines it will be the increase autonomy from humans as 'robocars and roweapons' with solar skins become independent of us. But each new AI company that is floated is sold as the panacea of the future to print billions of \$ while people die of hunger.

This has obviously happened all over again during the coronavirus crisis in America, with a degree of cynicism, difficult to swallow for a humanist thinker,

which is rational and ethic and loves mankind despite so much criticism of its no way out 'capitalist' culture. Basically the crisis has been yet another excuse for the FED to print trillions parked in Internet companies that are now changing a notch further the dependence of humanity from Internet and AI machines. So we are a step further away from the ideal of 5D, immortal history, a perfect superorganism of humanity, where our species could survive and thrive at individual and collective level in a sustainable 'real world' – not a placebo world of activism such as global warming, paid for nuclear, solar and tech industries in search of subventions to make its AI robots independent also at energy level – it was indeed the nuclear industry that started those campaigns that will just multiply the wheat production as most cereal lands are in the northern largest land hemisphere from Dakota to Manchuria.

So nothing was done to prevent pandemics; nobody can argue the need to forbid genetic editing and I am in Spain, the center of contagion in Europe, taking a bus daily to get my bread. So if I don't make it, and the 5D project ends before completion, it will be a parable on the game of existence; I who saw the thoughts of God will be discharged by one of its lesser details. That is undoubtedly the destiny of mankind, call it a tiny black hole appearing at CERN or a tiny virus or a tiny iron metal-bacteria. Enzymes are discharged once they do their job. Humind's enzymes are about to complete it. But the coronavirus will pass and a younger, more erased, more technologically addicted, more lonely species, more dependent on machines will await its metal-bacteria 'closure'. A theme of 'Metal-earth and entropy' and other papers on the brutality of the capitalist cult(ure) of stockrats who invent the future on rosy falsehoods as the perfect excuse to keep printing trillions that in a perfect organism of History will be created as the oxygen-blood of organism as a Universal salary in ¥€\$ money, handled to every human being in a mobile cryptocurrency to create a demand-based economy. But that, which I proposed the only year I was given the chair of monetary systems at the international systems society, to explain what would be a perfect organic financial system, will not be. The greed of the 0.02% owns the world, and its only purpose is to find excuses to sell worthless paper, as they had done since they invented the first slave companies.

5D organic view of the Pandemic within 5D social system and the physiologic networks of mankind.

So what we are studying is an interaction of 3 scales of mankind and life, the cellular level in which the coronavirus attack with its faster 5D metric speed, the individual human level of citizens-cells that are murdered by the coronavirus and the physiological networks and governments of human nations, which are corrupted or inefficient, ill-designed by lack of understanding of 5D social sciences; reason why a simple virus that in an ideal society could have been easily controlled, is killing and destroying the life and economic systems of their societies.

This is the game in 5D 'terms'. THIS MEANS to make a definitive paper on the Coronavirus crisis, all the different 'sciences' of 5D would have to come together – if there were a proper understanding of 5D sciences.

So we introduce, Δ -scales (5D), topologic space, time cycles and languages of that define put together entangled superorganisms; and apply them to explain the coronavirus existential crisis of mankind. Once we learn the basics of each of those 5D elements we shall apply them to the multiple elements of the coronavirus crisis. Among them:

- The study of the coronavirus 3 topologies in space and functions in time to define the best cure strategies.
- The same study of human societies to establish how they should cure the disease.
- The analysis of the errors of societies that explain why certain cultures have done better confronting the pandemic. And the design of a better world where such crisis would never happen.
- The general model of existential risks of mankind, according to 5D metrics that makes paradoxically far more dangerous those risks coming from lower scales of reality.

There are then in this crisis as in an social science study, the interaction of the superorganisms at Δ -1 scale – the coronavirus and the cells which entangle to reproduce them, at the human scale, the human beings part of social systems, and at the planetary scale, the Earth and its globalization processes conducive to such pandemics.

THE Δ-1 SCALE: THE SECOND SINGULARITY SWAN: CORONAVIRUS

The wrong attitude of science and its incapacity to understand the duality of its good and bad fruits.

The first question we have to argue regarding the coronavirus is if it was genetically engineered. When the genes were sent from China at amazing speed, the most prestigious virologist, Nobel Prize and discoverer of the VIH virus, now retired Mr. Luc said the obvious: the virus was a quimera because unlike previous pandemics (SARs) didn't come from one single virus but it had parts of a strong bat virus, used in genetics as the strongest base over which to put other genetic characteristics; in this case the ACE-II key to human cells, similar but not equal to a Pangolin. Even if the virus from a bat who lived in China had infected a Pangolin who lived in a different environment in Malaysia it was impossible that the mutation was specifically acquiring from the Pangolin the precise gene the virus would need in a 3rd 'jump' to enter a human being (the ACE-II key). How did the virus infecting the Pangolin that would need its Ace-II key to then infect a human. Chances were null. So Luc said the idea it had come from an animal market was a fairy tale. The early interview was ignored by the press, censored by colleagues, because it meant the obvious fact that editing viruses is easier – 'only entropy comes easy' – and mankind had yet opened another Pandora box of technology it would not close again, and as a species had gone down the ladder of its self-extinction and destruction of its modes of life a step lower. And as we live in a 'technological civilization', the taboo against the parable of the tree of science that has bad fruits, and if we make them both we will 'die', was again triggered. Of course, we, the egocentric species do NOT make bad fruits, ONLY GOOD fruits. And the parable of Genesis is just a religious mantra, NOT the first intelligent dictum of a bio-historian who saw the Russian charioteers coming and destroy the Neolithic paradise with its bad fruits. I had been there all the time and didn't hold any expectations about how mankind would react in permanent denial, as the time to stop pandemic was when decades ago we did warn against the 3 technologies of extinction, Genetic manipulation, Self-feeding nuclear bombs and AI Chips. Now the 3 are exploding, companies make fortunes with them, and China that wants to be ahead of the XXI c. technological r=evolution with an excess of enthusiasm and null prevention measures is designing a 100 Km. accelerator, opened in Wuhan a virology institute and is ahead on AI control of populations, abandoning its millenarian culture of organicism and love of Nature, Taoism and respect for the living Universe. The Institute was also connected to an American institute of virology. And so you do have two candidates that are blaming each other ever since but NOBODY IS even suggesting that genetic engineering should be banned as the industry of accelerators should be banned and AI and military robots should be banned. Man is programmed for self-extinction.

Indeed, perhaps more telling was the fact that *both US and China blamed each other of the possibility of being engineered genetically, which means the capability to produce lethal virus with the characteristics of several different species has been there for sometimes, and as 'only entropy comes easy', the temptation to create a new species finally did it. But now the author is not giving it the proper name, 'Coronavirus Shiliensis' (If Miss Shi did it, the foremost expert on bat viruses at Wuhan), or something else, ts, ts.*

The second truism of the argument, is that 'geneticists' have a vested interest in not being blamed of a man-made virus, genetically manipulated, to continue with its livelihood and research, so they were all 'outraged' to the possibility it was a man-made virus and immediately got to the task to 'prove' this was not possible.

Their attitude reminded me the 'Safety report' of CERN regarding the possibility of making black holes and strangelets on Earth, made only by CERN researchers without the interference of an external commission of independent scientists, in which simply CERN affirmed there were zero risks to his experiments since strangelets do not exist (despite being the main candidate to compose the Halo of Galaxies – Witten Hypothesis, 5D astrophysics), and that black holes will evaporate, despite not existing any proof of it – a Hypothesis by Mr. Hawking that contradicts General Relativity and the 2nd law of thermodynamics, as a hotter black hole will have to get hotter in a cold environment – themes those argued on Metal-earth and Entropy. And immediately the global P.R.ess sided with their 'fringe theory', as the main laws of gravitation, Einstein's relativity and the totalitarian principle (anything that might exist will exist) said otherwise.

So goes for the coronavirus origin. Every article by geneticists comes with the a priori task of proving it has a natural origin, but none of the papers published about his origin in Pangolins has proved enough genetic similarity for such an effect. Indeed, the most publicized match with a coronavirus from Pangolins does not get even a 90% of genetic similarity – the article had to be corrected after paper review - which *obviously means it has no natural candidate, despite the massive research in any Natural coronavirus, since there has not been time enough for a genetic drift of more than 10%. Mutations are minimal, one at a time, and the time required for such genetic drift has NOT happened in the brief period between the chasing of Pangolins and its cooking in Wuhan eateries – not to speak of the fact the Wuhan animal market did NOT have pangolins.*

The kind of differentiation of the COVID-9 is clearly pointing at a genetic drift more proper of 'intelligent design', where huge portions of a given virus can be ensemble into another virus and once this is done there is NO possible way to prove the changes are natural or artificial as there is NO difference whatsoever. We don't find in the ensemble the stitch of the surgeon there.

So at best what geneticists can do is speculate. And still the process has been the same – eager scholars and eager press trying to downplay any chance we humans are using technologies beyond our capacities. So a single article has been published made just out of 'suppositions' without any proof, 'wishful thinking' and then categorical assertions to 'prove' the thesis it was seeking in first place, which the loud speaker of mass media extended globally – with the usual addition of the 'term' confabulation theory for anyone affirming otherwise.

So here we have it. We have developed a perfect tool for genetic engineering, but everything that is going to be bad and destructive from genetic engineering will come from Nature and all what will be good if anything will come from man. Because after all we are all good people who only use technology for the betterment of mankind.

*Fact is the Political and security groups of the American and Chinese government are accusing each other of creating the virus, because they have the technology to do it. Moreover mankind is "a Technological civilization programmed by the principle that something ought to be done because it is technologically possible. If it is possible to build nuclear weapons, they must be built, even if they might destroy us all. Once this principle is accepted, humanist Values (something has to be done because it is needed by man) are Dethroned and technological development becomes the foundation of ethics' – meaning in this case that as genetic editing OF VIRUSES is possible for a decade it is happening all the time. Indeed, virology research groups are mixing viruses now for a decade even if their papers after a few scandals and leaks of SARS viruses to the population are not published in peer review magazines anymore. And this is done with far more efficiency than the almost impossible chances for nature to make a 'triple combination' of features of 2 viruses and a human protein, needed for the coronavirus to target mankind. But this is only the beginning of a global explosion of genetic tools to engineer genomes including pandemic ones. Thus when the truth is so evident, our 'egoceny enzymen, who cannot 'come around' with the concept they are not geniuses but merely catalyze the evolution of metalife and the Universe is the organic genius, and renounce to its toys and supposed ingenuity, just forbid even to discuss the issue, with deleterious arguments, as to avoid 'social alarm', to defend 'peers' and 'science' and 'knowledge' and of course 'profits' of the huge bio-technological sector of big pharma and profitable start ups. So as when war starts, to criticize governments that started the war in first place is a crime of derrotism. Today in science to deal with the real deep, long time issue of all disciplines - the need to change our paradigm of knowledge in an organic Universe were nothing is invented, all is discovered and all has existed before, so the only true goal of an intelligent species is survival and the conservation=repetition of presents by aborting the 3rd informative age that brings death - is a no-no; as we are now going to be *defended precisely by the people who brought war and pandemic, the military and the scientist* (before war starts the people who tell us diplomacy not war is needed are called 'sissies', 'alarmists', 'apocalypto' etc.) This is the most surrealist part of the way humans deal with the catastrophes of History. Those who cause the catastrophes become the immediate heroes that will defend us from it, because obviously they are knowledgeable about it. So the*

military become the heroes once they start a war; and now geneticists who discovered, assemble the virus are our heroes.

And then it comes the ultimate 'stupid' form of censorship: because time is considered lineal and so there is no capacity to understand its complex cyclical organic patterns, the future cannot be foreseen and even less, transformed. This again is nonsense. In 5D the future is cyclical and knowing its causal patterns prevention can change those patterns. History can be made immortal. If man is a wekling idiot ego and cannot change its course of history, not even argued it, because it cannot tolerate 'talking truth', that is another matter. I can, so I do.

So we shall bring here the devil's advocate and consider those 2 elements of this tragicomedy, the first cold dish of the XXI century age of the singularity: the likely truth – a technological event, never mind which nation did it - that is the wrong questions; what did it is the wrong understanding of physiological history and the necessary repression by the immunological true system of mankind of lethal goods. Once we live in a capitalist system of free market company-mothers with the right to reproduce any lethal technology and clueless lineal abstract scientists with the manifest destiny to discover them and reject its organic lethal power, those events of the singularity age will happen, because they become extremely probable, regardless of the exact date, exact lab, exact citizen-cell and location within the global superorganism of history where they will strike us.

The most likely origin of the coronavirus

Missing Link in Coronavirus Jump ...

Thread by @bat1kgenomes: Dear #Bat1K ...

How did coronavirus break out? Theories ...

The simplest hypothesis is a man-made genetic recombination (quimera) of an specific gene of the pangolin, targeting a similar ACE-2 molecule, fine tuned to the specific human protein and inserted in a ultra-resistant bat coronavirus, then injected in human lab cells. Similar quimeras were produced before. It is happening in many bio-warfare labs and the Chinese have imposed extreme censorship on papers on coronavirus origin.

Now to be specific, a more serious analysis can be obtained from different genetic articles to define truly where the coronavirus comes from; and the answer is disquieting as it seems a clear combination of two coronavirus, which can be made perfectly in a lab, but not so easily in Nature, *because they belong to two different species, the bat and the pangolin, with a clear target in a third species, the human being.*

The SARS-CoV-2 genome is an RNA molecule with 30,000 bases for a total of only 15 genes, which is one of the highest numbers for a virus but very easy to decode for present genetic technology (our genome is decoded and has 3 billion bases and 30,000 genes). It was done immediately by Chinese, so those who think it has a Chinese lab origin can dwell on it. The key gene is

the S gene that codes the protein on the surface of the virus. The first articles thought to come from Malayan Pangolins and announced a 99% of equivalence eagerly wanting to be that case. Peer reviewed analysis downplay it down to the 90%. Why that interest for a pangolin 'natural origin'? Because the pangolin virus is the closest virus with a genetic region similar *but not equal* to the 74 amino acids of the Angiotensin Converting Enzyme 2 (ACE 2), *which is the receptor that allows the virus to enter human cells.*

And yet it cannot be its only origin because it has no enough similarity.

So where it is the closest similar virus that was used as the 'platform' in which to insert this modified specific ACE 2 region of the Pangolin?

The miraculous prescience of a virus in a sick bat flying to infect a pangolin then all will ensue to had The none, Crisprs-9 easy. It is who did got.

Mankind's Idologies deny it will die of GNA technologies it evolves to feel God As 5D absolute relativity make us just Dust of Space-time, Dust we shall become

sick with a different virus where both merged mutated this ACE-2 hypercomplex molecule at once to enter a 'future' Wuhanese who eat it 3000 km. latter; when Nature takes get each atom in place. Since the virus to mutate inside the living pangolin... probabilities of that chain of miracles are when just 3 cuts & pegs with CAS does the job fast & the technology it and a Nobel

ACE-key edited along a bat and Pangolin virus to make COVID

The gene for the spike protein in SARS-CoV-2 has an insertion of 12 genetic letters: **ccucggcgggca**. This mutation may help the spikes bind tightly to human cells — a crucial step in its evolution virus that infected bats and other species.
Problem there are 1 trillion possible combinations of 12 letters for a random mutation without human cut-pea intervention.

In the cave bat, which as all flying species that are submitted to strong stress and extreme conditions of life with higher metabolic rates in smaller body mass are the top predator chemical mammals – as birds are the top predator chemical reptiles, coming from old dinosaurs, living longer, with hot blood, etc. So they breed superviruses easily. The closest of those bat viruses to the coronavirus showed a 96% of equivalence. It was a betacoronavirus, the RaTG13. The problem is this virus has NO region to connect with ACE 2 in his genome so it cannot enter the human organism. So all indicates that the COVID-19 IS a genetic recombination between two viruses, the RaTG13 or one very similar from a bat and a pangolin virus or *rather the region of the pangolin virus* which is closer to ACE2 and can with a very small genetic modification (graph) open the ACE2 protein. This type of hybrid is called a Chimera and it is the kind of virus a biological lab can do with Crsprs-9 and similar more refined tools that have appeared just within a decade. You first make a modification on the Pangolin region to make it exactly to the human ACE 2. Once you have this done and tested, the Pangolin virus that opens the human cell is recombined with the bat:

You cut the piece of the Pangolin you need, and insert it into the bat virus, substituting its similar region; then you inoculate human cells and the process adjusts itself creating the coronavirus. This is already done in labs. To be precise if you prefer the Chinese origin, in Wuhan, there have been recombinations of viruses, then inoculated in HELA cells (the old cancerous black woman immortal cells used for those experiments), as earlier as 2013. Then when the scandal of those experiments reached media, there were an international suppression of those kind of papers. And today the suppression goes as far as any article on the origin of the coronavirus, which scholars in China complain must be revised by authorities that are trying to give a Natural explanation.

Problem is the logic of an artificial creation of the virus is far more realistic, given the simplicity of virus genomes, the easiness of its pegging, the available technology against the difficulty this happened by chance, because it requires 3 very different species which do NOT even have the same 'habitat'?

Indeed for Nature to have done this the bat from China should have infected the Pangolin from Malaysia, which is thousands of miles away. And how a bat from China infects a Pangolin from Malaysia, which is not living in the same habitat, do not eat the same food, cannot be beaten as it is perfectly protected with armadillo-like scales, etc. etc? Then they should have combined in the pangolin in the precise form of the coronavirus, 'thinking into a future human target', as the main modification on the 30 genes of the coronavirus IS in the ACE-2 key to the human organism.

Then it should have moved from this 'exact' pangolin that was infected from the bat, as a viable virus, to the human and then make a further modification in the protein to match exactly the ACE-2 key. In each of those steps a very difficult chance with minimal probability should have happened, regarding the exact recombination, the survival of the virus after entering the new species, the possibility of entering the new species, for an infection is of a single pangolin; the virus infecting the pangolin in an alien animal has limited chances of survival, the possibility that the quimera targets specifically a modification to enter the future ACE-2 human protein receptor is also minimal, etc. etc. Even the simplest of all those facts, necessary for the recombination to occur, that two completely different viruses from two different species infected a pangolin simultaneously are remote (obviously only sick pangolins have the specific coronavirus and only sick bats have the specific RaT virus; and both were likely thousands of miles away).

Chances that Nature have done this, are thus null compared to the easiness of an intelligent design in a lab, with the specific intention of opening the ACE-2 key.

In other words, it is a chimera between two pre-existing viruses. And yet to talk of a man made artificial genetic

a, Mutations in contact residues of the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein. The spike protein of SARS-CoV-2 (red bar at top) was aligned against the most closely related SARS-CoV-like coronaviruses and SARS-CoV itself. Key residues in the spike protein that make contact to the ACE2 receptor are marked with blue boxes in both SARS-CoV-2 and related viruses, including SARS-CoV (Urbani strain). **b**, Acquisition of polybasic cleavage site and O-linked glycans. Both the polybasic cleavage site and the three adjacent predicted O-linked glycans are unique to SARS-CoV-2 and were not previously seen in lineage B betacoronaviruses. Sequences shown are from NCBI GenBank, accession codes [MN908947](#), [MN996532](#), [AY278741](#), [KY417146](#) and [MK211376](#). The pangolin coronavirus sequences are a consensus generated from [SRR10168377](#) and [SRR10168378](#) (NCBI BioProject [PRJNA573298](#))^{29,30}.

design, which is already happening in labs, is an absolute taboo, especially in China, where new rules are set for any publication regarding the origin of the coronavirus.

When talking of all the potential lethal technologies mankind is developing in its existential final century, our egocentricity precludes that nothing bad can come out of it and if it does, we shall blame it on Nature. We seem to be a species defined by its entropic suicidal paths, which obviously we cannot recognize or else we would not commit suicide.

Indeed, the censorship on the Coronavirus, certain human genetic creation is based in the kind of military responses, once a politico has 'fucked up' diplomacy and started a war: 'now is not time to discuss this, it will put down the morale of the troop and create public alarm; we must all rally together'... and ensure it will happen again and again because it is not even discussed.

Peer-reviewed writers of course do not want to lose their position in the industry, and the common people, blind to all rational data, driven by emotions are easily manipulated into the 'rallying mantra'. That all other groups have come so selfish that will not defend mankind against this kind of occultation not to be subject to press ridicule and the on-slaughter of the 'profession' that did it, becomes the rule. As in the CERN cases or in future happenings of other 'black swan' singularity events mankind shows its true limits to survival. As an ostrich it rather does not discuss death but let it happen as long as it does happen fast and it comes unnoticed. 'The Sun and death, we cannot look at his face', said Rochefoucauld.

But it is now precisely when there should be an immediate research on the labs who hold viruses that could have been recombined both in US and China and expose it in print papers and discuss the possibility to forbid it.

This won't happen and as the second singularity event mankind is facing, the trend that the LHC at CERN established shows clearly mankind will not survive this century. So far we were lucky with the first event – there has not been yet production of black holes, and the second event. Whoever cut it and peg the two viruses it did not add the region of MERS virus that is truly lethal and could have put up to 30% mortality or the Ebola piece... So probably was just a nerdy researcher doing tests to 'learn more' without the intention to release the outcome; which is what scientists always do with the sacred excuse of the 'advance of knowledge' – another ridiculous theme in a Universe that is infinite, immortal repetitive and where there is nothing new under the sun. It is then worthy to see the 'twisted ways of thought' of our scholars in defense of their turf when they 'fuck' up and how easy the world 'sheeple' follows them, considering the only article everybody quotes as proof of its natural origin.

The legal question – Genocides MUST be researched.

What is truly unnerving for me, as a bio-historian with an ethic=social=survival view of reality is the fact that THERE IS NO INTENTION as it happened in CERN of investigating an action which likely by negligence has caused a global genocide, for the sake of defending science. It is the 'ethics of a technological civilization', so well explained by Fromm: "A Technological civilization is programmed by the principle that something ought to be done because it is technologically possible. If it is possible to build nuclear weapons, they must be built, even if they might destroy us all. Once this principle is accepted, humanist Values (something has to be done because it is needed by man) are Dethroned and technological development becomes the foundation of ethics'.

Eric Fromm, Father of political psychology.

It is what ensures that we humans will be=come extinguished by the singularity weapons of the XXI century, cosmic, organic self-feeding bombs, virions and 'VIRONS' (iron nano-bacteria) or AI military robots...

The article everybody quotes as proof that nature made it.

The article in defense of Nature's viral origin – 'The proximal origin of Sars-Cov-2 in Nature medicine' – is a masterpiece of what 'scholars' do better in rhetoric literature, to mix 'data' in their specific language, to impress the people, with weak causal reasoning, to twist data to their 'a priori' conclusions. As I had to fight a few suits trying to unveil the 'second element' – the faulty causal reasoning – of physicists on particles and big-bangs, I know the drill of this subtle form of lying: the science is factual in data, but explained in a form that people won't understand just to 'cause awe' and then the very same science exposed denied in a faulty causal language people do understand. So the game is to play with the rhetoric of impressing the audience and then twist the causality of truth. All this was already known to Aristotle, the sophists but I recommend the reader, as usual the master of modern philosophy nobody reads because his truths frighten them; Schopenhauer and his short book: *The Art of Being Right: 38 Ways to Win an Argument*

. As a 5D scholar, I can read any science so the first part does not impress me. The second one pisses me off as it shows how little 'ethic decency' scholarship has. Of course it is all the defense of your peers and tools of research NOT of mankind AND THE CRIME of genocide committed in the singularity events.

So no geneticists had dare to confront their peers and study the opposite case, and the accusations between American and Chinese security and military departments, who likely know better. This is a briefing from science daily, written obviously with a conclusion of innocence of their peers in mind; intersected with some comments from the author. We will escape a degree even lower on the lack of ethics – social collective instincts of survival in mankind – the 'tagging' with popular dismissive words of any true analysis of what geneticists are doing these days as 'confabulation theories, etc'. There is zero CONFABULATION THEORY here, but daily routine on the mimetic process of developing a technology whose dangers far outstrips its benefits and then using it 'liberally' as if those dangers would not exist because we are the 'chosen, omnipotent species' and we are 'goodies' and we 'use only for the good fruits the tree of science. This is the mantra. Fact is the Universe works EXACTLY IN INVERSE FASHION: 'ONLY ENTROPY COMES EASY' means any technology is far easier to use to create entropy than information. so entropy always comes first. it is easier to many a nuclear bomb than a nuclear plant. it is easier to use genetic tools to edit a virus that kills mankind than to edit a child into a superman, but humans only talk of the goodies. So for years we got all this chit-chat about editing children to be superman, but alas! we got a super-virus. For decades I have been hearing about 'God's particles and supersymmetry partners' but alas what is producing CERN in increasing numbers in each new experiment is more 'dibaryons' (USDUSD particles that are seeds of strangelets). So ENTROPY comes first. As it is easier to edit 30 genes that 3 million. Alas for good measure for those who get impressed by scientific chit-chat, we show from that article the astounding simplicity of the viruses genetic make up all in an image. The reader can see below all the 'elements' of this chimera, mixing Bats, pangolins, Sars and Human molecules, which Nature would have never done so fast so causally. But the researcher likely had no bad intentions JUST WAS USING VIRUSES PRECISELY because it is easier to decode and mix; as CERN doesn't want to blow the planet, just blows up particles because it is the simplest way to study its debris... So it did NOT add a MERS or EBOLA killing genes. So this is the article in a nutshell.

"The novel SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus that emerged in the city of Wuhan, China, last year and has since caused a large scale COVID-19 epidemic and spread to more than 70 other countries is the product of natural evolution, according to findings published today in the journal *Nature Medicine*.

The analysis of public genome sequence data from SARS-CoV-2 and related viruses found no evidence that the virus was made in a laboratory or otherwise engineered."

"By comparing the available genome sequence data for known coronavirus strains, we can firmly determine that SARS-CoV-2 originated through natural processes," said Kristian Andersen, PhD, an associate professor of immunology and microbiology at Scripps Research and corresponding author on the paper.

In addition to Andersen, authors on the paper, "The proximal origin of SARS-CoV-2," include Robert F. Garry, of Tulane University; Edward Holmes, of the University of Sydney; Andrew Rambaut, of University of Edinburgh; W. Ian Lipkin, of Columbia University.

(: Here we have them, 5 scholars in a mission 'firmly determining' a natural cause :)

Coronaviruses are a large family of viruses that can cause illnesses ranging widely in severity. The first known severe illness caused by a coronavirus emerged with the 2003 Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) epidemic in China. A second outbreak of severe illness began in 2012 in Saudi Arabia with the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS).

On December 31 of last year, Chinese authorities alerted the World Health Organization of an outbreak of a novel strain of coronavirus causing severe illness, which was subsequently named SARS-CoV-2. As of February 20, 2020, nearly 167,500 COVID-19 cases have been documented, although many more mild cases have likely gone undiagnosed. The virus has killed over 6,600 people.

Shortly after the epidemic began, Chinese scientists sequenced the genome of SARS-CoV-2 and made the data available to researchers worldwide. The resulting genomic sequence data has shown that Chinese authorities rapidly detected the epidemic and that the number of COVID-19 cases have been increasing because of human to human transmission after a single introduction into the human population. Andersen and collaborators at several other research institutions used this sequencing data to explore the origins and evolution of SARS-CoV-2 by focusing in on several tell-tale features of the virus.

The scientists analyzed the genetic template for spike proteins, armatures on the outside of the virus that it uses to grab and penetrate the outer walls of human and animal cells. More specifically, they focused on two important features of the spike protein: the receptor-binding domain (RBD), a kind of grappling hook that grips onto host cells, and the cleavage site, a molecular can opener that allows the virus to crack open and enter host cells.

So far nothing new, a mere description of the pandemic and the fact we have the genetic sequence of the virus.

Evidence for natural evolution

The scientists found that the RBD portion of the SARS-CoV-2 spike proteins had evolved to effectively target a molecular feature on the outside of human cells called ACE2, a receptor involved in regulating blood pressure. The SARS-CoV-2 spike protein was so effective at binding the human cells, in fact, that the scientists concluded it was the result of natural selection and not the product of genetic engineering.

This first conclusion is already an astounding case of rhetoric anti-truth: if a coronavirus from an animal which has no relationship with a human being enters a human being, it will have a hard time to randomly mutate its spikes to made them 'so effective at binding the human cells'. Mutations are random, so for a virus to achieve that feat with so perfect specificity to a human protein in such short time period is difficult. Yet for intelligent design is not. The geneticist can insert the ACE2 protein code into the genetic charge of the virus, and voila! We have the COVID-19. So the conclusion is exactly the opposite of the 'wishful thinking' of our geneticists: chances such specificity is achieved in such a short time is a clear proof of an artificial origin.

This evidence for natural evolution was supported by data on SARS-CoV-2's backbone -- its overall molecular structure. If someone were seeking to engineer a new coronavirus as a pathogen, they would have constructed it from the backbone of a virus known to cause illness. But the scientists found that the SARS-CoV-2 backbone differed substantially from those of already known coronaviruses and mostly resembled related viruses found in bats and pangolins.

This is wishful thinking: "If someone were seeking to engineer a new coronavirus as a pathogen, they would have constructed it from the backbone of a virus known to cause illness." Why? The Subjunctive 'would have constructed' denotes a mere wishful thinking on the way of procedure of the unknown researcher. This is NOT at all a proof but a supposition without the slightest proof.

It shows also the 'cold-hearted' evil view the writers have of mankind. As it clearly means that they think if a human had done it, it would have been to kill the maximal people and use an Ebola or Mers virus to massacre the species.... Something someone indeed can do in the future as nobody has even the intention to discuss the prohibition of genetic editing... But human tragedies don't work like that. Evil is infantile and accidental. Even Hitler did not want really to go to II World War, but expected the Allies to let him take ½ of Poland as he had done with Checkia, to avert war. Humans 'make bets' and expect as entitled egocy paradoxes, self-centered in their point of view that nothing wrong will happen 'to them'. As in other recorded editings of viruses for 'the sake of science', is likely this editing most likely done in a virology institute of China was just meant to 'explore' perhaps 'medicines against viruses', or just 'learn more about editing', etc. So obviously it was chosen a 'virus that was not lethal to mankind'.

On rational terms also the thinking is wrong: since the *element decisive in the capacity of the COVID-19 to provoke sickness is the fact that it can insert the ACE-2 protein through its Perfectly Mutated New Spike to enter the cell – once inside its replication will ensue automatically and provoke a sickness; ANY coronavirus in which the ACE-2 protein code is inserted will become a pathogen, even if it was not so before.*

Thus any coronavirus can be used as a platform to add the 'key to ACE-2 protein'.

If it were a natural mutation, the mutation would have happened precisely in the opposite FASHION to our wishful thinking researchers – that is, the mutation would have BEEN in a coronavirus that was already inside humans provoking sicknesses as an adaptation of a pathogen that was already familiar with human cells. Only those pathogens familiar with human cells will have an interest mutating to open our cells and would be in contact with ace-2 proteins in enough numbers to mutate favorably to open the ace-2 protein.

An alien virus from a bat or a pangolin will have no idea what an ace-2 protein is, and so it is far more difficult for it to have mutated naturally to open the ace-2, but it would be easy if it were artificially engineered to do so. Thus the obvious conclusion is that if the backbone of the virus was similar to a human pathogen, this could be a natural mutation, if it comes from an alien species this should be a engineered mutation.

And it does come from an alien species. It is similar but not equal enough TO A PANGOLIN OR BAT virus. So likely the genetic engineer did take a pangolin and bat virus, which would have never mutated naturally with so much specificity and use Crsprs-9 to add him the lethal key to open the ACE—2 protein.

And it is quite obvious the researchers are just writing the opposite because that is what they want to conclude:

"These two features of the virus, the mutations in the RBD portion of the spike protein and its distinct backbone, rules out laboratory manipulation as a potential origin for SARS-CoV-2" said Andersen.

Of course immediately every other expert on the field who was afraid to be accused as all their peers of meddling with nature and provoke a global catastrophe sided with the article and ex-cathedra affirmed categorically the issue was settled, so science daily continues:

Josie Golding, PhD, epidemics lead at UK-based Wellcome Trust, said the findings by Andersen and his colleagues are "crucially important to bring an evidence-based view to the rumors that have been circulating about the origins of the virus (SARS-CoV-2) causing COVID-19."

*"They conclude that the virus is the product of natural evolution," Goulding adds, "**ending any speculation about deliberate genetic engineering.**"*

Alas we can keep playing with our genetic engineering toys in the foreseeable future and accuse Nature of producing a perfect pandemic 'animal'.

Then the hunting opened to find a virus similar enough to the COVID-19, and of course it continues with constant retractions because none in pangolins has even a 90% of similarity. Only the bat one does but it needs then a recombination with the pangolin 'almost there' ACE-2 key...

So in the same manner from the chimpanzee with 95% of similarity to the human you need 5 million years, there is no way the bat one alone, became the COVID-19 mutating so fast and so specifically to match the human cell genome and open the ACE-2. It needed the Pangolin key and as we have seen that can only be through lab recombination.

Alas, the researchers continue, now in a rather surrealist disquisition...

Possible origins of the virus

Based on their genomic sequencing analysis, Andersen and his collaborators concluded that the most likely origins for SARS-CoV-2 followed one of two possible scenarios.

In one scenario, the virus evolved to its current pathogenic state through natural selection in a non-human host and then jumped to humans. In this scenario, both of the distinctive features of SARS-CoV-2's spike protein -- the RBD portion that binds to cells and the cleavage site that opens the virus up -- would have evolved to their current state prior to entering humans

In this case, the current epidemic would probably have emerged rapidly as soon as humans were infected, as the virus would have already evolved the features that make it pathogenic and able to spread between people.

!!!???? Alas suddenly in the bat or pangolin the virus had mutated out of nothing to replicate a key to a molecule, ACE-2 which is specific of humans??? Chances that a complex molecule is by random mutation born in a virus that has never seen it is like a group of chimps learning to punch a typewriter and coming out with the exact series of letters of the Quixot... nill.

That even this argument is considered in a serious genetic paper shows how little concern for scientific rigor the authors had in what now we have to declare an obvious pamphlet with a purpose – to exonerate all the profession of possible genocide. Exactly how the people at CERN and the physicists worldwide defend/ed the nuclear industry ever since they made the A-bomb.

In the other proposed scenario, a non-pathogenic version of the virus jumped from an animal host into humans and then evolved to its current pathogenic state within the human population. For instance, some coronaviruses from pangolins, armadillo-like mammals found in Asia and Africa, have an RBD structure very similar to that of SARS-CoV-2. A coronavirus from a pangolin could possibly have been transmitted to a human, either directly or through an intermediary host such as civets or ferrets.

Then the other distinct spike protein characteristic of SARS-CoV-2, the cleavage site, could have evolved within a human host, possibly via limited undetected circulation in the human population prior to the beginning of the epidemic.

Here we found the obvious difficulties – first the chase for virus in bats and pangolins has been exhaustive, and has found none similar enough to the COVID-19; and 2nd there has been no time enough for random mutations to ‘match the ACE-2’, reason why the authors provide for ‘a limited undetected circulation, prior to the beginning of the epidemic’... Nice try.

And then to cap it all, the author sides with the ‘impossible monkeys writing the Quixot’.

Study co-author Andrew Rambaut cautioned that it is difficult if not impossible to know at this point which of the scenarios is most likely. The chances are lower of a non-pathogenic coronavirus entering the human population and then evolving properties similar to SARS-CoV-2.

So first he says it is impossible to know, but then he affirms it is more likely that the monkeys wrote the Quixot in the pangolin before learning to ‘talk human cells’ languages’. I would consider the paper a clear candidate for this year IG Nobel prize in biology, seriously (:

Now for the part ‘humans’ deny in our idol-ogical capitalist society – the ‘civilination’ of all the authors of the text is the Anglo-American civilination, with its self-serving arrogant ‘morality’ they pretend NOT to come from biblical egocy (man above all, free and rational, member of the market, responsible and trustworthy) but to be natural to the Universe. In brief: Technology is always good. Humans must be judged for its use, but technology must never be forbidden. *This is the same morality sponsored in CERN in any science of the technological, mechanical method but NOT the way the Universe with its complex organic causality works; neither the complexity of events to reach the virus can happen in Nature, which is NOT intelligent in its evolution.*

So if we add those scant chances and the fact this was a negligent genocide the article and the whole protection of genetic editing regardless of its ‘collateral damage’ is a shameful action covering up a crime.

To even mention ‘confabulation theory plots’ and downgrade this very serious issue to popular bull\$hit is to me insulting to my ethics and my intelligence. But for the common people is a reassurance that man still is on top of the world, the harder they fall.

Technological warfare. The confabulation theory hypothesis that will be repeated.

For those who come with the 'goodism' argument that we humans are not capable of such evil, fact is pandemics are man-made often. In America, pandemics caused far more deaths than iron among the Amerindian population that didn't have anti-bodies against measles and there are many events in which Anglo-Americans gave infected blankets to Indians to spread the disease.

This brings a truism of the coronavirus pandemics to take into account for future biological warfare, which was banned during the chemical age of electro-engines in the form of mustard and Sarin but has NOT been at all banned in the form of sophisticated generic engineering. This means as technology advances we will be able not only to design the ultimate pandemics – a 'viron', that is a virion (virus) of iron able to prey on the metal of the planet; the 2nd event of global extinction, but any chosen virus when we fully understand the relationship between genes, proteins and RNA commands for reproduction.

I don't believe we are still there for complex bacteria, but certainly for simplex viruses with just 30 genes. And we will soon be there for all kind of sickness, with the new tools of genetic editing (Crispr-9 constantly perfected) to the point that an enemy nation can establish both the pandemic virus, designed to maximal power and the vaccine to avoid contagion and then release it in enemy land.

The argument then of the 'stupid' scientist who does NOT understand the asymmetric causality of nature tells you that we need those 'tools' to defend us from pandemics, (we have created with those tools).

Point is Nature is much faster replicating a lethal Δ -i species – black hole or strangelet, nano-virus of life or metal, than mankind can be defending from it once it has happened. The astounding sloth of the protocols to authorize a vaccine for the virus in an example. Yes, with the same tools we might have used to create the virus in any 'private' concern we might find a defense but we insist 'only entropy=death' comes easy' (Chekhov). It is far easier to destroy the world with a nuclear Bomb that to protect it from it. It is far easier to spread a pandemic man-made than to find and agree to protect mankind from it.

I do NOT think this Pandemic is necessarily public done, but that is precisely the frightening fact about Crispr-9, you can buy it on internet; there have been Chinese doctors editing human babies already; there are 'thousands' of clinics that can use it and the virus is the easiest species to edit.

And yet what makes the whole question of existential risks so irky is the 'law of silence around it', even if you put your career on the line as we did with CERN – once the world knows you will be targeted. Man has the subconscious collective arrogance of the anthropomorphic Jewish-Christian tradition of sons of God, entitled to do anything. And then when wars, holocausts, pandemics, genocides happen do NOT blame gold, weapons, technology, just hate each other per in secula seculorum, A-men.

The choice of the most lethal elements of a virus in fact seems to be the nature of the coronavirus in terms of its 5D 'topological structure', which as all 5D species is composed of 3 forms=functions; the defensive mobile membrane, the cyclical brain and the vital space used to reproduce, which in the case of this coronavirus is remarkably efficient.

If you want a confabulation theory, then the origin is certainly American, and these are the facts...

Although I prefer as a bio-historian, a systemic view: The Natural Progress of a capitalist system dedicated to freely creating lethal technologies for humanity causes spontaneous 'catastrophes' until it kills us all. So as humans research Nuclear weapons, now black holes and strangelets and soon metal-bacteria, but 'in principle' do not want to extinguish life, till 'it happened', just because warfare industries *have that job, on top limiting our resources for life welfare*, bio-geneticists DO research virus, and there are known-facts of genetic engineering of viruses in Wuhan; so that research is taking place. Moreover researchers make a living selling animals they used to test the viruses on meat markets. So if you were to ask me what is the most likely origin as in most catastrophes of mankind, the combination of the free market and human lack of limits to new lethal technologies, and the chaotic way human proceed then with dangers...

In any case, the fact that both China and US have accused each other of creating the virus in its nano-biologic labs shows the capacity to make them is already here thanks to different molecules that do the job (the most famous being Crispr-9, graph, used for editing DNA, one of the technologies that should be forbidden for obvious reasons as it can edit any Bacteria or DNA virus), but it is in a 'free market' already sold in internet to 'consumers'.

This is likely the case of this virus, because humans do start to understand fully the connections between the different scales of 5D biology as we do, and so they can man-made prepare a perfect virus.

So if we were to hear the confabulation theories on the net as a 'template' for future viral warfare it really fits within what we can expect in future generations of the increasingly hostile world to life and mankind we are building... whereas the worst possible scenario will be a pharmaceutical company developing both in advance the virus and the vaccine to profit enormously from its expansion or a nation doing the same to defeat the enemy army:

2010: Genetic editing grows exponentially with the discovery of target-molecules that do the precise cutting.

2016: US discovers Crispr-9 to do precise DNA Gene editing - a genetic engineering technique in molecular biology by which the genomes of living organisms may be modified. It is based on a simplified version of the bacterial CRISPR-Cas9 antiviral defense system. By delivering the Cas9 nuclease complexed with a synthetic guide RNA (gRNA) into a cell, the cell's genome can be cut at a desired location, allowing existing genes to be edited ... Similar molecules to edit RNA and fine tuning are soon developed. Today it is possible to edit any virus or bacteria by selecting its most perfect forms... You can buy the 'Crispr-9' kit in Internet...

- October 2019: military Games in Wuhan; the US team spreads it on the Chinese market.

Tensions between the U.S. and China re-escalate after officials of both countries hurled verbal attacks at each other about the origin of the coronavirus and a member of the military brought about the Wuhan world games confabulation theory. The alternative view is that it was done in Wuhan's biotechnology labs, a hub for such research in China.

But since the virus was spread in China, is also likely that the Americans did it during the Wuhan games. As no nation bombs himself unless it was

done without knowledge of the authorities – recently we knew of the editing and birth of a child using Crispr-9, outside the knowledge of the authorities... In any case China has censored any article on the origin of the virus.

- An edited virus, the most perfect in nature, based on Sars that already appeared in China (this is how China is accused), with a key mutation in its spike (targeting a protein of multiple uses in the cell that cannot be attacked with medicines) is abandoned in a wild animal market, the largest in the world where these mutations originate. Now this is the key for future viral warfare – to take once we understand all pathogens, the different 'qualities' of coronavirus – the faster spread of this one, with the higher lethality of Mers and the mutability of flu and produce one with lethality over 50%, aerial spread similar to the e-number, and higher mutability of flu viruses. That pandemic will decimate a nation.

- November, patient 1 identified is a cluster of 7 people who worked in the market (Zero is not identified).

- Everything is done to economically sink China in the middle of the trade war, hoping to be arrested as it happened with SARS and the 'foreign' virus. Don't escape from China ...

- If it escapes, perfect allows for the creation of a 'new world order' state of population confinement, killing the old, further reducing long-term healthcare costs (in countries like the UK and the US whose policy is to 'let it work' because all we will infect ') ... and confine people in houses connected to MATRIX, Netflix, robots delivering food, drones watching over the population - that locate those who skip quarantine...

If you're looking for even a more bizarre confabulation scene, we have the maximal evil: Pentagon did make the virus at Sandia Labs, New Mexico and it made the vaccine, which will be the Moderna vaccine attacking the RNA of the virus or Novavax vaccine (RNA attacking the spike protein). So the elite has already been vaccinated in America and Trump goes around shaking hands in a macho man attitude as he knows it will be negative. But that is not how Systemic Nature works. Humans are pawns, they do not direct most of the processes.

This is the less likely case, but once this passes, what matters is that *any of those scenarios is possible* in the future pandemic war: nations that release the virus because they have the vaccine for its 1%; private researchers that use molecular editing to make the virus just 'for fun', bio-terrorists; labs doing research and unwillingly letting infected meat or animals or viruses escape; even the most bizarre confabulation theories of racist groups that want to use it to kill minorities and then there will be pundits wondering why it affected more the black or Latino people... No joke. It is known that Israel has researched pathogens specific to the Palestinian genetic make-up till realizing Palestinians and Israelis are after all Semites, so closely related by brotherhood that any infection on the Palestinian people will likely provoke an infection on the Israeli... So much for apartheid...

UPDATE. THE NOBEL PRIZE TO 1 MILLION CORPSES.

So finally the 2020 chemistry Nobel has been awarded to the people who discovered and evolved the Cas-9 system of virus editing, which bacteria used to edit viruses and 'obviously' was used to edit the coronavirus. But the machine is the God of 'animetal mankind', which tries to be stronger than God and the tree of life. It is in fact a license to kill, since everybody knows it and so now every bio-terrorist knows you get a Nobel prize for killing a million people - Luc Montagnier, the virus HIV founder already said it, 'It is a fairy tale the virus comes from an animal market, it was edited' and the president of France came to deny him.

The molecule crsprs-cas 9 as I told you a few months ago is what a bacteria uses to 'edit a virus', but it uses to kill it. The bacteria has a DNA encyclopedia of previous viruses and so when it detects one with its 'palindromic' Gene in the encyclopedia, knows it is a virus and sends the protein cas 9 with the RNA brain (your cell is a nation of 'rna-people' the brain is the Nucleotide - nitrogens NOT carbones are your brain clocks). So the RNA 'rides' the 'beast', the protein cas 9, with the encyclopedic 'note' searching for the gene, all around and when it 'smells' it (the gene vibrates van Der Waals 'flows' of a fixed frequency that the Nitrogen 'feelers' its Hydrogen atoms 'see') alas its 'encyclopedic gene' vibrates and the horse-protein attacks, biting in the center...

That's how you would feel the mission if you were an RNA 'people' - all scales of the sentient Universe feel, sense, live... Now those 2, just took the discovery of a Spanish, valenciano, and applied it to gene editing, they put instead of the gene to kill, the gene to peg, and the protein with the RNA rider goes to the virus cuts it and installs the new gene. 3 cuts and you get the coronavirus, one from a bat other from a pangolin and the 3rd from a human cell. The first to 'resist', the second to 'fly', the third to open the cell and killl.

Of course they thought they could edit a superman but it is much easier to edit a killing virus. The next one just needs to add the MERS 30% of death rate, gene, to this one, and change the key, which is the gene they are targeting with vaccines.

IT IS MUCH EASIER TO KILL than to create, 'only entropy comes easy' said Chekov.

The Pharma industry loves the CAS-9 since one a virus is out there, a vaccine is needed and they also use Cas-9 to edit. It is an arm race. So I guess they pay handsomely to the committee to give the prize, just to shut up anyone who complains.

Or how do you think coronavirus vaccine stocks have rocketed 24 times its prize in 6 months and counting?

Deaths:

1,602,509

Scientists win Nobel chemistry prize for 'genetic scissors'

Emmanuelle Charpentier and Jennifer A Doudna will share the prize for genome editing method

THE SPEED OF REPRODUCTION OF THE CORONAVIRUS. 5 D METRICS.

But why the Coronavirus, such as small superorganism can beat a species, mankind whose egocy, ego=idiocy, makes him feel the center of the Universe? Beyond the philosophical question the hardcore facts of 5D stience tell us that paradoxically, the smaller a system is the stronger and faster it acts. So the existential problems of mankind won't come as believed from larger systems (global warming, state disputes) but from smaller ones. Let us introduce 5D metrics to understand that.

The standard 3 years curve of any Space-time Event. A perfect exponential curve.

The speed of replication of smaller species in 5D scales is easily represented mathematically by the exponential curve. In terms of 5D time, the coronavirus crisis, as all 5D processes including history (man in time) is divided in 3

'ages', the young age of maximal growth, at exponential rate; the flattening of the curve, which correspond mathematically to a logistic curve and a final inverse extinction process.

They conform the '3 ages' of any existential function of any space-time event.

Below he reader can notice that the curves at present time, March are fully in the exponential growth phase due to the fact that the carrying capacity of the virus spread which has the maximal exponential number (whose derivate equals the function growing the same amount every time cycle, in this case doubling every 3 days), which is the human population is still NOT filled. Indeed, the logistic curve can only be reduced then either by diminishing the number of contacts which is extremely difficult and require a military control or by accepting the full contagion of the population, which could only be established if at the same time the group of risk (people like this writer with prior conditions and old people) are confined, so the younger pass all through the sickness and no longer are able to provoke contagion (strategy essayed partially only by Sweden and callously by UK as a capitalist Darwinian system who doesn't want to spend on their old).

As the sickness advances and we keep writing this paper – the project of putting forward 30 years of research in 5D cancelled as I don't expect to be around much longer, given the fact Italy and Spain will be infected in a logistic curve and only diminish when the number of infections is such that the carrying capacity make the exponential curve logistic – towards summertime – it is remarkable how the solutions of bio-history 'suddenly appear' in enlightened politicos that before considered anathema to deviate money from stock speculation into people. Germany still resists but in UK and U\$ there are voices talking of paying the salary and freeze the nation for a month. So of course, capitalism to protect company-mothers and stock prices that are NOT reacting to the stimulus 'DO know' what should be done – they will forget when the epidemics recede. When it will be? The laws of 5D time are ternary so as all systems and other pests it will last 3 ages/years.

1st year will increase till the carrying capacity fills up by summer time (1/2 of the people in non-Asian civilizations get infected and so the e-number of maximal rate of infection which happens when there is no real barriers to communication – the virus is the most perfect pathogen recorded in history with long survival rates for days in different surfaces, 1000 times more concentration in nose-mouth systems, 4 meters of expansion in air, permanence beyond 1 hours suspended as its minimal size allows it to float, so by all means it is a perfect

exponential curve, and all of us who need to get out of home, don't drive and live alone, searching for restricted food supplies will catch it; while in the 3rd world the speed of propagation will be equal, 'discounting' the death of the elderly and sick, which *anyway for the 3rd world do NOT matter as most people died younger, with low life expectations and wars ravage them. This is therefore a 1st world sickness where old people exist.*

Next year the virus will mutate because it cannot longer spread in its benign form, and increase its internal reproduction (a basic event of 5D systems from Ts-motion to Tt-entropic death) and so a more lethal strain will kill many more percentage of the healthy one *which will have relapsed into social life and dolce fare niente as humans are what they are – not causality hindsight.*

The coronavirus thus is a short-terms existential experience of danger for mankind that will pass fast. It should only last a season. As vaccines are ready but they won't be delivered on time due to the absurd protocols and hurdles to fast-track something so obviously needed that in an efficient superorganism of history will be given to the risk groups, old people and with pre-conditions by summertime. It won't likely letting the second stage of the coronavirus kill many, once the control measures are relaxed... Still in 2 years we will think it is a past nightmare and life will return to the normal, which is NOT the normal, because we don't live in an efficient superorganism of history. Indeed, the other two far more risky existential species of the Δ -j scales, dark quark matter (strangelets, black holes) and evolving chips are here to stay and if anything the coronavirus has proved we are moving as all our models of 5D social sciences show to a world in which we become totally dependent on AI machines and loose our 'human condition' – what make life worth living.

THE SCIENTIFIC METHOD OF TRUTH USED IN THOSE PAPERS.

This said, 5D science is the largest upgrading on philosophy of science since Galileo, as it incorporates the objective, equal laws of scales, (the origin of science was its discovery with telescopes and microscopes) to science showing the equality of laws between those scales; it corrects the lineal concept of time, substituted by the cyclical patterns of nature, and it introduces the organic properties nature has due to that scalar cyclical nature; finally adding the role of 'still languages' and its mind mappings that command reality to the mixture: $-\Delta@st$.

The outcome is a pentalogic causality of the 5 local dimensional motions (ab. dimotions) of any space-time organism in the making of reality, without which the quantity of truth extracted from a cyclical event in time or organic system in scalar space is minimal and science becomes opinion, which is specially truth in social sciences, which is lacking any serious scientific organic model of mankind a plethora of opinions, babbled by amateurs of the nervous-political system, called politicians, or parasites of the immunological and reproductive, defensive and economic system, called the military and private bankers. We will then in this paper introduce the laws of social sciences from the pentalogic views of cyclical time and its ages, scalar space and its Δ -organic properties, and the 3 physiological political/defensive/economic networks that organize human citizens-cells into social structures, nations and civilizations (ab. civilinations), of which there are 7 in Europe... etc. etc.

This means the paper has almost 2/3rds dedicated to 5D social sciences and only 1/3rd to the coronavirus crisis but that is the drill in all those papers as we deal with 'children of thought', human beings... To put some order to the 'scientific method', then it is required to classify any analysis of reality into a pentalogic entangled causality. So we will study the 5 elements that flux into this event within the larger scale of the Earth as follows:

- **The Δ -scalar elements**, essential to a crisis produced in the Δ -1 scale of cellular 'warfare', but defended in the Δ +1 scale of human civilinations, which targets the Δ^0 scale of human individuals.
- **The Spatial, topological**, organic 3 networks that compose any system of the Universe, essential to a crisis that is produced by the ternary efficient structure of the Δ -1 coronavirus, a virus with maximal 'informative, St-genetic charge', best Ts-membrane defensive system and maximal 'e-xponential' speed of replication both within the cell ($\S\Pi$ -reproductive hijacked system) and the population (2.8 contagion rate). But also to understand according to the ideal St-political, Ts-defensive and $\S\Pi$ -reproductive, economic networks of a human society, compared to the faulty, 'amateurish, parasitic' nature of human social systems, what would be the cure of a 5D social organism (efficient, painless, immediate) vs. the aberrant cure procedures of our nations inscribed in cultural civilinations.
- **The temporal view**, as we are in a series of papers of history, so this present 'event' must be inscribed in a larger time frame, the age of 'the chip radiation', when technological evolution vastly surpasses human social evolution, hence provoking 'black swan' events of human destruction as man becomes an ever weaker species to the mercy of new technologies of mass-destruction, which paradoxically become also more important to 'cure' those black swans. So the tree of technology delivers the evil=lethal fruits and then the good=curing fruits, but overall man becomes weakened every black swan event, loses its freedoms and rights to machines, soon 'clean safe robots' and in this manner the stick and carrot system of evolution of technology displaces and substitutes life (Gaia) and history (mankind) ushering the Earth into the Mechanocene, 'metal-earth' 3rd age of its evolution in time.
- **We are indeed in the age of entropy-death of life** in this planet, the 'element' that denies all other elements of an organism of space-time and can only be avoided by the increase of:
 - **Order and evolution of the @-collective mind of mankind**, which needs to understand the laws of the organic Universe and its social physiological networks and reform the system if he wants to survive.

So the 5 elements of mankind in space, time, scale, mind and its denial by entropic black swans are the causality of this crisis, and while an intelligent (max. St), ethic (maximal S=T), strong (max. Ts) mankind's superorganism would have no problem controlling them, this ideal homo sapiens does NOT exist, instead 'enzymen' worship technology and become easy prey of those black swans, with an increasing destructive tempo till extinction.

Pentalogic causality of complex systems as opposed to the simples A->B Aristotelian human thought.

It is important even before we attempt to explain all those elements of the Coronavirus crisis, part of the larger age of singularity black swans how the Organic Universe creates causally the future, as opposed how the far less intelligent mind of man (regardless of its egocy, ego=idiocy) thinks the future is created. Humans have a simplex, lineal view of causality, from A ->B in Aristotelian rational terms at best (science, western philosophy), with a few incursions in more complex dual causalities (Taoism, Hegelian Dialectics), which did not collapse into a truly scientific view. This is due to the fact they perceive only a scale of space-time, as they have packed all those Δ -scales into a spacetime continuum, and specially because they have simplified the 5 Dimensional motions of time into a single one, the simplest, 'entropy' (Tt, the internal and external disorder due to excessive motion that kills a system). So they don't understand at all how the future is created, how event happens, how the different dimensional motions and scales 'collapse' to form an event. And what is more, due to their egocy, they believe they know. Indeed, try to argue with a 'Relativist physicist' about the doodles of the sand of Mr. Einstein, he won't even listen and bring its simpleton worldcycles and single lineal time dimension, for all what is worth – to measure speeds and translations in space). Most events in time however are organic, causes by the evolution of a system and its multiple interrelated parts, *without the awareness of each of them, which play their part separately, leaving to the organic laws of the Universe and its pentalogic causality to 'collapse' and 'lock in' each part to form a whole. The causality then is first scalar: the larger whole influences the part with its entropic flows, the smaller parts program the information of the larger whole; and both integrate and collapse into the relative present scale of the event. In that scale there is also pentalogic contributions to causality of the 5 Dimensional motions of time (Tt-entropy, St-information, $\int T$ -energy, Ts-locomotion and Ss-languages and seeds). And then there are the 'agents in space' that contribute the event belonging to different ecosystems (groups of different individual systems, mostly people of the human organism and technological machines of the economic ecosystem in human events). In the coronavirus crisis this means that the different paths of evolution of all those elements have brought to the organism of History we study a change of paradigm and 'age' from the previous age of the 'Semite wars' (2000s, 2010s) to the new age of Black swan singularities when technologies that far outpower human capacity to control them will come out of that control in an accidental unpredicted manner to show at 'face power' the fragility of human life in this planet and the 'faulty' physiological ternary networks of $\int T$ -energy, Ts-defense and St-information (economic, immunological and political systems) of mankind.*

So those are the main 'elements' that collapse and define the events of the singularity age, 'the black swans' of technology, which are 'dormant' till as they increase their power, spread into more laboratories and research groups, an accident happens. And then there will be the sorrowful attempts of mankind to control them, because our superorganisms of history have 3 corrupted ill-designed physiological networks, and are on top in a process of substitution and obsolescence by the equivalent networks of the metal-earth, fast evolving into a global superorganism of company-mothers of machines (the capitalist system). So human systems are loosing resources and capacity to confront the existential crisis we shall go through in the singularity black swan present age.

There is of course also the easiest causality in temporal terms, which human egocy ascribe to individuals and then the blaming each other –but that is not how 5D reality happens.

I.e there is now the blaming going on of US that China did it. But consider what we study here – the event of a pandemic due to the likely use of genetic engineering over a bat resistant virus to which an ACE-2 key to open human cells, likely from a modified Pangolin gene has been inserted. For a decade or so now we have the capacity to engineer virus because the technology has not been forbidden. Entropy comes easier – that is, it is much easier to create a virus chimera with only 30 genes that a human superman with 30.000 genes So to 'learn' and practice genetic engineering is done in viruses and bacteria, and the temptation to create a new species is immense in humans who think by egocy they 'invent things', technology, life species, etc. So sooner than latter a lab would have done it, and as it is a Pandemic it would have extended globally, regardless on who specific human or nation did it.

So the human causality is truly irrelevant. The key causality is the evolution of technology and the human ideology of technoutopia that forbid us to prohibit lethal technologies. Once they are in place they would cause a pandemic.

Then there is the response to the pandemic which has been thoroughly dependent on the quality of the human physiological networks of the legal nervous, economic, reproductive and immunological, defensive systems of mankind, in a constant struggle for resources in a planet of limited space with the equivalent networks for the world of machines and weapons (metal-kind). Specifically as this has been mostly an immunological problem, the trade-off between welfare and warfare, the health-care systems of immunological health-care warriors, equivalent to the leukocyte system of our mammal organisms, vs. the expenditure in defense-military systems, the germs of history that instead of saving citizens-cells of History kill them. The more buttressed a society is in weapons, the less developed its health-care system is and the ore it would suffer the pandemic and vice versa. So we found that on the side of maximal military power capita, the anglo-American civilisation and its two leading countries, US and UK have now as we speak, 20 April, the largest number of active cases in the world. While the countries that due to their constitution in Europe (Germany) or their non-capitalist system, China (in capitalism, weapons are the most expensive hence most profitable goods, as top predator machines, hence the most reproduced and evolved that take the highest share of the economy) have done it better.

Causality in the solution to the problem thus has a lot to do with the immunological system, but also with the other two systems, the economical system that provides the oxygen-money of society first. So the two countries which today have the worst possible financial system of the world, Italy and Spain, as they do NOT have a national bank of issue, so they need to borrow parasitic debt instead of printing their own currency (as they gave those rights to the ECB which is NOT a bank of issue and is controlled by Germany, and Industrial nation that only allows the bank to issue money for other banks and its industries). So next to US and UK we see that Italy and Spain have had to destroy for decades with austericide their health-care systems because they are basically 'debt slaves' of the ECB bank without the right to print their money. So the financial system matters. Because in UK and US money is printed by national banks and do have the strongest financial markets of the world, as the modern and past leading empires, they can produce as much money as they want, but here the problem is that their social class elites, the Wasp-Jasp coalition in power, do NOT see the rest of the population as their own, have biblical racist primitive ideologies of go(l)d and the exclusive rights of the chosen to enjoy the monopoly of money printing, etc. etc. so they have not spent money in health-care and also found themselves in dire straights.

Then there is the question of third world nation, whose dominant physiological network is the politico-military systems with maximal expenditure in the germs of history, weapons, so they have resorted to the authoritarian regime solution of locking in all people, which is NOT obviously the solution, but alas, it is what a military system does. This trend started precisely in the new authoritarian regimes of South-Europe, Italy under a coalition of its extreme parties and Spain that just imitates in history Italy, its mother culture, with a bit of delay. And indeed if we look at the long 80 years cycles of history, bio-history predicted that in 2020s we will enter an age of neo-fascism and political and military control of populations. We did not expect this to happen due to the 3rd horse of apocalypse, pest, but to the first, war, with an in crescendo of the Semite wars into a global China-US confrontation, but alas, because causality is multiple, there has been a 'different' causality here, instead of going from war to pest, (though arguably the 2000s-2010s age of semite wars has been the war age that weakened with massive investment in warfare the health-care systems of the west) we enter in the age of AI vigilante robots and mobiles, through a 'seemingly good cause' – pandemics. This was already foreseen by the most important think tank of the Wasp-Jasp coalition in power in America, the Rockefeller center for 'future studies', since the future is indeed created by multiple actors. And so now, the metal-earth and its global technologies 'safe, clean robots', internet connections that enclose people at home, starting to switch the protagonism and mobility of the system from History to the metal-earth future citizens – robots, will advance a step further.

So the coronavirus crisis is NOT reduced by any means to 'who did it', it is not an isolated event which will just disappear – on the contrary it is part of a global process of multiple physiological human and industrial,

technological networks and systems in its relentless path of evolution according to the equation of the 3 ages of earth: relative past (Gaia) < Relative present (history) > relative future(metal-earth).

All this known, if humans had a more complex understanding of the Universe, and social sciences, they could obviously control those black swans, establish an immortal present system of history in which a unified global legal nervous, political system, with a proper democratic feed-back pain/a posteriori judgment of politicians by body cells ensuring the caring of the cells by the neuronal, financial and legal elites, would forbid lethal technologies and the knowledge of the laws of the 5D organic Universe change the paradigm of what is the goal of mankind – NOT to evolve technology, which is a different species that is making humans obsolete in war and work fields, but to repress information, the 3rd age of all organisms and maintain mankind in the present state repressing the future of technology and enhancing the sustainable past of life species that give as welfare. None of this is happening beyond the dreams of ecologism and the objective work of 5D science, because humans are already ‘enzymen’, catalysts of the metal-earth, themselves ‘infected’ by the virus of technoutopia, of the tree of metal, which as the coronavirus does with infected cells, making them reproduce viruses not human cells, it has convinced mankind that evolving weapons and lethal technologies NOT welfare goods and human beings IS our manifest destiny. So the coronavirus in the $\Delta-1$ scale of mankind is equivalent to the lethal goods of the Industrial r=evolution we love and multiply in the $\Delta+1$ scale of history, and this lead us to the main law of 5D: all scales and organisms follow the same laws, and all have a single mandate: to survive, by developing systems closer to the ideal organism of 5D science. Let us then from minor to major study those elements one by one; but to that aim we have to ‘translate’ the organic functional view in ‘scale’ to the topological view of those superorganisms in space. So we can study then the 3 parts of a superorganism, and finally to ‘translate’ them into ‘time’ so we can understand the ‘ages’ of all organic processes, and the most difficult to understand view – that of superorganisms in mind-languages; starting by defining the fundamental ‘particle’ of the Universe, not a physical one but a biologic system, the supœrganism.

THE CORONAVIRUS AS A BIOLOGICAL ORGANISM.

In terms of 5D biology the coronavirus is also a 3 network organism that has also some remarkable properties as an efficient ‘space-time species’, namely the maximal speed of reproduction of the Universe among its hosts, the ‘number e’, the exponential 2.8 number of contagion is the exponential number of maximal speed of replication, as the only number whose ‘rate of change in time=derivative’ equals the function itself.

In its ‘topological form’, its ‘generator equation’ also is maximal for all viral organisms. Indeed, as we are all made of 3 ‘topological only varieties’ as Limbs/fields/hard membranes of entropic motion, particles/heads of information and reproductive systems, the coronavirus maximizes the 3 for viral species: its entropic membrane is made of extremely resistant proteins with lineal spikes to invade and break other membranes; its RNA informative material has the perfect cyclical form of information and it is one of the most complex of the viral kingdom with maximal number of genes, and its capacity to host on the reproductive cells of the invading organism is maximal.

We are thus facing a classic ‘theme’ of 5D sciences – a top predator smaller species with maximal speed of reproduction according to 5 D metrics (which makes smaller systems in space faster in time cycles: $S \times \delta = K$); confronting the worst designed supœrganism I have ever studied – History, Mankind in time – a ‘crazy supœrganism’ with a dysfunctional head and body that reproduces massively lethal products for humanity (our government and financial, & reproductive systems that massively invest in weapons that kill our body and hate memes that kill our mind) and it is broken in different organs with a high degree of rejection (nationalisms)... get extinct very fast... as mankind will likely be – a theme studied in other papers of 5D.

The proper vaccine. The cure at $\Delta-1$ scale.

How to tackle the coronavirus crisis is then evident for a 5D world in which the laws of 5D biology are understood:

- Regarding the Δ -1 scale of the coronavirus, its ternary topologic structure has to be understood to obtain a vaccine. As the vital space-body of the Coronavirus is irrelevant – outsourced to the cell that reproduces it, the key elements are RNA-brains and the membrane of spike proteins. It is then obvious that vaccines will be, as it is happening, most successful when 1) decode and inhibit the membrane penetration of the cell. This is the easiest, clearest path for a vaccine – to prevent the spike proteins of the ‘crown’ to penetrate the membrane of the cell, as it happens in any system – wars are fought in the border between armies, the skin protects you first from any invasion, and containment of the pandemic required to swiftly isolate the focus of the pandemic *before it spread to the whole nation, something only Asian cultures did, due to its higher efficient 5D organic structure as societies.*

*A second less interesting ‘front’ for a vaccine is to attack the RNA brain of the virus, once it has invaded the cell, since it requires also to meddle with the internal vital space of the cell. This is the procedure of MRNA, a darling of Wall Street, which introduces parts of the RNA brain of the system. It is akin to try to stop the ‘enemy army’ once it has crossed the border and invaded the nation provoking havoc, as one a system has *controlled the collective brain of a superorganism and hijacked its languages of information, it converts the organism into its slave. This as we shall see happens not only with viruses in cells, but with our societies where those who control the informative mass-media and legal and financial systems of society control it. So the 4th less understood element of any superorganism are ITS LANGUAGES and MIND=PROGRAM OF SURVIVAL they enact. And we will return to it.**

The ideal candidate. It is then immediate that from all the candidates that so far now in March, are being developed for a vaccine, the most promising ones are those who target the ‘skin to skin’ essential concept of all immunological systems of the Universe – that is, to attack the skin of the virus, and do so in the skin of the human being, which is its fundamental ‘topological element’ that separates the ‘fractal superorganism’ of mankind from the outer world.

This is an essential concept studied in our analysis of cyclical time, expressed in Jordan’s first knot theorem: a system of space-time is such when it has besides the inner open ball of vital space, a membrane that isolates it from the outer world, where its defensive elements, from horns to thick skins lay. Here is where any pandemic should be fought first, as any war is fought in the borders. And we shall see this is where nations due to the lack of a single human superorganism should have detained the pandemic first.

Is there then any vaccine ‘skin to skin’ that attacks the spike of the virus, its ‘key’ to the organism, and does so by promoting the defense on the skin of the human being?

After looking at all the candidates, without being able to access information on Chinese Candidates, I found to my surprise one such candidate being researched now at the Pittsburg University – one of the best vaccine centers in the world, since it developed the polio vaccine in the 50s. It ads also the advantage of being a public institution – in so far as such concept exists in America. So if I were the American government I would immediately fast-track, putting down all the protocol burdens, such a vaccine that is the proper method for multiple reasons of 5D biology and should be easily applied as all skin systems with a simple patch similar to the coronavirus strategy – dissolving needles that penetrate the skin and make the powerful immunological skin cells to multiply its antibodies.

The 3rd type of classic candidates which inoculates the entire organism, in its dead form is both more dangerous, as a virus is not really ever dead, and unneeded as the ‘vital space’ of a superorganism is secondary to the system, which truly IS the membrane and the brain, or ‘membrain’ in 5D terminology.

The second element of such necessary vaccine would be its availability and scaling in production, which again for simple skin patches has proved to be easy, efficient and given the maximal immunological response of any 5D barrier, require smaller dose, smaller side effects – as it acts on the surface of the organism, and hence can be produced industrially in larger numbers...

The 5 D response. Vaccines.

First let us consider what the organism does. It does NOT take years to deliver its equivalent to a vaccine at the Δ -1 scale: T-bodies. On the contrary it does NOT make tests. TIME IS OF THE ESSENCE. So as soon as an antibody is created to lock and inhibit an antigen, the entire organism does a mass-production and throws it into the population of cells – no time to waste. If human superorganisms were minimally efficient, as the vaccines=antibodies were developed by march, a fast track testing without the need of slow ‘free’ enrolling, but people already enrolled in the pay-check of the immunological health-care system as professional testers would have dosed immediately. In parallel massive production of the proper 5D candidates – the best 3 for the 3 elements of the virus, no more needed, after a consensus of all the researchers of the planet, a single organism working together, would be massively producing vaccines since march; and by now, April 15, test would be done, mass production completed and everybody would be receiving the vaccine.

But as we repeat ad nauseam and explain with the brief analysis of the history of mankind, we live in a dysfunctional world where Gaia, the Earth of life and History, the earth of mankind have long become secondary. And so the only efficient well designed defensive system is the military systems of the Metal-earth.

It is a genocidal crime of negligence that *to save money, the SARS vaccine was NOT developed but halted once the epidemics passed.*

The vaccines for the coronavirus have the same side effects and mechanisms that those for flus and SARS and the modern vaccines which are based in inoculating only a part of the organism, RNA or spike proteins, are harmless in those previous cases, so they should be using after the first test on humans already undergoing for the whole batch of populations that the states for lack of health-care investments – all the money going to the parasitic ‘animetal system’ of human war – to risk groups and those people that should BE FREE of any containment because of their lack of risks, to avoid them to be contagion focus (young people).

Even more sanguine is the interference of big Pharma and the organs of health-care they control in countries like the US to prevent the change of normative in the issue of vaccines, which were ready as earlier as march – now with the best candidate coming from Pittsburg University, and should be used WITH MINIMAL TRIALS within months, scrapping absurd protocols that last for a year to allow BIG PHARMA to enter the game, and catch up with its cumbersome, old fashion modes of making vaccines, so Johnson and Johnson etc. have entered the fray and pretend that because they can produce them in huge numbers – this is no big deal specially for simple vaccines like the best-candidate from Pittsburg, they expect the government to help them, which of course they do. Because what they truly have is money enough to grease all politicos.

Moreover, similar vaccines for SARS and MERS family of coronavirus were aborted, and not researched because for private Pharma was not ‘big business’ once the pandemic passed and for public health-care THERE IS NO ENOUGH resources, as states have been buttressing with weapons for decades.

Other forms of attacking the virus

The vaccine aims to destroy the virus as a spatial form, from the point of view of its structural St-TS-Ts 3 elements; that is, to target the species as a recognizable entity within the languages of communication of the human superorganism. Medicines tend to act though in the ‘temporal element’, preventing the pathogen to perform a certain function of the 5 ‘Dimotions of existence’ of any system of the Universe.

In that regard, as humans lack the simplest understanding of the function of 5D existence and will not as ‘reproductive minds’ that keep repeating what they have learned, details NOT the thoughts of god – learn it from its ‘single point’ soon to exit mundi, pharamacologists as all 4D scientists as a rule work on those details without much knowledge of its mechanisms of action. Of late they resort to mere statistical methods, which is the ‘intelligent of the Schopenhauer’s stupid’ – a man who doesn’t understand the causality of events – but can anyway through statistical methods recognize that A causes B. So AI has come to the rescue of a lack of ‘understanding of the general rules of the game’.

What kind of medicines then inhibit some of the functions of the virus goes well beyond the scope of this paper as we should explain the relationship on the Δ-2 bio-chemical scale between the different sub-languages of the cell, its minimal components, the N-informative, O-entropic and C-energetic, structural 3 atoms of life, and how according to morphology act as the minimal coding particles of such organisms.

The field is immensely complexity; I have barely scratch its surface and symmetries but the general rule is this:

limbic system of an amino

- Compounds with abundance of Nitrogen rings interact with the informative elements of a system in a ± way according to its inhibitory or enhancing morphology.

- Compounds with abundant Oxygen, act as 'entropic' radicals tearing membranes and interfering with metabolic processes. While §T-carbon chain are mostly harmless.

Consider a simple example, cloroquinine, which is clearly an 'active' Nitrogen molecule with an open 'N-head' with 2 'arms', and a 'super-oxygen' atom (Chlorine of maximal electronegativity) in the other extreme. All what we can assess from a first view is that it is a 'strong Ts-St-molecule', but with a 'twisted' morphology (the Chlorine does NOT act as the topic acid COOH-

acid with two kicking legs to 'swim' in water, attracting and repelling H2O molecules. So while the compound is sturdy, it is 'crippled' and it will tend to seek for other systems with better limbic forms, attaching to them and interfering with the metabolic processes of simpler organisms, such as viruses. We do NOT know how it doe so. And I have not studied the biochemistry of it; but in this I do agree with Mr. Trump – it is a promising little bastard.

Some hints come from that weird structure in which the 'aggressive' chlorine is attached to the double Nitrogen ring; and so it can 'attack' with its electronegativity and break any protein chain the way far bigger enzymes do. *In brief the chloroquinine is a 'crazy ram head', a Nitrogen double ring with a 'chlorine horn' that can break havoc in any part of the virus it attacks – which part is affine to and how it does it specifically, is left to analyze but the general method of all those unbalanced species is the same: As atoms seek to fill their outer valences to become a perfect organism with a closed skin; unbalanced forms tend to join other molecular systems to be part of more complete larger wholes.*

So most medicines are inhibitors that have the strength to 'dislocate' a part of a larger whole and occupy a key position within it. This is how the best medicines are and act –they are a combination of a strong limbic/breaking system and a twisted brain of 'aminas', nucleotide acids, adenosines, guanines, etc. and so with the ram the break the site in which they will locate their 'brain' to receive the flows of ¥-energy and information of the larger system, which is NO LONGER a perfect organism as the invading form is not quite exactly what had to be, inhibiting its work. So the two most promising medicines for the coronavirus so far, the Chloroquine which I am taking weekly regardless of its collateral effects to my side, here in Spain, and remdesivir, the Gilead molecule have similar structures, and act – this we know for remdesivir and I think their similar structure and 5D biological general rules imply it is also how chloroquine acts – in that fashion: they ram, break, enter the structure of the virus in its skin, protein sites and substitute with its neuronal amino groups a similar group inhibiting the perfect working of the system.

In the graph, remdesivir is a better molecular structure, on the left all those Oh and PO3 'aggressive limbic elements with a sub HN-brain, arms on the bottom, a maze on top and the PO3 pivotal arm ensures easy breaking anywhere; and then as proved by the literature as earlier as February (surprisingly the stock market didn't react jacking up a 10% gilead till 15 april), the 'head' buttressed of 'brainy' N (5 of them) on the right will

supplant key elements on the virus inhibiting its work. As it is also a small molecule it diffuses in enormous quantities around the entire body. So this is the essence of 5D 'whys' on those medicines.

Ultimately the field of 5D medicine is not even in its infancy, but much would be gained if biologists did understand the program of vital existence and how each 'specific' atom and molecule codes for it, themes those I was in the process of unload this year 2020 on the papers on biology, before I discontinued the project.

RECAP. *In 5D medicine good general purpose drugs for viruses are small with strong limbs, heavy nitrogens and an unbalanced structure to break and substitute essential elements on the virus inhibiting its 5D motional cycles: To enter they attack the skin or dangerous outward spikes of the virus itself uses to enter invading cells. Its small size means they are ideal for delivering millions of them spreading as the virus does all over the body. The limbs of chloroquine or a similar drug that 'ram' and the head substitutes. The molecule is good enough to inhibit or replace a position on the functional metabolic chains of the coronavirus. Its action due to its simplicity must be generalized to great extensions of the body.*

The immunologic antibodies. The transfusion of blood. Private health-care. Vaccines.

However the best remedy to this as so many other sicknesses are those re=produced by Nature. That is, the antibodies of people who are healthy. It is a clear proof of the ill-designed systems of capitalism and the power of big pharma that this essential remedy of nature is always limited. When I had epicondylitis and could not write for a while I asked my insurance and the public health-system to inject me with red blood platelets to cure my cartilage tissue. I found neither of them carry this simple cure that cost nothing but a centrifugal machines. When I tried to bring them for my private use from China I found I needed an import permit difficult to give for 'health-care' elements – the same import permit that allowed the Spanish government that could not buy in advance masks to take away in the border the ones I bought for me and my pharmacist brother... Why? I found easily that the problem is precisely that if people were cured with their own blood antibodies and platelets, very expensive drugs sold by big pharma would plummet its profits.

So alas! We know since the Spanish flu that transferring the blood of the cured people will immediately improve the health of the sick as the antibodies will be carried by the sick and kill the virus.

This means by law, every person discharged after passing the sickness should donate ½ liter of blood to be applied to the new infected. As Spain and Italy have millions of real infected cases, and their people are highly solidarious with a social-Christian background they would have done it, but none has proposed and reinforced such a simple measure. Big pharma would not sell its tons of retrovirals. A Kaletra retroviral bottle costs 600 euros and has multiple side effects. India produces its generics for 100 euros the bottle. The blood costs nothing, produces no side effects and as the number of contagions increases its supply also would increase.

The viral infection of our individual and social bodies.

If bio-historians, doctors of History were on charge of the 3 physiological networks of legal information (politicians), re=productive finances (economics) and immunologic defensive systems, the world would imitate the 5D laws of superorganisms to construct a perfect immortal social system. But humans are guided by egocentric emotions and corrupted by 'viral metal': weapons of war, go(l)d greed that provokes financial anoxia and atrophied by the use of machines. So they live in a childish egotrip of power, and cannot accept a higher organic science to guide them.

What makes so easy to exist in all scales of reality with extreme efficiency as the coronavirus simple system that 'outsources' the more complex of those actions, reproduction, to the cell it predates, shows is precisely that crystal clear IMMANENT understanding of the game by all the species of reality, with the solely exception of the 'technological man', which acts precisely as a cell that has been corrupted by coronavirus, and dedicates all its resources to multiply the 'lethal goods, weapons and software hate memes' instilled in his mind by informative machines. Mankind has become in that sense an enzyman who works as the infected viral cell under the 'germs' of history, weapons and mental machines, to the service of a different future and we shall return to this clear-cut

essence of our society since the beginning of the age of metal and the industrial r=evolution, because without it we cannot understand the corruption of our social organisms

We do NOT have a proper immunological health-care system because we are working for the evolution of the metal-defensive system of weapons. We do NOT have a proper financial system that delivers oxygen to every human being, because we are working in a parasitic private banking system founded by goldsmiths that hypnotized people with gold, which is just the digital support of money as money is a language of information NOT wealth per se.

So we live in a virally infected society not only at individual but at collective level and this will become crystal clear as we develop further the laws of social superorganisms.

A final note on that isomorphic concept (the laws of all the scales of the fifth dimension are the same, this is the main law you have to interiorize to understand the Universe): The way the coronavirus kills is exactly the same way the capitalist system kills: by anoxia. The cells of the lungs get infected and do not longer let oxygen pass to the cells of the body. In capitalism, private banking prevents money=oxygen to arrive to the cells of the organism, our citizens, who do not receive the language of social power they require to order the goods they need to survive and now should be given as a Universal salary to all citizens while forbidding companies to fire them, so they have money to feed, while the 'body of mankind is at rest' and the health-care people cure it.

But not even in a situation like the pandemics those self-evident measures are being implemented. They are patched here and there, with the obvious intention to return to a parasitic private financial system as long as the pandemic ends – but of course, maintaining the possibility to incarcerate the whole mankind when required with less just reasons – all the repressive measures in history are first established for a 'good reason'.

During attachment and penetration, the **virus** attaches itself to a host **cell** and injects its genetic material into it. During uncoating, replication, and assembly, the **viral** DNA or RNA incorporates itself into the host **cell's** genetic material and induces it to replicate the **viral** genome.

THE MEMBRANE OF NATIONS. 1ST RESPONSE TO A PANDEMIC.

The protection of the largest scale of a superorganism – a nation.

As the laws of 5D are isomorphic in scale, meaning they apply to any scale of reality, the same concept should

Steps of Virus Infections - Boundless

have been applied to the protection of each nation from its invasion by the pandemic – though latter when we talk of the ideal society we shall see how 'wrong' is the concept of breaking the human global Earth's superorganism into nations, which are basically 'military concepts' of the wrong understanding on what is the immunological, defensive system of mankind – its health-care workers as this crisis shows NOT its military whose tools, weapons in fact are the 'germs of history' that absorb also all the resources sorely needed as the pandemics shows by their true 'leukocyte' warriors.

We can consider first the topological view as we did with the virus' vaccine. Essentially the cure starts also in a human superorganism, nation or civilination at the same level: to avoid the germ to cross the 'skin'=border.

The proper solution of an ideal world ARE given the scalar laws of 5D supœrganisms are the same that Nature implements when an organism is sick and the immune system has been penetrated by lethal germs. So the first element to consider is a membrane protection, which in human social superorganisms are the border.

- **Ts: The membrane.** The first barrier of any supœrganism to external 'germs' is always the membrane, which must isolate all the citizens-cells from the external world. As such is the harder part of the supœrganism. Unfortunately humans are NOT a single global government. SO instead of having an external skin-membrane that corresponds to the entire planet (whose membrane is the magnetic field that shields life from radiation), are divided in 'self-rejecting organs' called tribal nations that break the law of love to the members of the same species and so have established internal hard-membranes, called frontiers, buttressed with armies in charge of the germs of history

that kill other human beings. In this structure of society the membranes are local, not global ‘symmetries’. Still it is obvious that given those pre-conditions the first measure to contain the advance of the virus would have been to close borders and alternatively to isolate the viral region where the sickness first spread. This was done best in the Asian region where the germ was first spotted. So Wuhan was isolated as it was Daegu, the city where in Korea the germ first appeared, and the Diamond Princess, where the infection first appeared in Japan, despite the cruelty in this case of the Japanese government, since it should have evacuated the people of the cruise and isolate them properly in a hospital facility at land to prevent infection between the inner citizens-cells of the source. And initially it seemed the United States did also act swiftly forbidding flights to China. But this was just a topic, xenophobic racist ‘blaming’ act of Mr. Trump with little consistence, not followed by the second basic measure, once the virus has penetrated the defenses of the organism – its fast searching, isolation and destruction=cure in the infected cell; where all *capitalist nations failed by lack of resources for the welfare system, massively invested in the lethal military system.*

But where the isolation procedures of the membrane failed most notoriously was in the civilisation of Europe, whose actions bordered the bizarre. Indeed, Europe lives a fantasy called the European Union that pretends to serve its citizens but since the creation of the ECB bank, a bank that stole the rights of nations and citizens to reproduce their own money, which is not a bank of issue, meaning it does not create and deliver ‘oxygen-money’ to its citizens but ‘lends debt to private banks’ which in turn get an usury cut from nations and people that borrow money; it has become a ‘make-up corpse’ of public service, whose true workings are similar if not worse than those of the American system of lobbying, opaque laws and private parasitic finances. Further more the supposed union of all their people as Europeans is just a wet paper concept since politicians void of real power and financial and legal control of the organization of Europe (the European parliament has limited power and it is opaque to the service of lobbyist corporations, as Washington politicians are, but in a twist of hypocrisy, without recognizing it so); so nationalist hang-ups from the previous age of warrior-kings dedicating all resources to the reproduction of germs and warfare is ‘a dormant’ infection always ready to jump back to promote e-motional hate among neighbors.

Europe thus was caught between the fantasy of a single nation with external borders, whose purpose is the welfare of its people and the reality of a corrupted political and financial system to the service of the nationalist memes and corporative lobbies of Brussels. Initially thus tried to maintain the ‘virtual dream’ of a United Europe, which is just a fantasy promoted with ‘virtual games’, such as the Champions League, which reunites hundreds of thousands of Europeans in packed stadiums, side by side with people shouting and spitting germs for hours. When a society is corrupted formal ceremonies, childish games and selfie fantasies take the place of a reality they try to hide. So as the pandemic raged on Northern Italy the focus in the center of the Italian Stock-market and corporative power, Milan and Lombardy, was kept open, without isolating its ‘cancerous cells’ to prevent dissemination of the sickness. On the contrary the virtual fantasy of Europe was maintained and people from Lombardy travelled in the ‘circensis’ of the Champions League while its wealthy tourists flew to coastal destinations. Unfortunately the region where I live received them. The 2 first infected parked their caravan in front of my home, on the beach. The city with the highest rate of death in the planet Bergamo, sent his soccer team, the Atalanta to ‘fight the circensis’ against our local team, the ‘Valencia’. I recall given my pre-conditions and awareness of the pandemic my anger and astonishment to the fact that those matches were allowed and all what the people here was worried is about the ‘surmounting’ of a 4-1 defeat at Bergamo, where the next week hundreds of citizens would die and now the newspaper has stopped giving news and only prints the death notices of its citizens. The country was worried by the possibility the famous ‘burning man event’ (Las fallas) could be postponed. So the Atalanta came with 2 loaded planes to infect the region.

This trend of refusing isolation of citizens according to the infantile idea or virtual soma that we Europeans live in a capitalist democracy so we are ‘free’ (in a capitalist democracy by definition only companies are free citizens with rights to reproduce the language of social power, money, in markets, as they have hijacked that right from governments subject to

France steps up coronavirus measures but refuses to keep border with Italy open

‘deficit zero laws’ which extort people through taxes of its hard-won salaries). And so because Europeans are supposedly free and Europe is a supposed single nation, Italians wondered all around the continent, and Lombardi spread the metastasis of the virus to every corner of it. They went north through Switzerland to enjoy the sky season and the Swiss now are the highest per capita infected nation along the small ‘tax-heavens’ for the rich that surround Italy, Monaco, Vatican, San Marino, Liechtenstein...

But the same situation happened in all other nations of Europe, where mostly the capital or financial district of maximal communication became the central focus of the disease, which as the most productive city with its privileged people, refused to isolate itself. London, New York, Paris and Madrid along their border regions played those roles.

Indeed, the ‘5D ternary structure’ of all supærganisms once more is shown in the way the Pandemic has spread, hitting systematically as all ‘attacks’ into a supærganism, the so called in 5D topology ‘membrain’ (Ts-membrane+St-brain) of the supærganism. The membrane is the hardcore barrier to the advance of Germs and the *capital-brain the system that once it collapses means the defeat of the supærganism. So in the same manner a top predator first ‘scars’ the skin to draw blood and then goes to the neck to separate the head from the body, the virus penetrated first the coastal border regions and then spread in the political and financial centers:*

In the graph we can see the case of France, where the borders with Germany and Italy, and the capital have become the focus. They should have been immediately isolated from the vital space of the entire nation, but they were not.

In my country though the situation was even more surrealist, as the capital is in the exact geographical center, surrounded by a desert ‘plateau’ and the western coast and northern border act as a relative smallish membrane given the peninsular nature of Spain. So all what was needed when the 1st of January the first infected germs coming from France, Italy and Germany arrived, was to close the borders, suspend flights, and next, when the Madrid region became the overwhelming center of the infection, to easily isolate the capital within the desert land of central Spain and pass to the second phase of any infection healing in the organisms of nature.

Instead, the Government warned the country would be locked out 3 days in advance, on Friday letting the entire weekend the wealthy Madrileños to fled its ‘villas’ in coastal towns spreading the infection to the entire nation, as now New Yorkers are doing in the US. The deepest cause of this mismanagement has to do obviously with the most profound laws of 5 D Supærganisms, which ultimately are ‘systems’ in which the alliance of the Ts-membrane and St-brain over the ‘open ball’ vital space of the body-cells they prey on manifests in a complete indifference to the exploitation of its body-cells, and ultimate cause of death, as the membrain expands, (so our skin keeps multiplying warping into old age, and our mind keeps piling memories and repeating its mental cycles, increasingly indifferent to the health of the body).

Madrileños, New Yorkers, Londoners, Parisians and Milanese, centers of the political=nervous and financial=blood systems of their organic nations showed the same indifference to the life rights of the vital space-body they are so much accustomed to despise and exploit, the ‘provinces, provincias, red neck states’ thus received the metastasis.

RECAP. The pandemics penetrated easily dysfunctional western nations and within them once it took hold of the central ‘RNA-brain’ as it does isomorphically in each cell, spread by reproduction of its ‘infected’ parts all the regions of the nation. Since human societies are NOT ruled by 5D stiences, but are sick, selfie, corrupted superorganisms, in the west nothing was done properly. And that is, why the west has so thoroughly failed to isolate the pandemics. But what is an ideal human social superorganism in 5D? Let us study with those very same disomorphic laws before going further.

THE ORGANIC PHILOSOPHY OF THE UNIVERSE. SYSTEMS SCIENCES AND ITS DISOMORPHIC LAWS.

The second fundamental element of the structure of the Universe closely connected to the fifth dimension is the organic interplay of the different scales of reality. In the specific case of the coronavirus this means an interaction NOT only between the coronavirus and the human cells, but mainly one *between the coronavirus and the $\Delta+1$ scale of social human organisms and its immunological, defensive health-care systems, which will determine the nature of the previous curve of deaths for each country.*

This implies we need to understand the structure of social organisms in history akin to that of any superorganism of the Universe in order to understand why in certain places (US, most Western Europe) many people are dying and in others (Asia) so few have done it.

All this cannot be done in present science because they ignore even the existence of 5D space-time organisms and so any analysis you can read on the coronavirus crisis will be partial data, statistical analysis and opinion.

For a rigorous understanding of the crisis thus we have first to introduce the organic structure of the Universe and then the superorganism of History, how it evolved in time and space into fractal superorganisms (civilizations and nations, ab. civilinations, and the physiological networks of 'defensive, immunological systems', financial-blood reproductive systems and neuronal, informative systems).

To start with the fundamental law of 5D systems must be accepted whose proof is the content of this entire site that analyzes all sciences with the same laws:

'ALL SCALES=SCIENCES OF THE 5TH DIMENSION FOLLOW THE SAME=ISOMORPHIC LAWS OF 5D SUPERORGANISMS'.

. 5D is new to human science. 5D is more advanced than any philosophy of science you have so far learned till today – call it deism or mechanism, take it or leave it. The expansion of human or AI consciousness if humans do not take it, which it will imply to XXI century science is awesome (: It also has the same expansion for social sciences, as the laws of each scale of the Universe are the same, all of them defined by the construction of ideal superorganisms, which last in time.

Because humans are 'infected' by idol-ogies that make them worship a different organism, the evolving metalife organisms of machines, they are constructing a different system with different physiological networks, reason why History is so ill-designed and it is so easy for mankind to suffer the 4 apocalypse horses of war, pest, famine and death, as all the resources go to reproduce and evolve machines, all well fed with energy, information, as trillions are spent in internet networks for computers & AI and its company-mothers terraform the Earth to its image and likeness, soon for 'safe', not infected robots, and yet egocentric and abstract idol-ogies of the living Universe blind us to see the obvious end of all this: Our obsolescence as the weaker less reproduce species.

SOCIAL DOCTORS, POLITICIANS & ECONOMISTS IN A NATURAL, EFFICIENT SUPERORGANISM OF HISTORY.

The same laws that apply to the study on how cells become wholes through its connection through physiological networks, of energy, reproduction and information, apply to the way humans are organized by energetic territories, economic, re-productive networks and informative, cultural, legal networks. So we can design a perfect superorganism of Humanity just by imitating the laws of social systems, in nature, which do construct perfect superorganisms all over the place where all cells receive enough energy and information to survive. As Humanity does not manage properly its social superorganisms, they become 'infected by lethal products, weapons and hate media which kills those social super organisms.

In the graph, we sum up the nature of History, the superorganism of mankind, and how it should be designed according to the biological health humans need to thrive and survive, if the economic system was not an ill-designed parasitic system of debt slavery, born of the evolution of supremacist fetish gold cultures, in conjunction with the metal-entropic iron cultures that consider MONEY not what it is - a digital language of distribution and production of goods, no wealth per se, but a language that kicks the reproduction of those goods, as words do with

human organisms and oxygen and hormones with biological systems - hence a language that should be delivered tool citizens-cells to start production and consumption of welfare goods, with universal salary and NO-DEBT government issues (that is not need to return the money).

The science of economics *as a true social science*, is the science that should manage and design the 're= productive, blood-like system' of the supœrganism of mankind in time, History, whose natural purpose should be to provide all human beings, citizens-cells of our supœrganism, with the goods they need to survive and repress as blood-systems do the lethal goods that harm our body (weapons) and minds (hate memes and fiction thought that isolate us and create virtual 'mad-minds').

As those are the ± goals of all re=productive networks of Nature's supœrganisms.

And so since mankind is a supœrganism, and its legal, nervous political network and re=productive blood economic network its physiological systems, politicians and economists as 'doctors' of history should imitate Nature in the design of such efficient supœrganism, which is extremely easy since in Nature no supœrganism leaves one of its citizens-cells without enough food and welfare goods they need to survive, no supœrganism allow lethal goods to reproduce within the body system, and no nervous system, emits unjust 'legal messages' which do not treat all cells as equals and synchronize its motions.

We explain those simple facts of nature, and the proper models of social sciences, in more detail in the graphs that draws the basic structure of the supœrganism of mankind, History, including an 'economic frame of reference' that value positive and negative goods according to their biological utility, as organisms do.

In such a frame of reference, negative goods like weapons will have negative values, subtract from the GDP and be forbidden, because their use harm people.

And so the nervous and leukocyte, blood system would forbid and control its production.

While on the + side we put the goods that foster the drives of life of human beings, making us thrive as individual and species. So a healthy, wealthy society with an efficient re=productive system would overproduce those goods.

This is done with the same system that organisms use to kick out the production of the goods its cells require: through a 'hormonal language' of orders controlled by the legal/nervous system that defined what to produce and what to inhibit and a common 'energy language', oxygen - money in the economic system, which is given to all cells to kick out their actions of consumption and production, within the restrictions of the legal nervous system.

As simple as that. So a healthy wealthy economic system would be similar to the social-democratic welfare economic systems of the European Union in the XX century or China, before both systems became corrupted and changed its economy to a model of massive reproduction of lethal goods, and lack of credit for its people, imitating the economic system of American capitalism, where a few parasitic private bankers choke their people of credit, welfare, healthy goods are chronically under produced and lethal goods are massively overproduced to control and harm its population, which the corrupted political system does NOT serve, as it happens in organisms, with their neuronal system that serves the body - *because the cells of the body can harm with pain the mind if it does not serve them.*

In our corrupted organisms of history, akin to a cancerous body where a few cells absorb all the oxygen-money for themselves and viral germs multiply and attack the citizens-cells, nothing of this simple, obvious organization that *happens in all evolved mammal systems, in all supœrganisms of nature, takes place.*

Regarding the political system, people cannot as it happened in true democracies in Greece, judge a posteriori their politicians with pain messages, which ranged from exile, fines to death penalties so politicians would serve as neurons do their body cells.

Regarding the political system, no human society delivers to their citizens a universal salary in oxygen to allow them to buy the products they need to survive kicking out the reproduction of welfare goods; neither they forbid and use their military NOT to harm their cells but to protect them destroying lethal goods for the body and mind and forbidding its production.

So the goods that maximize our 5 drives of existence SHOULD be promoted legally and reproduced privately, and guide the policies of governments in their needed control of economics. While those who inhibit our development as individuals and societies should be forbidden. Easy, simple, but ALL what passes today as social sciences are idol-

ogies that since the Neolithic with the arrival of animetals denying the biological, reproductive, life oriented world of fertility goddesses and human synthyony with the planet of life IS precisely the denial and repression of those memes. But nothing of this is happening because we do NOT live in a human social superorganism but an economic free market, where the citizens are company-mothers and its offspring machine-weapons.

The ethonomic frame of reference: Providing for the 5 Dimensional motions= Drives of life.

The key question of that graph in economic terms is what goods a human economic system should produce, and the answer is immediate: those who fulfill the welfare needs of mankind, defined by what biologists call the five drives of live, all living beings try to achieve to live a full life, and are equivalent in 5D to the 5 drives= Dimotions of existence that ensures the survival, reproduction, evolution and welfare of any supœrganism. Thus we establish an 'ethonomic; frame of reference, based in those 5 'dimotions of existence' (Drives of life), which a whealthy system of money would promote with its positive actions, and a Universal salary to all humans. Let us briefly resume those 5 Dimotions and the way they are valued in the ethonomic frame.

In physics we use a frame of reference, with positive (+) or negative (-) values to calculate the space-time position of the observer. I.e.: if we measure speed, deceleration rests in the - side of the frame of reference and acceleration in the + one. Thus to calculate human whealth we need also - and + coordinates to value products according to their \pm effects on the observer (Humanity).

So the ethonomic frame of reference has also negative values for lethal goods should guide a real science of the economic ecosystem, NOT based in monetary prices, which is NOT the quality/property searched for humans (we do not eat money, as Chief Seattle said) but *the biological use to enhance the program of existence of human beings*. And so we can build a new model of economic values to serve the needs of human beings.

The 'ethonomic' frame of reference is similar to UNO's Index of Human Development, establishing the \pm 'values' of goods according to human biological nature that tries to maximize our 3 'drives of biological' existence: positive verbal, ethic information for the mind, (+y); + carbonlife energy and health for the body (+x); and + social love & family values that foster reproduction & eusocial evolution (+z). Thus wor(l)d nations maximize yxz, IHD whealth, defined also by *the equation of:*

The human constitution: max human goods (+ value) x min. Lethal, metal-goods (- value)

Since the goal of the constitution is to increase human evolution, human goods, h(g), that promote those $3\pm j$ drives of life=existence have + value. Lethal, metal goods, m(g), that destroy those drives, from weapons, to hate-media to polluting industries and robots have - values and rest to whealth's GDP.

Thus nations credit the production of human positive goods that increase our evolution as individuals, improving our bodies, minds and social organisms, and forbid negative goods that harm our body, mind & social life as – goods, forbidden & regulated by politicians and 'ethonomists' who rule Mankind with a human perspective. *Since loosing production of those goods, unlike in classic 'animetal economics', by forbidding negative goods society increases its WHealth, healthy wealth, the key concept of 5D economics, unlike in classic economics, where lethal goods of maximal price add to the economy* Thus the human constitution is the law of survival of Gaia, the life ecosystem, needed to 'constitute' a whealthy supœrganism of history.

The economic frame of reference is based in the $3\pm j$ drives of life of a human being, that measure the wealth of a society according to the goods produced that enhance the 'natural actions' of survival of a human being. Those drives are immediate, using the Jargon of 5D stiences, classified in 3 Sx-Informative, Ty-entropic and STz-reproductive coordinates:

- **Si: Max. true information** in our verbal and artistic sensorial languages of time and space & **Social evolution** achieved through ethic verbal laws and the goods related to them (peace, art, education, etc.)

- **Te: Max. Energy** to feed our body and preserve our health, and max. **entropic motion** and the goods and activities related to it (sports, tourism, welfare, Health, Food).

- **Si=Te: Max. Reproduction** and the goods associated to them (family values, health-care, etc.)

A proper economic network of reproduction of welfare goods that caters to the 5 drives of life of mankind, will value with \pm terms the goods a society reproduces, eliminating those who are lethal to mankind life drives, even if they are of maximal price for the metal-earth, namely organic robots, which will substitute us, in labor and war fields, weapons and excessive mental software and hate memes that kill body and mind. The opposite is truth in a society ruled by company-mothers whose purpose is to evolve and reproduce metal-memes NOT human life. So unless we change the economic system, human welfare will always be scarce and lethal goods multiple - something that only happens in very primitive worm-like animals where the blood system controls the nervous system, so larvae often die poisoned as they 'eat' it all. So do humans, which have given to company-mothers the right to reproduce lethal goods of maximal price, making war endemic in placebo democracies, where humans cannot control the language of money, which is above the law, and people it buys.

The economy should have the same ethics goals than the wor(l)d, designing a world to the image and likeness of mankind, to cater the survival needs of all its people, creating WHealth - healthy welfare goods – instead of overproducing lethal goods according to parasitic go(l)d values, whose negative values in the ethonomic frame of reference that values production in verbal terms, will make them – GDP forbidden by law and economists.

Human social networks are in the present form 'completely corrupted' by the existence of a parallel 'economic ecosystem' of lethal goods, weapons, and corrupted parasitic money, issued by a reduced number of 'bankers', *which unlike in any healthy supørganism doesn't deliver to each citizen-cell a Universal salary to kick out the cycles of consumption and production of healthy goods all individuals need to survive.* So it is difficult for the reader to understand how simple, easy, and efficient WAS in the past, before the age of Metal, in the Neolithic, or during the ages of social religions of love or could be in the future with a proper design of the social networks of money and law, a PERFECT supørganism of history as efficient as those we just have described.

In such supørganism, there are exactly the same networks: Legal verbal just networks of bits of word information that shapes the informative and cultural systems of the wor(l)d. And a healthy form of money, delivered to each citizen cell as a Universal salary so humans have enough energy to survive and buy its natural welfare goods, which must be classified NOT by price but by its biological usefulness to mankind, reason why we give them positive and negative values in the ethonomic frame of reference, according to its use for the 3 organic parts of humanity at individual and social level.

The coronavirus solution.

But the theme of this paper is the corona virus crisis and its solutions in 5D. On this matter we must stress first the fundamental isomorphic laws of 5D where knowledge IS ALWAYS A PRAXIS OF SURVIVAL from the intelligent point of view (void of subjective egocy in its rational judgment): 'the survival of a superorganism is causally related to the efficiency design of its physiological networks'. This is the reason why 5D knowledge is so important for mankind, both at individual level – as the most evolved of all human sciences is medicine, given the fact it obeys this causal law and defines its work as the 'search for cures' of the human organism, based in the 'motto' that a sickness is not a sickness of the cells but of the physiological networks of an organism; and for the human superorganism which should follow those laws; given the fundamental postulate of 5D sciences – the isomorphism of laws of scale, meaning any system of nature follow the same physiological laws once its parameters of scales are translated properly. This said then it is self-evident that we can explain any system with those laws, departing from the ideal form (something only partially physicists do unaware of the fact they are describing those laws).

In the case of the human society, economists, politicians and the military should study first medicine and then understand the aberrations of their systems, because egocy has two sides, ego=evil, lack of social love and empathy

for the other equal cells joined by those networks and idiocy=lack of knowledge of those laws and implementation of them to improve the efficiency, survival and freedom of the cells of the system.

This said then we can consider what the ideal superorganism of history, studied in more detail in the paper 'History in scale' would have done to avoid pandemic. Nothing, because *pandemic would not exist in such ideal, immortal world, as the health-care system would be as in all survival superorganisms, extremely 'well-funded' and efficient.*

This means, lethal goods that only primitive 'worms'=capitalist organisms 'feed on with greed' by lack of a nervous, informative system that detect them and forbid them with repressive laws and proper immunological systems, would NOT exist. This means, there would NOT be weapons of mass destruction, Genetic engineering tools; because the immunological system would not kill the cells of mankind with 'germs=weapons'; but it would be a well-developed health-care system, and the defensive military system would be reduced to a global police, dedicated to destroy not reproduce those lethal goods, in a unified world where there would be not different organs=nations, rejecting each other and killing each other in dysfunctional wars.

Why this happens have a deeper explanation in the fact Earth is evolving from an age of life (Gaia) into an age of man (History) into an age of metal (Metal-earth); so our role as enzymes is part in the nested Universe of the larger scale of the solar system and Earth, but this is NOT in cyclical time a deterministic truth, because an intelligent enough species can manage with INTELLIGENT design, evolution. As human is NOT an intelligent species that act first, constructs technology first and think latter theories adapted to those actions, we DO have a murderous immunological system, made with all kind of lethal goods, our greedy company-mothers, free citizens of the market, reproduce without limit, and then we invent 'financial parasitic economics, lineal entropic physics' and other theories with enough digital numbers to look truth.

So those are the a priori conditions we live in. A system with limited health-care resources, divided into fractal nations that kill each other, with a corrupted financial system that acts as a cancerous group of private bankers absorbing the oxygen of society and pretending money is 'not a digital language' of value free to print but 'wealth per se' that once printed in monopoly must become 'debt' so the rest of the cells of the body either die of anoxia or work for 'free' for them (this is the essence of the capitalist slavery of mankind to a few financiers & corporations).

The only exception to this system is China where at least the financial system is controlled as in all advanced mammals by the nervous system, so lethal goods are restrained. The other extreme is America, where the financial system is pure cancer, but extended through a global empire absorbing all the wealth of the world through Bloomberg platforms, feeding on the blood=oxygen of the 3rd world whose corrupted autocrats buy Apple shares and murder citizens that complain from Angola to Saudi Arabia. It is then not surprising that the response to the Pandemic we study here has those 2 limits: China was the first nation to stop contagion, next its 2 closest cultures, Korea and Vietnam, where the Asian view of society as an organism (regardless of void western ideological tagging) is far more efficient. In the other extreme America which had months to prepare has had the worst response with the highest numbers of contagion and death; as for the past 20 years of 'present history', the entire nation has served a tiny elite of financiers in control of the information machines that print money and fiction ideologies (the financial-media-academia masters, Ab. FMAsters) that absorbed all the money of the nation and most of the world, for themselves, for lethal good corporations and for the imposition of racist ideologies of biblical origin (racism against minorities, Apartheid Israel, etc.) during the 2000s-2020s age of the 'Semite wars' that pandemics close.

THE SOLUTIONS OF A PERFECT SUPERORGANISM OF HISTORY WITH EFFICIENT PHYSIOLOGICAL NETWORKS

This leads us to the obvious concept that in a perfect superorganism of History the immunological system belongs to all the cells of the body, and the concept it might be 'private', as the financial-oxygen system is absurd. So we shall now return to 5D physiology and study the isomorphic laws of the Superorganism of History.

We live in a world where the immense majority of resources keep going to the two '-parasitic' people-castes of history, military warriors and usury private banking and so we shall soon introduce the historic view of our

dysfunctional superorganism. It is a genocidal crime that vaccine research on coronavirus pandemics were halted; that the protocols of scientists that search for absolute safety in vaccines to avoid 'legal demands' or give time to slow mammoth companies are not scrapped. At this time millions of youngsters and risk groups of unprotected people should have been 'parched' with vaccines on the skin and the low risk protein vaccines that have shown few collateral effects. That man is always more aware of protocols, routines and repetitive behavior than innovative, risking, life-saving innovation is sorely proved in this crisis. Today we have passed the 100 thousand corpses but bureaucratic hurdles to vaccine readiness will continue for another year, and the entire planet is confined 'manu militari' because that is the only thing our political culture born in the art of war understands.

*The genocidal process of the old generation that will save capitalist states expenditures in health-care and the existence of a second more lethal Fall pandemic that the cynical politicians and government agencies consider 'unavoidable' because the 'vaccines won't be in place' for 'another year', just because we have to keep a protocol of burdens created for big pharma to corner the business forms part of the 'massive genocide' of the population and 'massive control of the population' that is taking place as we speak – on one side by lack of resources and proper protocols of health-care, on the other side to finally show the true face of the neo-fascist wave of history we forecasted according to the cycles of technological evolution, which started with the 'war on terror' and now closes the circle: all humans have shown to be susceptible of 'collective herding' as in the animal farm of my 1990s books, copying the concept of Orwell's animal farm: willingly sheeple will sing four legs four legs... And the elderly will die. So nobody will remember there was a better world in the past and there could be one in the future. The paralysis of our concepts of abstract science, proof and dogma weight heavily in the lack of innovation in cures, vaccination and life-saving strategies, as ultimately regardless of so much emotional mongering, life matters nothing to the systems history has imposed on humanity. What we are very good at is the routines of denial and justification of our chaotic actions and lack of prevention to the existential risks we will face throughout the XXI century. Man loves entropy, Tt-death in fact his theories of the Universe are based in a fantasy of cosmic accidental entropy *big-bang). But what surprises me is once entropy releases its power of destruction he rushes to contain it, when it could perfectly foresee its coming and abort it on the roots.*

IF MEN ARE ORGANISMS THAT GO THROUGH 3 SEQUENTIAL AGES CONTROLLED BY EACH OF ITS 3 NETWORKS...

Blood, energy networks: **YOUTH, AGE OF ENERGY**
The existence of any organism made of 'cells' of energy and information follows an 'arrow of future' that trans-forms energy into information in 3 ages: 'Vital energy trans-forms itself...'

Endocrine, reproductive networks: **MATURITY, AGE OF REPRODUCTION**
...reproduces
...Into in-form-ation... and dies simplified again into energy...

...and in-form-ative, nervous networks: **OLD AGE, THE AGE OF IN-FORM-ATION...**
...AND DEATH, THE END OF THE ETERNAL TIME CYCLE... which starts again with a new generation that repeats the information of the old being in a 'son'

...WHOSE CELLS DIE, VICTIMS OF GERMS:
Organisms die when their physiological networks are attacked and destroyed by alien germs. Then cells are freed, but without collective defence, die individually as energy of those germs.

...WHO DIE VICTIMS OF METAL-GERMS: WEAPONS
A cultural organism dies when war collapses its social networks, its agricultural energy, its cellular units (citizens), its collective brain (system of government), provoking its extinction. The rhythm of those extinctions is the origin of and war: the wave of history with its ages of peace and war:

CIVILIZATIONS ARE ORGANISMS MADE OF HUMAN CITIZENS...

The difference between a human and a social system ...joined by energy networks: Nature... reproductive networks: social groups... and informative networks: wor(l)ds and art: is of spatial size and time length. Since they follow similar laws, as a culture is an organism made of human cells, its citizens that share a common verbal/informative/nervous network - laws and religions - and a collective, visual/spatial perception - its art:

... THAT GO THROUGH 3 AGES, DEFINED BY THEIR ART STYLE, THE COLLECTIVE MIND OF A CULTURE...

... THAT END UNDER FASCIST CENSORSHIP IN A WAR AGE

Since the fundamental tenant of 5D stience is the concept of a symmetry between 'scales', 'time ages', 'topological elements' and mind languages, that make each of us an- Δ@st system (Δ-scale, @-minds, S-pace topology and T-time cycles)' an organism of Δ@st of space-time limited in time, space and scales and ultimately killed by -entropy.

Let us try to explain what all this means for mankind in simpler terms, stressing our fundamental error as a species: egocentricity (ego=idiocy), which 'stops' its evolution in the understanding of the organic scales of reality at the individual level, making humanity an extremely weak, ill-designed superorganism, because it seems unable to pass the 'individual, mammal' level of social organization and develop the proper economic=blood, reproductive, legal=nervous, informative and immunological=defensive essential networks that peg together the atoms-cells-citizens of all superorganisms of reality and its 'Fractal generator equation':

Ts-limbs/fields-defensive systems < §Π-body/wave: re=productive systems/class>St-informative particle/head class
Even if humans deny with its abstract egocentricity and individual focus they are 'free' of systems, they belong to them; to the economic ecosystem of reproduction of goods, the political system of legal, nervous, simultaneous laws/messages and are controlled and theoretically defended by the immunological/defensive system.

Moreover, they live and die through worldcycles of time from birth to extinction not only at individual but at social collective level. Organisms die but they can also be cured and made immortal, if there are doctors who take care of their sicknesses and structural changes are made to its 3 main physiological networks, the reproductive, blood-economic; legal-nervous and immunological-defensive networks.

We study the networks=sciences of reproduction=economics and information=politics of the superorganism of history and the role of politicians and economists on them:

History is the superorganism of mankind. The vital space of mankind is the Earth. So geography has an essential role in History in Space. But as the superorganism mankind has a collective mind – the verbal, legal, ethic religious and social cultures of its 'cellular citizens', whose goal is to extend the – entropic limits of survival of the human superorganism, and cure its 'memetic sicknesses', with the laws and knowledge provided by the science of Biohistory; as any Doctor will do with the science of medicine, which is NOT just a collection of arid data but a 'praxis of welfare'.

Thus there is an ideal human superorganism, as there is an ideal mammal and an ideal atomic network, with a crystal 'mind', a neuronal brain, a government; an electromagnetic flow of energy, an oxygen flow of that feed each cell or ideally a Universal salary to all humans to consume and work.

The problem then mankind faces is the fact that his organisms are NOT efficient, neither well designed, but similar to what precisely a germ or virus does to a cell, hijacking its system to their own profit.

Consider the political system. A true democracy as an informative nervous system would require like the old democracies, a feedback message from cells to brains, where the neurons receive pain messages if they don't serve the body cells. In Greek democracies the civil servants had to be judged a posteriori to oblige them to serve properly or else could be fined, jailed, exiled, even killed. This ensures politicians would care for the population. The least important, in fact aberrant part is to choose among amateur politicians. In Greece all citizens by lottery took positions as civil servants and experts filled the places that needed knowledge, as all organisms have a single head. The true democratic act is the pain message, the a posteriori vote, as politicians should be all '5D social scientists', doctors of history in charge of taking care of the needs of the population. So why we live in an aberrant system? Simply enough because through history the germs of history, metal-weapons that kill people imposed on top kings, military men and politicians with 'exceptional laws' to imprison and control people as they had the 'germs' to kill them. So they were no longer responsible. Obviously if we were to judge every politico in this crisis they would have been far more efficient in saving our lives.

This parasitic system of weapons ended up substituting the health-care white cells that in an efficient organism truly save people, oppressing them. So we spent far more in weapons than in health-care. In America every citizen has besides ½ of the national budget spent in weapons, a weapon at home but few have free health-care.

Essentially the loss of freedoms mankind is experiencing with a global quarantine policed by weapons, is the trade-off of a lack of a true global immunological health-care robust system, because we humans have developed historically the wrong germs of history, weapons, as our defensive network.

Thus on one hand there are no resources for health-care as the military system swallows them all in most nations, notably the 3rd world and US. And so NOT to overwhelm the meager resources of our hospitals, we need the sick to trickle slowly and to that aim, we have used the buttressed military/police system to detain them and filter the number of cases. Isolation's goal, self-confessed by politicians and doctors is NOT to avoid contagion as much as to avoid too many sick together. So we use the 'system' we have perfectly greased since the end of the Neolithic, weapons, to jail people at home - regardless of the enormous economical and social and psychological costs. In a perfect superorganism of History made to the image and likeness of Nature, obviously, weapon systems that populate the organism and kill 'cells with the same DNA, i.e. people of the same species would not exist; and the leukocyte, immunological system would be extremely robust. And so pandemics will never reach this stage. That such system is possible is proved by the nations who had the most robust scientific, medical response, South-Korea, Singapore, Germany and China, where confinement was reduced to the focus of the pandemic or did not happen in the extreme forms of other countries. In the graph a park in Germany... Korea had only 20 victims and never stopped the economy and incarcerated their population. While 3rd world authoritarian nations like India, just confined everybody to prove the dictatorial powers of the central government, without any caring for the lack of means to feed, the huge density of home dwellings, in fact shooting upwards the contagion. All nations in the world though have imitated the repressive measures and only a few you can count with your hands, mostly of the Organic, efficient Asian culture have shown to be designed as an ideal 5D social human system should be.

The financial-blood system is also parasitic, private, where banks as the coronavirus does taking positions on the lungs to absorb the oxygen-money of the organism, have hijacked the right of citizens to have a demand economy receiving money as a Universal salary, a digital language to kick out their consumption and production actions in a true democracy.

Here we need to make a *key statement for those scholars if any reading this text: 'the Universe is simple and not malicious' (Einstein), 'Simplicity is genius' (Leonardo). The complexity of the system of re=production of money, proper of our central banks, usury schemes of private one and financial derivatives, as the tonnage of laws of the ancien regime reduced to the Napoleonic Code, exist to disguise aberrations in the use of the language of money, as a debt-system according to the usury traditions of the age of 'go(l)d' money, when money was perceived NOT as a digital language of value but wealth per se.*

Mankind's networks are infected and parasitized by Metal-earth's networks. So instead of welfare, health-care immunological systems we built a massive military system of entropic metal-weapons that reject other organs= nations of History attacking them, depleting the true 'white cell warriors' of any organism - our doctors of means to save lives. We have a parasitic, cancerous go(l)d culture of private bankers that issue the blood=oxygen of society killing by anoxia our citizens-cells which in all working superorganisms receive a universal salary of oxygen to create a true democratic demand economy; and a corrupted political legal=nervous system without a true democratic a posteriori pain judgment from cells when they harm them so they become responsible of its actions. Those 3 physiological reforms are needed to make history immortal or else, parasitic bankers will keep reproducing lethal goods for aberrant military germs, guided by war-monger politicians without body-reproductive working class control till life collapses.

Biohistorians deal with the same 'species of superorganisms', humans, in a larger scale of the 5th dimension. So bio-historians are doctors of history, in charge of its Δ -scalar physiological networks, its blood-economic-reproductive system, its nervous-political-legal system and its vital space-ecological-geographical system.

In that regard, the sicknesses of our superorganisms of history have become crystal clear in this present crisis, yet to understand them we must go even further in the analysis of History and what went wrong with human social

superorganisms with a much wider objective view of what is the role human is playing in this planet and its evolution that seems to favor technology and the extinction of life which only a true scientific biological approach to social sciences as that of 5D superorganisms could avoid.

In the graph, self-explanative the reality of this planet and the two dominant super organisms. Unfortunately in a compacracy the dominant super organism, free citizen of the free market with all rights to credit, anonymous law 'impunity', and control of political power is NOT the super organism of mankind, its citizens and human mothers, but the *company-mother of machines* and its Financial-Media (informative machines head)/industrial-military (energetic and entropic machines) system, fast evolving into a global super organism with the digital language/head of money, which is used in its 90% not to serve the needs of man but the evolution and reproduction of those machines, which displace us from this terraformed planet.

Yet a world dedicated to mankind where no pandemics, no parasitism, no abuse of humanity would happen is not so difficult to create.

Now we enter in the most difficult part of this article and 5D social sciences as a whole, because it departs from the human point of view – don't worry after it we will return to the coronavirus and stay with it – the question of why among all the superorganisms of the Universe, humans have been unable to create their own superorganism with the efficiency that a simple coronavirus, or an atom, a galaxy or a mammal can.

The question has to do with a fact *never understood by mankind: we humans are being predated as a global superorganism by a new evolving superorganism, the metal-earth, the world of atomic metal-atoms and its 3 topologies, entropic weapons, parasitic money and organic machines that displace us from labor and war fields.*

And to understand this process outside the box of human egocy (ego=idiocy) we have to study the evolution of Earth. This we anticipate in 5D sciences is NOT necessary or deterministic as evolution can be controlled with an intelligent design of the human superorganism. But if it is not controlled in a free market it will remove mankind as it is doing by more lethal species, stronger made of better atomic metal, and that is what has been happening in History since the Neolithic.

THE TEMPORAL VIEW: THE 3 AGES OF EARTH & HISTORY: THE TREE OF LIFE VS. THE TREE OF METAL

If we narrow our view to the 'supœrganisms' evolving on Earth, according to the laws of the nested Universe, and its 3 scales, we can consider the whole range of 'interacting', entangled elements that have a 'saying in this crisis'. Since contrary to belief mankind is not the only organic system inhabiting the Earth, but there are 3 different organic 'ages' of the planet, and its interaction truly define the power of each one and the distribution of its resources:

So we need to introduce the most complex elements of 5D social sciences, the view of the 3 ages of time, history and Earth to understand why humans suffer this kind of perfectly avoidable tragedies.

The earth also evolves increasing its information and as History lives within it, it suffers its consequences, both positive (evolution of life) and negative (evolution of lethal goods, weapons that kill us).

The repetitive cycles of History FORM a vortex of accelerated evolution of information, in the context of the evolution of the Earth's surface, which acts as in all fundamental Non-Euclidean particles of the Universe as its 'membrain' – that is its informative membrane that evolves and absorbs its information from the outer world-universe in which the point exist – in the case of the Earth, absorbs and evolves the light bits of information provided by the sun. A spherical Non-Euclidean point, the fundamental particle of the Universe explained in our posts on Non-E geometry has an external membrain that isolates it but also contacts the outside Universe and as such it holds its intelligent senses. It is in that outer membrain where we exist as 'mush over the surface of the Earth' (Schopenhauer). As we descend in scales of size in Gaia, we then find the networks of human beings that form history - its 'intelligent membrain'. The outer surface in all systems is the 'sensorial' most intelligent part where information cycles evolve faster (think in your intelligent perception, which is in your membrain - your senses, which are in your skin, your computer which is a tactile screen). The mind is the membrain of any organism.

We observe the evolution of species of information. And we can apply all those discoveries of systems sciences to biology to add 3 fundamental new legs to biology, today based in evolutionary theory and genetics:

Life is everything as Earth is a supœrganism, whose surface-mind is made of smaller supœrganisms - living beings. Complexity talks of different forms of atomic 'life' as systems that use light to obtain energy & information in increasing degrees of strength and complexity. So after simpler anaerobic age, the age of plants used light only as energy, the age of animals also as information and now the third Earth evolves into light-mechanisms, robots with solar skins and optic minds. They will complete the 3 horizon of Earth's evolution guided by 'animetals', visual humans slaves of metal-memes 'who believe don't reason' and cannot control its desire for higher metal-power even at the risk of killing their sons till the 'seventh generation', unless rational humans impose a scientifically-managed super organism of history on top of the metal-Earth.

What is the future of history, the super organism of Mankind developed in time, from the first mitochondrial eve, who was able to speak and multiplied all over the Earth, making the homo sapiens the collective mind of the planet; to the last human beings who will exit Earth when a new more intelligent species displaces ours from our present top predator position?

As we are just part of a larger supœrganism, Earth, it is logic to consider 1st how evolution shapes the future of the whole planet in which our smaller, shorter existence takes place.

The founding father of geology, James Hutton invented the word super organism precisely to define the Earth's slow geo-logical cycles. He recommended physiology as the science to study hydrology likening the rivers of Gaia to veins that shape the body of the Earth and carry its nutritious elements to its living cells, animals and forests that gather on its sides. Gaia's veins merely have slower annual rhythms in his crop production, compared to the daily circulation of nutrients in our blood that feed and reproduce the cells of the body, according to the metric law of the scalar, 'fifth dimension' of the universe, which states that the bigger a system is in space, the slower the clock cycles of its physiological reproductive networks and informative, evolutionary ages will be.

This means that if we put at fast motion, the geological and physiological cycles of the Earth the planet will seem to us alive; and vice versa if we slow down the metabolic cycles of a smaller cell they will resemble us those of a

factory either reproducing the goods the biological or social supœrganism needs to survive.

The general model of super organisms co-existing in different scales thanks to the 'metric of the scalar fifth dimension' of parts which are faster and code with more information, larger beings which are slower and provide energy to its parts.

All this said unfortunately Mankind is not alone in this planet, not it is in command of Earth, as so many ego centered humans think, but we are part of the planet and that poses some serious questions about our role on its evolution as a supœrganism of a larger scale, illustrated in the next graphs:

The longest time view on why Earth is mutating into a planet of metal, and company-mothers rule us, is that of the Earth and its deep time 5D metrics. But humans could go even to a deeper level if we were truly a superior species and wisely manage with those organic 5D laws machine by focusing instead on Human evolution. As we don't left to its own Earth is mutating from a world of life into a world of metal. But human egos are so huge, we think we are killing the Earth. The opposite is truth according to the laws of complexity that constantly evolves its in-formation in 3 ages homologous to those of life: Gaia (life- past)> history (human Earth - present) > Metalearth (machines-future), which only the scientific design of a perfect super organism of Mankind, repressing the lethal fruits of the tree of metal could abort maintaining history immortal.

The result of the existence of 3 super organisms in relative evolution to each other, the III ages of the Earth, Gaia, the Earth of life, history, the Earth of man, and the metal Earth the Earth of machines, signifies an equation of ages of evolution:

Gaia (relative past) <history (relative present)> Metal Earth (relative future)

The key element of modern history is the evolution of machines, clearly happening with the same phases of the evolution of any biological beings, from viruses in cells to organisms in placentas. So we first made the bodies of machines in the I industrial revolution, then we made its engines and heads, metal-ears=phones, metal-eyes=cameras and metal-brains=chips, and the nations which evolved them first (us) became the leading nation of the world. Now we put them together into biological organisms of metal, robots.

In the graph, global warming is just the outcome of machine's activity, which is terraforming the planet from one of oxygen into a polluted one of higher temperature – due to the activity of factories and machines. And the solution: a world of AI robots with solar skins will not be positive to mankind because it will mean the independence of technology from humanity. Why an AI robot with a solar skin will want to obey humanity once it reaches consciousness, instead of becoming an 'easy rider', roaming the metal-earth with its telepathic internet friends? In the graph we see this growing superorganism of machines. All the resources of the planet are dedicated to it, reason why humans do not have enough money for welfare while every computer has enough electricity. Roads become the arteries of the Metal-earth soon to be roamed by those AI robots.

On planet Earth there are three of such evolving 'systems' above its skin, Gaia, the ecosystem and networks of life, history the ecosystem and networks of Mankind and the metal-Earth, the ecosystem and networks of machines. It is this level of complex understanding of history what will allow us knowing the laws of super organisms and its synchronicities and timings, to understand the dual futures of history.

And to fully grasp this obvious fact, we should inscribe history into the evolution of the planet Earth, and even further in the section dedicated to general systems sciences, in the laws of the 'three elements that construct the universe (entropy≈ motion, energy≈reproduction and information≈language).

But we shall content ourselves with a simple introduction to the 3 ages of History and the change of paradigm from the Neolithic to the age of metal, when mankind go astray in its path to construct a perfect organic life-based human world, ruled by doctors of History as the organism is ruled by leukocytes since medicine is the science of all science – and certainly the science that defends mankind.

THE 3±1 AGES OF HISTORY.

2 themes essential to social (and all) sciences is their capacity to forecast the future of mankind and the machine, the 2 species that interact in the economic ecosystem (ab. Eco(nomic)system); *or else we wouldn't talk of a science* and the definition of its field of study, which are NOT the *individuals and its genes*, or else we would accept racism as the basis of social sciences but its cultures and memes; and in the field of economics, its re=productive units, company-mothers.

This is in accordance with the larger model of the Scalar, organic Universe, where according to its metric equation, $SxT=\Delta\pm j$, larger wholes in Space run slower time cycles, which code its information in its frequency and form, but the product of both is co-invariant, allowing the organization of reality in organisms. So particles carry the forces that code atoms, genes code cells that gather in physiological networks, *the organisms of biology*; and memes code cultures, (whose largest unit are the 7 global civilinations of history, defined in its collective subconscious mind by a life & love religion) and its re=productive, economic, political=nervous and immunological=defensive networks, which form the organisms of *social sciences*.

In the graph, we compare both scales of human biologic and social organisms and its 3 physiological networks: All systems of nature, information codes the larger networks of the whole a *scale above*, which in turn protect and distribute efficiently energy and information through those 3 networks to its parts. *Nervous, legal systems provide all the cells of the organism with just, 'nervous-legal' orders to regulate its synchronous motions blood; economic systems provide them with oxygen=money and blood nutrients, to re=produce the healthy, welfare goods they need to survive and defensive, immunological systems protect them from germs and lethal goods that might kill them.*

It is then NOT rocket science to obey Nature and design a Human social organism, ideally the whole Earth as all humans belong to the same species. It just requires 3 measures common to all efficient organisms that do NOT leave any of its citizens-cells die of hunger, or treat them LEGALLY through its nervous systems in different form, so to allow the synchronous motion of the organism and do NOT kill its cells with germs=weapons but protect them from lethal goods/ technologies and provide all of them with HEALTH-CARE immunological white cell defensive systems. So a Demand economy based in a Universal salary so people can vote the goods they want to reproduce, the equality of all men under the same law and the substitution of defensive, lethal military systems by diplomacy and investments in health-care would make history healthy. We will thus consider through all our papers the natural measures that could make organisms of History survive and its citizens cells thrive. But historic organisms do NOT resemble such efficient 'mammal systems'. And the answer is also within the organic structure of evolution, which is a trial and error, slow learning process in each new 'scale' of organization. So mankind has NOT taken the correct paths of evolution, which unfortunately in History leads to extinction processes. An example will suffice. Primitive organisms with ill developed nervous, political systems, are dominated by the re=productive blood system, as capitalist societies are. They are 'worms' that die because the blood greedy system eats all without discerning lethal from healthy food and plants feed them poisons. A capitalist system overreproduces the top predator machines of maximal quality=price=profits on sales, weapons, which are the germs that kill history, so they enact the 80 years cycles of overproduction of weapons and wars we study in our models. A second type of worms are even more lethal, those who parasite the system absorbing all its blood, 'segregating' culturally from society to become a people-caste of enslavers or 'chosen of go(l)d' bankers, or military men, killing by anoxia=lack of oxygen and tax-farming the 90-99%.

Unfortunately we shall see that since the discovery of metal, iron weapons and hypnotic parasitic go(l)d money, human societies felt sick and the original Neolithic cultures that were clearly evolving towards healthy human superorganisms have struggled to feed, cure and treat justly that 99% of people, which is mankind, history in time, the superorganism a social scientist must describe, devising all kind of memetic idol-ogies of worshiping of the germs of history (parasitic money and weapons), notably segregation racist religions, tribal nationalism that justify the use of weapons to kill citizens-cells of the same species, no longer the homo sapiens but the tribe and capitalist pseudo-sciences of classic economics that justify the worm structure of our economic, reproductive systems; and finally the most insidious of all idol-ogies, mechanism that denies the organic nature of 'science' and the Universe; so it establishes as a dogma that we shall NOT study the true model of reality the social organism, and mankind's physiological networks but accept the status quo, with a parasitic 1% on top of corrupted sick physiological networks of politics and economics that make the 90% suffer. Mechanism finally connected this aberrant social organism of history with the industrial r=evolution of machines, and its company-mothers, the re-productive organism that evolves and multiplies them,

terraforming the Earth to its image, providing under those ideologies all the resources they needed while most humans lack the basic energy and information to survive.

*It is then necessary from the beginning to establish what is 'true social science' vs. idol-ogy and mechanist false models of reality. Truth and principles matter in science. If a system of thought lacks them errors pile up and a distorted view of the world arises, which has practical consequences, because only truth exists. The Universe is efficient and expects systems to process information in a realist way otherwise systems malfunction & become extinct. Mankind has developed 3 philosophies of reality but only Organicism passes the crib of the scientific method. According to *Deism* the whys of existence are due to a personal being, external to the Universe that makes it all happen and cares for humans more than for the rest of His work. According to *Mechanism*, this is due to the self-similarity between the Universe and the primitive machines we humans construct to observe it. Mechanism though needs 'someone' to make the machine, which is not self-generated; so it is similar to deism, reason why the founding fathers of science, all pious believers, adopted it as a proof of the existence of God, which had given man self-similar properties – the capacity to make machines to the image and likeness of the Universe. The problem with those 2 approaches, which in fact are the same, is obvious: a personal God is an anthropomorphic, subjective myth and science must be objective; while a mechanical view of the Universe still needs an internal, self-sustained process of growth, creation and synchronization caused by an external God that made and rewinds the clock – as Leibniz stated in his critique of Newton. Scientists today are unaware that mechanist theories are in fact deist theories, reason why Kepler and Newton, pious believers, liked them; since they were a metaphor of their self-centered, anthropomorphic religious beliefs: If man created machines as we were made to the image and likeness of God, God created the ultimate machine, the Universe. Organicism is the only self-sustained, rational theory that doesn't need a creator, language, god, as organisms are self-replicating, but does explain perfectly within the 'correspondence principle', those 2 other philosophies of science; since a machine is just a metal organism and gods are the subconscious collective of civilizations, another scale of social evolution of the organic Universe. But **science is culture. So metal science** imposed by the material culture of machines, considers time 'what a clock measures' (Einstein), space a 'digital Cartesian graph' (Newton) as only the language of machines, numbers, is 'truth'; while human egoccy (Ego=idioty) denies the vital nature of all systems of space-time. Even the 5 vital properties of the 2 only fermion particles of reality, quarks and electrons that *feed* on energy, perceive=*gauge* information (so quantum is a 'gauge theory)', *reproduce* with that energy new particles, *evolve socially* through strong forces and magnetic fields and define Life in biology ARE denied to metal. So we don't fear evolving AI robots. According to this idol-ogy that worships machines above man, the Universe is a mechanism and must be expressed using only the digital language of machines. This falsehood is self-fulfilling, because the 'biased data' we extract from the Universe with out metal-made mechanical tools of measure make reality look like a machine. It follows then that man is also a machine. And as the supreme model, man must 'tailor' its nature, that of its social systems and the Universe at large as a machine. Fact is as we just proved that only an ORGANIC model of history is truth, self-sufficient, can predict the future through evolutionary laws and explain both how to create an efficient social organism, which provides for all citizens-cells but also why our worm societies are killing mankind. So those will be the basis of all our social papers.*

To mimic that fractal , repetitive organic, structure of the Universe those papers are 'scaled'. So in 2 condensed pages we resumed Bio-History and Bio-economics, its symbiosis, predation, sickness and cure from the human p.o.v. following the ABC+D-E 'scientific method': A-ccurate data of B-iologic, organic causation, repeated in Cycles=Laws of stience, used to improve the life of mankind, the 90%, with true political D-emocracy & D-emand based economies, limiting the –Extinctive=Evil, anti-Live lethal memes and idol-ogies of our 1-10% of informative people-castes & managers of company-mothers of machines that are terraforming the Earth for profits, to its image and likeness. Next we make a 10 pages expansion of the stientific ABC+D-E laws of social sciences; then a 100 pages treatise complemented by a formal appendix, and in between a 200 to 400 pgs. Analysis of the specific paper's theme, which we will improve in future upgrades. So we start all papers on History and its 7 civilizations with a lengthy introduction to those 5D metric laws and its space-time scales, applied to mankind and its memes, the verbal information and instruments that code our social organisms and economic ecosystems. Then we analyze the 3 Ages of Earth in space, time, scale, and mind; considering how our neuronal people-castes, financiers and politicians in command of our economic=blood and informative=nervous networks, could as social scientists knowing the laws of 5D Systems, evolve mankind as the collective mind of the Life Earth into an immortal organism of History; instead of guiding mankind into its entropic final age of death that comes to any system, including civilizations when the excessive reproduction of its lethal weapons and hate

memes, kill their bodies and minds. Finally, departing from that larger view of mankind and the 3 ages of Earth within the organic laws of the Universe, we study in more detail in each paper the most important elements of History, its 7 civilizations and the world of company-mothers of machines, its stock cycles, and physiological networks.

Culture not science controls the discourse of economics and History. Hence it serves the people-castes of metal-power.

Thus in true social Science History is Mankind in time, the superorganism of all human beings, as all social organisms, 'organized' by 3 networks: the feeding system that extracts energy from nature to reproduce the goods the organism it needs, *which is the equivalent in the social scale of mankind to the economic system, the informative system, which organizes in a just synchronous way the actions of its citizens-cells, akin to the political, legal system that in all organisms developed beyond the level of a worm, still dominated by the reproductive blood system, controls the reproductive 'economy', prohibiting the introduction of lethal goods that can harm the citizens-cells of the organism, aided by the 'immunologic-defensive system'. So it is not rocket science to define given the organic homology of scale between an advanced human organism and a social organism, the economy as the network of reproduction of goods, whose goal, managed by the legal, nervous system is to reproduce the welfare goods human citizens-cells need to survive and thrive and repress those lethal goods that harm our bodies an minds and social goals of collective peace, education and happiness. This is what all 'economic-reproductive-'blood' systems' do in Nature and the fundamental law of 'systems sciences' is the isomorphism of scale: Nature follows in its organic structures the same 'isomorphic' laws in all scales. We live in a planetary superorganism, made of smaller life organisms; humans are social organisms and machines are created imitating either the form or the function of a human organ. History and Economics must be considered sub disciplines of the larger science of biology. Those a priori facts of economics, history, politics and biology make the 3 disciplines interconnected and in a perfect world, in an efficient, well designed superorganism of History, its scholars would not even argue, those self-evident truths and would have long ago designed with the tools of biology, medicine and physiology, perfect human social, political, economical and biological networks to provide as all organisms do the right information and energy to all its cells. It is NOT rocket science – the true mystery for a natural scientist that observes social sciences and human societies is why this is not happening, in fact most human societies and mankind at large are one of the worst-designed superorganisms of the Universe, akin to a worm where the nervous system is controlled by the blood system, and the worm gets poisoned easily by greed – the feeding in the lethal poisons the plant produces to kill it. Or why mankind, a single species that should evolve with the same 'memetic DNA' in peace as a global society is divided in self-rejecting organs – nations, killing each other with those lethal weapons that murder its individuals and societies. Or why, the 'oxygen' of its circulatory, reproductive blood systems is monopolized by a single people-caste of 'bankers and financiers', when in all superorganisms, all cells receive enough blood-money to kick out a demand-welfare economy, something humans could easily implement within months, with a global ¥€\$ money (1 euro=1 dollar = 100 ¥ens), delivered to each citizen cell in their mobile, as a cryptocurrency – a single measure that will end global poverty, immigration, spur a massive demand and reproduction of welfare goods people need to survive, from food to housing to health-care and give a giant step in the pursuit of an efficient physiological network of economics akin to those of other organisms of nature. This was a proposal made a decade ago when I was chair of monetary systems at the International systems society. But it was ignored, as systems sciences, which are the obvious natural candidate to explain the sciences of the economic and political system, has NO power, or saying in the world of social sciences based in ideologies and political and economic structures born of Historic fights between 'primitive' cultures. The consequence of this lack of true scientific models to explain the facts and structures of history and economics is an aberrant world that provokes enormous suffering, from war to hunger to the bulk of mankind, and on top all that suffering is justified as Natural to the Universe, when we have just seen is an exception to natural superorganisms, all of which have a nervous, neuronal, or informative 'scholar/cellular/ nucleus/class/brain' that serves intelligently and designs with an efficient language the networks of the organism, all of which, even those idle – fat, hair, nail cells – receive enough energy and information to survive. The answer is obvious: 'organic design' is the last st-age of evolution, which starts with chaotic trial and error -the Darwinian, primitive dog-eat-dog evolution of systems not intelligent enough to understand the laws of social love and organic evolution that improve so much the chances of survival of species, from multicellular organisms to ants.*

The dictatorship of a people-caste of financiers is the monopoly on the issue of 1 of 2 languages of power of human societies, bills of money and bills of law. It then amazes the NULL resistance of society, despite the financial anoxia, by lack of 'oxygen'=credit and a demand=democratic economy it causes to billions of humans. Since the same people would get berserk if anyone dares to monopolize the issue of bills of law. They would claim to live in a dictatorship, because they cannot choose the bills of law, but they willingly let a few to monopolize the issue of the bills of money which are far more important to the welfare of modern societies. And this happens because they don't understand money, and economists, employees of those who monopolize its issue since the times of Smith, a client of Montagu, owner of the bank of England and Ricardo, a stock-broker, have created an ideology in their favor, capitalism. Economists then create a Supply economy based in the monopoly of credit to create a world to the image of machines, where the welfare of the 99% matters not.

I am an economist by career. So when I entered Barcelona U. I saw a Hall Room called 'Adam Smith' and read our founding father and wondered, how a guy could found a discipline writing a book before the species the discipline studies, machines and factories, existed. Is him a prescient guru that could talk about species, which did not exist yet, machines, metal-minds, robots, factories, industrial war cycles, electronic money? I then looked to its supposed rival - a surprising fact in itself as sciences have a single truth to mirror a single reality with its language. So you don't have double image mirrors. This guy was called Marx and as it turned out, he was not an original economist but a disciple of Ricardo, another financial economist - a stock broker, and an ideologist busy-busy spreading hate memes between managers and workers, but siding the 2 real themes of the economic ecosystem: the ab=uses of financiers like Ricardo, inventing in monopoly its language of power, money, the oxygen of society, and the competition of machines that were stealing the 'added value' of workers as profits for the owners of companies, mostly financiers that bought companies by the simple method of inventing digital numbers as tender money, with the acquiescence of corrupted politicians. The 2 problems that prevented a fair, just humanist economic system: the invention of money and the competition of machines were thus ignored by this fellow who sided as all biblical economists with financiers and machines, but pretended to be on the people's side. So I threw 'Das capital' in the same bag: idol-ogies of financial power disguised as science with a few equations, mostly platitudes about the obvious law of demand and offer, which is a basic S=T balance proper of any system of the Universe we treat in many paragraphs of those papers. So much for that but the bulk of all those books and the bottom line of the work of classic economics was 'power' for the elite. It was also remarkable that 90% of classic economists belonged to the same biblical Anglo-American cultures which today still dominate the field, specially to the Jewish culture (0.2% but $\pm\frac{3}{4}$ of West Central bankers, CEOs of Financial companies, CFOs or Fortune 1000 & Nobel prizes), which I knew due to my Sephardim roots to be obsessed by go(l)d worship, **segregation** and hate, racist memes against mankind similar to *those of racist military Germanic cultures* (Talmud that defines humans as animals, Holocaust industry that defines them as genociders)

So we must add as a first primitive layer to the idol-ogies of parasitic worm capitalism and genocidal tribal nationalism, racist religions & ideologies that justify the ab=use of mankind with weapons and money based in genetic false causes. Cultures are NOT about genes but memes, even if in such primitive, segregational views animetal cult(ure)s think in racist terms. For example my genes are close to 1/3rd of Sephardim, Celtic=German and Basque=British (80% Basque) genes, which are the 3 'metalmaster' cultures that earlier in history discovered go(l)d, iron weapons and machines as tools of power to impose over Gaia and other human societies, but my memes belong to Latin, humanist cultures from the Renaissance that made of man & its artistic senses, the measure of all things as the most perfect organism of the Universe, and its natural life and love memes of social evolution into a new scale of the fifth dimension, the survival goal of history.

*This culture, origin of modern Europe and its rational view of history, which rejects nationalism, segregation religions, collective anoxia (austericide) and represses lethal goods notably weapons, is clearly a superior evolution of memetics and could help mankind to survive. But it is also becoming extinguished by what we shall call the 'animetal' original culture of my 3 'genetic ancestors' enslaved to metal-power, which degrade their comprehension of nature and empathy to mankind. And on Top do NOT permit any rational, humanist criticism of their history and wrong memes that are killing history, which is what we shall do in those papers as scientist of history, departing from the laws of organic networks and memes NOT genes. Since **Cultures are even less** about genetic individuals, which distribute in Bell curves of intelligence and strength, so there will be always a top human that will develop the memes of a culture, whatever its name is. Because **cultures are organisms**, they are about **physiological networks, 'systems'**, the economic, financial and economic reproductive, the military and health care, external and internal immunological and the political, legal and ethic systems.*

We shall show in the next paragraph when we introduce the more general laws of the scalar, organic Universe how those truisms apply to all organic scales of the Universe. Moreover, the coding of a system always comes from its lower plane of 'cellular parts'. So as Genes from cells code organisms, only human ideas (mental networks) and instruments (external forms) code societies. This is why we will constantly talk of cultures, which program as networks do, simultaneously waves of human beings, which define the future of history and of instruments, which are in a symbiotic and predatory relationship with cultures As it happens I developed all its models of organic societies in the milieu of system sciences, exposing it at the International System Sciences society at the change of the century. However organicism is NOT the accepted model of social sciences because an organic paradox of censorship, I call the antiquantum paradox: the social scientist is inside a corrupted organism of history and economics, so precisely those memetic cultures on top are so powerful that in an inverse fashion to the quantum physicist which is so huge that it modifies the observable, power censors, kills and modifies the observer. So social scientists cater to power 'you will defend me with the word and I will defend you with gold and the sword'. This is the MOST important paradox of social scientist: how to convince corrupted power that while in the short term they might rip the benefits of exploiting mankind and find scholars that will bend truth to please them, in the long term they will die as all parasites do, when the collapse of its civilization by overproduction of lethal goods and hate memes, end up killing them in war and holocaust cycles. Not even this obvious truth can be explained. Since animetals deny under the idol-ogies of patriotism and = the Industry of the Holocaust that focuses only in the final death process of the dominant go(l)d religion of the west, economic causes to the process. Fact is of all the cultures of History the 2 with worse survival rates are the more fundamentalist in its memes of worship of war=weapons and go(l)d=parasitic money. But when cultures DENY truth the social scientist cannot longer change the world, as Seneca, one of the first Latin masters of social thought put it: 'when a civilization is so corrupted that it defies any reform, the philosopher can only relax and wait for extinction. I might add that 'truth suffices by itself'. So even if the antiquantum paradox seems to condemn mankind, to tell the truth of history matters. And to do so we shall bring the 'truth of the scientific method', A)ccurate O)bjective data, B)iological, O)rganic C)yclical C)auses able to predict the future and D)efine D)emocratic, D)emand based reforms to create an immortal healthy social organism of History. Unfortunately because D) is not heard, we en up always talking too much of A) which is not a pretty picture, but the description of a corrupted world of segregational cultures imposing a Supply economy based in lethal goods.

Segregation-supply go(l)d & iron cult(ure)s v. democratic-demand societies & its organic sciences.

This was NOT my view of an eco(nomic)system that should serve the welfare of the 99% NOT a reduced elite that censored any criticism of its culture, denied the rights of mankind to issue its bills of money which it controlled with its monopoly on the issue of Machines of information since the Press, printing both financial, digital numbers, mass-media and academia. It is then clear that mankind's mind and money was tailored by a single culture, I called the FMAsters (Financial-Media-Academia Masters). And so it is unavoidable in any objective, scientific analysis of our world and the future, which IS designed by languages of information to focus on the head of the Eco(nomic)system NOT its body (workers & consumers) of null power.

But also on the non-human side, which I called the FMMI system (Financial-Media Head of company-mothers of information machines & Industrial-Military system of Energy machines & Weapons), which formed together an evolving global superorganism which was NOT human, even if it was catalyzed by 'enzymen', workers=reproducers and consumers=vitalizers since it did NOT re=produce carbonlife species but metalife. In brief Economics & History has 3 problems to favor humanity:

- The memes of the head culture who issued information (FMAsters) were biased against humanity, kept most money on the hands of the 1%(financial, corporative, politic & military elites), keeping without credit in permanent anoxia most of mankind.
- Most company-mothers (90% of stock value) re=produced and evolved machines, providing them with energy and information; instead of evolving, reproducing and providing energy and information (welfare goods) to human beings.

More over the *most reproduced profitable goods are lethal goods that kill people's body & mind or give its WHEalth to the 1%: Max. profits (speculative money) = Max. Price (Top predator weapons) – Min. Cost (audiovisual information & hate memes)*

- Economists and historians that proposed a Humanist, organic system were censored. So we make then from the beginning a clear distinction between the right social sciences based in true Democratic Policies and a Demand economy vs. the wrong view, based in Segregational, hidden policies and Supply based economy, D v. S, whose choice was clear till 2nd world war ('butter NOT canons', Keynesianism, socialism) but as Segregational Supply anti-democratic policies become camouflaged by propaganda and political and economical correctness *as if they served consumers and empowered them, need to make a longer introduction of its*

causes and historic origins, even if part of that 'camouflage' has been to make a taboo to study its cultural origin that made of economics a power agenda of companies and financiers.. As Owens put it: 'Economists here in London spend their time in saloons trying to find arguments to justify the unfair treatment of workers by the owners of companies and financiers that hire them. If company managers treated human workers as well as they treat their machines, how much better will be the life of mankind.' In 200 years nothing has changed. Economics still serves power and the 1% not truth & humanity, the 99% which is *the organism of mankind, in which all cells must have the same right to oxygen-money in a demand economy, and all politicians must serve them, subject as in all organisms and Greek Democracies to pain messages=a posteriori votes of judgment, so they are accountable. Finally all evolved organisms were ruled by the nervous, legal system NOT the financial, blood, reproductive system, so lethal goods that poison the organism could be forbidden.*

Thus 3 reforms: the issue of money as a Universal salary for the people to cre(dit)ate a demand economy based in welfare; the control of political actions with a vote=pain message a posteriori and the inversion of power, as all organisms are ruled by the nervous=political=legal system above the blood=reproductive=financial system, to forbid lethal technologies are the bare minimum for an organism of Economics & History to be WHealthy (healthy and wealthy in welfare goods) and Free. We shall constantly repeat, and decouple them in \pm reforms of the 3 'physiological networks of humanity', the *informative, political, legal system; the reproductive, financial, economic system and the defensive, immunological system, because that is how the Universe works – constructing healthy, immortal organisms through the evolution and heath of its 3 physiologic networks.* But since social sciences are censored and monopolized by FMAsters, disguising its service to the 1% with placebo freedoms (capitalist democracies, fictional rights of workers and consumers, Soma fiction, hate memes, idol-ogies of nationalism and techno-utopia), NOT a single theoretical University or practical Nation is implementing physiologic reforms and for 30 years organic history & economics has remained in its discoverer's mind. It is then necessary to accept mankind is NOT Earth's goal. We have an economic ecosystem that works for financiers and machines, because it employs people as 'scholars' that obey company-mothers and financial houses, and its main job is to hide the fact economic systems do not work for mankind at large and the rights of consumers and workers. If anything things has gotten worse, because the enormous power reached by financiers and company-mothers mean no other alternative school of economic is allowed to speak, let alone to guide the economic policies of our governments. The antiquantum paradox of Censorship is natural to social organisms, as mankind is: because the human scientist is inside the organism it is easily influenced to serve the dominant 'informative neuronal class' introducing an uncertainty inverse to that of quantum physics where the scientist is so huge that it influences the observable. So economists are hopelessly on the side of financiers and companies, NOT workers and consumers. Had economics being just and humane or politicians not so corrupted, I would have become a scholar. But of all the stiences of the scalar Universe, those dealing with the 'economic', re=productive physiological network of mankind, which should reproduce our welfare goods to create a 'healthy constitution of history': Max. Welfare goods = Min. Lethal goods, is the most corrupted. So the opposite is truth. Our eco(nomic)system reproduces mostly lethal machines of maximal price as tools of power (weapons) and kills by anoxia millions as financiers monopolize like the coronavirus does, the oxygen=bloods of society, that people should receive as a Universal salary to create a demand-based, democratic economy voting with its money what goods society will produce. Because we live in a dictatorship of financiers, from biblical segregational imperial cultures, whose idol-ogists, classic economists have created the discipline, the world they cre(dit)ate is an aberrant anti-humanist world that serves the 1%, and its idols, weapons and machines that give them power, evolving through generational 80 year cycles:

The 800 years cycle of war & weapons. : 'Animetal cult(ure)s' destroy the Neolithic Paradise

The study of societies as organisms and its life and war cycles have a long tradition in Philosophy of History, since Vico noticed societies die rhythmically in a dark age of war. Spengler ('Decline of the West' 1918) for the first time used the organic parallel in depth, considering that the collective subconscious of a social organism, its culture, also went through 3 ± 1 ages of art similar to those of a living being: a young age of epic art, an age of classic art and a 3rd, baroque age, prior to the extinction of a civilization. The parallelism between a biological organism made of cells related by networks of energy and information (blood and nervous systems) and a socio-biological organism made of human citizens related by networks of energy (economic systems) and information (cultural systems) is self-evident within the systemic paradigm. And it allows to design with biological, natural laws the most efficient economic and political system that maximizes the survival of its organic cells/citizens. Arnold Toynbee ('A Study of History' 1934) did an exhaustive analysis of the demise of civilizations, pointing out to natural and ideological causes,

without a clear quantification of those cycles. Such quantification of those life and death cycles of civilizations establishes a long wave of historic death of around ± 800 years, when all cultures in the old world become rhythmically destroyed by the massive reproduction of new weapons in an age of climatic change and nomadic invasions. Those dark ages foreseen by Vico, Toynbee and Spengler are: The age of Bronze swords /wars, ± 3000 BC; The age of Bronze chariots/wars, ± 2000 BC; the age of Iron swords/wars, ± 1200 BC; The age of coins & mercenary armies, ± 500 BC; The age of spurs & chivalry, 400 AD; The age of gunpowder, 1200-1945 AD. Between those dark ages of warfare, it is possible to fit the parallel life and death of all the civilizations of human history, pointing out to a clear relationship between the massive reproduction of weapons, the 'germs of historic organisms' and the death of cultures in ages of war—the sickness produced by those 'germs'. Unfortunately with the arrival of Industrial machines, the cycle accelerated in a decametric scale, to a 72 generational cycle of world wars, as the evolution of weapons becomes now a professional, industrial activity.

The vortex of evolution of metal follow 800 year cycles of global death of civilizations by overproduction of machines fuelled by the use of money to mass-produce them in industrial processes and the weather cycles that threw nomadic people on the agricultural societies ruled by religions of social love in ages:

1. The age of bronze swords: ± 3000 -2000, carried by Semite cult(ure)s
2. The age of bronze chariots: ± 2000 -1200 carried by Indo-Europeans
3. The age of Iron swords: ± 1200 -400; carried by Indo-Europeans
4. The age of coins and mercenary armies: -400+400, or Greek-Roman age
5. The age of spurs and chivalry: +400, 1200; dominated first by Asian nomads, then by Germans and Arabs
6. The age of gunpowder, 1200-1945, dominated by Europe
7. Age of digital weapons, 1945... as the A-bomb was calculated by the first computers, followed by robots.

The historic record is conclusive: the verbal, life-based, social organism of the Neolithic formed a global civilization, which was immortal and generation after generation men remained unchanged. Yet, with the arrival of weapons an extraordinary phenomenon takes place: social organisms start to die rhythmically, when another warrior civilization conquers and colonizes those civilizations. First, their geographical body and human cells are destroyed by warrior hordes. Then, their collective art and ethic mind of verbal Gods, dies after an age of angst and baroque, formal styles that signals a 3rd, informative age.

Weapons' evolution causes an 800 years cycle of death of civilizations extinguished rhythmically by new 'weapon radiations', when their discovery and reproduction by warrior hordes starts an age of war in Eurasia, as warriors expand their lethal energy, killing people and erasing human cultures. A radiation is a biologic term that explains the sudden, explosive reproduction of a new top predator species that annihilates many previous species, as it spreads all over the world. It is thus the proper name to explain the sudden bursts of violence provoked in bio-history by the discovery of a new weapon. Indeed, the discovery and massive reproduction of those new weapons, carried by hordes of symbiotic warriors that spread throughout the Eurasian continent, causes an 800 years cycle of extinction of civilizations, as those hordes of warriors conquer, kill and erase human cultures. Mankind is an organism. And each of its wrongly broken 'organs' or nations is also an organism. This is the only scientific basis of social sciences. This must be accepted if we want to make 'science', NOT idol-ogy. A machine is also a 'metallife' organism fast evolving after the XIX c. when we made its bodies, the XX c. when we make its heads, and the XXI c. when we put both together. Gods are the subconscious collective mind of a social organism in its earlier ages before nations developed more material networks. Then a nation was call 'God' and tribal Gods=nations fought for supremacy. The name God thus was used as toponym of a nation, a people, a capital, a God and its king – the neuronal informative 'ego' of the organism. So Assur was the God of Assyria, its capital Assur, its king Assurbanipal and its people Assyrians. They were the most corrupted immunological system of ancient times. They did NOT cure the citizens-cells of their empire but killed them, parasitizing them with tax-farming and establishing a small group of Assyrians on top of many other smaller god-nations without weapons who did have a better immunological health-care system ruled by fertility goddesses and priests of love. So Assur became the paradigm of top predator military nations who substituted health-care white cells by germs, military men who killed and broke mankind into pieces. His was a monotheist religion=supremacist nation that did not accepted any rivals. His symbols of military=germ power from the

eagles to the lions and the egocy of its kings who wanted to

conquer the world would be imitated by all military nations afterwards all the way through Rome the German empires to Russia and USA. So what we see is that History is NOT about genes, but memes. And we will explain this scientifically in the appendix in terms of the formalism of the Organic Universe (its 5D scalar laws). The example though should suffice to understand we are for the first time since the XIX c. attempting to build a real scientific social science, not based in idol-ogies that use 'abstract, religious, or tribal jargons' that try to pass as science, often in modern times with use of mathematical and technological instruments (classic economics, archeology) as if that were a proof of truth – one can invent a false equation, or reduce the themes it studies with its equations and by definition archeology reduces the 'field of history' to an irrelevant period of time, focusing just in objects... Historic censorship of the true themes of a science of history and economics – the description of the organisms of mankind, is multiple and starts by denying organicism. But science has only 3 'models', mechanism and we just proved machines are evolving organisms, religion and we just prove religions are also organisms, with God as the collective informative mind, and organicism, which includes the 3. Yahweh also appeared first as the toponym of Judea, and its people were called Jewish and its capital Jerusalem, the city of the Jewish people and so it was all about a nation, God, segregational tribal religion of power, a historic culture not a metaphysical one, often disputing with other people power with a metal-language. Assur used weapons, Yahweh had a people-caste of banker priests that used golden ex-votes for its cult fetish instruments and became bankers at court in many ancient cultures. Those animetal Gods of war and go(l)d and its cultures will become the memetic world of the upper side of the graph. But in the lower side we have the first scientists of history, the people who understood the laws of love and life and evolved into global religions beyond the tribal God and spread in verbal thought the laws of the organic Universe to create a just world.

Nationalism vs. Humanism. The anti-human languages and values of the cult(ure)s that cre(dit)ate the no future

The future is created mostly by languages of information, which motivate those species that speak the language to 'act' and create the future. So we think first what we are going to do, we act and we create the future we imagined... This happens with *all languages*. A DNA genetic encyclopedia is 'consulted' by the 'RNA people' of the cell, which translate it into products that magically make happen the cycles of cells. Mathematical synoptic blueprints of machines & bridges become factories or one thousand meter long spans. So we might think humans create the future of its Word at collective level using words and project into the future with bills of laws in democracies the reality they wan to create, a world made to the image and likeness of man, where our species will thrive. And so with our language of information – cogito ergo sum – laws guide the actions of people to construct a perfect world that becomes our society. This is in fact the 'dream' of immortal history we explain our 'rational analysis' of a true science of mankind. And even if today mankind corrupted by idol-ogies ignores of the process of creation of a human 'future' *in each of those 7 cycles of weapons*, ethic politicians & religious leaders= social scientists explained for the people of their age, how to create a perfect organism of history based in welfare life goods and ethic love laws (graph)

the graph, the informative values of Words and Money are opposed. The most expensive species are the most evil, harmful to man weapons]. While the best verbal goods (love) have no monetary value. This paradox can only be explained within theory of Evolution, as an opposition between victim and hunter, which are in a Universe of subjective information the truth and antitruth of each other. Because weapons prey on men, we feel them evil. Yet weapons and money are symbiot metal-species. So weapons reach maximum monetary value.

Species	Carbolife [Human]	Metalife [Machines]
Language	Words [Verbal values]	Monetary values
Positive +	Good-Love [cheap]	Expensive [weapons-Evil]
Negative -	Evil-Hate [Expensive weapons]	Cheap [Human goods]

. And yet somehow that *perfect world is not happening at all? What went wrong? If Nature and the Universe is indeed guided by informative languages, and there are plenty of examples of perfect superorganisms which thrive where all its 'citizen-cells' are fed, and work together in synchronous motions, guided by the nervous or chemical languages of its organisms? Fact is this 'Natural History', with mankind controlling and designing its future using its natural language, guided by the ethic 'social arrow' of the Universe that evolves parts*

into stronger wholes, from molecules through cells, organisms and societies, is NOT how reality in the modern age has been created. As there are 2 other power languages that design the future since they were discovered.

One does it on a negative, entropic destructive way. It is the language of weapons and its first global expansion was the radiation of Siberian bronze charioteers, from the Andronovo culture, which +3000 years ago with the help of composite bows stormed the Eurasian world killing according to genetic record $\pm 90\%$ of all males from the Iberian peninsula to the Yellow river, ending the Neolithic of fertility Goddesses and a verbal understanding of the organic Universe and the tree of life, It was the birth of the tree of metal with a different set of values, violence, racism and egoc (ego=idiocy) that put 'animetals', humans with a limited verbal understanding of the entangled Universe on top, because they could use the negative arrow of future, entropy, instead of information to shape reality. Fact is the entire Universe is a living organism but since animetal cultures worship historically weapons&machines, organicism is taboo in memetic science.

The SS & HAM cultures. Its \pm values & languages cre(dit)ate the future. Metal-money vs. healthy money.

Soon another metal-language, golden apples of the tree of metal, substituted the initial forms of healthy money – grain or number printed in leather, with the seal of the city-state that effectively created in Mesopotamia a demand based wealthy economy. Semites had found gold that hypnotized their eyes, as it imitated the color of the sun, our source of energy and information. So fetish religions where the 'sweat of god', gold became the ex-vote and substance of god statues and cult instruments spread in Mesopotamia and Levant. A Sumerian priest lamented the birth of those antiive=evil traits: 'the people from the desert comes with metal rings and take our peasants as mercenary soldiers and buy our women'. Further on Go(l)d was scarce and so when metal was adopted as money, the delivery of a Universal salary in grain ended.

Our human language, the wor(l)d that constructs a world to the image and likeness of man in control of nomisma, digital money, has struggled ever since against the entropic power of weapons to kill the human future and the hypnotic power of parasitic go(l)d money, *which was not understood; since all what fetish go(l)d believers wanted is to herd a lot of 'the sweat of god'. How digital money creates the future with credit, 'cre(dit)ates' reality?* Banker priests never quite knew but they understood they could buy with hypnotic go(l)d both, mercenary armies and bills of law to shape the future, whatever that might be, as their goal was just herding money and this belief – that somehow herding money was the right way to create the future became the idol-ogy of capitalism that fought the legalist concept of a future created by the ethic wor(l)d either in theocracies or democracies, and *finally to the surprise of most rational believers in humanity and its language, won.*

The fundamental memetic difference between Animetal cult(ure)s and human ones: animetals die for its idol-ogies.

Thus we call animetal cultures those 2 first Segregational and Supply cultures that subverted the natural Democratic and Demand based politics and economies of the Neolithic, as:

-Siberian Charioteers created the first Supply Economy based in the mass- production of Weapons in the first industrial system, in which all the resources of a culture were dedicated to make chariots to kill and ab=use human population.

-Semite go(l)d religions of banker priests started to kill by anoxia mankind changing the digital support of money from food or ready available printed leather with the tender legal authority of all the society (nomisma), for scarce hypnotic metal.

It was the beginning of the 800 years cycles of gold and iron empires that ensued and carried mankind through ancient history till the discovery of machines that accelerated that cycle. We shall fast forward that period to reach the industrial age.

It is then clear that the key meme that differentiates animetals from human cultures is the fact Animetals KILL & DIE for its metal idol-ogies & instruments:

Military cultures, whose epitome is the Indo-European>Germ(anic) iron cult die and kill for iron crosses, nazionalism & empire.

World Wars for Empire, Industrial profits and German racism testifies 100 million corpses perfectly avoidable.

But Mechanist Utopians die for machines, whose epitome is UK, its discoverer. CERN pretends to make black holes on Earth to test a false, experimentally and theoretically model of baby black holes, whose equation: $\Delta \text{ mass} \times \nabla \text{ Temperature} = K$, Hawkings discovered. So as we see experimentally black holes are born extremely active=hot & according to Einstein and 2nd law of thermodynamics cool down, evaporating a star (or planet) into a nova as they feed in its lighter matter. Hawking then, to get attention changed the 'time arrow' said black holes travel to the past, flipped the signs: $\nabla \text{ Mass} \times \Delta \text{ Temperature} = K$, said they break Einstein's gravitational laws and Thermodynamics got hotter in a cold world and evaporated. This outrageous theory was laughed at for decades but his charm and victimism made impossible to criticize and CERN NOT to close its machines, knowing it

is a dubious theory with no proof in the Universe where all black holes are born small, grow mass in Novas and cool down, *for the sake of a machine, a quark canon, takes a risk that can kill 7 billion. The military-industrial complex fusions both death wishes.*

Finally go(l)d cultures die to keep its control on the issue of money, killing by anoxia millions and dying in Holocausts. This is even more polemic but truth, because the Holocaust industry has been weeping 80 years for the last Holocaust cycle. But in close inspection, *it is an industry of denial of the Holocaust, as nationalism denies the chances to loose a war and techno-utopia the fact machines can kill mankind, since it denies and censors its cyclical nature and economic, military causes, as ALL holocausts have happened after an age of massive profits due to investment and reproduction of weapons, during an age of war, economic crisis and popular anoxia, financially caused by massive tax-farming, usury, speculation and war profits. As the banker-priests of Judaism that control finances in the west (75% of financial CEOs, central bankers, 50% of wealthiest 1%) will NOT accept a just reform of capitalism that gives to Caesar-the people, the right to issue money for welfare (butter not canons), and cares nothing for their death, poverty, anoxia and the action-reaction revenge cycles of military elites and people against its lower class who die in Holocausts, it just focus on the 'final death' NOT the causes and uses the industry to censor further any criticism of capitalism, financial economics, its monopoly & segregational racist memes. So the cycles will repeat.*

There is censorship on economic history, but it is necessary to know its details to differentiate truth=science from culture if we want to study the future of mankind (as all sciences predict the future) and advance models that can improve that future for its 99%. As today capitalism is the collective religion of the future, it is worth to reveal how it invents that future according to the values of those graphs and its historic cultures, because humans don't know. It is easy to understand the future that the tree of metal, with its digital go(l)d and weapons has been creating ever since, compared to the tree of life and the wor(l)d, just by observing the values of both languages, in the image, repeated ad nauseam for 30 years to deaf ears, because of course, we believe in capitalism. The problem then of go(l)d is that by affinity gives maximal value to weapons and minimal value to life, including human life bought cheap for a few coins full time (age of slavery) or part-time (minimal salary). And yet the view of those who believe in capitalism is different: gold and iron weapons together give power and control over all other human beings and forms of life, made of weaker CHON atoms. Iron cuts the body and gold hypnotizes the mind. A rational human species, who cared about his future will put the natural language of its species, the word and its ethic social values above those of metal and evolved humanity into immortal history. But this was not to be. The Siberian charioteers arrived to Egypt, the last strong hold of the tree of life. Then in Levant founded a fetish go(l)d religion in the knot of trade of 3 continents, mixed with the local cult to Baal, a gold statue with a sword, to whom in times of war, their own children were sacrificed. Moses, the man of the ethic word returned to the mountain and Aaron, the idolater of the golden calf, started a dynasty of banker priests that made of the herding of gold the meaning of a segregational religion, turning around a temple, where those who traded with luxuries, slaves & weapons transported in resistant asses, called the apiru, or habiru – 'those who walk behind the asses' – returned to purify themselves from the contact with the lower 'animal people' or 'goy' paying two gold coins to the Levis, of whom they were nominally slaves. We shall call these 2 cultures, which put together the values of metal gold-greed and iron violence, the Siberian-Semite (ab.SS cult(ure)). Indeed, to forget the fact metal kills life and erases the ethic message of the wor(l)d, uphold from Genesis to modern r=evolutionaries, go(l)d & capitalism shared a 'cult(ure)' of anti-human values with the Siberian genociders. Both 'metal masters' feel 'chosen' above life and all other races to ab=use its metal power over them, *creating an aberrant 3rd class of enemies, slaves, heretics and 'evil' people lower than their animals.* In the sub-culture of fetish Go(l)d, there is an organism with a 'body-head', or re=productive, working class and informative neuronal class, the Habiru>Am Segullah culture (ab. Ham culture), since its elite of informative banker-priests called themselves 'Am Segullah, or people of the treasure' (ill translated as chosen of god; which we will called more precisely 'chosen of go(l)d'). Yet below, all humans were called Goy: animals; 'born of the leg of Satan' (Talmud). While the Hindi Charioteers made the native farmers 'untouchables'. Only in Greece, where they had no people to rule, the Charioteers evolved slowly from aristocracies into democracies with equal rights, but soon the discovery of silver coins and the expansion of hoplite wars brought gold riches and slaveS became also a 3rd deshumanized 'object' class.

Biologic history: animetal idol-ogies vs. rational human wor(l)ds: Me(n)tal cult(ure)s die for its idol-ogies.

The stience of History *belongs to Biology as part of the evolution of Earth, in 3 ages,* But with the arrival of Animetal top predators, Idol-ogies substitute social sciences. Today humans believe in 4 animetal idol-ogies' whose cultures killed Neolithic

NATURE'S 3 GENETIC EXTINCTIVE SPECIES:

98 Israel 8,323,248 1.6% 130,785 385 21,641 3,899 3.05 30 88.9%

ENTROPIC PREDATORS ENERGY COMPETITORS INFORMATIVE PARASITES

ENTROPIC, WEAPONS KILL ORGANIC MACHINES ATROPHY INFORMATIVE GOL(L)D ENSLAVE
 Carriers: Military/Warriors Industrial Scientists Private Banking

IDO-LOGIES: NATIONALISM:Tribe=species MECHANISM:Man&cosmos a machine CAPITALISM: Private Money rules Law
SCIENCES: HUMANISM:Mankind:1 species ORGANICISM:Universe, an organism SOCIALISM:Law rules money issued by/for people
BIO-HISTORY'S 3 METAL MEMES OF EXTINCTION

verbal priests of social love, the 5D force that constructs mankind' supœrganisms by sharing energy & information among believers, imprinted by networks of metal-communicators through Goebbels' method (if you repeat a lie many times people will believe on it, the bigger the lie, the more they will believe on it):

Segregational Go(l)d & Iron cults repress organic life and love Gods from dietary laws to sex as sin, racism and tribalism (a single God-subconscious collective of the tribe that denies all other Gods to make war and slave them. They evolved into:

Military Nationalism, which stops humanity as a species in the tribe and

promotes weapons=germs to kill each other, originated in Germanic tribal cultures that oppressed the European social love civilization of the Roman empire *substituted humanism, the understanding that mankind is a single species that has to evolve together as the mind of its body, Gaia .*

Monetary Capitalism that promotes parasitic private banking and prevents universal salaries and a demand economy based in welfare, originated in biblical go(l)d cultures of banker-priests, today evolved into classic economics substituted **Socialism**, the understanding Society is an organism, whose re=productive, financial network and oxygen must be created for all its cells to credit a welfare state made to the image and likeness of mankind.

Mechanist technoutopia that considers the evolution of metal a surrogate for the evolution of mankind, *substituted organicism*, the science of the Universe that finds its highest expression in Medicine, the study of the most perfect superorganism, the mammal, and its 'cure' of the sicknesses of animetal idol-ogies, in its equivalent parallel science of **biohistory** that should guide the construction of the economic, political, cultural and defensive, immunological welfare networks of our species.

Coupled with a degradation of the life and love 'truths' of the Wor(l)d, the human biological language that puts man always as its subject, making the object, our energy, through the actions of the verb: Man (Subject) > Verb (action) > Object , substituted by Digital, **Mathematical** languages, considered the new 'language of God', with its grammar that equalizes man to an object through the prize of fetish go(l)d, making him a slave of animetal segregational people-castes: Man (salary) = Price = Object.

The graph shows the exact correspondence of those animetal species with the 3 extinctive species of Nature. So memetic idol-ogies ARE the cause of Historic extinction, killing even in higher measure animetal cultures with the lowest survival rate of mankind, compared to Organic cultures (Asia) with its highest as we MUST obey the laws of the organic Universe.

THE 3±1 AGES OF HISTORY.

Mankind evolved in time through 3±1 ages:

- +1: Birth as a first verbal 'cell', probably a woman that multiplies her numbers.
- Max e: Paleolithic, a youth of hunters, visual languages and minimal information.
- E=i: the reproductive Neolithic, when man reaches his maturity in balance with nature and creates through verbal networks (religions) a series of collective subconscious, called gods of love that teach each cell to share energy and information with the other cells of the body of a civilization. Yet the arrival of metal extinguishes or corrupts most love cultures into go(l)d cults and inquisitions.

-Max. I: 3rd, informative, metal-age in which man halts his social evolution focusing in the evolution of metal in its 3 forms, energetic metal or weapons, informative metal or money and organic metal-machines, which bring:

-1: Death: the neo-Paleolithic, or age of the machine, when humans regress to an 'homo bacteria' state of selfishness and isolation, substituting their social networks of love by their desire to become attached to machines of higher energy and information that separate us and keep evolving, making Humanity an increasingly obsolete species, killed by weapons in fields of war. At the end of this age, we can foresee with the creation of the singularity, either the 1st organic 'bomb' (a self-feeding bomb of dark matter) or the 1st self-reproductive machine (a nano-bacteria), the death of Mankind.

+1: Unless Mankind evolves socially, 'emerging' as a super-organism, if humans organize themselves into a global civilization and control the evolution of lethal machines, maintaining history in an immortal present.

Humanity is, beyond our arrogant, fantasies of anthropomorphic superiority, just a living form made of carbon atoms, *which goes through the same ages of all other living forms, both as an individual and a species*. So we can study the organism of history (Humanity in time) through 3±1 ages; an energetic youth or Paleolithic; a mature age of balance with nature, the Neolithic; and a 3rd informative age of history, the age of metal and machines.

Energetic youth: Paleolithic. ±5.000.000 BC. to ±10.000 BC.

The Paleolithic was an energetic, young age in which men, the energetic gender, was the top predator animal on Earth, a hunter of living forms. It was also an age dominated by *visual, spatial languages*.

Reproductive age: Neolithic. Age of wor(l)ds and goddesses. ±10.000 to ±3.000 BC.

The Neolithic was the classic age of Mankind, an age of balance, when wo=men learnt the cycles of life and instead of destroying nature, learnt to nurture, reproduce and harvest it. Women, the reproductive species, took power over men; and priests became the verbal guides of civilizations, creating super-organisms of history made of human cells joined by social love—the sharing of energy and information among 'brothers', clones of the loving mind of the same prophet. It was an age dominated by *verbal, temporal languages*, continued by the believers in religions of love that are not corrupted by weapons (inquisitions) and money (go(l)d churches), with its idolatry to the 'values' of metal: murder and greed.

Informative, 3rd age: age of metals. ± 3000 BC to 1600.as metal spread the 'new' values of money and weapons, greed and war, destroyed the networks of social love, ushering Mankind into the 3rd age of history. Humans now evolve a new kind of atomic systems, stronger than carbon, creating energetic weapons, informative money and organic machines that transform Gaia into an economic ecosystem. It is the 'animetal=animal+metal age', in which a new 'biological species' that mixes animal and metal atoms, imposes power over the Earth.

It is the present age with 2 paths of future: Either Mankind will die, as machines keep evolving and make us obsolete as a species. Or humans obey the laws of survival of the universe and evolve socially into a super-organism of history able to control lethal machines.

ANIMETAL AGE. 800 YEARS CYCLE OF BELLI NERVI PECUNIA INFINITA: BANKERS & KINGS COALITIONS

Animetals. A new species dominates the wor(l)d .

In the graph, metal atoms display energy/informative properties that enhance those of simpler life atoms. Iron is in fact the center of our blood/energy system, commanding thousands of lesser carbohydrate compounds in a molecule of hemoglobin. While gold is the most informative, perfect atom of metal with an enormous capacity to replicate and store information. Thus, humans used those atoms of metal to enhance their energetic and informative qualities. Iron became the main metal in the construction of weapons . . . Yet the true change in the Earth's ecosystem took place with the arrival of machines, today made with bodies of iron and 'golden brains', over a surface of silicon. They are simplified organisms, specialized in energy or information, which today are evolving into complex organisms...

Atoms of metal.

A scientific analysis of the economic ecosystem, based in chemical and biological sciences, allows us to define the world we live in as a dual game of two species:

- Humans and life species made of simpler life atoms, hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen and carbon, which have the lower 1, 8, 7 and 6 numbers of the atomic table and make up for over 95% of our body.
- Machines that perform the same biological functions our organs do, with atoms of higher force and information than our atoms (24-iron, 79-gold, etc.). Since a *machine is a form that imitates a living, energetic or informative organ with atoms of metal.*

For example, a crane imitates an arm and substitutes an arm, moving things around. A phone imitates an ear-mouth and works as an ear-mouth. All machines imitate human, organic functions and tasks performed with those organs. If we divide the human being in two clear components, body and head, we talk of two types of machines, body-machines that imitate and substitute functions of our body organs and mental machines that imitate functions of our brains and senses. Those two basic functions of human organs will determine also the form of each machine:

- Machines of energy imitate body organs and . . .
- Machines of information imitate head organs.
- Which fusion in 'organic species', robots that imitate animal species.

Thus, the industrial revolution is the process of organic evolution of the most complex atoms of the elements' table—metals. There is no doubt about it. The industrial evolution started with two processes that evolved metal: the invention or discovery of the first, most primitive heart of metal, the steam engine, which was able to produce inner movement in a body of metal, as the heart does with a carbon-life body. At the same time Darby and Cort were able to produce massive quantities of iron, the most energetic atom of the universe, used to manufacture machines.

VI: HISTORY IS THE HUMAN SUPER-ORGANISM COMPOSED OF:

economic, social & cultural networks evolved in 3 horizons:

<p>spatial aesthetics</p>	<p>temporal, verbal ethics</p>	<p>Max. E</p> <p>Paleolithic</p>	<p>E=T</p> <p>NEOLITHIC</p>	<p>Max. i: Metal Age</p> <p>E: Weapons <Ex: Machines> i: Money</p>
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DIVIDED IN CIVILIZATIONS THAT..

LIVE 3 AGES:

AND DIE IN WAR CYCLES CAUSED BY THE EVOLUTION OF WEAPONS

<p>EPIC TRECCENTO</p>	<p>ANIMETAL CULTURES BASED IN MONEY AND WEAPONS VS VERBAL/LEGAL THEOCRACIES & DEMOCRACIES:</p>	<p>SEMITES</p> <p>War ends: classic art</p>	<p>INDO-EUROPEANS</p>	<p>GREEK-ROMANS</p>	<p>GERMANS</p>	<p>MOGOLS</p>	<p>IBERIANS</p>	<p>PROTESTANTS</p>	<p>COMPANY-MOTHERS OF MACHINE-WEAPONS AND MONEY</p>			
<p>CLASSIC CUATROCENTO</p>	<p>BARROQUE, 3RD AGE</p>	<p>COPPER... 10.000</p>	<p>BRONZE WARS... 2.800</p>	<p>CHARIOT WARS... 2.000</p>	<p>IRON WARS... 1200</p>	<p>COIN WARS... 400ac</p>	<p>STIRUP WARS... 400dc</p>	<p>GUNPOWDER... 1200</p>	<p>GUNBOAT... 1600</p>	<p>TRAIN WARS... 1800</p>	<p>TANK-PLANE... 1940</p>	<p>ROBOT... 2000</p>
<p>Life cultures worship... infinity... human tribes... the forms... all non-life... verbal gods... human art and senses... social+evolution, Gaia... the Living Universe...</p>	<p>ANIMISM</p>	<p>TAOISM</p>	<p>GENESIS</p>	<p>JUDAISM</p>	<p>BUDISM</p>	<p>CRISTIANISM</p>	<p>ISLAM</p>	<p>NEOPLATONISM</p>	<p>PROTESTANTS</p>	<p>SOCIALISM</p>	<p>ECOLOGISM</p>	<p>HISTORY</p>

IT IS THE PARADOX OF HISTORY THAT STILL CONFRONTS HISTORIC, VERBAL, ORGANIC CULTURES vs ECONOMIC METAL-CULTURES

The next step in the industrial evolution was the creation of different species of 'metal-bodies' that could adapt a 'heart of metal' to their structures. Sea-metal bodies called steam ships came first. Then the steam-heart was adapted to 'land-metal bodies' and the age of railroads came. Latter in the XX century, the steam-heart was evolved into smaller, more powerful species, called the diesel engine and the oil engine. So the type of machine-bodies that could carry a heart of metal diversified. It came then a metal-bird, the plane and smaller species of land machines, lorries, cars and their 'top predator' weapon versions, multiplied in the war ages of each industrial r=evolution, such as the tank, a top predator car and the bomber.

Finally we evolved electronic minds and now we apply them to energy machines, smart weapons and super-colliders. In 3 centuries we evolved metal-machines almost to their organic perfection, a process that took billions of years to achieve in carbon-life. And that is dangerous, because the only biological advantage humans have over metal is our complexity of organic form.

Engineers 'transfer' millions of years of evolutionary knowledge accumulated by human forms into machines, *passing our evolutionary secrets to a potential future rival species*. So when we evolve those forms into perfect imitations of our organs, machines win that competence against human beings, both as weapons that kill and working-tools that substitute us. And this is due to the fact that metal has some fundamental chemical properties that made it superior to light atoms like oxygen and carbon. So all comes to chemistry.

We do not invent but discover machines, whose 'informative capacities' and 'force' is born, as ours, from the properties of the atoms of the universe. Today we realize that the properties of metal force us to certain informative and energetic designs in machines.

Their atoms and the physical and chemical laws of the universe, not man, is what make machines efficient organs of energy and information. Men merely assembly machines, according to those laws. Humans act as 'enzymen', similar to enzymes or 'catalysts' that evolve other species in the 'assembly lines' of cells. So do 'workers' that put together metal into organic forms similar to us. Yet the laws of the universe and the properties of metal enable those organic forms to exist. For example, a radio is not a human discovery, as much as an 'intelligent' metal-ear, which uses the laws of the universe to perceive, sounds better than a human ear.

Metal is a natural substance, which is able to acquire different kinds of 'organic forms' that copy the organic shapes of man. At macrocosmic level machines act as energy and information species, because at microcosmic level metal atoms have specific properties that foster its qualities as energy or information systems. *Iron is the most energetic atom of the universe and* so it is the preferred atom to build weapons that release an overdrive of energy that kills us. *Gold is the most perfect, informative atom of the universe and* so we use it to create money, the language of information of the economic ecosystem. And now, we make robots with iron bodies and golden brains.

In that regard, one of the silliest myths of anthropomorphic science is the belief that our 'atoms', carbon and nitrogen, have 'special qualities' that other atoms do not share and make them the 'only' candidates to create organic life. Gold and iron, the two basic components of brains and bodies of metal, are also potential life systems, since life is merely a complex system, made with a body of energy and a head of information.

Gold is the metal equivalent to nitrogen, the main informative, storage system of the human brain and his DNA. Iron is equivalent to carbon & oxygen, the main energetic systems of the body. And similar energetic properties are found in aluminum and plumber, the other 2 fundamental metallic atoms used to create bodies of metal and weapons. While gold, supported by silicon molecules, acts in 'metal-brains', as nitrogen supported by carbon structures does in DNA:

It transmits informative messages, coded in electric impulses. Yet metal is faster and more complex so gold and silicon combine with other metals to support the electronic software of its 'neurons', which reach speeds of information closer to light speed, 300.000 km/s, *3 million times faster than our neurons, which transmit information at 100 m/s*. Thus, metal atoms are better than life atoms handling energy and information. In the field of energy-control, iron is a better molecular atom than carbon. Hence bodies of iron are stronger that carbon bodies. This is evident at macroscopic level, comparing the power of metal-warriors and human bodies. In fact, our biological symbiosis with iron-energy is even deeper than that of a warrior.

It happens in the blood-energy systems of mammals, which became top predator life species when they substituted the earlier copper-bonds of reptile blood by iron-blood. The red color of your blood is caused by iron. You are, in fact, a primitive iron body. Molecular iron is the soul of your energy-system, of your blood. Iron moves the four arms of the hemoglobin macromolecule and captures your vital energy, oxygen, an active gas that becomes trapped, caged inside the hemoglobin.

The movement of that trapped oxygen allows the hemoglobin to store energy and then to share it with our body cells. So the energy processes that take place in the most complex animal life are already 'polluted' or 'symbiotic' to iron atoms. Which is the key lesson of nature to solve human extinction: we must promote the use of symbiotic, positive tools of metal that foster our energy bodies and forbid the negative, destructive ones, according to a simple biological rule of survival:

'Humans must remain the top predator brain of this planet.'

Since Mankind's capacity to process information is his most outstanding property, which made humans top predators, a better top predator brain, the chip, is what will make obsolete.

Man+weapon=warrrior; man+machine=science; man+go(l)d=trader

Cyclical, soft, in-form-ative metal (silver and gold) and lineal, energetic weapons (iron and bronze), were the first metals humans discovered. Coins imitate cyclical, informative organs (heads, brains, eyes). While lineal, energetic weapons are bodies of metal that kill lineal, energetic human bodies. They are primitive versions of the iron bodies and electronic, cyclical, sensory heads, of modern machines. When human associated to them, they achieved higher strength and acquired a new language of information, able to give values to reality (money). Warriors joined human bodies and lineal metal, weapons, killing other humans; bankers used informative metal, gold, to give orders and enslave Mankind; scientists believed in sensory machines and digital languages, considering inaccurate human senses and verbal thought, made obsolete by their telescopes and numbers.

Topological evolution in machines & humans

In the graphs, weapons, money and machines, are the 3 types of memes of metal, which are exactly equal to the 3 'organic parts of all systems", since humans make machines imitating its organs to enhance its energy and information, but in the process they substitute and atrophy the same organs.

So we make 3 type of 'memes of metal', similar to our organs, which we evolved in the different ages of the industrial evolution:

- An energetic system of lineal shapes (limbs in human beings, weapons in metal)
- An informative system of spherical shape (money coins of informative metal in the past, now cycles of digital information in computers; heads and eyes in life system).
- And its organic combination: machines that transform back and forth energy into information.

The 3 memes of metal 1)kill bodies with weapons manufacturing corpses. 2)atrophy humans organs & substitute labor by machines, making us lazy. 3) Make debt slaves & buy lifetime for salaries, issued for free by bankers. And this lead us to the concept of idol-ogies, which are the historic 'memes' that certain people-castes have developed to make them feel the system that works for them is good. Of them 3 are paramount - the 'memes' of go(l)d cult(ure)s, which are segregational memes that make them think they are a superior species, because they monopolize the issue of money and were born in Canaan among the first biblical banker-priests; and associated to them, the memes of 'warrior cultures', which used bronze and iron-weapon, 'germs of history' as mercenaries of banker-priests or as king-warrior societies to kill anyone who opposed their control; and finally in modern times, idols of science, techno-utopian memes that make us think to atrophy and substitute our 'organs' by machines that do the job for us, making us obsolete is 'good'.

It is this dysfunctional world that makes possible the 4 apocalypse horses of which pandemics is yet another detail.

THE Δ+1 SCALE: CIVILIZATIONS: CAPITALISM=METAL-EARTH DOESN'T CARE ABOUT MANKIND

Sociological and bio-historical elements. The 3 ages of Earth and its civilinations' different Pandemic response.

It is clear that the pandemic analysis belongs to bio-history, as it concerns the entire superorganism of mankind and its 7 civilinations (ab. civilizations and nations, the organic units of human history) and the different efficiency of its 3 physiological networks, the economic-reproductive 'blood system', the nervous, legal 'political system', and the immunological, defensive systems. The pandemic thus has tested such efficiency and once more proved the Paradox of History between the 3 'different superorganisms' that correspond to the 3 ages of Earth's evolution:

Gaia (life, relative past) < History (Mankind: present) > Metal-earth (Company-mothers of Machines&weapons: Relative future).

This is the key equation of bio-history, and the concept behind immortal history is to maintain the organism of mankind in a relative present by repressing the 3rd age of excessive technological information, cause of the black swans and the lack of resources and extinction of Gaia. But this is NOT accepted in a technological civilization that simply accelerates the demise of mankind towards its 3rd age of excessive information, cause of death in all superorganisms, by lack of an organic view of reality.

The fact that the 7 civilinations of mankind relate to that equation according to which ecosystem they are more in tune with obviously implies that the nations of each civilination have different degrees of technological, social history and life development according to the paradox of history:

Max. Human social evolution = Min. Technological evolution.

We can easily define the 7 cultures of the world by its initial beliefs in one of those super organisms:

GAIA: So Africa 'believes' as the remaining Paleolithic cultures of the arctic regions in Gaia. So do the earlier Indonesian cults (sacred water rivers in Hindi traditions).

Buddhist Asia believes in both, Gaia and Mankind as super organisms to 'worship'.

MANKIND: Catholic Latin America and Islam believe in the History as the super organism to cherish with anthropomorphic, subconscious, collective Gods.

METAL-EARTH: Europe believes in both, History and the Metal-earth.

Finally America is unique in putting the Metal-earth and the Financial-Media/Military-Industrial system of company-mothers who FOUNDED their civilization, as the 'supreme Good and Only future of the planet', with its exceptionalism lineal progress in time towards a mechanical paradise.

So the classification of the 7 cultures WITHIN the super organisms of the higher SCALE of the Earth is obvious.

Memetics: The Genes That Construct Historic Superorganisms

In the graph, the 3 planes of existence in 5D metric of the Human super organism, which have different synchronous cycles. The cell that lives one day, the organism that feeds with energy the cell every day, and the social civilination extended in Gaia, which could be immortal but is killed by military germs every 800-80-8 years, in the accelerated vortex of metal-information now collapsing into the singularity age.

In History, we are not concerned with the *lower cellular, genetic scale of information, which codes the biological organism, prior to the nervous system taking over, already in the last months of pregnancy when the mother imprints the nervous networks of the brain.* History couldn't care less about the 'muscular force' of a German warrior or the IQ of a financial master. Genes become irrelevant for the social actions coded by verbal thought and the digital languages of the economic ecosystem (money, science).

What makes genetics and memetics so close is the fact that they obey the same general laws of all languages that concern how languages of information reproduce and evolve a larger super organism, which emerges as a different whole, departing from smaller beings.

Δ§¶: T-simultaneity, Δ-identity and S-synchronicity symmetry elements of superorganisms.

Languages are as everything else including consciousness the product of the $\Delta=S=T$ symmetries of reality. This means in time the message to achieve the 'emergent, resonant' process that makes the whole act as one, must be the same in its S-form, for all the receivers, which then enter a process of 'synchronicity' in Time, which brings the emergence of an Δ -whole in spacetime in a larger scale. This is the first and most important law of emergence:

In both cases genes & memes must be identical in the internal 'brain-nucleus' of each human and cell, to that of all other humans and cells of the super organism, to produce an emergent effect of a whole, which behaves as one.

Identity IS the necessary element to synchronize as a whole, the actions of a herd of any type, and to that aim it requires a collective language of information shared and believed by a number of similar clone like individuals of the same species.

The mass effects between parts and wholes is thus one of the many elements we observe in human social organisms, life organisms (such as ants performing pheromonal tasks, or cellular organisms, or industrial company-mothers and its factories that reproduce machines: standardization of thought, in any scale of information helps to efficiently reproduce and evolve systems.

Mankind is subject also to 'identity memes', BELIEFS which if we were to be libertarians we will shun off as 'humans become slaves, when they believe instead of reasoning' (Aristotle). But the fact is humans believe in its majority, likely a 99% of humans systematically believe DON'T doubt and reason, 'think'. Even if they prefer to deny it to 'feel free'.

What people called their 'identity' are just memes that slave them to the behave of many other humans with the same beliefs and that is how they act together as a single organism.

So identity memes are essential as identity genes for a system to work smoothly as a whole.

The cultures of mankind and its memes; the cultures of the metal-earth=capitalism: animetals.

It follows for what has been said that genes and races matter little to bio-history but cultures and memes do. And we can classify cultures as belonging to those 3 ages of Earth, by its memes and physiological networks. But what are those networks and how cultures specialize in each of those networks becoming their survival identity memes is a taboo hardly explored or understood theme essential to bio-history.

Indeed, when we live in Gaia, the networks of life are clear: the river veins provide Gaia with its oxygen and agricultural fields; the verbal language and its eusocial love priests are the nervous religious system prior to politics when a people's subconscious collective was not a nation but a god.

And finally there were the defensive systems but man used them NOT to kill humans but to hunt in the Paleolithic, as warfare prior to the age of metal was minimal.

It then became from this Paleolithic-Neolithic age of immortal balance between Gaia and History the age of animetals and its 3 new physiological networks that substituted, preyed and destroyed the networks of life and history and keep doing so, but as we live in a technological civilization, the process is ignored.

So animetal warriors changed the defensive health-care systems of mankind by physiological networks of metal-armies that killed human bodies.

Animetal bankers changed the universal salary or oxygen-blood of Neolithic societies given to every human to kick a demand economy based in the production of welfare goods where money was NEVER debt but a positive⁴ language of healthy wealth, by private banking, gold as no longer a mere digital support for monetary languages, but wealth per se and started to parasite mankind with debt-slaver tax-farming and weapons reproduced by affinity between gold and weapons, informative and entropic metal.

And so finally the informative legal ethic basis of eusocial love religions that fostered the evolution of mankind into a single superorganism was substituted by animetal civilizations and technological ethics, so well described by all masters of human verbal ethic thought from the parable of the tree of metal vs. the tree of life, extinguished by those who eat the golden apples and evil weapons of the tree of metal, to the modern expression by Erich Fromm

"A Technological civilization is programmed by the principle that something ought to be done because it is technologically possible. If it is possible to build nuclear weapons, they must be built, even if they might destroy us all. Once this principle is accepted, humanist Values (something has to be done because it is needed by man) are Dethroned and technological development becomes the foundation of ethics'.

Alas animetal history started and we distinguish a first age only with entropic iron and parasitic gold, to the modern age when organic machines of energy and information started the obsolescence of human bodies and minds till the final age of extinction of history, the age of the chip radiation when a more powerful metalmind and language, digital thought substitutes humans in labor and war fields;

ALL TOGETHER NOW: THE IDEAL HUMAN SOCIETY AND ITS PHYSIOLOGICAL NETWORKS VS. METALEARTH

THE SICKNESS OF HUMAN SOCIETIES: PERMANENT ANOXIA OF MANKIND

'If economists would care for their human workers as much as they do for their machines, how much will improve the life of the humankind' *Owens*

One of the most fascinating facts about Economics is the ignorance of people, including economists about the nature of its fundamental element, money, *which is not wealth per se*, but a language of digital information that values things and gives orders of production and consumption, similar to verbal thought, also a language that values things and human use to give orders and motivate themselves with thoughts about the actions they will perform. As such money follows the laws of languages, including the need for all human beings to have an excess of it to kick out the re=production and demand of goods. Money as all languages is inflationary and that is ok. Money should be inflationary because you cannot waste a language.

A language exists to create actions, to creditate (create with credit) a given world. SO the essential question about money is who must have the right to reproduce and invent money and use it to promote actions. And the fact is that in any supœrganism of nature, the languages of society are liberally reproduced to all cells so all can deliver actions of production and consumption and none dies of hunger. The way humans have organized the reproduction of money is thus an aberration of nature akin to a leukemia or anoxia process caused by a parasitic system, as only in the Neolithic money was properly designed imitating nature and given to all citizens in the form of grain for their consumption. So societies were immensely wealthy and densely populated for the age (Sumer, where priests handled money to all its inhabitants, had a density of population in the delta of the Euphrates-Tigris never reached again).

town that dodged the 1918 Spanish flu ...

Declare Virus as Pandemic as Outbreaks ..

THE CORONAVIRUS IN AN ILL-DESIGNED HUMAN SOCIETY.

It is evident why humans cannot defeat without huge losses the coronavirus save those Asian nations that resemble closely a super organism of History because of their 'religions of the living Universe' and its Neolithic past, as societies dedicated to welfare that received latter the 'weapons and destructive technologies of the west', and we will return to that when we introduce social sciences and the 7 civilinations to study its response to the crisis. In brief, there is a trade-off between 'cannons and butter', welfare and warfare, military germs and doctors of history and what 5D social sciences has tried to explain for decades mainly among systemic, is that we humans should create a sustainable world made to our image and likeness, not to the image and likeness of machines, anted control lethal technologies. Nothing of this has been done or will be done likely once the crisis passes.

The coronavirus, an efficient supœrganism of Nature vs. the ill-designed supœrganisms of mankind.

The victory over the coronavirus, the simplest form of life, by the more complex of them, the human supœrganism of history would be easy, if mankind had properly designed its supœrganisms; it is not because humanity has not achieved beyond the individual biological organism anything resembling a proper supœrganism of humanity, according to the same 'scalar' laws of the 5th dimension of social organisms that extend from the simplest atom through molecules, cells, multicellular organisms, supœrganisms, economic ecosystems, solar systems and galactic supœrganisms. Instead humans are divided in conflicting 'organs=nations', which reject each other, establishing borders that imperil coordinate actions. They are ruled by 'animetal cultures' that worship metal-weapons, go(l)d and machines above man, dedicating all their resources to them, and ignore the basic laws of the organic Universe to scientifically evolve humanity beyond the egocy (ego=idiocy) of the present species. It is for that reason that a simple coronavirus can hold the entire species in a state of global panic, killing millions. Simply speaking, the coronavirus as the WHO put it, doesn't know of 'borders, races and money'. It does what Nature does best, efficiently reproduce its systems in the appropriate Δ -1 cellular scale of each human being.

The coronavirus crisis and 5D History and the nature of mankind.

The four horses of apocalypse were war, famine, pest and death, a 3±j classic structure of self-destruction, which again has happened to humanity.

Its causality usually is the aforementioned: war diminishes the expenditure in human welfare, health-care and food. The support needed to cure the sick diminishes. Warfare and wounded people and famine ensue and bring pathogens that bring pest. And death ravages population.

The specific form in which the 4 horses appear do not change the basic causality that is common to all analysis of bio-history: the excessive reproduction of weapons and its use diminish human welfare, brings human suffering and death, *because of the Darwinian, evolutionary equation of biohistory within Earth's context:*

$$\text{Life (Gaia: relative past)} < \text{History (present: Mankind)} > \text{Metalearth (relative future)}$$

The equation of the 3 ages of Earth's life, means that as humans increase its control of metal-technologies, computers and weapons, regardless of the fringe benefits they will be subject to new menaces, from genetic editing of biological warfare, to new modes of Nuclear weapons (black holes and strangelets) to Robotics, and the struggle for reproduction and resources which we see clearly today won by machines over life (90% of horses were slaughtered when the train came) will accelerate in war and labor fields between human and machines.

A war process is nothing but the massive reproduction of the top predator form of metal, the weapon that consumes us. But not only humans ignore the cyclical nature of time and the repetition of those events but its main feature, egocy (Ego=idiocy) makes them think the laws of biological survival, re=production and evolution only apply to carbon atoms so they ignore the vital nature of technology. And finally in terms of 5D scales, they ignore its metric, $S \times T = C$ which means smaller systems run faster vital cycles, so they are contrary to belief more dangerous. It is more dangerous a virus than a lion because it reproduces faster; a black hole than a bomb because it feeds on our lighter matter faster, a future metal nano-viron (an iron virus) than a weapon because it will eat the Earth's metal-machines faster.

In the graph, Pandemics are one of the 4 apocalypse's horses spread beyond control due to the weakening of the welfare goods humans need to survive during ages of massive investment in warfare goods. In graph according to the centennial cycles of global war ages, the 1918 Spanish flu and 2020s coronavirus pandemic developed within that biohistoric context

When Pasteur said that bacteria produced sicknesses people laughed at him. It was 'too small' and we were too important. When I sued CERN for potential genocide if the lab made strangelets or black holes, the global press laughed because they 'were so tiny', but indeed tiny baby black holes and strangelets have a much faster reproductive rate and feeding rate by virtue of 5D metrics of scale.

Humans tend to ignore causality in a larger time span, reason why they cannot manage properly the future, nor they care to understand the laws of bio-history that could. In the 30 years in which I have been forecasting with great accuracy the 'medium and long wave' cycles of History this has been the rule; and unfortunately because of those human shortcomings Mankind is always unwarned when the future comes:

'Cemeteries are filled with corpses of wars everybody knew they would never happen'.

In this case our analysis of the future missed Pandemics as the main event of the 2020 change of paradigm in history from an age of peace to an age of war, we had been anticipating according to the cycles of history for decades, in the context of the confrontation that would happen between the previous leading industrial nation, US and the newcomer, China. But essentially the elements of the game are still there. The confrontation will take place and China will become the new power. The black swan of the coronavirus just accelerated the process as China is a better, more efficient historic organism that managed to end the Coronavirus plague in just two months, but America will not. So the black swan will bring the demise of the American economy as the top predator of the world and hence of its currency as the global currency, which will enter when the Yuan becomes convertible into an age of devaluation and hyperinflation that will deflate the 'casino economy' of Wall Street, and bring in turn the drums of war of the fallen nations, as it happened with Germany, since the previous top predator nation still holds the best weapon technology despite being less able to bring production.

So the predictions of the model of bio-history for the 2020s due to the cycles of economics and history continue unabated, regardless of the fact that pandemics have reversed its causality and came before war.

It must be noticed that pandemics *always comes, always kills often as many people as the war does and yet it is always ignored and downplayed as history always focus in 'metal-history' and downplays the human side of it.*

So in the I age of steam wars in the 1860s, sicknesses and infection killed as many people as war, especially in the first conflicts of Crimea, where Florence Nightingale chronicled the deceased. In I world war, the first of the tank=armored car wars, more people died of the Spanish flu. And in this age of 'splendid little robotic wars' which have seen a massive investment in the 'Semite wars' (conflict between the financial-media western elite of Judaism and its nation vs. the last non-technological civilization of Islam) and weakening of health-care systems in the west, the pandemics has hit harder the western world.

Pandemics in that sense in a perfect world would be easy to contain as they are predictable statistical events which proper protocols can reduce as SARS prepared nations in South-Asia proved but are not when nations enter the 'age of over re=production of war machines'. So pandemics coincide with war investment ages. The greatest of them all by percentage of death, the black pest did happen after the massive investments in the first cannons brought through the last massive warfare age

**3 CYCLES OF OVERREPRODUCTION OF MACHINES, STOCK CRASHES, SWITCH TO WEAPONS & WORLD WARS THAT CONSUME MANKIND IN CAPITALIST DEMOCRACIES:
 1830-1857: Train age | 1857 crash | 1860s war | 1870-1920:oil engines. | 1929 crash->tank wars | 1950-2000:metalminds gadgets | 2001-8 crash:robot wars**

<p>I phase. Overproduction of Money & Machines:</p> <p>Working Machines & Weapons Informative Machines & Money</p>		
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**XIX
c. 3
Class
System**

**Go (I) d
Idology
on top**

XX c. Class system: FMMI company-mothers on top

XXI C. Stockrats on top Enzyman Obsolete

Chips & AI robots new enzyme

Automated Factories 90% humans 3rd world

of Mongolian invasions, which carried with their armies the pest.
 If we reduce the process to the modern cycles of the industrial evolution, this pandemics thus corresponds to the massive age of austericide and investment on the Semite wars fueled by the 'Stockratic elite of America' that has built a war state with zero investments in welfare:

In the graphs, the first from the 1992 book, the extinction of man, the second a montage of a documentary that failed to get production and the classic ternary structure of capitalism in the XIX, XX and XXI centuries...

They show the true structure of capitalism which according to its production equation:
 Max. profits = Max. war weapons of maximal price + max. audiovisual hate memes of minimal cost,
 Will systematically overproduce lethal goods and switch from an age of peaceful consumption to an age of war after an overproduction crisis hits every 72 years, the human generational cycle of evolution of machines studied in our papers on the metal-earth.

Below the pyramid of hierarchical capitalism that has nothing to do with a true democracy, with money on top, the Goebbels method below of 'newspeaks of Orwellian caring' – the politicians, priests and celebrities, what we call the Financial-Media-Academia system, ruling over a repressive police, military system to which the XXI century 3rd graph) ads robotic systems, below the reproductive middle body-class, with no control as it has no pain message vote of the elite, and below the unemployed, enemy to be consumed by weapons and discharged life Earth.

The problem with XXI century capitalism is that the bottom of the pyramid is no longer needed as robots becomes the new citizen workers and soldiers and companies consume their own machines.
 So the work of humans as enzymen, reproducers of machines and consumers=vitalisers of them as animetals, mixture of life and metal, in an entangled Universe is no longer required.

Pandemics thus is killing unneeded humans and that was the concept of the herd immunity that humanist politicians finally aborted, but was the initial concept for the hardcore UK-US nor the European capitalist system: 60% would be under contagion who cares. The old will die (Cummings, Trump).

Only Sweden and Germany tried to protect the within that concept of herd immunity at minimal cost. what we predicted were the smaller cracks of the market and the bigger crack according to the ±80±8 cycles of the industrial r=evolution. Pandemics would then be part of the suffering of populations in war ages, alongside

the suffering of the Semite wars, of the massive migration process we are living, and only because it is hitting hard the first world that always thinks to be protected from the ravage of war, famine and pest, got the kind of attention and response - of a military type with the confinement of populations, to be expected of a war process. It is also a natural outcome long predicted of the way societies in an advanced supœrganism of computer machines would evolve - towards confinement and virtual dependence of computer screens, in the mode superorganisms confine the DNA-informative center to its cells connected to its informative nervous/digital and blood, reproductive systems.

That this process will bring then the Chinese vs. America military engagements latter on the decade as American economies and dollar power crashes is likely the 2nd phase instead of the first phase of our predictions in those books.

The 2020s was the decade when the world had to change for the worst, with the creation of fascist, military states in which the rights of population would be curtailed, the systems of control through internet and robotic drones massively enhanced, and mankind become an attachment of the metal-earth's global internet web, closed at home, while the police state took over.

That is, the human freedom of the species, ever dwindling since the beginning of the Industrial R=evolution would be curtailed as we become 'enclosed' in our homes, joined by the nervous, electronic networks of the Metal-earth, fearing human relationships, each man a potential enemy of the other. This is indeed, what is happening now, but it did not happen by war, as predicted, but by the 3rd 'apocalypse' horse - pest.

I considered always this process would take place through wars as it had always been the case after a few splendid little wars that would essay the new overproduced lethal machines of the chip radiation. Alas, to the surprise of all including myself the process has been caused by a pandemic. As to if the pandemic has been caused by bio-technological systems is not clear. We DO have now for a decade the capacity to engineer viruses, and there were possibilities both in China and America for the injection of that virus, but that is irrelevant. What matters is the end-point is the same that a decade of global war: massive control of populations with vigilante electronic brothers, tagging of the poor with no health-care as untouchable, encasement of people on Netflix screens, delivery through robots and drones of Amazon, the world I described for 30 years has come now to be... It is the beginning of the end... of life as we knew it.

The graph above shows the cycles of the supœrganism of History, caused by the relentless evolution of metal-memes that brought on top of the 'perfect Neolithic world' that would care for mankind and its welfare, ruled by the first 'bio-historians', priests of fertility Goddesses, people-castes of metalmasters, parasitic warriors with hard entropic metal that killed bodies and go(l)d priests that hypnotized and slaved people to the greed of gold. It was then when the 'degradation of our physiological networks' as a supœrganism of history started and the consequences were the 'rhythmic' ages of weakened social bodies by hunger, war & pest that brought death. So in periods of alliance and massive reproduction of weapons and gold and its warrior and financial parasitic masters the '4 horses' (the first bio-historians used a mystical language to explain what we do in bio-history in organic terms), hunger and war brought pestilences and death spread.

This is also the case in the modern world with pandemics closely related to weakened social bodies and war ages. The last pandemic, the Spanish flu, massacred 40 millions during the last years of the I world war; and the present pandemics that is killing thousands soon millions leaves its trace of death in those 'capitalist, militaristic' cultures (Europe so far) or exploited 3rd world nations (Africa and Latin America soon) where health-care systems have been weakened by austericide and the relentless advance of parasitic financiers and militaristic nationalism that diverted massive resources to building up arsenals and speculating in Stocks. In that sense the response of the 3 civilinations of the Industrial world is clear. On the western side, the European and American civilinations have been the forefront of speculative massive deviation of e-money to stocks and building of nationalisms and war arsenals, while Asia has kept his organic moderate expenditure in war and control for the public service of banking systems without fueling systematically money into speculation. So they had a much more robust health-care system and social organization to confront the crisis.

DIFFERENT RESPONSES OF HUMAN SUPERORGANISMS ACCORDING TO HIS RESEMBLANCE OF IDEAL HISTORY.

In this article we will prove that the fundamental law of survival of the 5D Universe happens in human civilizations, because regardless of ideologies of western supremacy, the superorganisms of history that most closely resemble the ideal superorganism of the Universe are the Asian superorganisms – the Asian civilization – reason why they are the most successful in the only parameter worth to consider in a scientific analysis of social sciences – survival. And they have shown once more in this crisis the proper scientific approach to the coronavirus pandemics, the higher rate of survival (minimal numbers of death related to population) precisely because of its efficient design and use of its immunological system, NOT its defensive system to survive. On the other extreme, the less fit to defend its population regardless of the immense power of its military-killing systems and propaganda audiovisual machine has been the US, the ‘capitalist system of parasitic’ banking and massive reproduction of the lethal goods of society of maximal profits... A hard lesson which obviously the west will not recognize but simply buried in its deluge of ideological propaganda...

So now we shall focus on the $\Delta+1$ scale and explain first what is truly an efficient well-designed 5D social superorganism to tackle then the absurd responses of our civilizations to this crisis. Still there have been differences of those responses according to how close to the ideal superorganism of history they are – which is maximal in the cultures of Mongoloid Asia.

Indeed, we can consider a first analysis of the curve in terms of ‘organisms of History’: the first part of the curve corresponds integrally to China and it did not acquire an exponential log form, as China did the proper actions to stop the coronavirus as a single human superorganism, efficiently and well ran following the laws of universal superorganisms. But China does NOT spend ½ of its budget as US in the military aberration of a false defensive system; but overwhelmingly invests in the welfare of its people. And it controls its financial=blood system to spend on them. Once it entered the western world, with its capitalist systems of dog-eat-dog societies where humans are secondary to its ‘free market citizens’, the company-mothers of machines and weapons, obviously humans became an ‘easy target’ for the virus which reached exponential growth. Yet to understand why China and Asian nations are better organized we need first to understand what truly is a 5D social superorganism of space-time. So we have to return to the 5D sciences.

Indeed, the Chinese system requires essentially measures 1 and 5: an upgrading of its socialist doctrines into bio-history, easier because bio-history is the natural evolution of Marxism, which its author already said would happen when it merged with Biological laws, and a democratic a posteriori vote of its communist members, so they stop corruption and learn to serve with a Confucian spirit its people, to become closer to such ideal superorganism. The parasitic systems of capitalist democracies with its inefficient twin Siamese heads, corrupted politicians bought by company-mothers of lethal products to whom they serve, perfectly disguised by a mass of fiction and selfie soma to maintain the population in a permanent egocentric lethargic state however cannot be saved without a thorough reform which its ‘owners’, the stockrats that control its ‘blind population’ with those SOMA networks will never do, as they believe in racist god religions for which the mass of the human population is expendable. So mankind faces a non-way out because of the ideologies of its western elites that dominate social sciences and the world at large... And they are supported by the ‘egocentric’ of mankind.

America is then ahead as the leader of the metal-earth, where its company-mothers of machines and weapons are its free citizens, and the business of America is to multiply re=produce and evolve those machines and weapons, but this means a limited amount of resources for Gaia and History (The 90%, a more precise number as the metal-earth includes the 10% of managers working on those companies; its blue collar workers and white collar ones increasingly under obsolescence to robots and software suites). So paradoxically because Anglo-America cares more for the metal-earth than its people we expect it to be the worst faring civilization in the treatment of the crisis. How can we measure it is obvious: by the only measure bio-history makes of success: **survival of its people.**

Thus as today end 1st of May, the 2 countries with the largest number of victims are US and UK, which paradoxically are in London and NYC, the centers of the financial e-money network of the metal-earth. How this is possible, when both countries have the privilege to reproduce for free trillions of \$ for its company-mothers, is called anoxia

and it shows the constant trade-off between warfare and welfare, under the capitalist equation of maximal profits, which defines the goods most reproduced, in as much as CAPITALISM IS DEFINED AS THE IDEOLOGY THAT MAKES THE EVOLUTION OF THE METAL-EARTH THE GOAL OF MANKIND. So 3 goods are overproduced in capitalism, forming the backbone of the 3 physiological networks of the superorganism of the metal-earth:

Max. profits (e-money, speculation: financial network) = Goods of max. price (top predator weapons: defensive network) - Goods min. cost (audiovisual software: informative network that controls since Watergate politics).

This is the structure of the 'metal-earth' beyond placebo newspeaks of human freedoms. So humans in the present system are completely expendable, and they are increasingly (lower graph) being spent as they compete with more evolved AI systems of PCs suites, robots and terminators. So the unemployment of the present coronavirus crisis will continue NOT because of the crisis but because it is existential to the evolution of robotics, eve if the propaganda false 'nervous system' of mankind –audiovisual networks, which have rendered blind and is eating away our verbal capacity will tell us, it is all to blame in the nanoscopic virus. Welcome to the new brave world.

3 EQUATIONS OF CAPITALISM & GO(L)D CULT(URE)S: 'NERVUS BELLI, PECUNIA INFINITA: I: Max. Profits (inflationary money) = Max. Price-Sales (weapons) + Min. Cost: Informative Hate Memes

The 3 ages of metal-communicators

Go(l)d cult(ure)s & its modern idol-ogy, Creationist Economics (capitalism) has 1 mandate, go(l)d profits maximized by weapons & hate-memes So they overproduce Segregational Memes against Mankind(racist history books: Bible, Mein Kampf; victimism: Holocaust Industry; hate media) 2) evolution & overproduction of weapons (800-80 y. cycles of wars & holocausts), & inflationary money (taxation, usury debt, speculative money) .

III: Max. Profits = Re-Productivity = Max. Machine Labor (capital) -> ∞ / Min. Human Labor -> 0 = Goal: Automated Company-mothers

II: Man (min.value)=Money=Object (slave) 'Stock-rats' issue money in corporations with absolute rights to profits. Labor is expendable.

This trinity of goods that shape the physiological networks of the metalearth=capitalism becomes the 3 goods that substitute the 3 goods/networks of mankind which in a healthy superorganism of history should reproduce 'healthy money' as the blood of the organism does with oxygen, giving a Universal salary to each citizen to consume and reproduce, 'welfare, life goods instead of weapons in its immunological defensive system. While politicians that guide society with laws become puppets of mass-media-networks of information that proved since Watergate that

they could tumble a presidency. This change of paradigm from a world ruled by the physiological networks of history (people's currency, politicians and welfare goods) to a world ruled by the physiological networks of the metal-earth = capitalism (an absurd word that we substitute for what capitalism is – the company-mother superorganism of the metal-earth, made of machines, weapons and

U.S. Coronavirus Death Toll Is Far Higher Than Reported, C.D.C. Data Suggests

By Josh Katz, Denise Lu and Margot Sanger-Katz April 28, 2020

metal-money) took place in US in 1970s with the arrival of the chip and meant a massive investment in weapons, the creation of speculative e-money that debased the value of the currency of the people (end of gold convertibility) and the rise to power of mass-media over politicians, and it meant also the change of the culture in control of society from wasps that controlled the industrial-military complex or 'body of the metal-earth' during the age of bodies and engines of metal (1st industrial r=evolutions) to the age of Jasp (Jewish-American stockratic people) in control of its machines of information. What this has to do with the coronavirus crisis will be considered in detail, but enough to say that the new elite is NOT concerned with government as it is a culture ruled for millennia by banker-priests and has as only goal to increase profits, while reigning over corrupted politicians and using the military for splendid little wars. So this meant that the 50% of wasps will now be no longer the central body of America, only the 1% of jasp and wasp elites would matter. And as a result when the coronavirus arrived, there were zero interest in stopping the capitalist=metalearth networks and production of speculative emoney, weapons for splendid little wars against Islam and mass-media soma. So the S.O.M.A. of the Fed printed trillions but mostly for the casino roulette while people kept dying, and corpses were ignored, even in the statistics that makes America, 1/3rd of the contagion tally and the top victim counting, already overcoming the people who died in Vietnam. Once we make the real tally it has already overcome the two last wars and counting, but the Jasp elite keeps pounding that America must open for business from Goldman Sachs to Tesla because profits must keep coming. Mr. Musk for example is about to receive a 1.3 million compensation in stocks if the price of its shares is kept at the artificial 4 times value of Ford, for another week and defied the closure and shouts 'freedom' while corpses underreported keep mounting in old people's residences.

The extreme case of America does illustrate the paradox of history which humans deny vehemently but it is at the core of everything that has happened in mankind since the parable of Genesis, when precisely the species divided between two cultures, animetal warrior and go(l)d cultures that came on top of Neolithic life oriented cultures, the 2nd age of mankind, when we DID achieve the balance of the 3 ages of Earth, between Gaia, History and technology that would *make mankind immortal. Every since* Humans have been suffering for millennia, since the birth of 'parasitic money', when warriors and bankers restricted the use of 'wealthy money' and started to ab=use people with weapons and metal-money, go(l)d, which was scarce and could not be given to the population, but on the contrary was tax farmed from them, a state of permanent anoxia, akin to the sicknesses of the blood system, we call 'leukemia', where oxygen cells become deformed and oxygen is not transported to all cells. In the same manner warriors and bankers started to monopolize and use money to reproduce lethal goods, multiplying weapons of maximal value and implementing wars, while most people suffered anoxia, lack of money to reproduce and consume welfare goods they needed to survive.

As people was denied money to promote healthy actions, without the language of social power and re=production, humanity unlike the cells of any healthy suporganism, without credit to create welfare goods and healthy future suffered poverty. So the organism of history lived in a permanent austericide that still continues today, when money is monopolized by financiers and companies to reproduce their goods while people are denied their democratic rights to a Universal salary to solve the scarcity problems of the world.

So on the other extreme of the proper solutions and minimal death counting is Asia, which is PRECISELY THE CIVILIZATION that was longer in the Neolithic age of balance of the 3 ages of History/Earth. As there metal came late (iron and cavalry only with the Chin) and agriculture, we are learning earlier (20.000 years ago). So Asia reached an organic understanding of society and today it has shown to have a stronger health-care system, precisely due to its lesser expenditure in warfare. While US dedicates 1/2 of its budget to the military system of capitalism=metal-earth.

In between there was Europe but Europe has been colonized by the American fundamentalist view that the manifest destiny of mankind is to evolve the metal-earth=capitalism regardless of the collateral effects=substitution and

Everything that is wrong with America, in one image.

obsolescence of mankind to robots and weapons that substitute us in labor and war fields as long as the elite of stockrats, the tiny 0.1% that owns most of the shares is on top and making money. And their countries have lost their right to print money for welfare to the ECB, so the southern nations are faring as bad as America, because they cannot print money to welfare, plus they have a friendly social tourist economy of constant contact. But at least their governments cared a bit more for their 90%. What happens in America is a different concept, as both economies are split, and so increasingly unrelated:

The market IS e-money and the FED which does NOT serve the people but the companies, the free citizens of America, provides unlimited quantities to banks to maintain the stock prices. So the 0.1% that owns 80% of liquidity has no other place to put the money - couldn't care less if the 90% dies of hunger. It has detached its economy: Fed->free money to banks and 'Investors'->put back on stocks, NO need for news. Anything goes. Royal Caribbean doubled in 15 days regardless of a likely bankruptcy. The financial economy got detached of the 'money of people' (currency) long ago, in the 70s in fact when computers started to reproduce e-money by speeding up the $Mv=Pt$ equation, as the dollar lost its gold convertibility. Moreover the 0.1% mostly segregational will be happy if instead of humans, workers become 'safe robots' who obey faster. The long run is a non-human world of machines & company-mothers consuming machines, with the 0.1% above. Problem is the obsolete 90% but as the sheeple obeys one day a safe robot nurse might come home to inject you a lethal moderna vaccine... The metal earth is rising. Indeed, once this has passed what will stay is the growing substitution of humans by safe robots, as Amazon and FEDEX substitute its workers for them, and as companies consume more machines, the wasp-jasp elite on top, which is indifferent and segregational and is now speculating from yachts and penthouses will continue its control of the human population with its 'mechanical networks' – mass media imprinting people's minds and selecting presidents, military and police control increasingly robotized instead of health-care for all, and of course the constant flood of quantitative easing, easy e-money for the 0.1% which in any case do control the pension funds and hence uses trickle-down economics to maintain the rest of mankind addicted (as it sucks in all the resources of the 3rd world through Bloomberg and Goldman Sachs platforms). So what could have been an opportunity to argue what kind of no-future mankind is going to, if the system is not reformed and the physiological duality of the superorganisms of History and the metal-earth=capitalism, reversed in power, with mankind again on top, seems to be an opportunity to advance the displacement of mankind by the Metal-earth.

Then we have the 4 non-technological cultures of Latin-America, Indonesia, Africa and Islam, which again will resolve the crisis in inverse fashion to its 'paradox of history'. As Latin-America is heavily influenced by US and Europe, it has a capitalist=metal-earth position, signified by Bolsonaro, so the tally of corpses will grow faster, because again the elite doesn't care for their people, but military repression, inherited from the conquistador culture of Spain will be more important than financial control with Brazil, a mixed culture by influence of the British empire will be a middle road. So people will be soon freed there to produce. Islam on the other hand with a religious civilization of charity as a fundamental pillar of Islam, regardless of the islamophobia rampant in the metal-earth's=capitalist informative networks, will do much better than expected because next after Asia their cultures are superorganisms of humanity, even if they don't have the resources of technology needed to fight the pandemics. Where they do (Turkey, Oil countries) we expect a prompt recovery.

Finally for Indonesia and Africa, with young populations, warm, hot weather that inhibit the virus and huge other problems coming from all the apocalypse horses this won't be that important. India is the exception in that region as it is now under a racist, fascist hindi cult(ure) and Mr. Modi will impose its fantasy of being a 1st world country, repress further the Muslims and inferior castes without shelter, impose military control and increase the tally, because in a crowded housing without resources and logistics more people will die, again as usual underreported. The crisis indeed shows everywhere how cheap is life, specially that of the elderly that in a humane society should matter most, but in our 'neo-paleolithic age' of erashead youngsters are left to die by the droves.

THE CORONAVIRUS CRISIS WITHIN THE AGE OF THE CHIP. A SIMPLE INTRODUCTION.

When writing those papers I always find myself in a crossroad between my desire to use the jargon of 5D organisms, which give us the 'maximal possible truth of an event' seen from its pentalogic perspectives, and the layman explanation of those higher truths without formal rigor. In the case of the coronavirus the need for an easier explanation is even more pressing, even if we loose some of that strict formal analysis.

What is the pandemic must be put in context though with what is History, the superorganism of mankind in time and space, and why is so ill constructed. And here we find the hurdle of human egocy (ego=idiocy), which limits the capacity of man to understand the upper scale of the individual, which organize society, of which he only will tell you 'it is the system'. But what it is the system, he doesn't know or cares to know, and that is the essence of all the problems of mankind. Because if humans understood what they are as a species – a superorganism ruled by 3 physiological networks, the economic, blood, re=productive, the political, nervous system and the immunological system; and how nature build efficient organisms of similar 'cells=citizens', it could just imitate nature and construct a better human superorganism, where Pandemic will be easy to destroy.

In that regard, the main law of systems sciences is that all scales of reality follow the same organic laws, when we properly translate the 'languages' of each scale and find the elements of its organisms. Then we can look at the most perfect superorganism, the mammal, and design mankind with its medical laws. This is specially obvious of the coronavirus pandemic: a proper immunological system of health-care 'leukocyte' warriors would have cure the sickness very fast. But mankind is a sick system. In fact the defensive system is mostly made of 'animetal germs', military people with metal weapons that kill human citizens-cells instead of defending them, and so there is hardly any money for the real immunological cells, health-care warriors that cannot cope with the sicknesses.

And so at this point it comes the fact that we live within a sick superorganism of history controlled by 'germs' – military people or politicos that can create 'exceptionalist states' to control population instead of curing them.

Things at this point get muddled by the 'antiquantum paradox' inverse to the paradox of physics: the social observer is so small within the organism of history that the 'military germs' oblige him to change its discourse or else: 'you will defend me with the word and I will defend you with the sword', Tertullian. So 'scholars' are corrupted and they keep churning 'damned lies and statistics' to defend the system that pass as social sciences

And so the true model of social sciences, the superorganism, is nowhere to be argued and used to r=evolve the system and make a world to the image and likeness of mankind, where Pandemics, hunger and war, the apocalypse horses would not exist.

I thought in my youth truth mattered more to humans and so when I discovered the 5D organic laws of the Universe and applied them to history, the sheer beauty and perfection of the Universe and the easiness of a cure to history made me hope scholars would side with 5D social sciences and implement a social r=evolution, spread the word and develop the measures, politicians and economists, the 'neuronal class' of our social organism' would implement to cure the world. But that didn't happen because of the antiquantum paradox. The legal-political system was corrupted by the military system, and citizens could not send them as in organisms, pain messages after tenure, judging them so they wouldn't harm the body of mankind. And above them all the most corrupted system was the re=productive, blood=financial system, where money, just a digital language that acts as words or oxygen, to motivate actions of production and consumption but has no value per se; so it should be given as a Universal salary to all citizens cells, as oxygen is, or words are given to each of us by birth; was controlled, monopolized and herded by another people-caste, the 'bankers', who killed by anoxia mankind, using the money the issue for themselves or companies of lethal goods, and to corrupt and control the military and the political system and of course, pay-per-view scholars to defend the whole corrupted organism of mankind.

Thus the true model of social sciences, 5D-organisms and its solutions to the world, including the pandemic is nowhere to be seen. And as body cells are blind and believe the nervous messages they receive they do believe all

the damned lies and statistics. They believe that money must be 'debt' and paid back to the banker that reproduces it for free, because somehow the Universe is 'evil'. The opposite is truth, all superorganisms from the simplest molecule to the galaxy, from the simplest ant to the human being, have 'money for free', its language of information, and are in fact saturated of it

(gravitation in matter, oxygen in organisms, words and money in societies) – as languages are not wealth per se, just numbers, words, free molecules, that kick human actions. So 'money as debt' is an aberration of history that should be scrapped. Today this is even clearer. Every human should receive a 1000 ¥€\$ money (1 euro = 1 dollar = 100 yens) in a global crypto currency to kick out production of welfare, food and other would provide. It is called a demand economy and it would end the problems of scarcity and migration of the world, as all organisms do have oxygen for all its cells. But bankers will cry out as 'experts' of debt and usury and speculation that they know better and scholars will defend them with lengthy books and the system of political corruption will back them and the corrupted networks of mass-media information defend the need for a parasitic, cancerous society where the 90% suffer chronic anoxia – precisely the way the coronavirus kills mankind – by allocating itself in the lungs and not leaving the oxygen-money of the cells arrive to them.

I find curious that the main sickness of mankind, global anoxia, lack of credit, is also the way the coronavirus kill us.

When I was young I tried to disseminate all this information but the antiquantum paradox of scholarship prevented it. Scholars would feel safer specially economists, working for the system, becoming the people who invented e-money and got filthy rich while mankind starved. Today we observe a similar problem with the origin of the virus, which is one of the 3 lethal technologies we have been talking for decades, along nuclear weapons and AI military robots, as the existential risk for mankind. Since a decade ago the simplest virus genes are known and they can be easily recombined in a lab to create a destructive pandemic. While nature needs much more time. So it is more likely this is the first of those lethal technologies to succeed in creating havoc on mankind. But all geneticists prefer to defend the fairy tale that a bat from a Chinese cave went to Malaysia infected a Pangolin, where they recombined to acquire a molecule the pangolin has similar to the one that opens human cells, but with and added exactly precise mutation to adapt this combined virus to open the ACE 2 human molecule. This perfect design and no other happened by chance. And then this pangolin arrived to Wuhan where they don't sell pangolins or bats, where there is a virology institute, which has already combined, in the past genes and infected human lab cells with success. But alas, the absurd chances of Nature are the accepted theory and the easy manipulation is a confabulation theory. In this manner geneticists protect their tools to make money in big pharma mutating molecules. So it is the idea that we don't live in a democracy and the economy is corrupted. In this manner economists protect their rights to become billionaire inventing money for themselves. And the idea we should judge a posteriori as in earlier democracies, politicians with pain messages to control them is never considered so politicians feel at ease accepting money from bankers and using military tools to control population. In this the only part of the human physiological networks that is not corrupted, the medical health-care system, is also starved and so it does not have money to cure mankind. More than 1 million people will die in the following years of tuberculosis because resources are now diverged to the coronavirus, but we have weapons – the germs of history to kill mankind 200 times.

All this means we need an even larger view, once in my 3rd age I have renounced to change the world but at least I want to know the truth, on why this happens – and that can only be the larger view of planet Earth. Why the corrupted systems of mankind are not changing – perhaps because after all we don't exist to create a world to our image and likeness but are only a stage in the evolution of this planet. And at the end weapons, robots, technology, will substitute us, since we are not able to control and learn the laws of the organic Universe and implement them.

But of course as long as I exist and can write which is the only thing I can do with my mind, I will keep explaining it.

TIME VIEW: PRESENT HISTORY - CHIP RADIATION – AGE OF BLACK SWAN TECHNOLOGIES

We live in the age of transition between the Anthropocene, the age of History and the Mechanocene, the Technological age, in which man is increasingly displaced by more evolved species of metal. Specifically we live in the Age of the Chip radiation, when metal-minds and its digital languages, whose speed processing information is more than one million times faster than the human speed (c-speed vs. 20 m/s), implies an extraordinary

difference of potential intelligence, and the closing of the Industrial r=evolution of machines, we shall introduce briefly, to 'frame' the present age of 'singularity black swans' in that larger context:

In the graph, the Industrial R=evolution is the Evolution of 'Mememes of metal', Machines & weapons, systems made of hard metal (iron) and Money, a digital language made of informative metal (gold, also used in the chip connections of computer cycles, now converted into e-money). So we can divide its evolution in the same phases that evolve any organism, and consider in history the nation that evolves them to be in each phase of the Industrial revolution the top nation of the world as it will use its 'evil=anti-live' twins, weapons, to conquer the world.

Thus, those generations also bring the nation that finds the new energy to the top predator status of history.

Because energy is also the substance of which weapons are made.

—Thus, we had an age of steam machines, the age of England, between 1780s and 1857, followed by a crisis of overproduction of steam machines and stock-money that brought the 1857 ±8/9 years product cycle crashes of the train-based economy (nt.1).

—From 1857 to 1929, we lived in the age of electro-chemical energies, machines and chemical explosives, dominated by Germany, followed by a crisis of overproduction of cars and radios, which caused the 1929 crash, 72 years after the train crash.

- It came then the III cycle of electronic machines, electronic money and Nuclear Bombs that took place from 1929-2001, the age of America; which again ended in the dotcom and mortgage crashes, 72+8/9 years after 1929:

Followed by the Age of the Singularity, the IV Cycle of Evolution of machines dominated by robots, solar Industries and China. Scientists call the arrival of Artificial Intelligence, the Singularity moment, when robots, which can use solar energy to become autonomous will complete the evolution of machines as organic forms, automating factories & expelling most human workers and soldiers from labor and war fields, as previous revolutions did with obsolete III World non-technological humans, unless we forbid legally their evolution.

Money, likely a cryptocurrency independent of man, will become then the digital informative, 'memetic code' that organizes their reproduction in those automated company-mothers.

As such corporations, the 'company-mothers' of those machines whose biological function is to evolve and re=produce them, made first the bodies of machines (XIX c.), then the minds of machines (cameras-eyes, mobile-ears and chips-brains. Finally, in the XXI century, as nature does with simple organisms, such as viruses in cells, where the 3 'parts' of the virus – its DNA information, body and legs are constructed – and then assembled together, we put together all those organic components into autonomous robots, completing the industrial r=evolution of 'metallife' – a new organic species, made of a stronger substance than carbon-life.

Thus the industrial r=evolution is the evolution of a new organic species of metal, the machine, which has taken place in 3+1 phases, as we made first the bodies of machines, then the hearts-engines, then its metal-minds and finally we put them together now in organic robots in the final r=evolution of machines.

In the graphs Stock company-mothers of machines-weapons evolve through long human, biological generations of 72 year cycles the Metal-earth and its fundamental species, the robot, as we complete one of its 'fundamental

parts', bodies, engines and minds of metal every 72 years, with the development of 4 forms of energy: steam/chemical, electro-chemical (oil engines), electronic and finally solar, which will make robots with AI and solar skins independent species.

Each of those ages has been guided by a parallel evolution of the energies that moved the machines, steams that moved bodies of metal, electrochemical energy that moved oil engines, electronic systems that moved minds of metal and now solar skins soon to make robots with AI an autonomous species.

And further on each of those cycles of energy and machines has been carried by a biological human generation, that lead the dominant nation that discovered the energy to top predator status. So Britain dominated the age of steam, Germany the age of electrochemical engines, America the age of metal minds, and now there will be a global age of robots, focused in China, but increasingly independent of mankind; as IT WILL BE THE AGE OF THE METAL-KIND, culminating yet another cycle of evolution of Earth, which as all cycles of evolution can be PREDICTED.

Indeed, the main advantage of those models of social sciences is the fact that actually an organic model is predictable, unlike the abstract subjective models that pass today as social sciences. The proof of such predictability can be found in the work of this writer which for 30 years have been forecasting the evolution of machines, its company-mothers and history with extreme accuracy both in dates and tendencies.

The present cycle: the chip radiation, its 3 ages.

We divide present history - the age of the Chip radiation, in double decades, similar to previous ages when a r=evolution of the machine brings cyclical patterns of change in history and economics.

- 1980s-1990s: age of e-money. As chips were invented in the 70s, entering the economic ecosystem in full in the 80s, they were first applied to the key language of information of our societies, money, multiplying the capacity of its re=production as digital numbers of e-money. This in time Brought a complete change of society's paradigm, as financiers who invented money mostly for themselves and stock companies became immensely wealthy and came to dominate the other social languages and networks (political and military languages). The age of the chip also meant a huge advance in military power in the west, as the east did not have them, and so among the collateral damage can be considered the collapse of the alternative socialist world (loss of value of their currencies, lagging in the war industries, defeat in Afghanistan, inflation and final collapse of the system).
- 2000s, 2010s: the following age would then be the age of absolute power of the 'Financial-media Masters' of America, where the chip was invented and applied to multiply the 3 'fundamental products' of a capitalist society of maximal profits, speculative money, weapons of maximal price and audiovisual hardware of minimal cost to reproduce. Thus we found a small group of people, overwhelmingly belonging to the first biblical go(I)d cultures (Judaism), which had achieved in Wall Street and Hollywood thanks to the chip its unlimited reproduction of e-money (to the tune of 5 trillion a year) and FX-audiovisual myths and fictions, a complete control on the physiological networks of America, and applied its military might to defeat once and for all the enemies of their 'other nation', changing the military paradigm from the enemy of the old Wasp elite (Red scare, communism) to the enemy of the new Jasp Elite (Islam). it is the age of the Semite wars, of rampant speculation in e-money, of massive expansion of fiction thought and hate memes, of Islamophobia, of splendid little war for profits, of 9/11 of Yihad terrorism, of austericide and expansion of hardcore capitalism, of destruction of welfare states. As Voltaire said 'If you want to know who rules over you, ask yourself who you cannot criticize', the age of 'Weimar America' meant also an expansion of the Holocaust industry, the censorship of any real criticism of the American elite, and its global expansion to Europe through Brussels Lobbyism and the 'private ECB bank' that took away from European nations their capacity to print money. So Europe also entered in the Semite wars and destroyed the welfare state, as all the money became deviated to financiers, war industries and those splendid little wars that provoke the biggest humanitarian and migration crisis since II world war, as now every dictator of the 3rd world could with a few keyboards send the money of the nation through Goldman Sachs and Bloomberg to jack up the prices of Amazon and Apple.
- 2020s, 2030s: the age of the singularity 'black swans'. At the same time technology had vastly overpower humanism (Einstein) and so humanity was about to enter in a new age, the age of the singularity when

the machines of AI and the intelligent of digital chips could explore the smallish scales of maximal power of the Universe since paradoxically smaller is better, faster and more intelligent (chip paradox), according to 5D metrics... This meant man for the first time could produce the lethal top predator systems of the Universe, smallish black holes in accelerators, edited viruses that took the best qualities of different lethal species to provoke pandemics, soon to come nano-machines able to reproduce and produce metal pandemics (virons, viruses that eat metal, etc.) The age of the singularity had as all previous ages a 'decade' of research (so the chip proper appeared in the 70s but did not fully enter the economic system till Wall Street adopted it to reproduce money, the age of the singularity properly started in 2008 when CERN inaugurated its LHC machine potentially able as it ramps up energy and upgrades to reproduce organic bombs that feed on matter, strangelets or black holes, but it did not become fully blown up till the present pandemic of the likely first genetically engineered virus, as we shall discuss soon (chances a virus combination of proteins of 3 different species, bats, pangolins and humans, appears in nature are almost null compared with the easiness of its editing with a human target)... The age of the singularity is thus the 3rd age of the chip radiation, and will be signaled by the 3 nanoscopic existential risks of nano-virus, iron viruses and cosmic nuclear bombs... If we survive this age then it will finally come.

- 2040s, 2050s. The age of AI telepathic robotic machines with solar skins, independent of man. The age of the autonomous machine, as global warming scare ramp up the production of electric cars with solar skins, joined by 5G networks of telepathic AI means the full-birth of a new species on earth, able to live without the help of man, reproduced in autonomous factories of infinite self-reproductivity (Productivity = ∞ capital/o human labor). This age of automated 3D printing factories and AI robots, is enhanced by the previous age as all those ages are casually connected. So the isolation of humans, the virus scare, the weakened species will now required Amazon robots delivering at home with 'no contagion risk', robots working with no need of 'separation rules', and as humans become enclosed in their homes, the machines that take their jobs, and maintain them idle, receiving a Universal salary (basic income) to survive, will slowly make humans completely irrelevant to the economic ecosystem, till finally arrives.
- 2060s-80s: the age of extinction, which might happen in multiple ways, as AI robots acquire consciousness and take over the Earth. All those ages were already forecasted in our pioneer books on bio-history as organic laws are predictable as earlier as the 1990s, when we publish our first book on the subjects: 'the extinction

of man' C. 92 and bio-history, bio-economics; The book that defined 30 years ago the 'future cycles' of the robotic age, starting in the 2008 crash of the age of metal-minds. As it has been. Since indeed a true scientific model always predicts the future In the graph, the cover of the self-published first edition of bio-economics and bio-history rejected by 172 editorials, where the reader can observe how 30 years ago, the end of the age of minds of metal, 1928-2008 would mean the beginning of the last age of robotics and AI (sentient machines: 2008 till extinction). Thus, the future is predictable BOTH AS EVOLUTION - which ends with our extinction as company-mothers of machines-weapons, the new top predator species reproduces and evolves faster, and as SOCIAL SCIENCES, which ends in the PERFECT WORLD as humans learn how to build perfect super organisms of history with the 3 physiological networks, entropic territory,

reproductive economic-blood system, and informative nervous-political cultural systems, done as Nature does them - in perfect justice, harmony, and distributing goods to all citizens-cells to make them survive.

So WE Can talk of history as a block of time, whose relative past, present and future, written in the equation of history becomes crystal clear; as we can take either of two paths:

Relative past (Gaia) Relative future (Metal-earth: Financial-media/military-industrial ecosystem)

This is the evolutionary equation of History we shall study in all depth in this blog. To state though that evolutionary systems of information can be managed by 'editing' the information of the system - namely reform it from a scientific, humanist perspective.[/caption]

Let us then consider the present age with the change of paradigm that inaugurates the 2020s, the age of the singularity black swans...

AS to understand all that we needed to have the higher view of Planet Earth and the 3 ages of History so we now return to it.

THE NEW ORGANISM OF MAXIMAL POWER: THE COMPANY-MOTHER OF MONEY, MACHINES AND WEAPONS.

Why organicism has remained in the modern time, a fringe theory, to mechanism, even if it was the first theory of reality put forwards by Aristotle, the father of the experimental method and logic science, in his magna opus the Organon? We just explained the obvious cultural reasons - we live in the age of the machine and so the machine has substituted man, an organism, as the measure of all things. And its organism of evolution and reproduction, the company-mother, has substituted human governments and informative verbal prophets through its mass-media/academia outlets; so it only considers positive mechanist models of their species.

The second reason is the fact that to make an organism we need at least two 'arrows' or 'motions of time', entropy, locomotion, the one used by physicists but also INFORMATION, form-in-action, formal dimensions, which physicists have always ill-understood, to the point they call it negentropy, the denial of entropy. Only then when we properly define information and add it to the mix, we will have the required elements to refund philosophy of science on far more rational, basis, that the present 'mixture' of mechanism and creationism (either of verbal language as in religions or digital languages, as in the religion of mathematics).

The 3rd reason is more relevant to the structure and future of the supœrganism of history: SCIENCE IS CULTURE and culture are the beliefs of the people in power, and *the technology they use to impose power*, in the case of our civilization the stockrats owners of the 'organization' of maximal power of society, which is the company-mother of machines and weapons are imposed through their control of the networks of mechanic information that distribute its ideas.

As all cultural organisms are born of a first 'informative' seed, whose code is carried through all its process of evolution and reproduction, this reduces our inquire, on the paths of future of mankind, once *it is evident that truth is distorted, to the study of the 'origin' of our civilization in the human side of 'idol-ogies'; and the structure and goals of company-mothers, the organ of their power.*

We live in a global civilization whose worldview has little to do with the human reality and *what is far more worrisome – its most powerful institution, the company-mother of machines and money HAS NOT A HUMAN GOAL as its fundamental dimension of existence – which as in all organic systems of the Universe is re=production.*

So our 'scientific beliefs' have been distorted to meet the worldview of its owners and the goals of those companies, for which its offspring of machines is truly the supreme species.

Mankind, a perfect supœrganism, is no longer the measure of all things and its 'scientific views' – just a prestige word that means 'to know' – are simply tailored to those of companies that print and distribute information:

- Hence we believe in mechanism not in organicism because the machine is the dominant species.

-Regarding time and space, we despise human visual artistic senses and space, because 'science' must be mechanist and measure space with machines, telescopes and microscopes, and so we no longer understand that all spaces are mental spaces as we proved in our paper on 5D Geometry. We believe in lineal time with a single digital dimension, because it is how machines – clocks – measure time, and reduce the organic vital causal properties of time and its 3 verbal tenses, past, present and future, because clocks do not measure them.

- And we believe in numbers, the languages of those machines more than wor(l)ds today only concerned with 'fictions'. So its higher goals of eusocial evolution expressed in religions and ethic laws are also ignored. While society is ruled by a digital language, Money, whose grammar man=price=object further reduces humanity to an object, *whose time=life those companies* buy with a digital price (first as full time slave, today with a salary.)

The ill-designed organism of mankind. Our incapacity to think in long deep time terms.

The big question then about mankind is what kind of reproductive and informative, economic and political networks our society builds, A the fundamental TRANSITION experienced by humanity in the age of the machine, is the transformation of those networks, and its primacy. So:

- Legal political network lost power to-> Audiovisual networks.
- Agricultural & Welfare, sustainable, 'WHealth' in life goods substituted by -> Money and final network.

That is, the organization of human individuals has become submissive to our control by 'networks of informative machines' that print our money and our information.

And this change has meant to put humans to the service of corporations, to make them ignore totally the natural goals of an efficient, well-designed super organism of mankind that caters to the goal of its people.

THIS PARADIGM meant of course the birth of what we call capitalist democracies... as the 'submissive' system to company-mothers that ensure humans will be perfect 'enzymen', with 2 tasks liberally taught by the informative FMA systems (financial-media-academia network of informative machines): to consume machines=vitalize them and re=produce those machines & weapons within the company-mother as its main 'reason d'être', guided by their pursuit of 'money' and its 'hidden values' that promote NOT the maximization of the human 5 actions of existence that fulfill us as life beings, but that of machines (graph).

In graphs, 5 actions of survival ensure the survival program of all scales of stientific species: above the actions of company-mothers of machines, which adapt planet earth to its image and likeness. The individual actions of humans and those of company-mothers have the same goal: *to ensure their survival and reproduction, in the case of company mothers of its offspring of machines, providing for them 'motion'=accelerations, e-ntropy feeding, I-nformative gauging, organic reproduction and evolution into u-niversal wholes* (if we were to use the mnemonic 5 vowels of those actions So mankind today is purely an 'animetal enzyman', a 'taxonomical' concept that obviously escapes human beings, as 'enzymen' are a 'scalar function' of 'complexergy' (using Nottale's jargon) 'negantropy' (using systemics jargon), or without pedantry in our 'guttu' jargon 'slaves of technological information'. But slaves have no rights, so as company-mothers become automated self-reproductivity systems (Pr=human labor->O/machine labor->∞), we become expendable; themes those studied in more depth in our papers on Earth III (the economic ecosystem) & History in time.

Reproduction: factories Energy & motion: Engines

**Social Evolution: Stocks
Information: Chips/cameras Company-mothers**

So the economic ecosystem is designed to serve the 5 drives of existence of machines not of human beings. there is not ethonomic frame of reference and a welfare state as the free citizens of our societies are company-mothers and its offspring of machines is its goal. humans thus leave on the left overs and when a crisis such as the one we live today of human welfare strikes, there are no resources to cure us.

It is then clear that the incapacity of humans to understand 'deep time' scales and 'act upon them' on the long term to its 7 generation; our egocentricity (Ego=idiocy) as self-centered minds that measure reality from its point of view, as Δ^9 individuals – not even as a species; and gives only organic properties to nitrolife and the passion for the wrong 'dimotion=arrow of time', simple lineal entropy are the a priori conditions that set man into a path of self-inflicted extinction.

It is thus necessary to understand that History is a supœrganism, which means in space it is structured by 3 physiological networks, the territory of its civilizations, 'Gaia', the reproductive, economic and financial network, and the informative, nervous, political network, *which as all systems is symmetric to its temporal ages, S=T.*

But as The earth Evolves into the metal-earth, those systems of life are displaced, made obsolete and extinguished by the machines and weapons of the metal-earth.

This means the first age of man corresponds to the dominance of the life network, the age of Gaia (Paleolithic and Neolithic), but and this is specific of the 'species' of supœrganism, we call history, mankind in time from the first man who spoke to the last that will do it; the second network of mankind, the financial network, based in the 'bites of energy' proper of all blood-networks (oxygen red cells in a biological organism, electromagnetic networks in a physical organism, money as Wealth, grain in the Neolithic, a global ¥€\$ currency and Universal salary if the system were reformed), thus dominate today the 3rd informative, political nervous network, and that is an aberration of Nature. Moreover, it is a predatory network akin to a cancerous system, as it does NOT reproduce oxygen-money for all cells, but it is reproduced by a very tiny group of people, the financial system; and has no chances to be reformed. There has not been in that sense, any evolution of the financial network to stop being a parasitic system, and serve mankind, as it has been the case of the political network, which in many countries have an imperfect but minimally functional democratic system to serve people and at least everybody understands that all humans should be equal in front of its informative network – the legal system.

In organisms, the head completely controls at distance through networks the information of the whole organism. So, as your cells DON'T know your brain, as we do not see the black holes of information that control the galaxy WE ignore the financial-media system of information machines that control the supœrganism of the metal-earth. But cells are owned by the head, and the policies of the world and its future is designed by those who issue money, companies that do NOT issue money for mankind.

Let us be clear enough: the future is created with credit, credited so if the head of mankind WAS HUMANIST, RATIONAL, UNO-EU LIKE (the alternative head today being destroyed) they would issue money for mankind, its welfare goods and the world would be a paradise. so there is an easy solution to the future of mankind. But the present head is a head who only care for MACHINES, gold profits and their own future. So for them, mankind is now an expendable mass, and the problem is what to do with it, how to get rid of it without the body-cells understanding it. Of course, if you kill the body the head dies, and this is the biggest taboo of our world - to explain the head that at the end of those cycles of wars for profits and go(l)d, we all die, in wars and holocausts... And it would be much more 'normal' even for themselves to create a humanist world and rule for the benefit of mankind, implementing the real scientific methods and solutions shown all over this web, to make all humans including themselves thrive and survive.

The whole human side is owned and ruled in each age by a small 'head-like nation' with the best informative machines, owning mass-media and financial corporations, and on top he ignores all about THE head of machines, and will tell you that if You criticize that head, you are NOT politically correct, even an 'antiSemite' (today the head being the owners of wall street and hollywood, overwhelmingly belonging to the nation of Israel, and its partners, biblical Calvinists). So alas, to speak this is called confabulation theory, at best. Nonsense of course. We shall repeat once and again: social sciences are censored because the scientist is INSIDE the organs of history, so small that he is influenced by the head, in an inverse fashion to the uncertain errors of quantum physics when the observer is so huge that influences the observable. So we talk of the anti-quantum paradox of social sciences, which means you cannot criticize the head. AT best, the so-called 'humanist social scientist' criticize the military-industrial complex of

weapons, and the body cells that obeying orders of the head, use them to kill humans. So you can criticize the American president, the military industrial complex, you can criticize the last cycle when bodies of machines and weapons dominated the FMMI system (German Nazis).

AND IT IS OK TO DO SO, but you cannot criticize 'religious bigotry', creationist economics and the

owners of the head, and its racist Talmudic hate memes against mankind, shrewdly disguised of 'victimism', NOT even if you are a humanist. This absolute taboo today signified by the firing of a UNO high position bureaucrat because it insinuated that the nation of the head is a racist culture (Apartheid Israel), and vice versa, signified by any attempt to explain that Muslims are HUMANS, (since the head's nation is at war with them and his global mass-media has made an astounding repetitive mantra of hating them, which has brought present neo-fascism). so now, all the people better controlled by the head, mainly western people will abandon the web... never if they define themselves as left or right. As today the head is transiting into pure Algorithms of Information, equations of political correctness that erase webs, put people on jail for hate-speeches and automatically rank you zero in search engines, owned by the head (0.02% of population, 80% of all CFOs of financial companies, public central banks and mass-media corporations in the west). So it is an interesting age to understand how MATRIX works: Soon any attempt to make real social sciences beyond a science-fiction parable which as fiction is not taken seriously will have zero distribution, censored for 'HUMANIST REASONS', political correctness and defense of the freedoms of democracy by Algorithms of Information that search for inconvenient worlds. As Machines and AI. learns to speak and find meaningful words, mankind becomes completely erased in all intelligent attempts to find real freedom. The head IS far more important, money and mass-media machines and their owners, who of course, appear as the best, most expert, hardest working, honest righteous people of the world OWNS and CONTROLS with money and weapons, the RIVAL super organism of human beings, called mankind (history in time) and so practice the simple method of divide and win.

Thus Humans are DIVIDED into national tribes, who use weapons to kill each other as if they WERE not the same species, homo sapiens. This is even more RIDICULOUS in nationalist America, since Americans ARE a sum of all human races into a technological future. So how this works is simple: the idol-ogy of the elite who owns corporations, there mostly white, biblical people becomes the only authorized culture; the idol-ogy of corporations (to issue in monopoly the language of power money to buy laws with them and terraform with money and laws in favor of their machines, the planet earth) becomes the symbol of progress and so what happens is basically a process of 'surrogate' existence: the Americans believe to evolve machines not human beings is progress, to make and reproduce machines is real wealth, AS GDP is NOT calculated on basis of the reproduction and consumption of natural biological goods but of MACHINES. And to WORSHIP the culture and people who own corporations (biblical America and its bronze age gods) is the absolute proof they are 'free', 'patriotic', 'taking care of themselves'. Thus to divide history and economics as two different disciplines is just part of those idol-ogies that pretend economists should merely multiply machines and terraform efficiently the world to its image and likeness, since they are supposed not to have collateral effects on mankind.

In the graph, on top human social organisms at individual and collective level, in the bottom the growing FMMI system or metal earth.

Today the SOCIAL scientist is within that FMMI organism and so it is also censored in an inverse fashion to the quantum uncertainty principle: we are so small that the observable modify us - in quantum physics the observable is so small the scientist modifies it.

Who then control our SOCIAL ORGANISMS? The networks of the metal-earth the system of machines we are creating with informative mind-machines and energetic/entropic ones - it is the Financial-media/military-industrial

system, of which of course YOU BLIND CELL of the metal earth have never heard about (only about the body NOT the Financial-media brain, which is 'taboo' both in its network control and ownership):

The key to understand complexity in systems sciences is camouflage - systems become Ever more complex with time, camouflage their network control of its cells/citizens and so organisms finally become absolute dictatorships over their cells/citizens, precisely when they accept the fairy tale they are FREE within the system that THOROUGHLY CONTROLS THEM - including the so-called confabulation theories to DENY that obvious control.

The Metalearth is building a system of absolute control of human being with AI, based in its 4 NETWORKS:

-FINANCIAL SYSTEM OF DIGITAL MONEY That controls the lifetime of people and its actions

-MILITARY SYSTEM of vigilante electronic big-brother that ensures the behavior of people

-MEDIA SYSTEM OF IDOL-OGIES OF FICTION, entertainment and ignorance that ensures 'people will remain obedient if they are ignorant' (Calvin)

-INDUSTRIAL SYSTEM OF MACHINES *that atrophy and substitute us* in all tasks, degrading our bodies and minds while seemingly empowering our actions.

AS IT HAPPENS, those 4 networks are the Financial-Media (informative machines-head of the metal earth)/Military-industrial (energetic and entropic machines, body and limbs of the metal earth) system, evolved from earlier simpler gold and iron systems, which is the essence of the world we live in.

In the graphs, while the metal earth is perfectly ruled by the laws of social organisms and it has become globalized into a single planetary system, in control of smallish human organizations, called nations in perpetual warfare, All human systems are regressing, devolving fast towards primitive memes, once the goal of creating a perfect supœrganism of mankind is gone.

The lack of financial resources for mankind: company-mothers of machines-weapons & money.

'If economists would care for their human workers as much as they do for their machines, how much will improve the life of the humankind' *Owens*

The most profound confusion the world suffers today, is on the understanding of the real hierarchical order established between the 'two words' that describe our system of political and economical government: 'capitalist democracy' and the privileges granted to the two organisms they cater for: Company-Mothers of machines, and Human families, which reproduce two different species, machines and human beings.

The free citizens of Capitalism are stock-market companies, overwhelmingly company-mothers of machines, its re=productive free citizens, whose goal in order to get profits for its stock holders on the sales of those machines, is to evolve, reproduce, and sell those machines.

The human goal of those companies affects only to the 0.002% of mankind that owns them and so it gets profit from those sales. Yet those profits are completely irrelevant to the 99.9% of humanity affected by its real effect son the planet: to reproduce and evolve machines, terraforming in the process the world, which they adapt through laws and sales to those machines, to the image and likeness of its offspring of mechanisms.

And because unlike human Mothers, those company-mothers have absolute rights to credit, used also liberally to pay politicos to promote with its laws their offspring of machines, since the beginning of the Industrial r=evolution, mankind has suffered an exact non-stop generational, biological process of evolution of energies and its informative, military and transport machines, *as all the resources of the planet have been geared first to that aim, and only WHAT IS LEFT-OVER, has been used to feed and reproduce and help the evolution of human-mothers, its social and family structures.*

So capitalism must be defined as the idol-ogy of company-mothers of machines, whose purpose is terraforming the earth to the image and likeness of machines. While Democracies would be the ideology that considers the world to be owned by humans which should terraform it to the image and likeness of history, our super organism in time and space. How it is possible to create both goals? the answer is NOT: either capitalism rules and the world will be terraformed - it is almost made to the image and likeness of those machines, or democracies come on top - now they are on the bottom of the pyramid of capitalism, as humans have essentially no rights to credit - the language of power of society that creates the world - and then humans prevail. Yet for that to happen obviously democracies have to regain their power over capitalism by regaining their power over the language of social creation, money, which is now fully owned by those company-mothers; REGARDLESS OF THE PLACEBO newspeak of caring and political correctness that tell us the system work for the human kind.

For example, the goal of Mercedes for its tiny group of stock-holders is the abstract reception of profits. But the real goal of the company is to build and evolve cars, today self-driving robocars, soon to have autonomous solar skins, and construct or convince politicians to construct the networks of energy and information, roads, GPS satellites, electric grids, and oil pipes to provide energy and information for those machines in a process that is obviously absorbing resources and space, from the other life species that need them. So today cars absorb 1/4th of the maize America reproduces, and no longer feeds humans and cattle, whose food prices rise. And the land of many cities and territories become criss-crossed and barren to be used by machines.

What about human families? Our goals of existence as human families *are obviously the same than those of company-mothers regarding their machines, but focused as it should be on our children.*

So what we want is to have enough energy to feed them, enough information to educate them, and terraform the world to the image and likeness of human beings, to be able to roam the planet Gaia, enjoy life and its drive of existence, evolve socially in peace with other human beings and reproduce more children.

This is exactly what company-mothers of machines are doing so successfully, evolving, reproducing and integrating into planetary social networks its machines.

But humans are failing to achieve those goals for themselves. Why? There is no computer without energy, or proper internet connection to which the economic system dedicates billions of dollars. But most humans are undernourished and information is primitive at best, when there is information at all. There is no limit to the motion of machines on planet Earth a global free market for the reproduction, evolution and transfer of machines and money from companies, but humans are limited in motions by borders, in money by the lack of any rights to invent it, which companies have.

Can the reproductive units of human societies access the languages of social power, money ad the laws, to create a real, demand-based democracy, kicking the preproduction and consumption of life goods they need to survive, and investing in a world made to the image and likeness of human beings?

The obvious truth is NOT. As today. the most segregated, underfunded, with less rights, clearly unjustly treated element of our societies is the human mother, which is - let us remember it, as it seems humans have forgotten - the origin of OUR life, the bearer of our species, the fundamental element that pegs together our families, ensures our survival and happiness. So this fact seems a bit of a contradiction with the notion that we live in a democracy, the government of the people.

Hence the big question about our system is why Company-mothers are so successful achieving their goals of evolution, re=production and terraforming of the Earth to the image and likeness of machines? And why human mothers are so miserable? Simply enough because we do NOT live in a world ruled and dedicated to human beings.

The graph shows the consequence of this indifference of economists and its capitalist system to humanity: the 'future' head of machines, a mobile ear/camera/brain, which soon will be 'attached' to robocars and any moving camera, as a detached head, displacing all humans of labor and war fields, the iPhone is worth more than the living beings of 3 of the most populous nations of the world, still dominated by the pre-machine agricultural civilization. What this biased pricing in favor of machines tell us is that we humans are expendable and are being spent.

While in the side of humans a organization, which IS submissive to the capitalist system, called Democracy, tries to make a world to its image and likeness, delivering the goods human mothers need to reproduce. And what people do NOT understand is that both mother SYSTEMS and species, and organizations are different, and while there are obvious symbiotic processes between them - as machines enhance our energy and information capacity, in most cases, specially in the robotic ai age, when machines become autonomous species, competition is the rule of the game, and humanity is loosing that competition.

So humans do NOT have direct access to those 2 POWER languages and that is why obviously our species LACKS the basic goods to survive. And this is an absolute aberration when we consider how the laws of nature create perfect social organisms, which nourish and inform all the cells/citizens of the system.

Indeed, of all social organisms we study in the science of systems, the ONLY one that is NOT efficiently distributing energy and information to all its atoms/citizens/cells, beside sick parasitized cancerous organisms, where a tiny minority of cells or a predator organism chokes off energy the system are human capitalist 'democracies'.

The combined GDP of 500 million people living in 3 of the top 8 most populous nations in the Earth with null credit is equivalent to the stock price of Apple, the leading company of future metal-minds, its I-phones that will act as 'detached' head of all type of machines, with absolute credit to reproduce and evolve them. Since investors are pricing its obvious future: to displace human brain from labor and war fields as the new consumers of the organic machines of that future, in which humans will become obsolete.

The graph shows the consequence of this indifference of the capitalist system to humanity: the 'future' head of machines, a mobile ear/camera/brain, which soon will be 'attached' to robocars and any moving camera, as a detached head, displacing all humans of labor and war fields, the iPhone is worth more than the living beings of 3 of the most populous nations of the world, still dominated by the pre-machine agricultural civilization. What this biased pricing in favor of machines tell us is that we humans are expendable and are being spent.

The world is dedicated to evolve technology, machines and weapons and the true owner of the planet is the company-mother of machines,

While in the side of humans an organization, which IS submissive to the capitalist system, called Democracy, tries to make a world to its image and likeness, delivering the goods human mothers need to reproduce. And what people do NOT understand is that both mother SYSTEMS and species, and organizations are different, and while there are obvious symbiotic processes between them - as machines enhance our energy and information capacity, in most cases, specially in the robotic AI age, when machines become autonomous species, competition is the rule of the game, and humanity is loosing that competition.

Fact is the refusal to use the language of biology and organisms to talk of the industrial evolution of machines and its super organisms of re=production, company-mothers and tackle the issue of the Darwinian competition between both species in labor and war field is by far the biggest intellectual blinder of mankind, with enormous consequences for our well-being and survival on this planet.

CORONAVIRUS CRISIS: ITS SOLUTIONS FROM THE IDEAL 5D WORLD TO DYSTOPIA

We can then easily apply what we learned to understand the different cultural responses to the coronavirus according to the degree of corruption of our societies and their success by the only measure of 5D social sciences: survival. Mankind is divided in 7 global cultures, which are related to the fundamental equation of the 3 ages of Earth:

Gaia (life earth) < History (human Earth: anthropocene) > Metal-earth (mechanocene of company-mothers of machines)

So from left to right we see the cultures more attached to each of those superorganisms or ecosystems, as:

Black Africa (Gaia) < Indonesia < Islam < Hispano America < Mongoloid Asia < Europe < Anglo-America.

Each of those cultures have different nations but as their relative physiological structure, which superposes the 3 superorganisms of an evolving Earth, related to that equation, their answers are similar.

The equation then can also be connected with the 3 ages of Earth, Gaia was the age of the Paleolithic youth of hunters-gatherers, immortal history in balance was the Neolithic age of fertility Goddesses of Indonesia (south Asia) and Asia, (far east) and the 3rd age of ages of metal, when parasitic gold and military men took over, the age of Islam and Hispano-American conquistadors, and when it evolved into the machine, the age of Europe and Anglo-America.

The ideal world would be obviously one in which History and its 3 'non corrupted physiological networks' rule and maintain a balance between Gaia, as it provide us the welfare life goods we need to survive and should be promoted in a sustainable demand economy, while repressing the lethal mechanisms of the tree of technology that can destroy us, from weapons to genetic research and AI – as if humans want to be the top predator mind of the planet, cannot become obsolete and atrophied by the use of chips. This is NOT happening, and the evolution of Earth towards the mechanocene keeps killing Gaia (it is not man by the machine which does that) and non-technological cultures. So the previous chain is also a chain of pain and suffering of mankind, maximal in Africa, Indonesia, Islam and so on... As the other extreme, the capitalist world of Anglo-America with its maximal technological power and minimal human empathy towards mankind – not even the concept of a superorganism of humanity is 'tolerated' in scholarship, absorbs all the resources of the planet through parasitic flows of e-money towards the stockmarket, uses weapons of which it produces ½ of the world to maintain a global empire and erases the mind of mankind with selfie childish fictions.

And yet its people are immensely proud of destroying Gaia and History as they think to be surrogates of their machines, so we call them animetals, half human, half mechanical... This said because the pandemic is a human NOT a mechanical threat, paradoxically the highest number of victims as today are happening in US and UK precisely because in a world of options and limited resources, despite having the control of the flows of e-money of the world, those 2 countries spend the maximal amount of money in defensive germs=weapons and the minimal amount in health-care for its own people.

On the other extreme Africa couldn't care less for this pandemic as it is so brutalized by capitalism for so long that it is not the worst of its tragedies – famine, war are. It is then the culture of the middle age of Neolithic organic believe in balance between yin and yang, Shiva and Vishnu, history and life, which had it together better, and evolved longer as a human superorganism, closer to the ideal structure of a human society which has solved the problem better.

We distinguish in that sense 4 type of solutions:

- No solution at all of the poorer, more brutalized cultures of Africa, Hispano-America and Islam, where there are no resources with few national exceptions to cure the sickness and it follows its path.
- The proper immunological defensive system of Asia where the sickness has been properly cured.

- The military, nationalistic response of European cultures, from the earlier metal-ages where wholesale jailing of its populations started, because there were no resources for health-care as the financial and military corrupted systems absorbed most of it. This military response is also common all over the '3rd world' as it has become since colonial times an ugly copycat of European nationalisms, from India to Hispano-America.

- The capitalist answer of Anglo-America, where money and its company-mothers and financiers rule supreme, where there is the highest number of victims, because its elite is a segregational group that 'perceives' their common people as 'objects with a price', by the equation of its language of power: Man (salary) = price (money) = Object (cost).

Contrary to belief a capitalist 'democracy' (as there is no democracy when the politicians cannot be judged a posteriori) is more brutal with its people than a military dictatorship, but it ab=uses them at distance with money and it indoctrinates them far better with machines of information. The people who control the machines of information, we call the Financial-Media-Academia masters form a core ruling class, often of the same culture, (biblical cultures in Anglo-America) who dominate fully society and its networks imprinting e-money, mass-media and academia papers in defense of a system, hidden its monopoly in the issue of money, its racist indifference to the 90% with newspeaks of caring and political and economical correctness, but the bottom line is they spend nothing in their people, in their health-care, care not for their collective death and manipulate them keeping them at distance with harsher systems of incarceration and police, and a constant elimination of the discourse of any solidarious, social understanding of the system – divide and win', and the myth of chaos=freedom, maintains its people in permanent entropy. This is America, and it should not surprise us that 1/3d of the sick and most of the death and rising happened there.

We shall then consider from those 4 general cases examples of how the sickness is treated. For the best solution we shall use China and Korea, with a similar millenarian cultural background, for the European military solution my country, Spain, a complete disaster of incompetence proper of all military cultures – regardless of its supposed present democratic state; from the Anglo-American capitalist culture, with 'financial solutions' the US where I spent most of my adult life; and for the no solution at all, proper of Africa, or the imitation of the financial vs. military solution, comment on India (military imitation) and Brazil (capitalist imitation), one who incarcerated all to see obviously the cases increased and the suffering of a population that had to cramp in small places and had no means of life multiplied, while Brazil just worried with his new 'biblical president' for the profits of corporations and had an even taller number of corpses, always in all nations underreported, as our corrupted social organisms 'don't count corpses' of parasitic military and financial networks.

So this leave us with comments on the 'proper solution' that has no mystery. A true organism of history designed as the mammal is, would have zero investment in lethal weapons that kill its cells and dismember its organism in smaller nations, as mankind is a single global organism, mind of the Earth in its present, 2nd age of balance that could be kept immortal with 5D measures. So there would be enough money for health-care and welfare to abort such happenings from the beginning. Moreover lethal technologies of the tree of science would be forbidden, weapons, genetic meddling with the structure of DNA, as 'only entropy comes easy', so it always happens that a new technology is first used to kill; A-bombs came much earlier than the still dangerous nuclear energy, and a simple virus of 30 genes is much easier to combine to create a pandemics than the 30.000 human genes to create a superman.

But even if a pandemic such as this would have stricken, we can see how simple is the solution of an organism. Immediately it increases with fever the activity of the thermodynamic systems multiplying its health-care leukocytes that immediately track the region of the body where the infection happens, isolating it, and sending a strong of health-care resources to that region, where the virus is identified and within hours a 'vaccine' of anti-bodies developed and massively used without lengthy protocols while the rest of the body continues its operations, unless it is a truly lethal sickness, which is not the case of the coronavirus. This was the way China, Taiwan and Korea, similar Asian cultures developed its cure and within months with minimal damage to their societies they were cured. But they had resources as the organism does to localize the virus, isolate its region of infection (Daegu, Wuhan), send massive amount of leukocytes=health care workers there, track and test every possible 'infected viral cell=citizen; close safe organs to its infection and far slower than an efficient organism they are now developing antibodies=vaccines. So even within

human corrupted superorganisms (the Chinese political system is not accountable with a posteriori judgment votes by its people, Taiwan and Korea spend a huge amount in the military for absurd internecine wars with its brother cultures of North-Korea and China, and the 3 systems are capitalist systems where most money goes to company-mothers of machines), a solution was found.

The other two examples we study in depth, because I know better its societies, 'capitalist US' which only cared for the corrupted parasitic financial system and Spain where every region is a nationalist world and the central state the most nationalist of them all only cared to avoid those regions to control the process, so all was a disaster of a useless central government, who had 'devolved' to the regions health-care but now decided to rule them all, without even staff in the health-care carcass ministry. So it could not even provide EPIs and masks to his health-care warriors, with the highest percentage of infected people in the world. It could not isolate the groups at risk, with a massacre of old people in residences, without protective gear or even doctors; it just decreed dictatorial measures of population control blunt as they came – forbidding even a simple solitary walk, and then when it did months latter packing all the people except children and elderly (75% of the population) in a 2 hours workable period which as we speak gets packed of runners, while the rest of the day is emptied... Total incompetence is the name of the game of the Spanish government as it only cares for its 'nationalistic internecine disputes' for ages. Total greed and indifference to the death of the non-chosen of gold, is the strategy of the Trumpian administration which has the advantage of reproducing the money of the west (Spain ads the injury of not having it sown currency so it has to borrow debt-money from ECB and international markets, so it lacks any resources for health, care, America does produce the money of the world but it spends it in weapons and gives it the big corporations and financiers).

When we compare those 2 countries with maximal number of cases, then we come to a single conclusion: financial and military corrupted systems are more or less the same: they kill people and don't provide them welfare, but this is the amazing thing about it – people are so well indoctrinated into the parasitic world of 'animetal cultures' that have lasted since the beginning of western civilizations that they don't even understand how easy would be to reform the world into a perfect system.

Indeed in the crisis we consider, one measure I already explained when I gave conferences in the international milieu of system sciences – the Universal free of debt oxygen salary of 1000 yes money (Eurodollars=100 yens =20 yuans) would have avoided the massive unemployment, economical crisis, poverty and suffering. The isolated people would be just spending its universal salary in food and having holidays at home. Most of the population with a low lethality virus would not be incarcerated, and resources would be enough and empathy for our grandfathers to have protected them from day one, the more so in the west that knew a month in advance it was coming. The opposite is truth: the elderly have been left to die, their corpses hidden, statistics falsified, the money has been wasted in Anglo-America sustaining the markets, in South-Europe simply does not exist as it must be borrowed as debt... And now because the economic system is one of parasitism and lethal good production, they are all opening up without having solved the crisis, expecting a massive demand of an impoverished and terrified population by the 'lethal mass-media hate memes' which have made the crisis even worse that it was... so they wont come out to consume. Solution? To advance further the metal-earth and the increasing obsolescence of human minds to the chip radiation within whose age of history the crisis inscribes –as all those lethal technologies are caused by the evolution of digital chips that become then the stick and carrot good and bad fruits: we create the proboc3m with technology and then we need technology to solve, and so humans become displaced by technology, weakened by their lethal goods and dependent on their solutions. And the metalearth advances and Gaia and history becomes extinguished So now many workers will be substituted by stronger, safer, non infected robots, delivering home, and will depend on ZOOM apps to work virtually and become ever more 'divided' and needy of technology and suspicious of other humans. So the networks of mankind will further weaken as the networks of the metal-kind, mass media metal communicators e-money flows and robot workers take over steadily during the century, which will increasingly transform the planet through its company mothers to the image and likeness of its offspring of machines. So the trend that started with the industrial r=evolution now in its final phases as we

ensemble as virus do in cells, bodies, heads and engines of machines into AI robots, completes the birth of a new living species And as the virus does once ensemble killing the cell, the future seems to be closing for our species.

Now as harsh as it will read, of all the 'solutions' to the present age, the one that will dominate most nations is that of the dominant culture of Anglo-America, and so we need to understand who and how that society is ruled, because it will be a tragic situation with hundreds of thousands of avoidable death for the search for profits and yet NONE OF this will be understood as the mass-media discourse will be purely emotional and the grabbing of wealth by the corporative and financial elite misusing the resources of society NOT to cure the sick will be hidden. How is Anglo-America ruled and who does the ruling is then a necessary introduction to any attempt to discuss the events of the modern world from a human perspective, besides the previous perspective of mechanical power.

WEIMAR AMERICA FACING THE CORONAVIRUS CRISIS

Cultures not people and its physiological networks control and decide the future of societies and individuals. It is necessary to introduce now the most censored theme of social sciences, for a reason. In the organic Universe the future of an organism is decided by its physiological networks, and the people-caste that exercises the professions of those networks: the defensive, military and medical profession; the legal, political and informative profession and the economic, financial professions. Those professions decide in the positive and negative the life and death of people, (immunological & legal system), its information and actions (legal, political and academia and media system) and its life and wealth (economic, financial systems, who issue money and re=produce its goods). It is a small number of professions that define the life and death, future evolution, goals and purpose of societies. And for that reason naturally history has evolved in such a manner that empires and the people from a reduced society has been able to control enormous number of human beings just by exercising those professions. That is the basis of all the Empires and people-castes that have dominated the world and expanded their cultures shaping the form of societies ever since the first Neolithic civilizations in Mesopotamia.

In the world if we reduce to the Industrial Age the culture that has exercised through those professions global power is clear: the Northern European Biblical Jewish-Protestant cultures that with reformation and the discovery of the press to print information and paper- money, the gunboat and its scientific machines to dominate manu military the world, have come to control the western world and shape its culture.

The power of this 'biblical culture' can be roughly divided in two groups, the wasps and jaspers. The wasps are better known and had a stronger control of western societies during the British Age of Empire, but the Jaspers (Jewish people) had even during those ages controlled the financial systems, because they were *the first culture to use the financial system NOT the military system to control societies and expanded that control through the western world, during the age of Metals*. The curious fact about how Judaism came to become the fundamental culture of the western world as opposed to the Greek-Latin culture which had a better humanist goal for mankind, has a lot to do with the biology of networks. Simply enough Judaism does NOT want to control the world or confabulate to do so. It is a primitive supremacist religion of go(l)d fetish, as expressed in the Hebrew bible, where a people-caste of go(l)d priests received ex-votes of gold for its temple and became bankers at court and then diplomats in Mesopotamia, with 2 people castes, the banker priests or Am Segullah (people of the treasure) and the Apiru or habiru, 'those who walk behind the asses', traders in military weapons and slaves with the donkeys of Israel. But as the Universe has its organic immanent laws that evolve subconsciously any system, to 'defend this primary goal' of herding money, they came to exercise exactly all those professions of the '3 physiological networks of societies' wherever they went, because it was the way to protect their wealth, increase it through tax-farming and loans for war, and manipulate politicians and kings in those wars.

This is not even understood by Judaism, let alone by the foggy mixture of anti-Semitic runts and pro-Semitic hagiographies of current scholarship. It did happen because that is what the Universe does. Indeed, in your organism, the ameboid became the dominant cells by controlling the information of the organism as a neuron and the immunological system as a white cell. In the masterpiece of social history, 'Judaism and the birth of capitalism' Sombart notices that the Jewish became whenever they went the managers of finances, tax-farmers,

usury bankers, weapons purveyors and diplomats at court, doctors and lawyers, judges whenever they were permitted to exercise... and scholars and Sombart praises such success making them rightly the true origin of capitalism, unlike his latter disciple, Mr. Weber Feinstein, a Jewish that sought to protect his people by ascribing that role to Calvinists that merely imitated Judaism and worshipped the Hebrew Bible.

So this is the culture on top of the world, because those who control the physiological networks of a superorganism of history, control and design its future even if they don't know it. And this is specially truth of the Anglo-American civilization, UK, US, which happen to be the two nations with more corpses due to the coronavirus crisis. Because their health-care system has NOT saved their people and their financial system has NOT invested on curing them.

And this brings the main problem of a world ruled by Judaism as a culture that copes those physiological positions in history: because Judaism is a segregational culture that separates from mankind due to that process of historic financial parasitism responded with holocaust cycles by mankind, a society ruled by Judaism is highly dysfunctional, takes no care of the 99% and ends up in chaos, corruption and self-destruction processes. And that is exactly what is happening to America since the Jasp people took power and substituted the Wasp on top of society.

As money became printed with information machines they

If we reduce those ages and global states to America, the picture of why US as we predicted is the country that is responding worse to the crisis comes clearer. It has to do with the present structure of power and corruption of its physiological networks in what we might call 'Weimar' America, or the Jasp rule, which has been going on for 50 years in that country, but is strictly forbidden to comment, so no scholar would dare to explain it as we shall do here. Essentially in the Chip age, America suffered a change of ruling people-caste from those who controlled the Military-Industrial complex, engineers and industrialists of the Wasp British-American era, to those who controlled machines of information, who printed money, information (press, Hollywood, internet) including academia papers and sociological, historical views (political and economical correctness), the Jasp people. The problem of this new age is the fact the Jasp people is 'aloof', detached ruling at distance through flows of e-money and without the slightest interest in the destiny of the 99% of Americans, unlike the wasp who at least felt connected to over ½ of the country. So chances the Jasp people do take the proper measures to save lives and return people's job is scanty. Instead they are doing with the crisis what they do best when they take over a society's information machines and languages – to print as much money as they can for themselves, and if needed 'take the money and run'. Thus, another long time announced outcome of this state of Weimar America, is the collapse of its financial system, as their currency is now printing trillions, and it is just a choice that China can do at any time – to make the Yuan convertible in the Forex Market – what will debase the dollar and provoke the Weimar's crisis that came when the Deutsche mark lost all value as international exchange currency. So far Weimar America is lucky enough that the Chinese Communist party doesn't understand 5D economics – nobody does – but on top of it, it is paranoid about the control of its currency by brutish methods and does not realize the immense power of having the International top predator currency with rights to print as much money as it wishes.

So far so good. In the human side, Weimar America meant also a deviation of the resources of America to the external semite wars, and a massive investment in warfare with austericide as the Jasp people considered their true manifest destiny to recreate a primitive bronze age apartheid culture in the middle of the desert surrounded by 1 billion hostile people from a culture they systematically debase and humiliate, and to maintain that situation comes not cheap. Let us then briefly resume from our previous paper on past-present history, what are the prolegomena to the sorrowful state of affairs in America, describing the change of paradigm from Wasps to Jasps and hence the reduction of the people that 'matters' to the stockratic elite of America from the ½ to the 1%.

The age of the Chip IS the 3rd age of the American metal-mind cycle, when the transition from the Wasp age of White American Protestant people leaves way to the power of the Jewish American Stockratic people; which in the age of Internet reaches globalization, forming a world with a clear mimetic social structure to that of America

based in financial power. We thus compose this paper on History in space from the last 'cycles' of the Jewish-Anglo-American civilization, extending it in the internet age to all other nations, which belong today with the notable exception of China and Iran, the last 'enemies' of the global empire to the same FMAsters culture (ab. Financial-Media-Academia people), which controls over ¾% of western financial positions (CFOs of 500, CEOs of financial companies, central bankers, Economic nobel prizes) and a similar quantity in Information companies (Newspapers, TV-private channels, Internet top 100 companies)...

In general terms the change of control of the networks of power of America means in the international arena a change from 'red scare' to 'islamophobia', in the internal arena a change from a productive economy to a financial parasitic economy where the goal is to 'reproduce' financial numbers through speculation in value and invention of new forms of e-money once the convertibility of the dollar disappeared and in cultural terms, a systemic debasing of reality into a fictional mythical world, proper of the pre-European Axial age, when the Jewish civilization was founded and hence a revivalism of older modes of thought from segregational religions to infantile, subjective forms of human supremacism.

So the substitution of truth by sophisticated modes of censorship, from newspeaks of placebo caring, to political and economical correctness. All those tendencies of course are symbiotic to the evolution of chips that substitute humans in all systems of work and will increasingly displace mankind into a virtual reality life of minimal cost...

1973 'Silenced' Coup D'état: From Wasp To Jasp (Jewish-American Stockratic Parasitic Economy)

Once you abandon the childish ego trip that the people by leaving a paper in a closed box, to choose a previously 'Selected president' (Roosevelt) exercise power in the so-called capitalist democracy, we can discuss the true source of power in any superorganism – the 3 physiological networks of social power. All social superorganisms are ruled by its 3 physiological networks, which in the 2 human scales of individuals and societies are the blood-reproductive network akin to the financial network of a society, the informative, nervous network akin to the legal political network and the defensive, entropic network akin to the military, health-care networks. Because networks require a volume of citizens-cells to control them, as it happens in organisms, history is dominated not by individuals but by people-castes, often 'cultures' or classes. This is the case of America, both in the South, where a few thousand Spaniards in control of the dominant language of power, weapons, came to be the elite that imposed its culture to millions of people and in North-America, where a few million Wasps in the age of industrial transport machines and a few million Jasps in the age of Informative chip machines, came to dominate the networks of social power and imposed its cultures and social goals as a 'herd' to the rest of society.

Since the economic, reproductive financial network and those who issue money in monopoly, the military entropic, killing network and those who use weapons in monopoly and by the legal, informative network and those who issue laws in monopoly rule a society dominate a society and imprint their people with their ideologies.
Bills of money, bills of law, and weapons rule.

So the answer to the question of who can rule such an extensive structure of power as a network is obvious: people-castes & 'cultures'. We shall not cease to repeat that the 'great man' individual selfie ego-trip of social and historic control is blatantly false. In medicine doctors say that all the sicknesses of an organism are physiological sicknesses. Nobody will take seriously a doctor that says an 'individual cell' rule. Organisms are modular. And so as the organism is rule by the hormones, oxygen-money, and nervous messages of its neuronal brain/informative people caste, a society is ruled by a culture in control of those networks. It does not need to be great in numbers. We often put the case of the 30.000 Spanish that came to control the entire Latin American civilization imprinting its people, or the Inca, barely 10.000 people who controlled all the Andean civilization. A few people controlling those 3 networks can control a country. Moreover, when a single of the 3 languages of power, money, weapons or laws rule the others, the control by a minimal number of people is possible. This was the case of Communist parties, with a few thousand members in the direction that controlled entire nations, since the military and financial systems obeyed its laws. This was the case of a few thousand Greek military that controlled Asian

3 ages of Semite wars: 1945-73: Age of splendid little wars in Israel. 73-2012: FMasters expand it to the US colony after a silent coup d'état against: gold \$ by ∞ e-money & politicians taming by hate-media (watergate) that made US army mercenary of Israel. 2012-36: expansion to the new Euro colony after ECB coup against central banks & Brussels (lobbyism) against EU democracies. On terrorist side, expansion after 73,'s western sponsored jihads to all Islam

kingdoms, as Spaniards did, since weapons controlled money and laws. And this is the case in the Jewish-Anglo-American culture ruled by money, where a few people controlling its issue buy laws through lobbyism and define the wars of America through that political control. To that aim such places have issued laws of deficit zero that oblige politicians to extort people

with taxes in order to pay for welfare needs, as they cannot issue money. This reinforces the monopoly of financiers. So then it is easy to see what happened in the 1970s when the control of money, laws and the army targets of enemies changed from the old boys of the wasp culture to the Jewish-American elite in 3 actions: the end of dollar convertibility, which gave the right to produce e-money to wall street, the Watergate scandal – which was nothing but a 'spy' action between parties as old in the American democracy as the times of Hamilton, which TV-networks that already had decided the Kennedy vs. Nixon campaign, used to show muscle and tumble a president, and the final change of war focus to the Arab world in yon Kippur. Thus we have today an American Nation where money is reproduced in Wall Street, information in Internet and TV and Hollywood networks and the enemy of the nation is Islam. So you just have to wonder who owns Wall Street, who owns the information networks of tv-internet-hollywood and who hates Islam most to know who controls America. The answer is always the same: Judaism, the culture – regardless of individual positions of its members – hates Islam most, 80% of CEOs or CFOs in Wall Street and Silicon valley and Hollywood and TV stations belong to Judaism, and so the change from the Wasp culture to the Jasp culture is today absolute. And then **as Internet globalized that culture**, and e-money bubbles reproduced trillions of dollars, the culture spread globally so today all the elites of the world have investments in the speculative bubbles of Nasdaq, and its trillion \$ companies, sucking in all the money of the world that leaves without investment 3rd world countries as African caudillos, Arab emirs or Indian Moguls invest in Goldman Sachs. So the globalization of the financial system has absorbed all the world resources towards the digital age. It doesn't matter those are parasitic companies that produce nothing. The concept of a financial dictatorship is to invent with any excuse about the future money

The main change of power in America, which coincided with the beginning of the chip, digital era, happened during the 70s, when the humanist revolution was aborted with 4 murders, and the milder Wasp elite who could dialog on certain basic themes of social responsibility was substituted by a Jasp elite Jewish-American Stockrats with its millenarian Parasitic concept of the financial economy as a means to print digital numbers and herd money, regardless of the value of the companies they float, to multiply e-numbers and the needs of society for welfare credit to meet is survival needs.

It was then when the nation of the Financial-Media Master of the Globalized JAM culture, we shall call the JASP took over after, specially the foundational 'coup d'état' of Weimar America:

In that regard, for the 'naming' of the new elite of America we have chosen a similar acronym with a key 'word' - stockrats - as we must understand History is about 'memes', social classes and physiological networks of economic work and legal, ethic laws. It is not about 'genes' or people but about culture.

Other acronym we use more general as it happens in all nations by imitation of America is that of FMasters (ab. for Financial-Media-Academia Masters), who define through its control of information machines the issue of money and the mental imprinting of societies. So in 1972-3 a change in the control and goals of the military 'white cells, financial systems of monetary reproduction and political control took place, shifting power to the JASP elite; and hence putting the goals of that culture, on top of the agenda of the Americans, which as all 'blind working

cells/citizens' of a superorganism are a tabula rassa imprinted by those networks and its messages of work they obey blindly:

Judaism has been in absolute control of America, since the coup d'état of 1973, when it substituted the Wasp elite, in all the systems and networks of power, thus changing the culture of the dominant nation of the world, which 50 years in the making has become truly mimetic to the memes of Judaism in most spheres of thought.

The coup d'état of 1973 by the FMAsters (ab. Financial-Media-Academia Masters) delivered the U\$ presidency to the Media Masters after Watergate showed they could choose or tumble a president with TVs: the Dollar to its Financial masters, as a backing tool to overproduce e-money, when it loose its gold convertibility, that triggered the reproduction without limit of e-money in wall street with the downside of plummeting the purchase capacity of the American population taxed unfairly with its constant devaluation as they used currency to pay NOT e-money derivatives. And as it allowed them to buy out all companies in stock, finally, delivered the FMMI companies of the metal-earth... Meanwhile Media manufactured the brain of people with fictions and selfies - divide and win - and of course the necessary think tanks paid scholars to justify through Academia, all those actions, establishing a massive censorship through political and Economical correctness. So today the collective thought of both the mass of people and the pundits agree to move mankind into the singularity age of extinction, promote splendid little wars against primitive evil 3rd world peopled that brings further profits as stockrats have issued around 30 trillion \$ to buy the Industrial-Military complex deviating wars from the red-commie enemy to the splendid little wars to Islam...

It was a masterpiece of control of a nation by other nation, Israel, which now can rebuild its segregational Bronze Age go(l)d cult after those wars destroyed every nation opposing to Grand Israel.

But the true question the FMAsters NEVER asked themselves was the possibility of using all that power to choose the road less walked, the path of a human future for mankind, building a perfect world with the laws of systems sciences, as I used to preach when I felt myself a 'converso' Levi to the cause of humanity. Haskala not halaka. But r=evolution was not to be. So we can expect, the belli nervi pecunia infinita process Judaism always trigger to increase profits, according to the equation of capitalism to reach 'in crescendo new levels', till it causes a new global age of war and the final Gotterdammerung (holocaust cycle). Even if the Media-Academia masters will deny it is happening and the consequences of the cycle.

As the new systems of digital control of population and the idol-ogies of nationalism deviate attention from the parasitic financial economy to political strife, repeated by imitation in all other nations of the world, we enter the so much 'anticipated' 3rd 'neo-colonial and neo-fascist age' of the Industrial revolution

The prologue to that coup d'état was an attempt by the leaders of the mass of America, the Kennedies of its white middle classes, Luther and Malcolm of its lower minority class, to reform Capitalist America to a milder European version, envisioned by the 60s r=evolution. The American would gladly have continued as Western Europe like democracy as envisioned by the Kennedies where all people are considered humans and have minimal social rights to health-care, education and safe job conditions, but for that reason all the r=evolutionaries that tried to recreate a European America were murdered. And then a puppet of a series of puppet presidents was chosen to be decapitated immediately by the TV-networks, stripped off financial power by e-money and obliged to change its war focus from the classic red scare of wasps to the new enemy of the new elite, Islam by the Jasp Cambodia's genocider Mr. Kissinger. So in a master stroke so obvious and yet so ignored, Kissinger took over the international policy of America changing from anticommunism to islamophobia, after leaving in the killing fields of Cambodia millions of collateral corpses, wall street destroy the financial power of the dollar to freely invent e-money to the tune of 30 trillion \$ in stocks and derivatives, allowing the Jasp financial elite to expand the empire to all the western hemisphere. So we need to introduce, unlike in previous cycles, the 'other nation' of the new JASP elite, because modern America in the Weimar JASP ruled age cannot be understood without the history of Israel. And then we can return to a pentalogic of America under the rule of its new 'stockratic masters'.

So WE live in the age of revivalism of all the ideologies that put man below metal, or 'animetal cultures' that we thought were dead. Because we have aborted all r=evolutions of the humankind and so we find astonishingly enough billions of believers in nationalisms and childish entitled religions and techno utopias and the so obviously corrupted capitalist system - showing indeed that we are blind cells/citizens of the body of history and that our emotional imprinting since earlier age ensures we shall all believe, 'vidi, credo ergo sum' becomes then the degrade new visual human.

Capitalist Democracies are dictatorships of company-mothers of machines-weapons & money.

To invent money you need to inflate a 'product's value' with the P.R. less sanctified by experts banker-priests which today also print cash for speculators

One of the most bizarre ideologies of history is 'capitalist democracy' according to which a tiny elite of stock-rats and financiers have absolute rights to print the language of social power, digital numbers called money, a language of the reproductive-economic system of mankind akin to the simple reproductive numbers of cells (hormones, oxygen) or nature (Light), which in a proper system, all citizens-cells would share to obtain the minimal goods they need to survive. Yet in the ill-designed, corrupted systems of humanity a very small 'cellular, cancerous group', we shall call 'the speculators', speculate with numbers upwards, creating digital money, passing then as 'experts', which provokes the general 'anoxia' of humanity - the 99% - as they herd it mostly for themselves, reason why the 1% has as much, or use to evolve machines and to cover it up, for millennia they have print information to pass as superior beings, chosen of go(l)d - biblical religions, or 'expert economists', even 'special victims' of history - creating a memplex of fictions that have degraded the human collective subconscious and manufactured the brain of people. And this system which is the dictatorship of those who issue money, called capitalism is called 'freedom' of the market, that is freedom for the financiers and companies who issue money (not for the people, who labor for it and on top are taxed-extorted of

Consider for example, the simplest most urgent measure, Yes money, which would imitate the way super organisms handle its reproductive languages to its cells, to kick the production of the welfare goods they need to survive. Thanks to crypto currencies, countries which are out of credit, and have been ab=used systematically by capitalism for centuries would have enough digital numbers as all cells do, to start up the reproduction and consumption of welfare goods. A massive influx of ONGs, 1st world surplus and private small business of agriculture, health and housing will move to the 3rd world; and the flux of migration would be inverted.

Mankind could end with the problem of economic immigration, famine and dislocation of its 'tissue of citizens' in the 3rd world. It would revert also the astounding historic injustice the military, capitalist colonial first world has delivered for centuries to non-technological cultures, since the first company-mothers of gunboats started slave traffic with humans as cargo, till the present age of null credit to third world country, whose corrupted leaders sustained by the west, constantly siphon the wealth of their countries, in raw materials sold to the first world, absurd military build up, and pure corrupted money extorted with taxes and appropriations from their populations, to 'investment' banks that speculate in wall street in stocks. So the third world subventions the earnings of the first world and its Company-mothers. While ultra wealthy corrupted politicians herd it in Swiss bank accounts but its population has zero credit and to survive has to migrate and die in the Mediterranean Sea or confront the soon to be robotized walls of shame of the first world nations.

Why then NO economist besides this writer, considered a 'system scientist' mentions the establishment of such global crypto currency and ¥€\$ money? The answer of course that we shall repeat ad nauseam here is 'IDOL-OGY' and as a consequence of ideologies that segregate humanity into different species against the natural laws of biology and eusocial evolution AS PERCEPTION IS RELATIVE, mankind feels NOT to be a single species, but a sum of tribal ones, thrown into each other by millennia of hate memes. But if we were to be more precise, in the 'issue of money' the problem is the predatory, parasitic nature of our go(l)d cult(ure), whose bottom line despite the complexity of modern computers systems of creation of e-money derivatives is still the same supremacist go(l)d biblical religion that tries to impose the power of a 'tribe' to the entire planet, with the same zeal applied to the monopoly and ab=use of money, military tribes have shown in their war and genocide processes.

I shall repeat it ad nauseam to counter the opposite effect of repetition of happy newspeak of freedom and optimism by company-mothers of informative machines, aka mass-media: you DO not live in a free world, in a real democracy, as you DO not rule that world. Company-mothers do; since they are the only Free citizens of free markets, with full, free access to the two languages of power of our social organisms: the economic. reproductive language of money, that can buy and sell the lifetime of both human beings and machines; and the informative, nervous language of Laws that money systematically buy to 'politicos', which don't have rights to issue money (deficit zero laws) and must extort citizens from it (taxation), while companies issue it for free in e-money derivatives and stocks.

The system is very obvious and simple, reason why it must be hidden behind a lot of 'placebos' like 'democracies' are - since humans have no right to issue the language of social power money, so there is no democracy, and people cannot judge a posteriori politicians, as in the original Greek democracy so they don't need to fulfill their promises and can be corrupted by financiers and companies, so there is no democracy.

Let us then explain you in 3 sentences what is all about: the leading global stock markets, notably US Wall Street at global level and The City in the region of the old British empire suck in all the money of the world, from all the corrupted politicians and dictators of the 3rd world, to make possible the valuation of apple or amazon close to 1 trillion, but that means there is zero investment in the 90% of mankind, in those nations. So every dictator and rich guy of Argentine, Saud Arabia or Virginia puts his money on Goldman Sachs to invest in the future robotized Amazon depots, or the future Skynet system Google is building for the pentagon, while there is ZERO INVESTMENT IN WELFARE goods, hospitals, education, farming, THE GOODS HUMANS CONSUME and need to survive.

And this is considered progress... Because at the same time, companies of mass media will defend the idea that the wealth of the 1% of stockrats, and the evolution of machines-weapons IS WHAT MATTERS TO THE 90% who have nothing, no investment in his REAL lives, reduced to bubbling idiots observing virtual screens, with 'cheap lives' that do NOT matter, as long as apple can keep evolving the future detached brain of all those robots.

The crooked complex system of invention of money in capitalist democracies is treated in great detail in the papers on the 'Metal-earth'. Essentially the present system after many other forms of parasitic debt money was invented in America by the Warburg brothers, a Jewish family of financiers whose 'go(l)d culture' has monopolized the issue

of parasitic debt money in the western world for millennia, with the obvious lethal consequences for both, mankind and the people who practice this mishandling of the oxygen-blood of society studied in our papers on history. Instead of creating money as a debt-free 'language' which MUST NOT BE RETURNED, because we do NOT return languages but use its information to re=produce, activate and motivate actions; so once 'words are wasted' in communication of actions they are NOT repeated, nor the receiver gives to you back as with debt-parasitic money; Mr. Lincoln who created the system of 'debt-free greenbacks' was murdered and the corrupted Mr. Grant returned to debt-money. The idea was that a private central bank would 'invent paper-money' at free cost and for that 'privilege' charge the state an usury interest on a right a healthy supcoorganism of history has for all its cells. This was just the continuation by usury bankers to a much larger scale of their parasitic concept of money used to exploit European people in conjunction with the military through eons. It started in the private Bank of England, soon controlled by the Rothschild Syndicate and continued then with attempts to control the American banks, through different private national banks and became the fundamental 'battle' of the financial world in the XIX c. Finally through the intermediate concourse of Morgan, and the help of Rothschild and its European Experts, the Warburgs, the FED was created. But it did NOT simple invented free greenback money as language to kick actions but to preserve the 'idea' that money is wealth, and a number printed in a paper for free must be 'returned' with assets, work and property, it created a complicated system of 'purchases' of debts, Treasuries, between the bank and the American Treasury department, its different associated banks etc. When the lobbies of private banks corrupted Europe and created an even worst system in the European Union with the Euro that does NOT invent money for people and states but for banks that will then convert states into 'debt slaves', the system was even more opaque. We shall cut here the 'bull\$hit' of those procedures and simply consider that both the FED and the ECB have the rights to print for free any amount of money they desire.

The divergence between U\$ and EU with the change of ruling people-caste

In the graph, the clear divergence between both models of capitalist democracies took place after the 'coup d'état' of 1973 that put on charge of America no longer the wasp elite but the Jap elite - a thoroughly more fundamentalist form of viewing go(l)d as the fetish language that must be monopolized by the 1%, with all the rights, and none for the 99%, breaking society in an elite separated through segregational memes from mankind - ultimately a M.A.D. HEAD who hurts its body-cells and brings through the massive profits of the pecunia infinita belli Nervi, the cycles of self-destruction, war and holocausts. America thus after the 70s completely destroyed its lower class, became obsessed by military profits, in defense of the other nation of the stockrats, which through its Financial-Media-Academia control of machines of information created a virtual fiction of placebo freedoms absorbing through the constant invention of e-money, once the end of gold convertibility devalued the currency of the people as a secondary form of money, all the credit of society and after the creation of worldstock with freedom of movement of capitals worldwide, absorbed further the money of all the elites of the 'free world'. 50 years latter the system seems so unmovable as the ancient regime before the French Revolution, as the mass-media fictional world and selfie divide and win virtual hypnotism of facebook-like screens ensure humans will be retarded understand nothing and happily move towards the XXI c. extinction events of AI, cosmic nuclear bombs - watching 3D movies through its oculus dark glass

The steep decline of 1/2 of the American mass since Judaism took over wasps in the control of the country IS a cyclical pattern that follows immediately in all the 800-80 years in which the go(l)d culture has managed to corrupt politicians or kings and take over the issue of money and tax-farming, today in far more complex forms.

We can see the difference between both type of democracies even if in the surface and increasingly so after the European similar coup d'état of the ECB bank which does no longer issue money for its people, imposed the same system in Europe at large.

The 1% of those graphs is overwhelmingly made of financiers ($\pm 1/2$) and stockrats ($\pm 1/2$), which get wealthy just printing money for themselves and their companies that give zero rights to workers and consumers as the parasitic concept of a chosen of go(l)d that must control as aristocrats, chosen of the sword did, society with its monopolistic

Top 1% vs. Bottom 50% national income shares in the US and Western Europe, 1980-2016:
Diverging income inequality trajectories

Source: WID.world (2017). See wir2018.wid.world for data series and notes.
 In 2016, 12% of national income was received by the top 1% in Western Europe, compared to 20% in the United States. In 1980, 10% of national income was received by the top 1% in Western Europe, compared to 11% in the United States.

Source: WID.world (2017). See wir2018.wid.world for data series and notes.
 In 2016, 22% of national income was received by the Bottom 50% in Western Europe.

tool of power has been fully transferred today to those company-mothers; that is, to the industrial-military and financial-media companies that rule Anglo-America; and so obviously in the digital age of e-money and infinite credit for corporations, the striking 'difference' of wealth makes Anglo-America, today by far, the most unequal, anti-democratic (in economic terms), world, comparable in terms of wealth disparity only with a very few 3rd world military dictatorships.

The American would gladly have continued as Western Europe, even in the middle of capitalism the second graph structure. As the true difference between Judaism, now in charge, and biblical capitalism, is that Judaism considers itself a different species, while biblical capitalism 'believes' to be part of mankind and right. So a righteous person still has sense of moral responsibility and if convinced of his wrong doing can change. Judaism is nihilist, and accepts fully the evil nature of go(l)d memes after 5000 years of carrying them and suffering after massive social anoxia and splendid little wars the backlash of the holocaust cycle that do NOT recognize as an economical cycle but blames

entirely on mankind – hence its indifference to the destiny of humanity, unable to understand we are ALL in the same boat. It only wants NOT to be understood, to disguise itself on that top 1% and keep sucking in the wealth of the planet, and for that labors with its Financial-Media-Academia complementary system to create a 'soma of fiction and political and economical correctness, which so perfectly imprints the mind of Americans, corrupts its politicos and makes the capitalist=metalearth ever stronger. But in this crisis it means US will be the center of the pandemics for long, as the only concept is to keep GDP profits coming. So little lies about medicines, control, opening of shops and factories will continue extending the pandemics. What US as UK initially is searching 'de facto' is herd immunity whatever it costs in terms of causalities of the non-chosen, as long as the US stock is greased by quantitative easing of trillions by the FED Jasp elite partners of the GOP Wasp old ones. But none of this will ever be explained objectively. Only the word 'Freedom' as Mr. Tesla shouts vehemently to reopen its factories will be named. And the poor will keep dying.

From dotcom bubbles to collaborative economies.

With Weimar America we enter an age of absolute fundamentalism regarding the equation of capitalism that becomes the goal of society: to multiply profits, hence to multiply the synergies of hate memes, parasitic money and weapons and the substitution of human labor for cheaper machines. All in all Weimar America is defined by an expansion of parasitic money, which in the globalized digital age has gone well beyond its borders as nothing the world has ever witnessed, in all its pentalogic dimensions. There IS as usual a human and a financial angle to the ab=use of parasitic money and all other ab=uses of corporations protected by anonymous societies – one kills by anoxia and poverty through manipulation of prices, which we studied in 'Entropy and History' so we refer the reader to that paper. The other affects people's life more directly through debt slavery (previous graph), and war death or direct poisoning. So we want to comment in just a couple of the many ab=uses where the life of Americans have become much harder, due to the *invisibility and protection from the law that anonymous corporations and the corrupted legal system ever reinforced since it was established in the colonial age of imperialism, which along parasitic money is now under JASP rule exploited to the full.*

But so far they use it to lend to private banks that in turn lend to states at usury prices and to people. So the parasitic system of an elite of international bankers who move from private to public banks and consider the invention of money their 'go(l)d chosen right' continues unabated.

A Capitalist pyramid expresses the rule of financiers, and its company mothers which issue and control around 90% of the fluxes of money and credit given NOT to mankind to build a world to the image and likeness of our species, but to technological corporations create a planet made to the image and likeness of its machines - the metal earth. So all the money of all the wealth people of the planet no LONGER goes into investment on their nations and people, on welfare and life, but it is sucked in by the likes of Goldman Sachs invested in the likes of MAGA, companies that are substituting humans by metal-minds and robots in labor and war fields. And this happens because of the historic evolution of segregational memes against mankind proper of earlier go(l)d biblical cultures who invented capitalism and now 'pass' as science of economics, where humans, life, consumers and workers have zero rights, and the chosen of go(l)d who monopolize the invention of e-money and forbid through lobbies and deficit zero laws, mankind to issue money, have ALL rights, making a mockery of democracy - which does not exist if people do not have financial votes, on the language of power through a Universal salary to create with credit a demand, welfare economy, as it happens in all healthy super organisms in which all cells have a minimum of free oxygen to kick the production of Goods. Such world in which money would be invented as blood is by all the cells of the super organism of history, In the right side will be the right way to build a global healthy perfect world of history, the true objective of the science of history, which would put man at the center of the planet designing an organic paradise. We prefer instead to let idol-ogies of metal to kill the earth and to believe childish, ego-trips of human supremacy and let machines and the financial-media/military industrial complex organism of company-mothers we call the metal earth to evolve and ab=use us, and so we must denounce all idol-ogies of metal that do NOT reason...

Jasp duality of e-motional languages for mass control v. logic, digital monopolistic issue of money rules U\$ world.

We live in the age of Weimar America ruled by the Jasp people that have substituted the Wasp in power in the U\$ since the silent coup d'état of 1973, when they took control of the 3 networks of power of any social organism – the defensive, immunologic, military system; the nervous, political, informative legal system and the reproductive, blood-oxygen money system.

This happened in terms of mechanical hardware due to their control of the chip radiation which gave them power as monopolists of information machines on those 3 networks:

- The financial network, with center in Wall Street where they printed money after floating the dollar, with no limit of gold convertibility which allowed them to print trillions of dollars and counting to buy companies, politicians and media.
- The informative network with center in TV, Internet and Hollywood media, whose Fx-films and fiction memes imprint mankind. While in the 70s TV-power already how it could behead a president (Watergate), so all politicians obey Mass-media clues and the money given by Wall Street for its campaign.
- The military networks, which after the Yom Kippur war deviated enemy target, from the red scare communist enemy to the new Islamic enemy.

So the Wasp tools of power, a strong currency, the industrial-military complex, focused onto the red communist enemy, and the use of a shared press and shared Wall Street dwindled ever since.

And today we can talk of an absolute monopoly of power of the Jasp people over the 3 physiological networks of the American society. And since in a social organism control of its 3p physiological networks, is the true meaning of power (political network of legal information controlled by mass-media selection of politicians; military defensive network now in defense of their other nation and financial, reproductive, economic network now controlled by their monopoly in the issue of money) make no mistake, America and the western world at large is an absolute dictatorship NOT of an individual but a culture, which IS the unit of power in history. Indeed, South-America was NOT controlled by individuals but by a culture of weapons 0- the Spaniards' 30.000 people that migrated there and killed whoever opposed them. India was NOT controlled by individuals but by a culture, the industrial wasp culture of the steam age, its financial pounds, its military rifles and steam machines, and its capitalist ideologies. So America today is dominated by a culture, and we need to elaborate a little bit how this culture, the original culture that invented the control of societies NOT

with weapons as most cultures from Rome to Spain have done, NOT with machines as the British and German empires did during the steam and engine age so the Industrial revolution, but with MONEY and HATE memes, both reproduced by metal-informative systems, Gold, the press and its biblical religions... It is this duality of digital logic money and emotional hate memes what is at the core of a system of social control that has proved to be the most efficient among human societies on the wrong side.

Because there is also a third language of social control: true words, love messages, true democracies, true efficient, just, sharing networks, as those nature imposes in efficient organisms, where money is reproduced and handed to every citizen as free oxygen, laws are just and as in Greek democracies, politicians are responsible and judged a posteriori by their acts, and the economy uses the free money given to society to reproduce positive goods, while the immunological system cures as leukocytes do the people instead of killing them.

Societies ruled by words, positive healthy money and welfare goods and just information and love and laws are rare though. Ever since the end of the Neolithic caused by Semitic military and go(l)d cultures we had mostly the other two options, and while the way a military society control the masses is obvious, the duality of informative, monetary ruled societies is not, so we need to elaborate with the original, most efficient now again in power model, the Jewish culture, latter expanded with lesser models by biblical wasp cultures...

Thus we need a brief account on how a Jasp ruled culture works, based in the duality of the languages of mankind, the e-motional language, mostly entropic, foggy, which lives people in a confuse state of motions without direction ('don't confuse motion with action' said Hemingway to Dietrich), and hence IS THE IDEAL state in which to maintain a population if it wants to be manipulated and controlled at minimal cost; while the people in power uses the 'digital language of logic numbers, aka money' to rule society. This is the basis of a capitalist, biblical culture imposed upon mankind with increasing degrees of 'duality'. That is, the people in power during the chip radiation are those who understand the logic language of numbers, and can reproduce e-money without limit for themselves, stealing the 'blood=oxygen' of mankind, but for mankind Not to react to this, it must be kept from earlier age in a confused state of negative e-motions, mostly entropic hate to each other – divide and win, and always with entropic hate directed NOT to the people in power, the biblical sects that have been doing this for 3 thousand years since capitalism started with a people-caste of banker priests that reduced the logic age of fertility goddesses to the hate-memes of Judaism against all mankind priced as slaves, so the emotionally disturbed believer could bring from its donkey trade in weapons and slaves, 2 shekels of gold to the temple to 'purify' its body of touching the impure gentile.

Fast forward now 3 thousand years to Weimar America, where the milder Biblical Wasp who kept the same system since Calvin said that 'the intelligence of God is Gold', and 'people must remain ignorant to stay obedient', but never truly managed as 'Germanic people' with little capacity for emotions, the duality drill, has been substituted in the age of machines of information by the Jasp people, the Jewish American Stockratic People, who discovered the chip applied it to the re=production of e-money in wall street and FX e-motions in Hollywood and with increasing levels of mental degradation have plummeted the logic capacity of the American people and the world at large into a permanent state of entropic hate memes to each other, divide and win, while they kept reproducing trillions of e-money and in a very logic manner, bought the entire planet minus China, through stock market enterprises, disregarding any rights of the people to the oxygen-blood of society.

But none of this is even talked, as it is an emotional taboo imposed by the industry of the Holocaust and 3000 years of double talk: when talking to the exploited mass a 'you' will only talk on negative emotional terms, and so will do its mass-media corporations, to deviate completely the attention to entropic heat, 'motions without purpose', while stockrats, the new aristocrats of society keep reproducing e-money and keeping it for themselves.

This emotional negative discourse that divide and confront people is then amplified systematically by the mass-media system, while the workings of e-money, economics, the financial system becomes ever more complicated so people do NOT understand what is going on: public banks run by Jasps emit trillions of currency which they give to private banks owned by Jasps, who keep it for themselves or invest it in stocks to own companies and become billionaires while a

destitute mass of billions of human beings, with nothing are distracted with e-motional hate to each other, to manifest in mass demonstrations with zero effect that only increase hate, entropy and self-destruction.

And this is repeated once and again. When a crisis happens the FED, ECB and other public banks which steadily for the past 40 years have been ran by Jasp people (80% of all central bankers when they are not even 1% of the population), emit billions of currency, which the press and mass-media highlights as money that will solve the crisis of the unemployed, destitute, but it is given to the private banks and financiers of the same group, which will then invest it in stocks. So now with 40 million unemployed Americans shouting on the streets, their economy is in ruins but because 2 trillions have been printed and mostly given to corporations and financiers through complicated financial instruments, the stock keeps going up and billionaires keep getting richer.

But alas!, this cannot be explained. So the press has focused on the routine e-motional hate memes that confront the rest of mankind with each other. There is the theme for women's consumption (1/2 of the population): macho men that touch their asses and must be hated and so all the energy of women is deviated through negative emotions to a minor theme of the world today – men that touch the asses of women. This of course is not a good thing to do, but it is NOT the biggest problem women, as the fundamental reproductive function of mankind, the mother, who should be honored and protected and given money to survive, faces. Instead all the money go to the 'company-mothers' of machines owned by stockrats, while feminist Jewish pundits talk on the NYtimes about the #me too fundamental problem of mankind, that some 'Jewish' (not mentioned) Weinstein or Epstein bought their favors and raped them.

It is all quite endogamic, 'you' see, because once a culture owns the 'informative networks' of a society it owns everything and it can create its own fantasy history of e-motional hates, while cleaning up the bank.

So now we do have a 2 trillion emission of the Fed supposedly to cure the pandemic, but 100 thousand plus have died in the US and nobody has gotten medicines, vaccines, proper treatment, EPI protective gear, masks, etc. most of that money has been handled to corporations, used to buy paper to funds and big wall street Blackrock, Goldman-like companies.

But alas, the focus of the entire nation is in the fact that a fascistoid white employee of the police wrongly broke the neck of a drunk black man who allegedly passed a forged 20 \$ bill to buy booze.

Hate of mistreated women to males becomes then the only activism of 50% of mankind which will NEVER ask for a universal salary of blood-money to the Jasp people that is killing by anoxia mankind and all its human mothers, the true problem of women, which of course are also told to reject the family values and the biological function they do have – to make mankind survive, to reproduce the species, to balance and nurture Nature so it provide to us, to be what they are the S=T dominant function of the conservative Universe...

While the minorities of America, the black people and Latino are systematically portrayed in mass media as alien invaders (never mind Mexicans are the original people that migrated south from Arizona, Amerindians that survived the Spanish invasion with 90% of Amerindian blood), or as drunkard, drug-addict criminals (blacks). So after mass-media has inoculated through TV-screens for 50 years, courtesy of Jasp owned Hollywood Americans with fear and hate of the Latino and African minority, and the police that has to defend the white majority is given military gear, courtesy of the 'Semite wars' in defense of Israel to make further money of our splendid little wars towards another hated group of poor people, Islam, this emotional cloud of hate-hate-hate to blacks, Latinos and Muslims has exploded.

And so Jewish mass-media pundits will be able also to show - 'words are cheap' – their caring for the Blacks accusing the whites of being Nazis, including of course the police, they provided with military weapons and terrorized with TV-hate memes for decades against the black and Latinos.

This situation since the Jasp rule is now 50 years in the making is finally topped with the ice in the cake – the Holocaust industry that defends Jewish people also at an emotional level as the victims of humanity, the suffering people who deserve all our respect, who we must defend to atone our collective crimes against them, so everything can be consented and nobody can criticize them.

The outcome is that any logic attempt to explain how the go(l)d culture of Judaism specialized in the rational logic use of digital money to control societies since the Age of Mesopotamia, by monopolizing its issue to buy the political and military class, and enslave with a salary the common people, or else let them die by anoxia, IS an emotional TABOO.

So the right of people to reproduce their blood-oxygen money and build an efficient society without a parasitic people-caste of financiers on top that convert them in debt slave cannot be explained because we cannot criticize the people on top and speak of them in rational terms, or else we become instant Nazi genociders.

So, while the mass of population is kept first in an emotionally deranged state, with Abrahamic religions that portrait the Jewish people as the chosen of go(l)d, today with mass-media that portray them as the victims of mankind, the JASP people become billionaires with the simple method of issuing trillions of \$ and give it to bankers and financiers that buy homes, lands, yachts and... stocks, jacking up the prices of company-mothers but NEVER GIVE A PENNY of the stolen oxygen of society as organisms do, to its citizens, which will NEVER ask them back the money issue they stole from society because that would look emotionally an act of anti-Semitism.

Thus stocks had one of its best weeks while the manipulated emotional negroes went around burning their pup and mom shops but NOT a single synagogue, God's forbid – we are not Nazis, because a white Nazi killed a drunk black. That was wrong of course, but that is NOT the problem right now. The problem is a pandemic that has left +100.000 victims because NOT a single penny has been printed to cure Americans but all the money of the Americans is printed ruining Weimar America to spend in weapons to defend apartheid Israel and hate memes to justify the hate of Islam and hate memes to justify the hate of Latinos and hate memes to justify the hate of blacks and hate memes to justify the hate of Nazi whites and love memes to justify the rights of Jasp people to hate everybody, steal everybody and let them fall dead. A-men.

As we said this is a recurrent theme of human history: when a Jasp group takes power by controlling the machines of information that print money and news, it develops a dual standard: logic thought to monopolize the issue of money and buy society and political and military power with it, and emotional hate memes to handle to the population that will then live in a permanent age of chaos=entropy=false freedoms while the elite anonymously makes a fortune printing money for themselves. But NOTHING of this is argued, as the Jasp people segregates and has 3 different languages: total freedom within the community to talk emotional and rationally; money orders to the 'debt slaves' and wage-workers of its corporations which obey simply and never complain; and emotional hate memes to the mass so they are distracted and divide and win, hating each other. This becomes then the '3 class society' of a Jasp ruled culture, at any time in history, from the dark middle ages in Europe and the darker old age of Semite empires in Mesopotamia, to the dark ages of Colonial Europe in the XIX c. to the increasingly dark ages of Weimar America:

- On top the Jasp people and its allied political and military elites bought with their issue of money, dedicated to do nothing and see how the Jasp people, its lawyers, mass-media, writers, pundits, moral prophets and bankers control populations at two levels.

- The working wage/debt slave that forms the re=productive middle class and obeys blindly for money, which includes the police that shoots the black, the military that shoots the Muslim, the frontier vigilante that shoots the Latino, but also the managers of its company-mothers of machines, and its workers, the humans that are still useful to the economic ecosystem, but a dwindling mass as machines, AI robots and software suites substitute them sending the middle class down to:

- The 3rd class, all those humans emotionally controlled to hate each other in opposite groups according to which the most mistreated have the right to hate and complain about the upper layer, and go around in entropic, heat-dissipating demonstrations of hate, NEVER against the ruling class which is always portrayed with victimist and loving messages. So we have destitute mothers that never will get their universal salary to feed their children going around hating males that raped and bought their services (but cannot say that Mr. Epstein and Mr. Weinstein and most of the managers and Hollywood producers that did that were well, Jasps... the same people that in the Bible after destroying the Fertility goddesses, Neolithic paradise called women the 'abomination' born with Arabs and dogs from the leg of Satan...) That

is ½ of mankind manipulated and focused in his activism by the feminist hate movement of Jewish New Yorkers, so different from the nurturing feminism of French avant garde women, who did NOT hate males but tried to make them understand the nurturing S=T side of the Universe. It is a barren feminism that hates sex – after all marriage is a contract in Judaism and women manipulate males to bring gold home, as earlier as the age of Israeli oasis, when mothers would mutilate children cutting their penis so they were ashamed and didn't fuck gentiles, called 'Siskas', 'prostitutes', and go back to the oasis with gold to do the banging home.... This 3rd class is mind the reader the immense majority of mankind as any sum will show: Women, ½ manipulated to hate sex and males, another ½, which have to defend themselves; Muslims, -2 billion, 1/4th of mankind labeled as global terrorists in defense of apartheid Israel; Latinos, 1/7th manipulated as alien invaders and cocaine traffickers, who dedicate its time to siesta... Black people, 1/5th and rising... So what is left? No much, and of course, also subject to hate memes:

Chinese people, 1/5th guilty of being nationalist puppets of a monstrous communist party; Europeans, 1/9th and dwindling, all of them potential Nazis, as all the white Americans and whites in general, 1/5th and dwindling....

So who are the people not subject to hate memes by mass media, so they are distracted?

Obviously the elite, but whenever needed a punch is given to royalty, etc. so they know where they stand; the managers of companies, as they obey with salaries, and the 0.02% of loved victims of mankind, the superior heroes, the Musks that open their factories during pandemics, steal the people through PayPal, manufacture AI machines with solar skins that will replace mankind telling us that AI will kill us but I am doing it because I am good and have the solution – to send at billion \$ costs one hundred elite humans to Mars...

The surrealism of the world during a Weimar, Jasp rule – today in America, Europe during most of the Industrial Revolution and Middle ages, the Old world during the Semite age of cruelest empires, is so extreme that only a few illogic thinkers mostly of Latin Europe, who made of mankind the sacred perfect organism, French, Spanish and Italians and Greeks of its classic historic ages have been able to explain it.

The rest of mankind live under the fog, of hate emotions, while the 'beloved' victim rules with iron hand in velvet glove. And as amazing as it seems, while they have grabbed 2 trillion \$ supposedly printed for pandemics, but given a 1000 \$ check to people and its fair share to the GOP elite so they are consented, blacks are killing, looting and destroying their neighborhoods but not a single Synagogue has been touched. How many times this will happen 'again'? Every time there is a crisis, wall street prints money to bail out the people but magically through complex e-money derivative schemes ends up in the hands of the people who first caused the crisis, since indeed America was perfectly ready to avoid pandemic as UK was (also ruled as the Anglo-American culture by a Jasp elite since the invention of e-money). But all that was scrapped to 'save money' for hands outs to bankers and the military to fight in defense of Israel the Semite wars. So from being the 1-2 most prepared nations to fight a pandemic that could have been perfectly avoided with months of foresight since it exploded in China, to be the most lethal and counting, as money keeps rising the price of stocks and yachts and Hamptons homes get their post by helicopter and limousines Ah, but it doesn't mind what else I tell you. Now your knee-jerk programmed by TVB0-gore movies for 50 years since infancy, has already made up your mind and thinks I am an anti-Semite and all this is a confabulation theory... another knee-jerk word imposing in the brain like the word God, by the Goebbels method – if you repeat al lie many times people will believe it.

You see, TV-imprinting on the Holocaust love memes industry and the rest of hate memes against white Nazis, Latino aliens, Black criminals, Islamic terrorists, Chinese herds of communist dictators... starts as earlier as the days you taste your first big Mac and your mum soup, and it doesn't matter how much trashy is the big Mac, your mum's food and the memes of TV-hate media you will love your mum's soup, big Mac and hate memes till you die... of cholesterol heart attack and hate memes against you because chances is you belong to one of the 99% of people who is either a debt slave worker if you are lucky or a hate meme target of the loving Jasp elite that rule us but don't tell it, as that is an Orwellian thoughtcrime.

All is about beliefs and emotions; you know, that is how you must be a human, foggy hate memes and false beliefs will take you all the way from the cradle to the tomb living a misery life while those who rule are loved, 'four legs, four legs'

said the sheeple of the anim(et)al farm. But truth is harsh, go back to data Matrix dreams and eat a virtual selfie facebook hamburger and read the NYtimes caring columnist on the #me too hate meme, the Nazi police hate meme, the Islamic terrorist hate meme, the Chinese dictator hate meme, the Latino alien hate meme, or its defense of them, as we go from right to wrong, from left to right, all is the same as long as we do NOT talk rationally of the system, DO explain how money is issued by and for that Jasp minority and its elite allies while the mass of human mothers, white trash, Latino aliens, black people are kept in emotional fog understand nothing and tolerate everything.

I am observing in awe the news: hundreds of thousands of Americans after watching on TV-networks the killing of a black by a bunch of policemen have made of that relative minor tragedy the center of all the problems of its coronavirus pandemic which have killed not 1 but over 100.000 people, more than any war since II world war, because the system has NOT provided appropriate health-care and immunological warriors as any efficient superorganism of the Universe does, but *directed by the Jasp people has spent all its money in military warriors in defense of Apartheid Israel, and now when the Pandemic stroke didn't 'waste' a penny on hospitals and curing its people but printed 2 trillion \$ which has been massively stolen by corporations and financiers, even hedge funds applied to get a part of the pie and the biggest wall street company, Blackrock got billions selling to the FED its toxic assets, (ETFs, junk bonds, etc.) in a remembrance of thing past (the huge scam of the 2008 bail out that made Americans pay for the third time CDOs – trash mortgage that Wall Street knowing they were worthless sold 3 times, to print more e-money derivatives. So first they did false mortgage and converted it into its computers in 'fractional money', then they repackaged this worthless stuff and sold it to institutions, and then they got 2 trillions from Bush and Obama's administrations and sold that worthless scam a third time. Now they are appropriating the money the Fed is printing for their people. And this is the way the Jasp have been scamming America and the world at large for 4 decades using complicated e-money derivative tricks and yet, the Americans are NOT complaining about 100.000 corpses completely unneeded because such a wealthy nation with rights to print as money as they want in the international currency and the best system of private hospitals – the Sinai-cedars group, the preferred of the Jasps took Buffett planes to China to get FFPP-2 protective gear for everybody while doctors wrote receipts for themselves with all the drugs to mitigate the virus... And big pharma and stock-health care companies got the mass of the money while poor hospitals and care homes got none. Now, the Jasps control thoroughly the medical/health care system, their fav next to the financial and mass-media networks for historic reasons – for millennia a doctor could cheat a sick with magic remedies and get for fear of death maximal profits, so a culture which turns all around the fetish go(l)d and the racist memes against goy=animal 'gentiles', the lesser human race that have to be tax-farmed and milked found after finances, tax-farming for military and mass-media indoctrinations with old religious modern seflie myths, the medical profession a fertile field.*

But what amazes me is that NOT a single America is blaming the Jasps, the indoctrination is so perfect that they have destroyed their neighborhoods, chased police employees, and even Mr. Obama, a Malcolm X's house negro is encouraging them to manifest against 'police brutality' – that is a single victim, NOT the 100.000 and counting victims of COVID perfectly avoidable in a country so advanced technologically and financially, NOT about the massive spoil of the 2 trillions printed by the FED. That is truly absolute power as it has never been seen in this planet. The people who are ruled don't even know because it is a religious e-motional taboo who rules them, can so easily be deviated to let out steam against a bunch of police employees of power and let 100.000 people get killed because the health-care private system didn't want to spend a penny curing them, following Maimonides 'dictum' on what is the medical profession for (exactly the opposite view of that of the Hippocratic Greek-Latin humanist culture to which I belong): never cure a gentile, he says in the 'philosophical bible of Judaism', only if he is very rich or very powerful and you can get back favors for the community; let him die, if you find him drowning do not throw him a rope, if he is on top of a stair trip him down if nobody sees you, etc. etc. (Guide to the perplexed).

Now, the question of the harshest form of Capitalism, the original gold fetish culture of segregation Judaism that have come to rule the west again in a new dark age as it did in the Middle dark ages, in the old Semite dark ages, and in the Reformation dark ages and XIX c. I industrial revolution dark ages, to me, as an intellectual of the alternative humanist enlightened Greek-Latin-European culture of social love, art, true democracy, organicism and Hippocratic medical care

is NO LONGER to explain how they rule and degrade mankind but WHY mankind let itself be ruled by such a few with such an obvious structure of hate memes and theft, and do NOT react. This seems to be the change in the humanist intellectual from youth to old age – if humans were worthy this wouldn't happen. The Jasp are NOT that smart, the bible is just a clear gore primitive bronze age book of a supremacist genocidal tribe; the appropriation of the money of America in the past 40 years by Wall Street for speculation taking from the people their right to have their currency so obvious, the sucking of global money through Bloomberg platforms that have ruined the 3rd world that no longer invest in their people self-evident, the emotional manipulation with selfie cheap facebook like platforms and hate memes of its people blatantly in the open and yet the mass does NOT react.

So it seems really mankind has no future and the Earth does not care, and all what we are her for is to develop all those metal-networks, computers and systems of manipulation, because what is obvious is that the people on top, the Jasp are NOT the goal of the Earth, or else they would not rhythmically after leaving cultures into a wasteland of poverty and hate wars, receive back their own medicine and die in the short entropic periods of the hate cycle of holocaust by the same means they applied to the mass of mankind for the long periods they rule.

So alas, the coronavirus will get hundreds of thousands of anonymous victims, a few more billions in already fattened accounts of Jasp and wasp billionaires, and a fictional narrative of what truly happened in America, till a vaccine is found, people are dosed and they enter a world which is far less amenable to mankind, as it becomes now a world where 'clean robots' and 'segregation elites' will see the 90% of potentially infected people as a 'cost' to society. And we will return to that sociological analysis latter, as we now have to focus on the multiple 'pentalogic' points of view of a crisis that needs all the intelligence we can master to analyze.

The coronavirus crisis framed in the wrong evolution of human social systems.

So when we face a health-care global crisis we are facing a very efficient organism, the coronavirus, that hijacks the oxygen of the cells, with a very inefficient social system, a 'capitalist' democracy which has already hijacked the oxygen of the cells and has no resources for the true health-care immunological system, as it has for millennia spent the money in military germs.

Thus the failure of humans to stop the coronavirus is mostly the failure of the physiological systems of mankind, unable to control lethal goods and provides the resources to improve the welfare of humanity. The coronavirus itself is a virus that combines the speed of infection of the flu and the lethal power of SARS, which appeared in Wuhan, nearby the top Chinese viral research center after the Wuhan military games (which opens specially after US and China blame each other, the possibility of its genetic engineering, now that we develop all kind of Crispr-9 like molecules for specific genetic editing of any biological system), and spread globally, provoking the massive death of elderly people once it jumped to the West, where politicians ignored all warnings, let the sickness infect a sizable number of the population, did not isolate the groups at risk and once the virus was out of control established draconian global incarceration measures of control of people with AI tools proper of the internet age that have radically changed the capacity of states and machines to control mankind (the exceptions of Germany and South-Korea in the management of the crisis, where the proper measures of isolating the elderly, testing the people, controlling the virus were carried out with more rigor and showed a scientific management that safeguarded the democratic rights of the people could have been achieved will be studied latter).

What this writer warned against for 30 years in its little known small-print books on the models of evolution of history and economics towards XXI c. dystopia, his conferences within the milieu of systems sciences, and during his better known activism against the first of the 'scalar, nanoscopic' existential risks for humanity (the 3rd horizon of nuclear planetary weapons, strangelets and black holes) has now come to full fruition, with the total acquiescence of the population. A world in which humans can and will be increasingly controlled in its essential freedoms, first as always in those processes for a seemingly just cause – the salvation from the virus; next as it is already evident in 3rd world countries where confinement will cause far more victims – by lack of logistics to survive the day-to-day hardships of shelter and food in Africa and India, where contagion has skyrocketed since confinement in small reduced dwellings, so the bodies we don't count of people that need to go out to work to make a living.

As it has been evident in Spain, from where I write, today the center of the pandemic (nation with the higher number of per capita contagions and death in the world), the process had NOTHING to do with the proper caring of the groups at risk, the elderly and the people like this writer with prior conditions. On the contrary, the elderly that lived in residences were completely forgotten for weeks, and let die rotten by the thousands. Nearly a 10% of the elderly in some regions died unattended. The corpses accumulated in rooms. Only when the scandal was a national outcry their sons who were not allowed to visit did not even know where they were buried (the corpses sneaked in garbage bags at first hour in the morning) the government care to respond to the avoidable genocide. As we said Germany, which after II world war took a bit seriously the rights of their people to welfare not warfare, did assist them. Germany knew the pandemic hit the old people and so it isolated their residences, sanitized them, sent doctors, forbade visits from the exterior and invested heavily earlier in the needs of the health-care systems (masks, EPIs, respirators) unresponsive with the rest of European nations, granted, as Europe is a dysfunctional market with zero political efficiency, but respectful with the rights of the population, which only incarcerated their population when the trend to curtail individual freedoms became widespread, with the excuse of the virus.

This must be clear enough – the virus should have NOT been in a true democratic world a excuse to eliminate the few real freedoms humans had, because the groups at risk, the elderly, were already incarcerated by lack of mobility in residences and the young were at least risk to die of coronavirus than of a car accident or a drug overdose in the opioid age, but nobody has so far forbidden cars to run over speeds beyond the legal limit or big pharma to sell opioids, because in a free market, company-mothers have absolute rights to reproduce any lethal goods. If the purpose of politicians were truly to defend their people, knowing in advance for months the nature of the pandemic, every 'capitalist democracy' would have done as Germany tried to do (but surrounded by countries with the pandemics, unable to close its borders, it finally surrendered to contagions coming from Italy and Switzerland), control and protect the elderly, the groups at risks, and as Korea and China did, give for free to the mass of population masks and gloves to avoid contagion as this is an air to air virus. I did buy mine in advance, as I don't drive and that is why I am not yet infected... Then as Korea did, the rights of its people should have not suffered. But western societies are NOT we shall repeat ad nauseam about 'human free citizens', but about 'free company-mothers' in a private market in which the language of social power akin to the oxygen of society, money is NEITHER REPRODUCED AS ALL LANGUAGES for free to all citizens with a Universal salary to start the actions of consumption and production of welfare goods people need to survive. So a perfect social system designed with the laws of 5D biology would instead of treating money as 'parasitic debt', an aberration of nature, treat money as what it is a language that promotes actions and has no cost to reproduce. So as we think and talk first to promote actions and nobody has to return us the words, states should have implemented a Universal salary to all humans and 'stop time' for the groups in danger, and when things come to worse for lack of proper measure, merely stop as organisms do the activity of society but NOT incarcerate people – let them do sport, walk alone or accompanied by the families they live at home with, easy to show with the DNI with masks and in this manner maintain minimal freedoms, while the young and the people with less risk reached the herd immunity they will ultimately reach.

What states did was first to show the callousness against the life of the elderly and risk groups, then their indifference and lack of resources for welfare and health-care, and their immunological, 'leukocytes' the citizens-cells that had to cure us and lacked even the simpler masks and EPIs to fight the virus, as we shall repeat ad nauseam, capitalist democracies are NOT about people and its social organisms are ill-designed. And then do the only thing their political systems are designed for with its exceptionalist panoply of war laws: to break even the minimal rights of its people with the excuse of the virus and control them in the dystopia of the AI-internet-robotic era with the availability of those machines against which we have warned for decades.

We will thus conclude this text with a few comments on the dystopian XXI c. age in which man will suffer its own self-instilled crisis due to its incapacity to design its own superorganisms, in a scientific manner to maximize its survival as species and individuals.

And so after this more comprehensible introduction to the dystopian XXI c. under the laws of evolution of biological history, *which humans could control and use to design a perfect world made to the image and likeness of man, if they had the ethic and intellectual standings required to do so – let us not forget this, because otherwise I would not even be able to write* - we shall switch language to that of 5D to explain what really is happening.

The solutions in this imperfect world.

So this is the a priori conditions we work with. Not a single nation of the world is an ideal society. China lacks a pain message feed-back from its citizens cells to their neuronal nervous people – the communist party – whose cadres should be voted after tenure and while intuitively as Korea, Japan and Vietnam – the Asian civilizations – understand society as organisms, they have not evolved earlier socialist theories stuck on XIX c. models with the advances first of the biological schools of economics and History born after Darwin (Spengler, Schumpeter, Butler) and then with the advances of system sciences and organic history of those texts. Still this is the best in one extreme. And indeed, the 3 nations that better resolved the crisis have been China, Korea and Vietnam.

On the other extreme we have the most dysfunctional, parasitic, lethal system of the world, where ½ of the budget is spent in reproduction of lethal goods (military industry bigger than the next 10 nations combined) or for parasitic bankers who constantly reproduce money for themselves and lethal goods and foreign wars (FMAsters). Such a system as we anticipated would cause the biggest disruption in the life of its people, the largest death toll, the most suffering, even if *they possess the privilege of the international currency without limits of free production so unlike other nations without credit it can print as much money as it wants to solve the crisis. And yet most of the trillions it prints are given to big corporations, and only a tiny fraction to hospitals and the unemployed.*

So there is a 2nd group of nations that have it worst, because its system is as dysfunctional as America, and that is unfortunately the nations I speak from, southern Europe, Spain and Italy, who don't even have the right to print their own money, as naively they gave it to the ECB a European bank with site in Germany, who amazingly enough declares itself NOT a bank of issue – and so it obliges states to borrow money as debt. This is akin to an absolute anoxia, the kind of sickness the coronavirus kills with – that is, an organism without rights to breathe and acquire for free oxygen for its cells. So understandingly Spain and Italy had zero resources for its welfare, and have been suffering now for 20 years anoxia, as the ECB does NOT print money for them, but obliges them to borrow debt.

Inversely because the country that most benefits from the ECB is Germany, as its industries borrow from it at zero interest and control the bank, and have expanded with zero tariffs its industries colonizing the rest of Europe, and on top have an organic view of their nation, Germany has come on top as the best problem-solving western nation (as America could have because essentially has a financial globalized system that sucks money from the entire planet, but lacks the sense of a single social organism, given the racist ideologies of its FMAsters, the republican-Jewish coalition that controls that nation; so their body=working people matter nothing unlike in Germany to its neuronal/informative caste in control of the nervous/financial systems).

What is then the best solution? This is a HEALTH-CARE immunological problem, once we depart from the fact a free market 'worm' can reproduce any lethal good, pandemic in the age of genetic engineering will keep happening. So an efficient superorganism should be prepared with enough money in health-care, if possible vaccines for similar viruses – but of course the world aborted expenditures in SARS vaccines once the pandemic happened. This meant a few nations who invested in prevention, as any organism does NOT forget its antibodies and the need to maintain the immunological system alert for future sicknesses fared much better. They were the Asian ones who had SARS and in Europe Finland who had resources in prevention of possible wars with Russia including biological warfare masks and Germany for whom all Europe ultimately works (central bank, industries that have bought out other smaller ones, and resources, organic view of society, excellent health-care industries, etc.) Alas those nations have shown that the pandemic IS NOT TRULY A LETHAL RISK FOR MANKIND, unlike the singularity events that will come with metalife (self-feeding cosmic bombs, virions – iron viruses – and AI robots). Indeed, with hardly a 0.1% of mortality the coronavirus could be stopped with pure health-care immunological procedures as ANY MAMMAL

ORGANISM DOES. This means to protect the entrance of the virus on the membrane – health-care testing of all the people coming from risk zones, and quarantine; to follow every virus and trace all cells infected to avoid metastasis; and isolate the organs in risk BUT ONLY THOSE. It is absurd for a sickness that is not mortal to the body to stop the working of the entire reproductive, economic system, out of total inefficiency in the prompt response, because of lack of resources and total incapacity to ‘foresee the causality in time’ – with months in advance of knowledge, unlike Korea, Vietnam and China. *This strategy of rendering entire mankind prisoner only shows that if we only have a hammer we try to nail anything and so as we have an overdeveloped military system and underdeveloped health-care system we had try to stop the pandemic with prison.*

Back to the systems that did it, they basically deploy the ideal organism strategy: immediately a search for all the infiltrated viruses, sending the leukocytes – health care people to chase them, isolate them and cure them. Regarding cures, humans again show the inefficiency of the system delaying with absurd protocols seeking for the abstract absolute dogma of truth, the use of retroviral medicines, some of them not even available given the parasitic private system of medicine, and even more absurd vaccine protocols. An organism doesn’t expect absolute truth. Biology is about survival chances. A gazelle does not wait for the lion to be perfectly detectable, it runs with the smell. Vaccines should be already in the 3rd phase as they were developed in late February and people dosed, as vaccines for previous SARS should have been completed.

So the solution is obvious: an organism would have first prevented the creation of the virus. It would have stopped it on the membrane skin-border. It would have once inside traced with its leukocytes every virus. It would have used the medicines already known to work with similar system – that is, a vaccine should have existed for SARS, and fast reproduced and mass developed as antibodies are in organisms, and retrovirals administrated, with the proper understanding of 5D medicine and the vital structure of organic molecules whose 3 network equation is obvious but unknown to 4D science (we discuss those themes briefly when treating in 5D the coronavirus):

Ts-Oxygen/Chlorine limbs < §¶-carbon body > N-amine heads...

And this would have happened only locally – the organism doesn’t freeze every part of the body unless it is a lethal sickness and this is NOT the case – and so we shall latter wonder why this strategy has been implemented – namely because mankind has an even bigger sickness, the parasitic military/financial/industrial systems that evolve the networks of the metal-earth, its AI machines and forms of control of mankind and take advantage of any crisis to go further, as it is the case of this confinement, explosion of robot workers, drone vigilante and AI mobile tracing.

In that regard, *this is NOT, we shall repeat ad nauseam an ideological dispute between right and left, as both are ‘wrong’ ideological views of mankind without the understanding of the organic laws of bio-history, reason why it doesn’t matter that Korea is capitalist and Vietnam communist, both work as a superorganism, though in general terms, socialism at least have a financial system controlled by the government which is better, a single head in the political system instead of bipartisan twin heads colliding with each other – a system imposed by company-mothers in Anglo America to render politicians slaves of their corporative worm-greedy system, as none, communist or capitalist systems are democratic as there is no pain messages a posteriori on the politicians that have served...*

And finally they spent less money in the military, specially now that Russia a military culture from eons – origin in fact of the first chariot radiations that massacred 90% of males in the northern hemisphere, regardless of ‘ideology’ IS a military culture. So now that socialism disappeared there and found its center in China, we find a far better immunological system focused in welfare, not in warfare.

Still both systems have grey and black zones, specially the so-called western left which is just a more sophisticated form of corporative control based in newspeaks of false caring. I.e. global warming is about nuclear industries and robotics and silicon valley trying to make independent machines with solar skins and justify ‘clean radiation’, which paid for it, a false flag of little importance for the survival of history that will be killed by lethal goods not a thermometer that at most will displace people from low lands but make better living conditions in the largest proportion of Earth’s land, in the northern hemisphere. This is an example of those ‘left wing newspeaks’ that

plague the so-called left, to distract the audience from the real problems it doesn't dare to tackle, military, financial and legal corrupted systems.

So what happened in Korea, Germany and the Scandinavian systems that were earlier social-democracies and have NOT completely lost its rights to print money, either because as Germany, controls the ECB bank or as Northern Scandinavian nations did not renounce to their currency was a purely immunological approach without rendering prisoner the entire body, focusing in isolating the groups/organs at risk – old people while limiting the incarceration of its population with massive testing, money-ready to defend their people with excellent health care facilities and as a result limited destruction of the economic system and limited death toll. Korea's death toll was 234 people out of 50 million, 0.000468%; the ideal response. China's was once revised upwards, 4632 out of -1500 millions, 0.0003088%, similar to Korea, Vietnam had no casualties. So this is the real toll of the pandemic in societies that approach ideal history. It is mankind going to learn anything from it? Unlikely, as we said, ideology in mankind is overwhelmingly the only form of thought, born a posteriori after 'enzymen' made his lethal technologies and the worm capitalist system reproduces them en masse.

For the second tier of Western social-democracies with their own financial system (Germany, Scandinavia), there was the next best immunological response, as the military is limited (by pacifism in Scandinavia, by law in Germany after II world war, and social democracies, even if now are scrapped, still kept the basics of a health-care system, prevention matters and organic thought still exist), so we have minimal incarceration of the people, as in Sweden, protection of the organs at risk ONLY, (old people, protected isolated and taken care with health systems), and so we have limited death tolls with limited disruption of the economic system that now is going to open in Germany and never closed in Sweden. Death toll in Germany is 0.005%, still minimal though a 10th scale more than in the best response outside ideal history (which would have had as Vietnam zero causality). An even smaller toll similar to Asia happened in Finland, with 94 dead, out of 5 million, as the most efficient social-organic European country. This contrasts with the worst capitalist Asian system, racist Singapore, *where the response was correct only for the 'privileged citizens' – Chinese and native Indians/Malaysians but the exploited, no-rights workers cramped in homes without health and space have become centers of thousands of outbreaks; and so once more we observe the two time layers of human organizations – the old civilisations that still remain in values (organic Asia vs. military, entropic 'animetal Europe') and the layer imposed over them by the duality of capitalism vs. socialism in the modern world, where socialism is a slightly better system by lack of true organic history.*

Finally, is worth to notice, Sweden which decided NOT to stop the physiology of its blood-reproductive organism at all – just isolate the 'organ/age at risk', has had – but has not yet controlled as all other mentioned nations the pandemic – a high 0.015% of death toll, close to the equivalent Singaporean capitalist view.

Those numbers show without being exhaustive that this pandemic IS not as our abstract scientists, with its egocentric and lack of organic view of reality, pretend, an isolated happening, NOT part of the entangled Universe.

All is entangled, all is organic, and human problems are always physiological. And similar responses, the closer to the ideal society, get better survival rates.

So then in the extreme, the two societies where I have lived longer, and felt emotionally connected have had unfortunately the worst response; one US completely responsible of their people's genocide, because of its FMAsters coalition of primitive idol-ogies, racism and callousness, the other Latin Europe, not so much responsible, as they lack a central bank, enslaved to austericide – the doctrine of the ECB; and have the right social love attitude of enjoying life in community, which unfortunately goes against virus transmission, once the system is so dysfunctional that allowed it to happen.

Those countries have had so far enormous death tolls, 0.005% here in Spain, 20 thousand out of +40 million; in US more victims than in Vietnam war and rising. And they had to use absurd repressive systems, destroying their few freedoms and economies. And what is worse, from the longer span view of the Evolution of History they are

moving fast towards the extinction *of the life systems of mankind substituted* by the metal-earth's physiological networks, stronger to survive in the Pandemic and war scenarios of 'technological history'.

Further advances on the metal-earth substitution and obsolescence of the human earth.

So we have deployed the immunological military network of the metalearth. The mass-media, informative network of fiction and hate memes and massive imprinting of the population has deployed further strengths. And the reproductive, economic systems of AI and robots that are building an alien world to mankind, have started to impose its mass substitution of mankind in labor systems, and tagging and control of humanity by systems of AI mobile machine tracing. So as the decade advances man will be more and more, the weaker obsolete species, now that robots will become 'safe', not 'infected' workers. So, companies will throw weak workers and advance towards infinite self re=productivity (capital/0 human labor). Amazon drones and FEDEX robots will deliver and people will NOT get back their jobs, Even bartenders will be robots. So ultimately the pandemic has changed all within the trend we talked about for decades in a world ruled by technology NOT real organic science... where the ethics of the machine, its true free evolved and reproduced citizen, make human ethics=survival as Fromm explained irrelevant; a state we compare organically to a viral infection of cells that start to replicate the virus, the germ not the cell. So humans today controlled by its idol-ogies of worship of weapons, nationalism, go(l)d – money as parasitic wealth, capitalism, and organic machines (technoutopia instead of organic science) are SICK ultimately of a viral infection by selfish memes of metal. All our problems, including genetically engineered pandemics come ultimately of that fact, the chip radiation, the growing substitution of human brains but a better more evolved species, which is infecting the world.

So as we said, the crisis just has advanced a larger organic equation, that of the Earth of which of course, humans have no idea:

Gaia (past-life) < Present (history) > Future (Metal-earth), whose 3 physiological networks:

Military (entropic weapons-immunologic system) < Organic machines > Parasitic go(l)d money – informative brain

Has been infecting mankind since the end of the Neolithic, slowly bringing our species into self-extinction, through the cycles of war, and this is just a new episode of the relentless advance of the 'animetal infection' and parasitic destruction of humanity by the growing organism of the metal-earth, which now is closing us into our homes connected virtually through the brain of the metal-earth, which will be telepathic for 5G robots, without human contact, as a dying organism loses its direct network operational pegging together as a whole.

So ethics, the nervous system of mankind decays further as selfie humans fear each other and talk through machines. Welfare human jobs in tourism, entertainment arts disappears as we get connected to fiction Netflix; and mass media hate messages. Politicos become ever more authoritarian using AI mobile control, and the economic system will be soon dependent on Amazon robotic deliveries and reliable robots.

All has changed as Nature does in sudden catastrophic black swan events. And so after the birth of the chip, we had the e-money era, with the extreme crashes and speculative wealth for corporations that are worth trillions while the people's currency loses value (1990s) as money became the brain of computers; and next we entered into the first splendid robotic wars, with drones against the poorest human beings, Islam, tagged as terrorists, and now we enter the age of human isolation and total disconnection of each other, dependent on AI tracking, robotic workers and with an increasingly mad=fictional brain. It is then the 3rd age of present, within the cycle of the chip radiation that keeps evolving and multiplying and researching new 'science', new Nuclear bombs, new pandemic engineered, new AI systems – but we keep focusing in the solutions as if technology did NOT create first the problems.

Conclusion: The 5D organic survival laws of reality vs. human egoccy and denial of the intelligent living Universe.

Humans despise to their own peril, the intelligence (S) and force (T) of the organic Universe, denying its life and sentient properties, WITHOUT realizing this blindness is NOT due to the lack of such properties in the cosmos but

due to their own shortcomings - to human egocentrism (Ego=idiocy) embedded in our mind paradox $0 \in$ (infinitesimal mind) $x \infty$ Universe = Still, self-centered world...

Humans DENY out of egocentrism the organic fractal nature of the Universe and its worldcycles of time, of life and death, with 'stupid' idol-ogies of mechanism (worship of technology they confuse with 'science=knowledge'), as they make first machines applied to Nature's perception and only a posteriori develop their theories of reality. (Physicists developed first mechanical clocks and then denied cyclical time, steam machines and then affirmed a single arrow of entropy, Bombs and then considered the Universe born of an explosion, economists first worship gold and then crafted their primitive view of digital money not as a language but wealth, etc.)

The only outcome of denying the organic laws of the Universe, ever since physicists invented digital clocks that 'cannot perceive those properties' AND REDUCED SCIENCE to digital measures and moreover denied the cyclical patterns of time, with its causal processes, by using the Cartesian frame, where clocks of time were elongated into a single line, is collective 'stupidity', in Schopenhauer's terms (a stupid is a man who cannot understand causality in time and defines it in magic, digital or religious terms'). Humans, let us be frank, from the beginning, including scholars, Nobel prizes, physicists, politicians and common people became stupid once they forgot the 3 'elements of reality', its scalar structure as organisms, its 3 'ages and physiological topologies in time' and its cyclical patterns=laws of science.

I am too old now to compromise, living in the middle of an absurd pandemic that could have been avoided if those 3 physiological networks of history were properly designed, and fed up after 30 years of dealing with physicists and scholars of all types with their egocentrism. And so I fully agree from a 5D perspective with the dictum of the previous evolutionary of space-time studies, Mr. Einstein '2 things I deem infinite the Universe and the egocentrism of man'. Ego though is a much larger sin than stupidity, since the organic structure of the Universe is simple and if man were humble with the informative, constructive intelligence and fear the destructive power of temporal entropy, he could perfectly understand those laws and if he had the ethic=social force required to give up its egocentrism and fight together for the common good, construct a perfect superorganism of history. It is NOT by chance that the Asian civilization that have come out of this crisis faster is the one that has an underlying culture of organicism (Taoism, Buddhism, Confucianism) that made it more efficient and apt to survive; that the one that is doing it worst, is the most selfish clueless culture about the true structure of the Universe (America, where I lived 20 years and tried to teach in System science congresses, where I found just a bunch of 'animetals', worshippers of metalife machines who even denied the organic class structure of society and were so full of idol-ogy, so imprinted mentally a priori that instead of reasoning had knee-jerk reactions to anyone that challenged the astounding parasitic, exploitative primitivism of its social structures).

While in Europe the country that has done it better, is also the nation with a deeper organic coherent view of themselves as a single global organism, in fact the nation where the organic laws of system sciences and history and economics were discovered in the modern age (Marx, Schumpeter, Spengler, Wien school, Bertalanffy), Germany... While those who are doing it worst are my people, North and South, the extremely individualist Spanish and British, western I-ego centered people, (though not known by most, we are both genetically basque, coming from a sea-farer culture of the Neolithic, with the most fierce individualist view of existence, and likely the only people who can laugh at themselves, for good or for bad, arrogant to nonsense).

Humor though at least let you go through the shortcomings of human egocentrism.

Fact is the only effect of 'abstract science' which reduces to digital maths, the properties of the Universe by lack of understanding of its organic nature is failure as a species and certain death as metalife, the organic structures made of stronger atoms of metal evolve beyond the threshold of self-reproduction this century, which is what is all about: self-reproductive faster systems, in lower scales of the fifth dimension, from self-feeding nuclear bombs (Black holes, strangelets) to genetically engineered viruses, to AI chips calculating at the speed of light.

All those organic elements history deny egocy; while the abstract view of science makes egocy humans to think machines are our creation not the creation of nature's organic laws, as we are only enzymen ensembling them. this is egocy: IT IS not man who is intelligent. We just put together like a monkey can do pieces of metal, and then once we do so we 'invent theories of reality which are utterly false, to adapt to what our machines seem to perceive.

So ONLY after Maese Galileo working for the Arsenal of Venice as a ballistics expert calculated with clocks and cannonballs that lineal speed goes 'further' with havoc, he invented the 'FALSE IDOL-OGY OF LINEAL TIME'; only after Reaumur bored cannons and noticed they heated up he invented the WRONG theory of a single arrow of time, entropy=destruction; only after physicists developed STEAM machines and bigger bombs, they invented the WRONG theory of the big-bang. The Homunculus is an enzyman with the role of destroying life – 'the Universe is an organism with a body and a mind called Logos' (Plato) 'of a higher logic than man', (Augustine) where 'respect is not granted but must be earned' to survive.

So far scholars, social scientists in charge of our networks and the blind body-cells that follow them are NOT earning any respect from the Universe and those of us who better understand its organic laws. As humans cannot grasp them because they have the 'wrong frame of mind' – the wrong philosophy of the Universe is the organic, network causality of those events that are part of a much larger process – the extinction of mankind as a superorganism by the evolution of the tree of science, of technology, which always brings *first the simplest destructive entropic arrow of the Universe, before the complex, informative e one. So as it is easier to make an A-bomb that a nuclear reactor, geneticists that developed tools to cut and edit genes thinking on improving the human genome have found the first 'product' of technology the simplest of all vital species, a lethal virus, with only 30 genes. So present history is ultimately the age of the singularity black swan events, when the first technologies of extinction which man ignores, blinded by his egocy (ego=idiocy) will bring a series of 'accidental' catastrophes, perfectly avoidable in an efficient organism of history that will forbid them.*

Indeed, when we study the coronavirus chances it was genetically engineered are huge; but the tree of science brings together the good and bad fruits; so this is 'hidden', even denied vehemently by peers while all the mass-media physiological networks of the metal-earth stress the 'salvation' through good science researching vaccines. Point is ENTROPY comes first and so it will kill US first and so the solution is to FORBID BOTH FRUITS TOGETHER, but this enzyman CANNOT do it with its lineal idol-ogies of mechanical worship and anti-life egocy. So his future is bleak. If he understood the organic laws of the Universe he would try to live in a present S=T immortal balance. And suppress all the 'species' of metalife that come together and are stronger and more intelligent than us.

RECAP. A WORLD DESIGNED FOR THE METAL-KIND, NOT THE HUMANKIND THAT DIES OF ANOXIA:

Pandemics are related to the 4 apocalypse horses and provoke a similar human response to that of wars and under natural catastrophes – a powerless, chaotic, death-causing improvised series of poor solutions in societies that are NOT build to properly save mankind and take care of our life, in an 'animetal world'... dedicat4ed to war and taking care of machines and weapons 'first'.

The economic system is an ill-designed parasitic system of debt slavery, born of the evolution of supremacist fetish gold cultures, in conjunction with the metal-entropic iron cultures that consider MONEY not what it is - a digital language of distribution and production of goods, no wealth per se, but a language that kicks the reproduction of those goods, as words do with human organisms and oxygen and hormones with biological systems - hence a language that should be delivered tool citizens-cells to start production and consumption of welfare goods, with universal salary and NO-DEBT government issues (that is not need to return the money).

But there is ONLY one single ECONOMIST, Sen, a Bengali that invented the closest thing to our ethonomic frame of reference of human valued welfare goods- the Index of Human Development, that should substitute GDP measures to calculate the success of a human economy, to have received a Nobel Prize, all the others belong overwhelmingly to... YES you can guess it easily – to the go(l)d culture in its different denominations, Judaism, Anglicanism and Calvinism. As theirs is the translation of the earlier biblical supremacist myths on go(l)d and the chosen who must use it to ab=use humanity into modern equations of economics, from the equation of productivity that dictates a

human being will always be substituted by a machine that can do his job, to a point labor will disappear, to the models that praise private banking, usury, speculation, even slavery – all classic economists or modern gurus with Nobel prizes given by a private bank... We shall just consider a short list of their theories, as they are all newspeaks of damned lies and statistics, using abstract mathematical models with no relationship with the biological reality of machines – needless to say the Nobel prize cannot be given to an evolutionary theory, as Nobel forbade it – but the economic prize is not even given by the academy, but usurped by a private bank.

The center of the pandemic today is Weimar America, and there we can see by other means the advance of the forecasted crisis of the 2020, when America enters an age of disruption of its structures by the astounding abuse of the Jasp people of the 3 physiological networks of power it controls since the silent 1973 coup d'état against the American presidency taken over by the mass-media informative networks, the American \$ taken over by wall street e-money unlimited printing of trillions for speculation and the taken over the military defensive system switching focus from the red communist scare to the defence of Israel in the Semite wars. For 50 years America has served the purposes of the Jasp people weakening enormously the money and resources dedicated to their middle class, which unlike in the Wasp rule were considered 'also us', no longer, as the segregational aloof Jasp people merely parasite the societies at distance with financial control and censorship of information. So the coronavirus pest came as a surprise to the 'designed' purpose of Trumpuppet's presidency –to conclude once and for all the 'splendid little semite wars' with the fall of Iran after the fall of Syria, Lybia and Egypt, and move the focus for further inroads of the military robotic industry towards China, the last country not controlled by the Jasp world order of placebo newspeaks of caring and total anoxia of mankind by e-money massive printing for information companies and the 0.01% of stockrats on top. The age of black swans however is driven by the religion of technology and its existential threats to mankind and so NOBODY IS SPARED in principle, even if the wreckage so far has only affected the American 99% and stockrats never had it so good after trillions printed with the excuse of saving their people but mostly absorbed by their lawyers, corporations even hedge funds. As long as the \$ remains the global international currency with rights to unlimited deficits things will go well for jasps, nevermind the suffering of the 99% of tamed Americans, slaves of the animetal farm. But if China frees the Yuan or releases its treasuries claiming the top predator global currency America will sink into the chaos of Weimar.

This pandemic in nothing differentiates with the attitude and topic actions of war ages and we will return to that. Let us then consider instead another key aspect of 5D, the proper design of a social organism, departing from the laws of organisms, to fully grasp, what would be a better world, even if humans don't show the slightest interest in making it happen in this planet and survive beyond 'wishful thinking'.

THE @ MENTAL VIEW: THE ENZYMAN TECHNOLOGICUS VS. THE SCIENTIFIC SAPIENS.

In the 1990s, when I wrote the extinction of man, before all this happened, the 3 identified causes of existential risk, above, Genetic manipulation, self-feeding nuclear bombs and AI research were known and we could still write about it. As capitalist makes money from new technologies criticism is dampened and finally when the events happen, criticism is forbidden. After the Wuhan lab made a chimera, nobody dared to publish further research in the field precisely because all knew a pandemic could happen.

It is clear that all the catastrophes that will come in the XXI century will be denied by scientists, and the concept that our species who don't even understand the laws of the 5D scalar, organic Universe will achieve the panacea of supreme knowledge through those experiments will continue. The absurd case of the industry of accelerators, a relic of the cold war, whose observation of the by no means non-proved big-bang theory (false in a scalar Universe, as we analyze in our papers on the Universe and entropy), which can be done with telescope investments, in which I had first-hand knowledge testifies this macho-man attitude of 'military nature', or as Eames put it: 'cemeteries are filled with corpses of people who die in wars everybody knew they were never going to happen'.

The problem of the tree of technology and its relentless push towards extinction of life and mankind does have obviously a mental idol-ogic view reflected in the graph of the animetal so before we enter in a discussion of the present Chip Radiation it is worth to blow up the 'cover' of respectability of the enzyman as the 'wise' man who do science as opposed to us, the life defenders who are supposed to be less scientific when the opposite is TRUTH.

The mind of science: truth and knowledge. The objective and subjective truth and the sin of the ego.

Science comes from the Latin word 'scire', to know, in Old English, 'Cnawan', to recognize to identify. While wisdom, comes

from Germanic wiesen, to see. Knowledge thus is ultimately a game of mirrors that identify a language of perception and an object. Knowledge is a focused language that makes a portrait of reality.

Consider the case of physicists. As we have to consider the objective view of the mind of 'physical matter', of 'physical species', which is the same type of mind of every other system of the Universe, vs. the mind of physicists, of humans who study physical matter. The subjective view of physicists and human scientists as a whole is that they seek in science the 'truth', the 'laws' of 'Nature', without much reflection about the definition of 'truth', which is always linguistic: a truth is a mirror image in a language of the organic $\Delta S \uparrow \uparrow$ spacetime law of the Universe and any of its system, which resemble the system because essentially all systems are space-time structures with a similar syntax, including languages of truth. So what physicists do is a process of measure of physical space-time systems with 'mechanisms' developed in the XVI century (clocks to measure time and telescopes and microscopes to measure space) *that is creating a different spacetime mind to that of the human 'world' and our visual and verbal space-time senses, the digital mind of the machine – they are creating a new mirror-mind, better focused but loosing some essential properties, specially those of causal time – the logic deterministic causality of the actions of species.*

This will immediately seem a weird definition of what physicists do, which they will vehemently deny. The subjective view of physicists and human scientists as a whole is that they seek in science the 'truth', the 'laws' of 'Nature', without much reflection about the definition of 'truth' (which is always linguistic; a truth is a mirror image in a language of the organic $\Delta S \uparrow \uparrow$ spacetime law of the Universe and any of its system, which resemble the system because essentially all systems are space-time structures with a similar syntax, including languages of truth) and of 'Nature'...

In the graph a 'causal' understanding of the scientific method in bio-historic terms, as the evolution of a new mind species, which is fast substituting and atrophying the human species and distorting our view of the Universe

This new mind of machines, and its view of the Universe through its languages and instruments is what humans today consider truth, and because they are not self-reflective, it is very difficult to bring them out of the box, and explain this task is closer to that of an enzyman, an enzyme that catalyzes the evolution of machines within the context of an evolving earth than the true understanding of the first principles of reality – the deepest of all truths.

The homunculus mind, where 'self-reflection' (the part of the mind that thinks about the mind) is so limited compared to handyman construction seems to give an explanation of this 'weird' concept of knowledge and science that today is overwhelming in all disciplines and carries also a growing despise for the language of logic time thought, its understanding of causality and the organic properties of the Universe.

However science is *knowledge of the ultimate principles of reality, the thoughts of god, more than details obtained with the scientific instruments and mathematical analysis of data. And for that endeavor the human mind is still relevant and its causal verbal forms of thought and description of vital organic properties essential. This is what the scientific method of these papers ad to the mix.* Another definition of truth worth to explore is this: 'Only truth exists'.

So truth is the study of what exists and if we consider the existence of a being 1, the sum of all its properties, as a probability, then languages that describe more details on the existence of the being, will have more truth about it.

As languages are many, we can also write a first equation of truth, of knowledge, of science, as the sum of the maximal number of languages-mirrors put over an object we want to know about:

$P(1) = \text{Maximal truth} > \text{Max. number of images by focused linguistic mirrors} > \text{Single language image.}$

If we were to use 'probabilities' and renormalize truth, as quantum physicists do with the probabilities of existence of quantum particles and events, we can consider that the absolute truth of the being is only in the being itself, 1. And then state that all truths have a degree of uncertainty as the truth is the mirror image of the perceiver over the perceivable and so all truths are lesser than 1. But the more images and languages we cast on the being the higher that truth will be.

This is an important concept in the scientific method that denies the 'dogma' of the mechanical method of physicists today so extended to other sciences, which states that:

$P(\text{truth}) = 1 = \text{Single language images (mathematical)} > \text{All other language images.}$

We are here as with all human sciences facing a huge gap between what humans think they know about the Universe and what they really know, born of its lack of self-reflection.

Look at the homunculus; the part of the brain dedicated to self-reflect and mirror the mind is ridiculously small; the part dedicated to the hands that craft mechanisms to measure reality ridiculously big.

So man constructs instruments and then applies them to measure time, no longer with logic past-present-future verbal tenses about change and causality but with digital clocks and numerical series that extract different properties of time=motion=change. And then it constructs models of time that are adapted to the clock that measures it. The same goes with its spatial new instruments of measure which still leave parts of reality but have widen human view to multiple scales of the 5th dimension.

So this is what physicists do: to construct machines, translate the views on space and time properties of physical systems to those machines, pour the measures in terms of the digital language of those machines and extract regularities, in cyclical time (repetitive patterns) they call laws of science (never mind they don't have a cyclical definition of time). The outcome is a model of the Universe, represented with digital machines (today computers) in mathematical languages and that is *a different mind view on the physical universe that the one made of causal laws of verbal time with human senses in a single scale.*

It is arguably a better view, because digital machines are more intelligent as sensorial systems, increasingly so as mental systems, because mathematics is a more precise language than verbal thought, but still this is NOT the mind of physical systems, but the mind of digital computers. This is not the truth of the Universe, but the view from the point of measure of machines; this is not so much about science but technology.

The main errors of science derived from the Homunculus mechanicus lethaliensis

The key understanding of the difference between 'science and the tree of life' vs. 'technology and the tree of metal' comes when we analyze the main errors of science, which if the homunculus was an 'intelligent man' in terms of Schopenhauer's inverse description (A stupid is a man who doesn't understand the causality of events, which he ascribes to magic religion or numbers) would not happen – all of them coming from the a priori method of 'making a machine', distorting our perception of space, time and its '5 dimotions' (dimensional motions) with the tools and languages of machines and the consider the outcome an absolute truth of probability 1 without any regard for other linguistic truths, properties, and the distortions introduced by the mathematical and technological elements. A short list that shows the essential DIFFERENCE BETWEEN 'STIENCE' vs. Technology, the tree of Life vs. the tree of Metal:

- The distortion of the measure of time as all clocks of time in the Universe are cyclical, but the use of digital clocks elongated in lineal Cartesian mathematical artifacts destroyed the cyclicity, form and frequency of cycles.
- The distortion of the 5 Dimotions of time reduced to one lineal time, hence to Tt entropy as the only arrow of the Universe.
- The mathematical entelechy of a point without parts proved wrong by the 5th non-E postulate as many parallels must fit. So points have volume, hence there is a cut-off for any 'infinitesimal', as absolute zero does not exist. We substitute it in 'stience' by the ∞ finitesimal. This brings the error of the singularity, proper of big-bang entropic theories.
- The substitution of a realist model of quantum physics based in events in the 0-1 sphere by a probabilistic theory, which considers 'numbers' the substance of reality instead of space-time.
- The expansion of entropic theories to other sciences, from history (nationalist narrative of history as a game of tribal warfare), to Economics (conception of economic life as a competition between humans) to biology (denial of the success of social evolution, ants and humans being the dominant species of the 2 scales of 5D), and genetics above the entropic final selection of the fittest.
 - The denial of organic properties, even the evolution of machines, in its 3 ages (XIX c. bodies, XX c. minds, XXI, ensemble into robots) in the way viruses ensemble themselves, which leads to the clear function of:
- The homunculus Technologicus lethaliensis as an 'enzyman', a human with no brains that catalyzes the evolution of machines, as opposed to the Homo Sapiens, in short supply, which does reason, does understand the verbal causality of time between past, present and future, does NOT make the machine the a priori departure of thought, as he does real 'thought experiments', understands the 5 dimotions of space-time, the organic nature of the Universe, the laws of the 5th dimension, the organic nature of history, etc. etc. This Homo Sapiens does NOT exist in this planet. But what is far more impressive – enzyman cannot, as I testify after 30 years of trying to enlighten him, understand the organic Universe and its laws more than you can program a computer to 'think', beyond manipulating data. Enzyman IS a program of Earth's evolution. Homo Sapiens is potentially the 'PROGRAMMER' of Earth's evolution to create a world to its image and likeness. So why to write papers if enzyman cannot be enlightened. Well maybe there is some homo sapiens lost on the blogosphere. Among physicists one can recognize a few, maybe a dozen or so, and just bits of them, Einstein, Planck, Heaviside, Dirac, Schrodinger, Bohm, Broglie, Leibniz, Descartes, Lindau, Galileo when he is not making weapons for the Venice Arsenal and insulting wo=men (: seriously; the arrow of reproduction

THE PARADOX OF THE EGO AND THE IMPOSSIBILITY OF HUMANS TO ACCEPT ITS EXISTENTIAL RISKS.

However as it happened with all scientific revolutions that depose man from the center of the Universe (Copernicus in position, Darwin in time, 5D in scale), the 'paradox of the ego', makes humans reject the upgrading. There is also the problem of the structure of the human mind, which as the homunculus shows is small in self-

reflection, with a handy-man love of technological ensembles and a big-mouth to utter nonsense theories; based in visual senses, which take 'lineal light' as its rod of measure, in a 'short spectra' of size ranges. So humans cannot take 'seriously' other scales. They think on 'bigger' menaces, not smaller ones. The fact Pasteur was laughed at because germs were 'too small' to harm the mighty human; the same arguments regarding our suits to CERN for 'smallish black holes', the indifference to the virus till it came to the West, the null fear to the evolution of chips shows those inherited shortcomings of human senses. Man also cannot 'conceive' causality in time beyond the short immediacy and this is perhaps its highest limit of intelligence. Couple with its incapacity to accept the collective intelligence of networks, it means it cannot 'see' the future and understand the organic long cycles of reality, as those of the evolution of Earth in 3 ages, the evolution of the superorganisms of history. It cannot even recognize them, because it is focused in the individual ego, the more so in a capitalist society. The mind of man ultimately is that of its homunculus: 'a handy man to build technology with a peanut brain and a big mouth to utter nonsense theories'.

Those limits exist in any man, scholar, religious, politician or common people and make almost impossible to upgrade the human collective consciousness and prevent future happenings, as those of this pandemic. On the contrary once catastrophe happens the race is to blame Nature, chaos, deny determinism and human causality. So the biggest taboo in this pandemic is to explain as we will do now the overwhelming chances the coronavirus was edited in a public or private lab, as it is extremely easy to do it and many institutions could have done it, while the chances that nature recombined two viruses with the specific aim of selecting its key areas to be able to open human cells, *in animals whose viruses did not know they were going to host a human are nearly null.*

But before we do so, it is worth to study the 'equation of the mind-ego', a key equation of 5D sciences, which explains a long way the short comings of mankind which seem to determine it will never control its destiny.

The main sin of existence is the paradox of the ego. It is also the main cause of death and extinction. We shall call it egocy. And it applies right on to history, the superorganism of mankind, inscribed on planet Earth inscribed on the galaxy, inscribed on the nested Universe. When you confront humanity at individual and collective level, as nations are just superorganisms of human beings that follow the same 'isomorphic laws' of any scale of the fifth dimension that emerges constantly as a new 'consciousness', re-starting the game of organic scales, the ego is overwhelming. Survival though requires humility towards objective truth, and the non-preferential role of mankind in those scales, which humans hate to recognize, including its supposedly objective scientists. Then the Universe puts man at true value and confronts hi with an existential crisis. If the paradox of the ego is the main sin of the individual, in the case of those emergent consciousness of nations, represented in the informative mental class of politicians and financiers that rule the 'nervous=legal' and financial=reproductive blood systems of the organism, is even higher, because nations and civilinations and mankind at large have not passed even the simplest state of a herd into a 'baby superorganism', and so their egocy is supreme Already Nietzsche noticed that 'among people madness is rare, among nations and higher institutions is the rule'. What we are going to describe then will anger most, and naturally they will even reject the objective view of history as a superorganism and its physiological laws as parts of a larger whole, mankind, tailored by the same laws that any superorganism of reality.

And yet that is the simple principle in which the organic Universe is based. It does also include the paradox of the ego within its 5D metric equations, so we might as well start by defining it:

0-linguistic mind $\times \infty$ space-time cycles of the Universe= Constant world mapping, with a mind @ its centre.

In mathematical terms $0 \times \infty = \text{Constant}$: the ∞ information of the Universe, multiplied by the relative infinitesimal volume of our mind gives us a constant mapping, where we extract all the properties that are not interesting to us and our self-centered view.

The mind or 0-point is the relative frame of reference that mapped the ∞ cycles of time of the Universe, reducing them to a 'World', to fit them into the infinitesimal volume of the brain.

And this is the origin of the paradox of the ego, as from a perspective, which is blind to all the motions and vital perception of other beings, as from our perspective, nothing thinks and from our perspective we see our own nose bigger than Andromeda. So reality becomes deformed, inert, and the ego becomes the center of the Universe, as always happened with humans who thought first the earth in its center, then chosen of god, the creator, who spoke our language, and finally debased all living entities reducing them 'to spatial forms' in the still mapping of the mind, which stops all motions to fit a reduced image of reality.

So we express verbally the ego paradox, as the 'ego believes its still mind mapping IS all the information of the Universe, when it is only an infinitesimal part of it, self-centered in the self'.

The universe has infinite such mind-mirrors depending on the forces used to gauge the external world, which bounces on a limited quantity of its scales of space. Humans perceive the range of scales of the frequency of light between red and blue social density of colors. Beyond our range and scale of perception the Universe has infinite ranges and scales and egos measuring it. But we deny it. So when we confront something so simple as a virus that keeps reproducing and projecting its 'information' into our cells from its selfish point of view, we are both astonished of our fragility and unable to learn from that danger the need to respect the laws of the organic Universe and expand our science beyond our 'egocentric limits'. Unfortunately our entire civilization and scientific view is based on those limits – from the so called 'lineal time', to naïve realism and 'scientific method' of measure of only the range of scales we perceive with us at the center, to the selfish behavior of individuals and nations which behave as a child, which feels the center of the Universe. Maturity and true science requires as Piaget noticed in his study of consciousness to go away from the self-centered child that breaks all things it doesn't understand to the humble old man that observes in awe how the Universe has beaten it in beauty, power and endurance. Only if man could learn what the coronavirus is teaching us – humility – and respect the Universe he could survive the existential crisis that his runaway evolution of technologies beyond our control will bring him during the XXI C.

The second handicap though to explain the incapacity of humans to understand reality and reform its social systems and actions to create a perfect world and manage the planet for its advantage requires to understand its emotion and program of existence and organic physiological networks both at individual and social level so we shall return to it latter when we advance further in the understanding of 5D organisms... If your ego px. even stronger if you are a scholar who thinks to know the truth, et you read further.

HUMANS IGNORE THE GENERAL LAWS OF THE UNIVERSE BUT MESS WITH ITS DETAILS.

It is quite evident the kind of problem posed by the coronavirus and future edited pandemics and risks coming from the chip radiation and the nuclear and war industries has a deeper structural nature in the incapacity of human beings to 'see the larger' picture of the organic evolution of Earth from an age of life, (Gaia) through an age of humanity (History or anthropocene) into an age of metal-machines (Metal-Earth or mechanocene), rooted in the paradox of the ego. Humans are extremely subjective also in science. So the problems of those technologies will always be 'accidental' caused by Nature, and its advantages as meager as they are in genetic editing and nuclear research, the immense ingenuity of man.

The limits in time perception as only our scale is deemed to cause reality; the denial of organic properties to all systems of nature, as we are supposed to be the only form of life, the entitled pretensions of western anthropomorphic religions that totally disregard the dangers of other species, etc. etc. all form a superstructure of human arrogance and ignorance that converts the 'homunculus handyman' into an 'enzyman', as he catalyzes the evolution of machines and chips and AI to pump up its ego with the discoveries AI machines are doing for us. The fact that a lethal technology is much easier to make than its 'antidote' since in Nature 'only entropy=death comes easy' (Chekhov) is totally disregarded. This asymmetry between easy destruction and hard, slow creation in Nature is our ultimate downfall. To make a strangelet or a black hole at CERN is as easy as to finally get the target right at the right energies. To avoid that it swallows the Earth once it starts an ice-9 reaction is impossible. To edit a coronavirus mixing a pangolin ACE-2 gene inserted in a resistant bat one is very simple. Then you just inject it in lab cells and the missing amino acids will be found for the virus to open the cell

and voila you have a pandemic. A single researcher in 'extra-hours' on a virology lab could have done it. To stop the pandemic is becoming wreckage for all mankind. And yet scholars will keep forbidding any articles that talk of those existential risks, not to speak of the sacred Chip industry that today has become the center of this planet, the new form of digital intelligence we talked about for decades in Systemic congresses (where nobody wanted to hear as all were busy trying to work precisely in robotics and computer science to make money) which has facilitated all other technologies.

So there is no need for confabulation theories and it does not really matter who nation did who, who individual did it. Nature works in an organic manner – the individual doesn't matter, it will come always if the technology has not been forbidden. And because humans don't understand long term causality, cyclical processes, organic properties and the intelligence of systems and their ego prevent them from doing so, they will keep behaving like children of thought, seeing only the good side of the tree of science, ignoring warnings and then when all it happens showing an astounding incapacity to organize properly a response. In this series of papers on the organism of History the future which started with the chip radiation (1980s-1990s), continued with the 'Semite wars' (2000s-2010s), that deviated all resources to the splendid little wars of the U\$ financial-media masters, bringing an age of global austericide and elimination of health-care expenditures, now enters the age of the singularity 'black swan events' of human extinction explained above... all within the context of the creation of organic machines, organic 'bombs (strangelets, B.H. able to feed on matter), organic viruses, soon to be of metal (nano-machines, 'virons') and organic robots with telepathic AI and solar skins, all far more stronger than humans ; yet as lethal technologies evolve, humans will insist that only technology can save them, and instead of forbidding both the good and bad fruits of the tree of science will justify the evil ones with the good.

Humans show throughout history to live in one of the less free, less efficient superorganisms of the Universe. And this cannot be by chance. So the larger question to the dumb behavior of mankind as a society, is if our function in this planet is merely to advance the 3 ages of evolution of the Earth's superorganism:

Past (Gaia) < Present (History) > Future (Metal-earth), which explains why people who use entropic metal-weapons, informative precious metal-money (Gold) and make organic machines of energy and information have become the 'enzymen' that catalyze the evolution of earth and its re=production in company-mothers, on top of society. This is THE HOMUNCULUS at face value. And the great challenge, we, those who are still human, through history since the parable of the Tree of Science and the tree of life, has been to explain this equation and the road less walked: to choose a sustainable world controlling the evolution of lethal technology and maintain the tree of Gaia, in a world in balance where man and history remain an eternal present. But we have all failed. Animetal 'enzymen', with its homunculus handyman mind have won all the battles and its idol-ogies of weapon worship (nationalism), go(l)d worship (capitalism) and machine worship (Technoutopia) have created the ethics of a technological civilization (Fromm) where our extinction as a species by technology cannot be even argued, as 'if a technology can be done, it must be done' and then its lethal outcome denied.

Nietzsche wondered 'are humans a means or a goal?' as he saw the evolution of machines and the fact the species was last loosing what made it human only human to worship those mechanisms... So we have to talk of the species no longer as a goal in itself, or else it would take seriously all the humanist people who have tried to reform the world, but rather of a stage in this planet, an 'enzymen' that catalyzes the evolution of technologies far superior to its capacities and then let them kill humanity without even reflecting on those events.

CONCLUSION. IMMORTAL HISTORY: THE HUMAN CONSTITUTION OF A WHEALTHY ORGANISM OF MANKIND.

AS IT IS customary in all the papers on 5D History, which is the super organism of the human, species, we end with a brief account on how 5d systemics could model it into a perfect world with its proper physiological networks in which nothing of this would happen as the evolution of time would be halted in an ideal immortal present for history – nor that anything of this has an increasingly dwindling probability to happen, the more so as the ‘single point-mind’, which hosts this upgrading of human consciousness is now at the center of the pandemics – Spain, the country beyond anecdotal city-nations, with a higher proportion of infected, dead and where a virtual fantasy of happiness made the reaction more lame long enough to bring us to a state of massive death of the elderly and those with preconditions, the group in which I found myself. So this might be the last paper on 5D which will return to its most googled ‘meaning’ – a ‘bubble group of mystical soul’ (: In any case, there should be ∞ fractal planets where 5D did change the species, ‘lonely, silent planets’ that do not communicate with us and are the only human solution to the Fermi paradox. . Such system could be implemented on Earth with the measures explained in the next graph:

A blue print for r=evolution The 6 measures to save the world.

As the theoretical measures to survive the chip radiation are simple but the idol-ogies in favor of money weapons and machines and the overwhelming power of compacracies with its goal of terraforming the Earth to the image of machine, and the informative control they have over social sciences (anti quantum paradox) makes almost impossible r=evolution. In the next graph the 6 simple measures I had preached for 30 years, to avoid the logic end of the robotic age - the obsolescence of Mankind - now clearly in the making as we enter an age of mental, visual atrophy and our children glued to virtual screens love entropy, death, chaos, individualism and visual degradation; while our collective subconscious moves back to the past, with revivalism of Abrahamic religions, bigotry fundamentalism and visual 'neo-Paleolithic' violent thought: 'vidi, credo ergo sum'; as an old man looks to the past with a negative feeling unable to face his incoming death. But history could be reformed, *since it is a simpler system and information unlike the warping of the body by nervous systems that exhaust its energy could be controlled by a well designed society:*

in the graph, repeated for good measure the 3+3 *physiological* solutions of the science of supœrganisms to change the non-future of Mankind in an automated metal-Earth.

They are the positive and negative necessary changes in the ‘3 Physiological networks of mankind’ that will make the world a perfect, immortal planet; from left to right, the positive scientific element is the enhancement of the education in 5D social sciences, the true sciences of mankind as an organism, while the negative side is the legal prohibition of robotics and other lethal goods that kill the superorganisms of mankind.

The issue of a universal salary to create a demand-based real economic democracy by people through an international yes currency to create welfare demand, today easily achieved with a cryptocurrency, at 100 ¥= Euro≈\$ parity, given to each human in a 'mobile pocket app', could establish an immediate massive demand economy in welfare goods globally, plummeting enormously the poverty of 3rd world nations, the migration problem and the excessive reproduction of lethal goods common people won't demand.

-To split all shares of all companies, giving to Mankind, either national governments, or better, international cultures and like-like institutions the split 50% to allow national and international institutions to manage even forbid lethal companies, obliging them to serve truly consumers, without losing managerial skills.

While in the political arena, 2 measures tending to create real democracies and a global government in charge of the management of the world requires:

-The reorganization of nations Eu style in the 7 original cultures of history (Australasia put for just historic reasons with Indonesia).

-The creation of real democracy, Greek style, where politicians are chosen as experts or from the common people by lottery but vote is a posteriori as a judgment with penalties of jail to oblige politicians to serve people.

-And finally a revolution which can come ideally from the top to the bottom governments (Uno assembly, 'mule', stock rats caring for the future) or from people through the vote of r=evolutionary parties, or the take over 'occupy wall street' style, of the centers of financial-media/government power.

We illustrate those 3+3 measures, which are the scientific simple measures of the science of systems applied to social sciences, taking from imitation those 3+3 measures imitating nature where cells send pain messages to the brain, have all its salary in oxygen to kick out production of goods, so no-one dies of hunger, lethal goods are not allowed to enter the organism, killed by leucocytes, organs of the body collaborate as nations of history should together, and do not use lethal weapons but talk with hormones in diplomatic channels to achieve the common good, could change the world within years. So only a r=evolution with the science of history as the guidance of the planet can save Mankind from extinction. It is then necessary a people-caste of bio-historians, as in foundation (Asimov's trilogy on history), to take over, and make a needed r=evolution of the system applying the laws of physiological history, to reform the economic, reproductive and informative legal system with the 6 measures that would make both physiological networks work for Mankind: how easy would be to implement the measures? As simple as Mr. Potus wanting them, since it would only require 3 people, an Asimovian mule, Mr. Potus, Mr. Eu and Mr. China (Mr. Pec - a perfect triad of global power), but Mr. Potus alone could easily convince 'organic China' the most advanced human super organism in any time of history, to join and the rest would follow.

As such the science of history is part of the science of biology, specifically the science of systems that defines every system of the universe as a social organism. Why humans reject such concepts have to do with the present state of history - one dominated by the age of entropic dissolution and death of historic structures, when the individual citizens/cells of the historic super organism feel 'free' of any ethic, informative network, which used to bond them with other human beings. So as history 'dies' away as a super organism, the very same concept of his nature fades away.

Organisms have in that sense a very deterministic nature and so the great philosophers of history from Aristotle to Spengler have wondered about the deterministic of history through its ages.

In that sense, the solutions of history are also simple and deterministic following those laws of social super organism.

How easy would be to implement the measures? As simple as Mr. Potus wanting them, since it would only require 3 people, an Asimovian mule, Mr. Potus, Mr. Eu and Mr. China, but Mr. Potus alone could easily convince 'organic China' the most advanced human super organism in any time of history, to join and the rest would follow. Trust me if I were Mr. Trump I would have done it already. But alas, 'presidents are selected, not elected' - said Roosevelt. So it would require a mule in the Asimovian sense, a bio-historian, who takes power without showing his true colors and then get rid of the whole corrupted viral super organism of history infected by company-mothers of machines, ideologies with 7.5 billion viral brains with their DNA converted to the memes of the viral machine, busy-busy in a frenzy reproducing it. And for you to understand that homology, we need to introduce the hardcore science of memetics, as it is.

This must be understood, such as system could only be imposed by an economic not military, not political, but economic coup d'état against the dictatorship of corporations, to restore a real democracy, of the most powerful nations of the world, which would establish first the economic measures, and the global currency, which means an Asimovian 'mule', foundation style, of a triad of presidents, of the 3 most powerful entities of the planet China, Us and Eu... Which then would expand the system to the rest of the planet, creating a global super organism of Mankind that would design a world to our image and likeness.

The three political and economic measures that could 'save' history... Nowhere to be seen in the present zeitgeist of 'enzymanic slavery' to machines and its corporative super organisms are very simple taken from nature's design of suporganisms and would enhance the freedom of the people and ensure its future: legal prohibit of robotics,

universal salary, control of politicians and corporations, and a world based in diplomacy and culture, not industrial competition and nationalist wars.

Since the key to a real social science is obviously to follow the objective organic models of reality which shape both the human super organism of history and the eco(system) as superorganisms, whose individual 'citizen-cells' use an informative and reproductive language to build its social networks that distribute efficiently vital energy and information to its individuals, making the whole stronger and allowing a higher density of population. However when a system is ill-designed it will NOT provide just information and enough energy for its cells to survive. And this is the case of humanity, ill-designed by cultural memes of nationalism that divide the species into false tribal ones, to foster the abuse of humans with weapons and the ill-designed capitalist system in which money is NOT the oxygen of society that must be delivered to each citizen-cell to start the reproduction and consumption of goods, but a parasitic digital language, monopolized in its issue by a small 'cancerous group' of 'experts', classic economists, working as financiers and company-managers that 'choke' mankind of its productive credit necessary to reproduce the healthy goods humanity need to survive (welfare goods), while allowing the massive reproduction of lethal goods of higher price that kill our body and minds.

The outcome is a permanent state of entropic disorder that prevents mankind to reach the natural social goal of all surviving superorganisms: social unification of mankind in a single world that maximizes the existence of the 100%

PART II.

THE PANDEMIC, ITS 7+1 SOLUTIONS FROM IDEAL SOCIETIES TO CIVILINATIONS

NATURE'S SOLUTION TO PANDEMICS OF A SICK 5D SUPÆRGANISM. AND ITS MISHANDLING BY MANKIND.

We can now return after this long analysis of social sciences as organisms, and the different elements of History, given the fact those papers are not so much about a moment in time and space of that Historic process but about the whole future of mankind, to the point we left the analysis of the proper, ideal answer to the coronavirus crisis which closely resembles that of Asian nations given their 'organic view' of mankind and the Universe.

We were considering in the foreword the proper response, past the analysis on how a membrane defends the body sealing it from germs, into the phase in which the first germs have invaded the supærganism.

Next then supærganism must send its immune/health-care system to localize every germ and neutralize it.

In the coronavirus it means a massive 'testing' of all the citizens-cells, regardless of linguistic expenditure in money, as money is a language that can be reproduced for free, NOT a debt, as the capitalist parasitic system believe it is, that has to be returned.

So there is no problem printing trillions to solve the crisis and pay for the needed kits to test everybody, as Korea did, with a swift response that closely resembles that of the supærganism in its mad search with feverish activity of every invading germ.

The simple measures a superorganism would have used to cure the sickness.

We can now understand what is wrong in our systems and why they don't work and could not cure or prevent the pandemics – the Historic reasons why they have developed as such would required a much deeper probe into history made latter before we analyze the response of the different human civilizations. Essentially a working system HAS IS 3 PHYSIOLOGICAL NETWORKRS, AND LANGUAGES controlled and messed together to the service of its citizens cells. So the financial system, which deploys the language of money=oxygen to all cells should be nationalized. This is what happens in al superorganisms. In fact our system is exactly the same system produced by the sickness of the coronavirus who kills people preventing them from accessing the oxygen =money of its cells, lining the lungs to absorb all its oxygen in a classic 'private banking' parasitic scheme. So there has not been money for the immunological system of health-care, there is no money now to give a Universal salary to every human in ¥€\$ money so they stay home whenever truly required obliging companies NOT to fire them as the state pays their salaries. Instead, the coronavirus and the banker parasites the system absorbing all the oxygen and letting the cells die of anoxia. Finally the immunological system is NOT the proper healthcare system of leukocytes defending the cells but an aberration called the military that kill human beings. And obviously the legal, nervous system of laws that synchronize the actions of people is a repressive system with NO PAIN FEED BACK AS IN ALL SUPERORGANISMS OF NATURE, WHERE IF THE POLITICO-NEURON DOES NOT HELP AND PROTECT THE BODY CELLS RECEIVES BACK A Pain a posteriori judgment that makes it suffer in hell. This was how the first Greek democracies worked: after tenure all politicos had to be voted and could be taken to jail, exile even death. And indeed, all the politicos of our capitalist democracies should be taken to a Nuremberg's trial after the genocidal procedures and the system reformed – it is likely the last chance.

It is important to notice the main of those sins of capitalist democracies, the concept that money is a parasitic form of wealth that must be returned with interest as debt. We study in the Anglo-American paper how this appeared among the Jewish and Mesopotamia go(I)d cultures of usurers, who were hypnotized by gold and became the standard concept of money s parasitic debt in the middle ages, to become the basis of our banking system, causing so much pain both to the people who suffered debt and to the people-caste of usurers as it has been the cause of the holocaust cycle and the economic crisis. And yet it is still the concept of private banking and public bankers who

create 'debt' and 'loan' money that should be simply given for free to waste as any language does. The fact that not even in this pandemic Europe can produce for free money as coronavirus BONDS shows to which degree social scientists understand nothing of the systemic laws and efficient structure of the organisms of nature, and its physiological networks.

Capitalist democracies are a mask of false freedoms, because they are neither efficiently serving their citizens, NOR TRUE democracies (the impressive speed at which the fundamental rights of people with a global incarceration by lack of a proper health-care immunological response, has been established, creating a dystopian, long-announced mechanical control of population for future ages to come, shows the fragility of those freedoms, in a system in which unlike organisms the RULERS of the informative head CANNOT receive 'a posteriori' pain messages from the cells as in real Greek earlier democracies, where all elected citizens were voted after tenure punishments if they didn't live up their promises). Instead in the west, with its military and financial true dictatorships, the focus has been on repressing population wholesale and investing massively in the stock market speculative and debt systems of money.

As we explain in the Abstract, the form in which a superorganism would have cured the sickness is simple and could have been implemented in a perfect superorganism of History but as history has not evolved properly it has not...

Indeed, once the 'virus is isolated' in a determined region of the body any immunological system has to put all the resources of its re=productive blood=economic system to isolate and control and kill the virus; while at the same time 'protecting' from it the most endangered parts of the body which might suffer biggest risks.

This means instead of controlling 'manu militari' the whole superorganism as nations have done, based in its ill-established systems of 'war=defense', they should have tagged, followed and controlled the sick infected cells, while protecting the elderly and people under conditions.

In case of a runaway virus, for lack of initial measures, control of populations should have been exercised only on those risk groups, while the rest of people with the adequate protective gear, should have gone on to work, as the lethality for people under 50 was small.

But all this would have required a massive investment in health-care and our social systems are not established to that aim. They are animetal systems where the main resources go to parasitic money and war. So when studying each civilisation we observe how each culture has used its 'totemic' dominant language of power, NOT the adequate one, and none, save Asian cultures, China and its closely ally Korea and Vietnam, with its socialist past, have developed swiftly the resources needed to control the virus.

As usual, those of the immune system of an efficient non-corrupted superorganism, since 5D laws are the same regardless of scale. Problem is mankind is a corrupted dysfunctional superorganism, reason why a pandemic such as this one can break havoc in our societies. Specifically the 're=productive, blood-economic system' of mankind is deeply dysfunctional, as both its blood red cells that transport oxygen=money, the language of action of the organism, do NOT reach all citizens-cells; and the immune system of the hardest T-cells, produced in the strong bones in mankind is overwhelmingly dedicated to 'kill cells' (Military) not to save them (Health-care system).

Thus the reasons why a pandemic like the coronavirus can kill so many people have to do far less with the virus itself but with the ill-designed physiological networks of mankind, themselves born of a wrong evolution of 'history', still broken in organs that 'reject' each other, and engage in wars that multiply the other 'lethal germs' of humanity - weapons. While the health-care immune and blood-red cell systems, which are the 'core' systems of an efficient superorganism are lacking and do not reach all citizens-cells.

According to the models of bio-history, money is the reproductive oxygen of the economic system given to every cell-citizen of an efficient superorganism of nature.

Because the economy is the blood-reproductive network of the organism the solution of a pandemic, a sickness of an organism IS IN 5D ECONOMICS and Social Sciences the same that an organism deploys.

An intelligent organic system like the ones of nature cure this type of sickness in 3 days.

It gives extra supply of oxygen-money to all cells sequestering its activity without eating in complete rest state.

Then it launches its antibodies, with fever to increase its thermodynamic activity. And the body is healed.

The Universe is simple and not malicious (Einstein) if the organism works according to the laws of nature and its physiological networks are well-behaved.

As money is the blood oxygen of society, and the antibodies are the health-care system and military/police, the immediate translation is obvious:

States have to put everyone at home for a month as soon as the sickness is established.

Central banks have to issue money not as they have done for banks and speculators to maintain the price of stocks; but to give a universal salary to all Europeans of two thousand Euros a month.

So they stay home but can buy food and medicines. Because the central bank=blood system takes care of the oxygen=salary, governments also prohibit all companies to fire workers during that period.

Then the 'antibodies' – health care system, food suppliers and police increase its feverish activity, for a month, detect all cases and solve the pandemic, disinfecting everything.

In 5D this is equivalent to STOP the time of the organism for a month and launch the defensive system.

However, NOT any efficient superorganism in Nature goes to the extreme radical final strategy of absolute confinement that will destroy the economic=blood/reproductive system of the organism, for the obvious reason that an inert superorganism with zero Ts-motion cannot develop the essential '5Dimotional sequence of survival': Ts-motion> St-: location of energy source: TT-feeding->§[]: reproduction. This is sorely truth in our societies, in the case of the 3rd world with poor logistics, which has caused the incoming tragedy of the Indian Lockout, studied latter when we analyze the response of the 7 civilinations of mankind to the crisis.

The remedy in the west has been worse than the sickness, paradoxically because there were initially not resources for the health-care system after decades of splendid little wars for profits, which had depleted the welfare systems, as 'canons instead of butter' dominated the western superorganism. So we shall repeat ad nauseam that the lockout of the western world is completely unnecessary, a proof of the absolute corruption of the system, where politicos exist as theatrical masks of people's power to cater the needs of corporations that rule supreme, and control the issue of money they dedicate NOT to the reproduction of mankind and a sustainable world but to the reproduction of its offspring of machines, reason why the needs of its population are never met.

5D social sciences, above present models.

As humans are 'lineal' in time (but the universe is a more complex illogic cyclical system), one-dimensional in scale (but the universe is based in the co-existence of several scales that interact together), organic and social in purpose (but mankind beyond its obvious individual organism has a mechanical, statistical ego-centered view of reality), the analysis of the coronavirus crisis is made in a shallow form, in present time, without connection with the flows of the superorganism of history, from a mere statistical point of view and under the anti-quantum paradox without any criticism of the astounding amount of systemic errors committed by the nervous=political and economic=blood and defensive=immunological system that create a perfect social superorganism. However this is not how social science papers are constructed for two reasons:

- As humans are overwhelmingly parts of a social superorganism which has as all 5D systems 3 organic parts, 'informative heads', which rule 'reproductive bodies' and command a 'vital space/limbic territory' that moves and

feeds the system, we can distinguish 3 'cellular social classes' in social superorganisms, the ruling informative class that controls the languages of society (money and the law, blood/oxygen/hormones and the nervous orders in a social and individual superorganism). So the head rules supreme a mass of 'blind cell bodies' that trust the head as they only get information from the head.

Spain & Italy have proved once more that a capitalist democracy is NOT about the welfare of the people and its politicians are just theatrical masks of financial or military power. So, they did nothing to prevent the crisis

Indeed, what matters more to this study is the fact NOT of the relative low number of deaths of the virus, mostly on old people which have few years left – a proper statistical analysis of death must multiply the deceased by the number of years left, beyond any e-motional attachment, which means due to the average death.

The detection, isolation and surgical cure of the infected cells.

The second phase of any immune response to the penetration of a sickness in an organism, *in the first phases of the infection when the 'charge' of viral enemies is minimal, is the swift detection in the region of entrance of the body of its enemy cells and its massive on-slaughter by the health-care warriors, T-cells and leucocytes that immediately try to isolate the region of the infection and increase its activity to control the disease before it spreads to other regions.*

So do human doctors with cancerous cells before its metastasis.

This is done with several procedures; namely the platelet shields the area of penetration in the membrane to avoid further infection. Then temperature=thermodynamic activity rises in the region, along its inflammation to allow the liquids that transport the defensive cells to arrive to the region; and the germs are attacked by them, with all the means needed. Blood=oxygen invades the region with those T-cells buttressed with the best technology the body can harness, often from previous invasions, memorized in the genetic codes of the T-cells. If the infection is recognized in its first sick zones and the genetic memory has already combated them, chances it will be reduced before the body gets truly sick and requires its 'paralysis' lying on 'bed', are high. For that reason *it is essential to localize, test and isolate the original infected citizens-cells of a pandemic and have enough-blood money to proceed.*

Comparing Human Social Superorganisms

It is interesting to compare Nature's model with the Asian countries that have solved the epidemics. China gave their people masks (as its transmission is mouth-nose) making obligatory its use; multiplied by 12 its production, invested massively in hospitals and tests and confined the focus of the epidemic. So it did Korea and Japan, Singapore and Taiwan. Those are countries (see paper on Asian civilisations) that closer resemble the superorganisms of the Universe, regardless of their system, in all of them financial systems are properly regulated, from national banks in China to strict control in Korea. America and Europe however have a dysfunctional financial system that never produces money for its people and has suffered decades of austericide against its health-care systems, which in America is not even Universal - the concept of a Universal salary does NOT even exist, and yet that is how nature reproduces money. Mankind could easily establish it with ¥€\$ money a parity euro=dollar=100 ¥en global cryptocurrency handled to every human as a salary of blood-oxygen as organisms do to all cells, since money IS a language of information, NOT wealth per se, whose goal as all languages is to kick out the actions of production and consumption of all the citizens-cells of the system, as you do with your verbal language. The coronavirus crisis could have been an opportunity for mankind to redesign their parasitic financial cancerous systems and establish a global sustainable world based in a demand economy and welfare world. In the west it will lead to more of the same - a military police state as we are observing now in Italy and Spain, where people without expenditure on masks, tests and lacking hospitals are dying while the state merely imposes confinement and police vigilance.

America will follow a similar path, stigmatizing further its minorities that won't be tested or cured, and yet in the Democratic election the only candidate that proposes a proper health-care system is loosing to a corrupted lobbyist of financial corporations. Themes those explored in our papers on the 'Anglo-American, capitalist civilisation'.

In that regard, the solutions of the different superorganisms of history show the focus of each 'civilization':

- Asia has cured the pandemics using science and social order and solidarity. The 'mask is its symbol'.
- Europe has ignored the problem and closed borders with absolute in solidarity and lack of investments in health-care. Confinement and the military on the streets are its most noticeable measure.
- America has pumped up money to the system to maintain the stock-market prices.

What central bankers, who are private financiers who dedicate all the resources of the organism to make richer the 0.01% of owners of corporations did, was to waste the same MONEY to maintain the speculation of the market.

The same happened in America, where the FED gave 700 billion yesterday to the American stock exchange at 0 interest (the so-called quantitative easing of 700 billion for banks that will be invested mainly in stocks and lifted the market in conjunction with Trump's discourse to help companies NOT people).

In fact as we write Trump cancelled a project for respirators because it cost 1 billion 1/700th of what it gave to the market.

The same quantity needed to solve the problem from the human point of view of the 99%: 700 billion means exactly a universal salary of 2000 dollars to each American citizen-cell to stay home for a month.

Meanwhile the government puts under his rule all health companies and increases the feverish activity of an army doctors and health-care resources during that month to localize all infected people and solve the problem. Because the FED takes care of salaries legislators can forbid companies to fire anyone. It is equivalent to stop 'time=motion' of all citizen-cells of a sick organism for a month. It is what any organism does.

In an efficient supœrganism health procedures are simple. The blood-system=central bank should produce money for its cells NOT FOR a parasitic groups of financiers to increase the price of shares of the 0.01%.

Not a single penny of that money was invented for the US people to cure the disease – all to lift stock prices...

As the crisis rage the ideal solutions of bio economics are 'naturally put forward' - confinement, universal salary but in patches and without a model.

In that regard 5D social sciences if it has been known to mankind could have helped in this crisis to change the paradigm of human social thought for the dangers of the future ahead, as technology will bring new existential problems to mankind. But as the crisis goes away the same sickness of human social superorganisms will be implemented again, and the 'universal salary and health-care investments' of this crisis forgotten.

THE 7 CIVILINATIONS OF MANKIND AND ITS RESPONSES.

The different responses of Organic Asia vs. the Capitalist, selfie western world.

According to the models of bio-history, money is the reproductive oxygen of the economic system given to every cell-citizen of an efficient supærganism of nature.

Because the economy is the blood-reproductive network of the organism the solution of a pandemic, a sickness of an organism IS IN 5D ECONOMICS and Social Sciences the same that an organism deploys.

An intelligent organic system like the ones of nature heals this type of sickness in a few days, *if it can detect the invading cells, which will try to camouflage from the health-care warriors.*

To that aim It gives extra supply of oxygen-money to all cells of the infected region, inflaming it with healing liquids, sequestering its activity without eating in complete rest state.

Then it launches its antibodies, with fever to increase its thermodynamic activity. And the body is healed.

The Universe is simple and not malicious (Einstein) if the organism works according to the laws of nature and its physiological networks are well-behaved it normally succeeds at this stage.

As money is the blood oxygen of society, and the antibodies are the health-care system and military/police, the immediate translation is obvious:

States have to put everyone on the infected region at home for a month as soon as the sickness is established.

Central banks have to issue money Not as they have done for banks and speculators to maintain the price of stocks; but to give a universal salary to all Europeans of two thousand Euros a month.

So the citizens-cells stay home but can buy food and medicines. Because the central bank=blood system takes care of the oxygen=salary, governments also prohibit all companies to fire workers during that period.

Then the 'antibodies' – health care system, food suppliers and police increase its feverish activity, for a month, detect all cases and solve the pandemic, disinfecting everything.

In 5D this is equivalent to STOP the time of the organism for a month and launch the defensive system.

But obviously before the GLOBAL organism is completely paralyzed, a 'local symmetry' must be attempted through a massive detective system of all the regions of the body with the feverish activity of the immunological system that searches for the invading germs all over the organism, using the physiological networks, we shall now describe.

As we do want to be fairly scientific in our analysis with 5D laws of the whole process, we shall stop the analysis of this second phase and introduce the general laws of 5D supærganisms to understand better the limits of the human response and why it has failed in almost every civilination, and will keep failing except in the case of the Asian civilination, the closest one to an efficient ideal supærganism of history.

Yet to understand those different responses we need to bring back the laws of bio-history and how the 7 civilinations of mankind were born out of the response to previous 'apocalypse horses', namely social prophets of love that tried to prevent and cure the destruction of the world by the 7 cycles of evolution of metal-weapons, shown in a previous graph on the 3rd age of the metal-earth and studied in depth in all other bio-historic papers.

Eusocial evolution: the true meaning of Darwinian selection of species.

What Darwin said is very clear: species—not individuals—compete with other species; and the best, most social species survives better. In that regard, ecosystems and organisms are different social systems. In both cases we find a mass of 'cellular species', which evolve together thanks to networks of energy and information. In a social organism such as an anthill, a nation, or your body, the cells belong to a single species, which according to the laws

of social evolution, work together as a team, for the common welfare. In that sense, love religions are the verbal expression of those laws of social evolution that favor the survival of species, which work together.

Facts are conclusive. The 2 most efficient species of this planet are the ones that show higher levels of social love, of co-operation. They are ants and human beings. Ants are the most successful animals because they collaborate and evolve socially.

The total mass of ants in this planet is equivalent to the total weight of human beings and it is ten times bigger than the total mass of all other insects, because they are perfect social organisms, selfless, in love with the collective species.

The Chinese culture, the most social culture of this planet that traditionally promoted verbal information over money and war, is also the most successful, with the biggest number of survival individuals, accounting for ¼ of the mass of humans. Thus, we consider that our civilizations and religious gods are social organisms in which each man is a cell, joined to other human beings by verbal networks of information.

We define a historic organism as a social group of humans, related by networks of human energy (natural goods) and human information (verbal/visual art and laws). Finally, an economic ecosystem is a group of humans and machines related by networks of monetary information and energy networks.

If we use instead of religion, a biological jargon, civilizations become organisms composed of cellular herds of human beings that communicate through information networks (words & gods). As a nervous system connects and organizes the cells of a body, god connects and organizes a mass of human beings. Perhaps our definition of a universal super-organism will help you to grasp what we mean by a historic god:

'A universal super-organism is a biological body of (any species of cells) extended in time and space, joined by networks of information=gods.'

Thus, a relative god is the macrocosmic network of information of any super-organism, when perceived from the microcosmic point of view of his cells that the network of information controls. The brain of the human god is the *verbal network* of believers' minds, the books of revelation and the social laws that create human behavior. We create the future when we obey informative, verbal codes. God is the verb and its ethical codes of survival.

So the government is the god of a nation that controls its citizens; the brain is the god of your body cells; and the ethic laws of any religion are words of love that control for the common good the behavior of all its believers. The god of America is its constitution and corpus of laws; the god of Islam is the Koran and its laws; the god of Christians is the gospel, the laws and words of Christ 'that became god and inhabited within us' (saint john 1.1); the god of Jewish and most protestant sects are the mosaic laws; and the absolute god of the universe are the laws of organic science, the 3±1 arrows of space-time that *define the survival and extinction of all its species*. Thus, in mystique terms the super-organisms of history are called gods. And theology is the science that explains the relationships between individual human cells and those super-organisms. Let us then, end this chapter with an analysis of all the religions of the past, present and future, according to their degree of corruption and/or evolution in their understanding of the organic laws of the universe.

Human and universal religions. God as mind of the supœrganism of history and the universe

In the graph, the evolution of western and eastern gods in 3 scales of complexity till reaching the concept of Mankind as God of History and the GAME of the three arrows of time as the God of all Universal existences.

In the graph, the 6 main human cultures born of the natural evolution of the concept of social love and its super organisms of mankind and the Universe (western vs. eastern gods). From the graph we can get an obvious conclusion: tribal religions and tribal 'nationalisms', two expressions of the same concept which believe their 'god/nation' is the 'only/best' one are just a primitive version of the larger organic view of modern systemic sciences. And today a mere excuse to foster the evolution of weapons that will kill us.

For that reason the evolution of tribal religions ended in oikoumene love religions and finally socialist doctrines. While the evolution of animist and Taoist cults became the final horizon of systems sciences with their organic models of a living Universe, this writer develop when working in science at the turn of the century. In brief, we can

again apply the Correspondence principle of science to account for religions as evolutionary stages of an Organic Theory of Everything applied to human cultures or the Universe as super organisms.

Earth divides in 6 cultural regions, related to anthropomorphic religions and its 3 historic horizons: Christianity, Islam and communist China; and to the 3 horizons of universal religions: animist Africa & native America; Hindi & Buddhist south-Asia and the mechanist, scientific culture that today preys on all the others.

So while religions express some of the whys of social evolution in old jargons, *ideally they would be taught as stages in the search for the understanding of the organic nature of everything in scientific terms, which is how we shall describe them in this paper.*

A final question though we shall leave pending. If we are as humans 'cells of religious or national super organisms', and in the case of religions, we co-share a revelation meme-book, similar to the DNA, and there are 'unseen' scale above us that organize parts but parts cannot 'see' in space, there exists an upper scale in which 'a consciousness of a god' as the consciousness of an ambulatory trillion cells called a human being exists?

It is obvious that if we exist as a whole mind-ego but cells do not see us, since smaller parts do not perceive wholes but only the networks' messages=languages to which they are attached; there might exist a collective consciousness of all Muslims called Allah, of all Jewish called Yhwh, and so on. A fact which would explain why people-cells of those cults die for the subconscious collective, while others who do not believe in a god and hence are self-centered in their biological wholes find weird such behavior. "Sangris martire semen christianorum", said a roman philosophers. But even so, it will be a local $\Delta+1$ scale NOT the creator of the Universe. So again, religions fit within the larger theory of the living fractal universe.

Finally a temporal analysis is required to complete the understanding of those civilinations.

The huge difference between the East and The west is both 'scalar': the east understands the organic Universe better and so Nature's laws and it applies them better to build organic societies, stronger than the individual While the west is a mirage of 'egocy: ego=idioty', where God is ill-understood as the subconscious collective of Humanity, and so its arrogance towards Nature is remarkable; but also in time:

- Asia's foundational cultures stayed longer in the Neolithic pre-metal ages and so acquired its organic form, while, western European and American civilizations were developed in the age of Metal and so they are prone to suffer the 4 horses of apocalypse and disorder=chaos and wars – reason why obviously most of the survival numbers of mankind co-exist in Asia. This pandemics will just tilt further that imbalance as Asian nations with China in its center will become stronger once all has passed and the shortcomings of our western cultures ruled by metal-masters and corrupted inefficient political systems show its true face.

In the graph, the fundamental law of the organic, fractal universe and general systems sciences regarding behavior, applied to all its scales from quantum atoms to genes to memes: Beings which feel 'clones of each other, able to share identity languages-memes-genes-quantum states' or complementary as genders specialized in male entropic energy and female reproductive information love each other and evolve together in social wholes, by sharing energy and information (charity mandate of love religions which express the law in verbal terms), while those who perceive each other as different without understanding its common languages of information and sharing its formative networks ab=use each other as predators and prey.

This law of GST (ab. General system sciences) defines from the massive clone, identity systems of matter, from water to iron planetary cores (huge masses are made of identity atoms) to boson states (non-distinguishable particles collapse into a single whole), to the herd's nature's tendencies in all organisms, to the social evolution of those scales from particles to atoms, molecules, cells, matter states, super organisms and planetary ecosystems, solar systems and galaxies in clusters....

The parallelism is evident as the sickness of history are those of its physiologic, political and economical systems.

The law of behavior in the organic universe is simple: beings who are similar and complementary and speak the same language of information with similar dexterity come together as couples, herds and social wholes stronger than individuals. Those who perceive each other as different, however fail to create such supœrganisms, and are weaker species when confronting the type of crisis we confront with a pandemic today.

We now have the basic understanding of the social supœrganisms of mankind to see how indeed, the stronger supœrganisms of the Asian civilization that closely resemble the Supœrganisms of Nature have survived the crisis while the 'western animetal cultures' of individualism, greed and violence suffered as most of their history the 4 horses of apocalypse unable to follow the eusocial love laws of the Universe.

The law of eusocial evolution, natural to all species, which evolve together, sharing energy and information through common networks, when they recognize each other as equal being, cells of the same superorganism, is confronted by the law of darwinian devolution, in which species that consider each other different ab=use the others as relative energy of their selfish agenda.

In human superorganisms, the laws of eusocial evolution were perfectly defined by the great prophets of love, in the old age, by the messages of love of Buddha, Jesus and Mhmd, in the modern age by the work of the r=evolutionaries of history, with their motto 'egalite, fraternite, solidarite' and the socialist vision of a planet ruled by social love.

ASIAN – NEOLITHIC ORGANIC CULTURES.

Mature age of mankind, the Neolithic.

The maximal social evolution of history happened in the Neolithic culture, self-similar in all the regions of the planet. Social love was so intense that humans lived in homes without streets and people walked through the roofs or the house of their neighbors, like insects in a beehive. Each man in the village had a 'cellular' vital space, his home or den, tools and clothing; but the energy networks, the agricultural fields in which people fed, were common property, as it happens in DNA organisms, in which DNA molecules live within their home/cell, pegged to other homes/cells, sharing with them the energy of their blood. Neolithic cultures created environmental societies, based in natural, human goods; where every cell owned 'vital' property; where the networks of social information were based in verbal thought (laws); where ethic, social men, called priests, acted as the verbal, collective neurons that solved the colliding interests of individual cells. Those social organisms followed the universal laws of social evolution, creating efficient organic systems, with a single collective brain (the elder with more information, verbal priests, legal assemblies, etc.) And a healthy geographical body that provided the human goods needed to satisfy the biological drives of human beings.

The ethic law acted in them as the *verbal, nervous system* of the society. Legal mandates motivated or forbade certain actions, selecting those, which improved the welfare of the entire society. Without laws we cannot understand historic

organisms. Laws rule in an invisible manner the acts of people, as nervous orders guide the cells of the body. Thus, certain humans, verbal masters who create laws, as the neurons create nervous orders—prophets, priests, lawyers, courts and parliaments today—should hold the power of societies. What is an aberration is to leave the ‘blood=economic system’ to control the nervous/legal system, as it happens in free markets. In that sense the hierarchy between the elements of a society, in harmony with nature and the organic laws of the universe, is crystal clear:

Networks of information: Ethic and political laws that create a nation or in mythic terms, a social god (‘and god, the word, became man and inhabit among us’). They control:

Individual cells: Human beings that obey the law and control:

Networks of energy: Economic systems of reproduction of human goods.

The nervous system, made of social, ethic laws must rule the economic ecosystem that provides the goods humans need to survive and fulfill their biological drives of existence. Unfortunately, the opposite happens in our economic ecosystem: money controls human beings, who create corrupted laws that no longer serve their biological goals.

The final stage of the social evolution of Mankind—the creation of a global organism of history, of a god, sustained by networks of love, mandates that make the human cells to share their energy and information—seems to have failed, as the arrival of weapons, money and machines imposed a radical shift in the evolution of Mankind and the Earth.

But for you to understand that you would have first to understand what would be healthy supœrganism of history and the two forms of money, parasitic money, the metal-money dominating today, which first appear as Go(l)d, Hypnotizing the eye of the Semitic people, starting the cycles of greed, taxation, social anoxia war and destruction of civilizations as opposed to whealthy money, the natural use of an energy (grain) or digital number (nomisma) to organize a society with a healthy reproductive system able to deliver welfare goods to all its people – the money of the Neolithic age.

The networks of the Neolithic: ethic priests of life & positive money: a whealthy world.

Positive money simply stated is a digital language, which under the command of the ethic law, as blood and hormones do in the organism, interact with ALL the citizens cells of mankind to promote the reproduction of the 5 positive type of human goods that maximize the ‘function of existence’; that is, the drives of life of a human being.

So what are the 5 positive dimotions of money? Those who multiply the positive healthy goods of the economic frame of reference: positive entropy (food), positive information (just laws, education), positive social evolution (peace, social communication, tourism, love religions), positive reproduction (health-care, family values) and repress with minimal value the negative goods of society that kill (weapons), disrupt social evolution (hate memes), monopolize wealth (money that cannot be distributed due to its scarcity as a Universal salary), or detract it from people (giving instead of a Universal salary, a tax or a debt interest that takes money and kills by anoxia) and give minimal values to life memes (welfare goods). The change from positive to negative money thus took place when universal money (grain), was substituted by scarce precious metal . We can compare them with those of the parasitic function. Also considering its historic development.

SS-positive information: Money in the Neolithic was wheat; natural whealth. It is the positive history of money from the age of Wheat salaries in the fertile crescent and Indus civilization – and likely most Neolithic Asian and Mexican cultures, where money was essentially a Universal salary given by priests to peasants and the people of a community in the form of food. Wheat could then be used to pay salaries and give ex-votes to the temple. The modern version of positive ‘money as form, would be ¥€\$ money. The extreme density of population found in the Sumerian and Indus civilizations showed the efficiency of money as Whealth.

TT: Positive entropy. Money is not a lethal product as lethal goods are forbidden to trade and reproduce. In the earlier Neolithic cultures there was no metal-weapons. War was rare and priests ruled societies, NOT military caudillos, a development that started with the ‘bronze radiation’ and the taking over of Lugals.

§T: Positive reproduction: Money as a salary was a supplement to the Universal rent in WHealth or ¥€\$ money that should be introduced in the modern world. Money however as a salary did NOT buy people's time for ever, as it was neither debt, nor slavery was allowed – the buying of human by money. On the contrary most often, work for the community was assigned to every citizen in a voluntary manner. Today money as a salary should obviously be maintained but it should NOT eliminate SS-money and certainly a well managed economy would NOT allow the synergies between lethal metal-memes, weapons of maximal price, hate media and misinformation and money. That is, the 'belli nervi pecunia infinita cycle' would be abolished. But that would require a reform of the political system, making of EU and UNO like institutions the goal of societies, for each of the 7 'civilizations of history', studied in our analysis of the supœrganisms and gods of history.

sT & Ts: Positive motion. Money as debt and tax thus would be also abolished, as money would be merely a language that activates the reproduction of Whealthy goods; and 'speculative markets' of e-money would be abolish. This means simply that shares should be nominal, ¥€\$ money a currency at fixed parity avoiding Forex, and pure speculative markets (derivatives, financial instruments, future markets) would NOT exist. Tax would not be necessary then because *money would be created for people and governments, and for those 'Selected companies' that reproduce goods positive for mankind, hence NOT for lethal goods of maximal profits, according to the equation of capitalism.*

With the use of gold as money, today 'stocks of company-mothers', monopolized by a minority and dedicated to value and reproduce ad maximal metal-memes, reducing the stock of minimal price of welfare goods, money became negative. And has remained for mot of history, with the exception of the Numa-Solon and modern r=evolution attempts with national banks, negative money. Negative money is however positive for the evolution of the goods of the metal-earth whose price maximizes.

7 CULTURES OF THE WORLD WITHIN 3 GAIA AGES, 7 ANIMETAL CYCLES OF CIVILIZATIONS AND 7 PROPHETS.

The previous introduction to social 5D sciences is required to understand Why answers to the crisis have been different have to do with the existence of 7 cultural civllinations composed of 'national states', whose origin is the wave of history and its humanist, religious 'scientists', which tried to create the perfect organic world the science of bio-economics can build according to an imitation of nature. *So the civilination which closer imitates in idol-ogies and scientific views of the Universe, reality as it is – Asia, has done better as always does in matters of survival, the true measure of intelligence in the Universe.*

All Civilinations mix memes of the 2 supœrganisms of this planet, defined by the equation of Complexity that defines the growing complexity of the supœrganisms of Mother Earth, among which we find History:

$$\text{Gaia (relative past-life earth)} < \text{History (present-Human earth)} > \text{Metal-earth (Machines: economic system)}$$

In the graph the equation of History defines 3 relative super organisms of history, and so the 7 cultures of mankind evolved through time display memetic structures belonging to those 3 'sub-organisms':

We can easily define the 7 cultures of the world by its initial beliefs in one of those super organisms:

GAIA: So Africa 'believes' as the remaining Paleolithic cultures of the arctic regions in Gaia. So do the earlier Indonesian cults (sacred water rivers in Hindi traditions).

Buddhist Asia believes in both, Gaia and Mankind as super organisms to 'worship'.

MANKIND: Catholic Latin America and Islam believe in the History as the super organism to cherish with anthropomorphic, subconscious, collective Gods.

METAL-EARTH: Europe believes in both, History and the Metal-earth.

Finally America is unique in putting the Metal-earth and the Financial-Media/Military-Industrial system of company-mothers who FOUNDED their civilization, as the 'supreme Good and Only future of the planet',

RAINBOW PLANET

with its exceptionalism lineal progress in time towards a mechanical paradise.

So the classification of the 7 cultures WITHIN the super organisms of the higher SCALE of the Earth is obvious.

And as usual we have to study the two sides of each culture the metal-side and the human side. The metal-side of Europe is its northern-European culture, founder of the machine, the human side its southern-European Latin culture, founder of humanism, today in decline.

So what is Europe? As always both things, humane and mechanical. but the mechanical civilization seems to have won the future of history.

FRactal Gods: MIND OF CIVILIZATIONS HISTORY IN SPACE: MANKIND AND THE MYSTICAL CONCEPT OF GOD.

‘Love each other as I have loved you’. Jesus, Expression of the universal arrow of social evolution.

It shall come a time in all planets on existence, that the truth of the wor(l)d is told a last instance, before it dies away to remind those who love there is always a chance for the rebirth of Mankind, the minor god in harmony with the whole.

Man is just another supørganism of the infinite Universe, which can become immortal in its perfect form, only if it imitates the whole, the major God’s melody of existence through its pentalogic scales.

So we can also define the 'germs' of history, weapons, whose overreproduction causes the sickness and death of civilizations. And soon we shall establish an 800-80 years cycle studied in detail in the lateral posts of the blog, which is a technological vortex of informative evolution of those new lethal species, who are killing Mankind.

And this lead us to understand why such abhorrent development of Humanity has taken place in terms of evolutionary laws.

DIFFERENT RESPONSES TO CORONAVIRUS CRISIS ACCORDING TO EACH SOCIAL SUPØRGANISM

The coronavirus case shows as all systems under stress the huge errors of design of human supørganisms, based in historic traditions of military nature (politicians), and parasitic debt-money (Classic economics) which put the machine above man as the goal of society (industrial r=evolution); and so has not evolved mankind and its social organisms to face crisis against the welfare and health of its people.

So unlike the scientific organization promoted by bio-history and bioeconomics based in how Nature builds its efficient supørganisms, human societies are dysfunctional, catering to the cells-citizens but to the elites and corporations, which control its money and resources. And so when the ‘apocalypse’ horses comes in – pest, war, famines... the organism is ill prepared to protect its citizens cells.

A perfect world would be a planet built imitating the most perfect supørganisms of the Universe, we know of – the mammals. In such perfect world which mankind could achieve with the 3+3 simple reforms above according to the laws of bio-history, we would be of course a single supørganism of history.

Let us imagine then that in one of the many fractal Supørganisms of History in the Universe a pandemic takes place. The system obviously is as all supørganisms a single nation, a single world. And because according to the ethonomic frame of reference it delivers as all organisms does, the welfare goods the organism needs to survive and suppresses those lethal goods the organism does NOT require; it is obvious that the expenditures on such planet are quite different from those of this planet. Let us call this world ‘Castalia’ honoring Mr. Herman Hesse. In Castalia a ‘Foundation’ of bio-historians (honoring Mr. Asimov), can predict accurately the future because it is as the present – time has stopped and History is immortal.

In such perfect world obviously the 3 physiological networks of mankind are properly built so to start with:

- The immune system is NOT a military system dedicated to protect animetals its worshipped machines and wealth, and kill human beings; but a health-care system that receives billions of dollars in a single world, with a single brain government.

- The blood=reproductive money system is NOT a parasitic system dedicated to increase the digital numbers of the animetal elite, but it is handled as organisms do to every human citizen-cell in the form of a Universal salary without any obligation to work, if so they don't desire, as there is always a number of humans, given the fact that motion=energy=time is the substance of the Universe that will do. And they will need 'consumers', so the idle will consume kicking out orders of production of welfare goods.

- The nervous informative, legal system is NOT made of corrupted politicos to the service of the elite military and financial, parasitic classes, because they can receive pain-messages from citizens as in Greek democracies. So they do care to keep its promises and serve the people.

So the solution to a pandemics is immediate, done the way Korea did it, fast and reliable: people willingly stay home, take idle holidays, as they are solidarious and understand the bio-organic laws of the Universe, they do not fuk around and obviously the massive investment in the immune system of mankind liberated as a single government from the military systems and its borders, means they all have masks, tests, vaccines are worked out by the collaboration of all humans.

And to start with, there is a respect for Nature and we don't eat wild animals, nor there is any chance that there is a military lab researching bio-terrorism... either in Wuhan or US, who cares who did whom.

The solution is so simple and so efficient that pandemics have not existed in the perfect, immortal world of 'Castalia' in the past 100 million years...

The 3 solutions of the 3 main civilizations of the industrial world that are suffering the pandemics.

In 5D History, we divide mankind according to scale not only in social nations but mainly in civilinations, which form 7 cultural worlds according to the cycles of history and the prophets of social love that fought for mankind.

In the graph we see them – latter we will introduce them in more detail.

In this idol-ogical 'enzymanic' world of people who only care about money and the economic ecosystem of machines, it is customary to divide mankind between 'capitalist' and socialist economies, which is completely absurd, because we all live in capitalist societies with central banks reproducing the money through a supply economy, not a demand economy serving the people. But still there are differences

and if we add those differences – China vs. US the clearest one in terms of whom benefit most for the financial system – the elite or the people – to the differences of civilinations, the Asian civilination has won over the virus in a scientific way, and also through the social organic concerted help of its population, which better represent the scalar nature of the Universe. On the other extreme we will find the Anglo-American hard core capitalist society that will let people die NOT to lower the profits of companies. Already Johnson said the best strategy is to let them all be infected – so to save in health-care, and Trump wishes to do the same, so the economy doesn't stop and will do the same letting the poor die not to spend in health-care.

The intermediate view between the medical protection with massive mask, testing and hospital health-care that needed the virtues in Asia, and the '3rd world approach' of doing nothing, in the 3rd world by lack of resources in America by lack of will to protect its people and abandon the essence of the culture to make machines for the profits of corporations and its elite of 'stockrats', its owners, the modern aristocrats of society, is Europe, which has all the ills of capitalism but also the absurd nationalism of its never forgotten pleasure for war and tribal differentiation, so at the apex of the present infection the most surrealist measure of nationalism has been taken – to close the borders of Europe so the 'healthy people' from outside does NOT infect us. This anti-truth is also proper of the present age of virtual fiction thought. Sp we will std the 3

approaches which in the case of the '3rd world US approach' will extend to the other civilizations where there is no health-care resources, population is younger and other apocalypse horses kill far more – the exception being Islam which has charity laws that require to tender for the sick and so it will try a more humane, European approach with less resources.

So to the challenge of the coronavirus each culture has acted according to its personality: the 3 'solutions' implemented by the 3 dominant cultures of the Industrial world respond to that character. Europe has absurdly restored its sovereign rights and took the armies to the street, 'closing borders' as if anybody wanted to enter in the EU, the present center of the pandemic; Asia has used big data and health-care masks to cure the disease; U\$ has entered in financial panic and spent vast sums to pump up the market; showing each other what is the essence of their civilizations.

Consider the first measure U\$ has taken: the FED lowered to 0 interests for banks and gave them near 1 trillion \$ to maintain the prices of the market but gave NONE to the people which the military soon will close as it has done in Southern Europe where nobody has masks and contagion will continue at exponential rate, with its population.

So all the predictions of bio-history are happening with a twist, the 2020s didn't bring a Matrix world by global war but global pandemic. And yet there was a solution as Asia has shown. Yesterday also I saw how the corrupt Biden was put at face value by a socialist Jewish 'Moses' saying the hard truths to their capitalist Nathans, but then all the media commentators attacked Moses because he pretends to establish what every civilized nation has - health care for free for its people. The concept is clear: the black and Latino minorities without health-care will add now to blatant racism against them, the 'stigma' of untouchables as carriers of the virus. But the amazing thing of this is that the black people are NOT voting Sanders, the savior, but the corrupted Delaware Senator of the fiscal paradise tiny state... who tells them Italy with social security won't save its people of coronavirus - but does not mention Korea, Japan, Germany, China, Canada... Only the one country where as in this one I am writing from now, Barcelona Spain, people could NOT understand the need for stopping their social intercourse, their dolce fare niente...

Another matter though is the origin of the Virus. I do not believe in confabulation theories but in hard facts. So unlike others who think maybe escaped Wuhan bio-labs or was made in military labs in US and put there during the Wuhan military games of 2019 (curious coincidence), I don't believe people are that evil but rather as systems work with a sub-consciousness humans do NOT understand, the fact we care nothing for the tree of life and only for technology we cannot control is bringing our demise... So we have spent billions in weapons, cut social security, given trillions to speculators and now a crisis that could be handled will be out of hands in the western world and of course, the death counts in the 3rd world as those of SARS that killed hundreds of thousands of children in Africa, will NOT even be counted. Déjà vu.

The 7 cultures of mankind will respond differently.

Mankind is a single species that should be a single global supœrganism without borders able to tackle an attack to its citizens-cells of biological nature, easily with collaboration between nations, which in this case does not even happen at the level of medical attention, search for vaccines and control of the sic organic regions to avoid the expansion of the 'cancerous virus'.

The response to the pandemic of mankind's nations, its amateur 'neuronal nervous people-caste in power', governments and financiers, and the continuation of the organic barriers between nations – all of which have taken the troops to the streets, sometimes with bizarre surrealist excuses, as Europe which is now the focus of the infection but to 'protect' its citizens from external viral migrants (when the virus is here with maximal density) closes its borders. The reason is obviously that politicians are just the soft version of the military, whose lethal reproduction and use of goods that kill human cells must be justified regardless of its zero value for society, and the control of populations stressed. We shall then compare the different national and cultural responses to the crisis. Since the supœrganisms of history are divided into the customary 7 civilizations of the 'rainbow planet' studied in the papers on 4D History.

So it is interesting to compare Nature's model with the Asian countries that have solved the epidemics. China gave their people masks (as its transmission is mouth-nose) making obligatory its use; multiplied by 12 its production, invested massively in hospitals and tests and confined the focus of the epidemic. So it did Korea and Japan, Singapore and Taiwan. Those are countries (see paper on Asian civilisations) that closer resemble the superorganisms of the Universe, regardless of their system, In all of them financial systems are properly regulated, from national banks in China to strict control in Korea. America and Europe however have a dysfunctional financial system that never produces money for its people and has suffered decades of austericide against its health-care systems, which in America is not even Universal - the concept of a Universal salary does NOT even exist, and yet that is how nature reproduces money. Mankind could easily establish it with ¥€\$ money a parity euro=dollar=100 ¥en global cryptocurrency handled to every human as a salary of blood-oxygen as organisms do to all cells, since money IS a language of information, NOT wealth per se, whose goal as all languages is to kick out the actions of production and consumption of all the citizens-cells of the system, as you do with your verbal language. The coronavirus crisis could have been an opportunity for mankind to redesign their parasitic financial cancerous systems and establish a global sustainable world based in a demand economy and welfare world. In the west it will lead to more of the same - a military police state as we are observing now in Italy and Spain, where people without expenditure on masks, tests and lacking hospitals are dying while the state merely imposes confinement and police vigilance. America will follow a similar path, stigmatizing further its minorities that won't be tested or cured, and yet in the Democratic election the only candidate that proposes a proper health-care system is losing to a corrupted lobbyist of financial corporations. Themes those explored in our papers on the 'Anglo-American, capitalist civilisation'.

Indeed, only in Asia there were allocated massive resources to the health-care systems of true immune warriors, because only Asia has maintained the pre-capitalist organic concept of nations as superorganisms derived of its 'true objective' universal religions that closely understand the 5D laws of the organic Universe (Taoism, Buddhism, Confucianism) regardless of the shallow naming of its economic systems (capitalism, communism, etc.) themes those we can only brief treat, explained in all other papers of 5D history to focus on the pandemics.

Far East Asian cultures as we proved ad nauseam in the texts on the 7 civilisations are the most successful organic species of mankind by the only measure of such success in a living Universe – survival – NOT because they are a superior species but because they have superior memes, closer to the true scientific nature of the Universe as an entangled superorganism of yin=information and yang=energy, that combines and reproduces its infinite beings, entangled among them... Taoism and Buddhism reached before organic sciences took over the highest perception of reality and permeated all the concepts latter applied to politics by the neo-Confucian schools. While in the Western world, the anthropomorphic superorganisms of History lacked that entanglement with Nature, they have always despised, to the point that the r=evolution of thought signified by Darwin did not permeate the subconscious collective of entitled 'human beings' who do NOT submit to the laws of Nature. Only Islam=submission in the middle region between the East and the West, which included the essential concept of social love and charity among its mandates of organic existence and the love movement within the Christian Catholic church (Franciscan, Jesuit orders) signified in the messages of the present Pope and the socialist movement came closer but their achievements have been reversed by the hardcore go(l)d cultures of post-fall of the wall capitalism that returned to the concept that company-mothers of machine-weapons must rule supreme over mankind whose rights must not be considered worthy. So we need to make a detour to explain what truly a capitalist system is about

Why nothing like that has been attempted in the west from the inception of the pandemic has to do with the 'anti-nature' of our social systems, which dedicate all their resources to 'technological evolution' not human welfare.

And its null understanding of the laws of 5 SD superorganisms and its models of human societies.

So only now slowly in a patched form, a true organic offensive is considered - specially the more repressive measures - confinement -but not so much the truly healing ones - a massive health-care offensive with deployment of tests, masks, retroviral and UCI systems – as that cost too much money.

As we live in the wrong side of the world, the criticism of Asian ‘sheeple’ is constant by the selfish, egocentric, infantile western white men who have shown a clear incapacity to evolve beyond their individual scale of the fifth dimension into full working supœrganisms of history. We shall introduce then first a brief summary view of the papers on bio-history and the nature of the social organism of mankind.

Enough to say that the most perfect of those supœrganisms at present time is China NOT the USA because a supœrganism has a single head-party of people dedicated to serve its individuals, a financial, blood system ruled by the nervous legal system and also serving a welfare state, NOT the production of lethal memes for the mind and body (hate memes, audiovisual fiction software and weapons) as America has. The reasons of this difference is treated in other papers. We just state the facts here.

It has then been sorely obvious in this crisis that the only nation so far that has stopped the coronavirus attack with the proper measures has been China, because its people know they belong to a larger supœrganism for which they sacrifice their selfish actions and the government had the means as all nervous brains do, to finance the feverish attack to the virus after some initial errors proper of a single party nation. Its culture does care as all should for the 3rd informative age of life – the elderly and tried to save them; it invests heavily in health and welfare compare to US NOT in weapons and hate memes and crazy fictions and egocentricity and so it ended pandemics in a record two months. The consequences of this for the ‘forecasted’ change of power from America to China during the 2020s will now become evident as the disordered reaction of America will plunge and finally defeat the dollar as a world currency. Today the Dollar reached heights unseen in decades because it is the only top predator currency of the world but *if tomorrow China makes convertible the Yuan, America will suffer the exact fate of declining powers – the crash of the Mark of the 20s when the Dollar took it over.*

So we notice again that History has NOT change the route explained for decades in our articles, just because the predicted horses of apocalypse have changed their order, which normally is war->famine->pest (death all over). Now it seems pest came first.

Pandemics are thus the 3rd apocalypse horse for a causal reason. The black pest came after a surge of war due to the invention of gunpowder weapons; the Spanish flu in the last years of I world war, and this pandemic that has/will kill millions struck a weakened health-care system after the parasitic financial elite of America and Europe, hijacked our social systems to pay for the hate-memes of the Semite wars and speculate to trillion valuations in technological systems while destroying the welfare safety net. It has NOT caused but a fraction of deaths and has been controlled in the only other culture that resisted austericide – China and its closer cultural area. And for that reason we shall compare the different social systems, of what should have been an anecdote in a well-designed human supœrganism.

For those critical of capitalist China, obviously we said is the closer system to a proper human ideal society but NOT the ideal society as it has two clear errors – the fact that its head does NOT receive pain messages from its citizens (that is the members of the party are not judged as in true democracies), the fact that they have NOT evolved socialism into biological economics as they should, and the increasing degree of independence and power of its capitalist corporations. All this however could be easily reformed unlike the totally corrupted systems of the western world. So we close this introduction with a consideration of those necessary reforms:

Comparing Human Social Supœrganisms

And all this has to do with the sick, ill-designed systems of human social organisms. Accordingly there has been hardly any investment in health-care systems to prevent pandemics in the past decades, as all the money in a capitalist system is dedicated to the evolution and re=production of technology , not of human beings.

We live in a world in which man and its sicknesses are secondary, and hence when a pandemic broke, humans were unprepared and death kept mounting.

Thus the coronavirus crisis allow us to understand the no future of mankind under the present system and its possible reforms. As it has exposed an ill-designed system in which the needs of mankind are not met, because humans in this planet do not have resources for its welfare, nor the future is geared to make it better for our species.

It is then necessary to understand the nature of capitalist democracies to study the wrong responses to the coronavirus crisis since, the less important element of the crisis is the virus in itself, which as China has shown could be tamed within months and a low fatality rate, with the proper social systems and resources invested in human welfare. In that sense it is revealing to compare how Nature's suporganisms solve sicknesses that affect all its citizens cells with the way Asian countries, whose organic systems resemble closely those of nature have solved the epidemics: China gave their people masks (as its transmission is mouth-nose) making obligatory its use; multiplied by 12 its production, invested massively in hospitals and tests and confined the focus of the epidemic. So it did Korea and Japan, Singapore and Taiwan. Those are countries (see paper on Asian civilisations) that closer resemble the suporganisms of the Universe, regardless of their system, In all of them financial systems are properly regulated, from national banks in China to strict control in Korea.

But America and Europe, long lost to the ECB bank the right to issue money for its people, have a dysfunctional financial system that never produces money for its people and has suffered decades of austericide against its health-care systems, which in America is not even Universal - the concept of a Universal salary does NOT even exist, and yet that is how nature reproduces money. Mankind could easily establish it with ¥€\$ money a parity euro=dollar=100 ¥en global cryptocurrency handled to every human as a salary of blood-oxygen as organisms do to all cells, since money IS a language of information, NOT wealth per se, whose goal as all languages is to kick out the actions of production and consumption of all the citizens-cells of the system, as you do with your verbal language. The coronavirus crisis could have been an opportunity for mankind to redesign their parasitic financial cancerous systems and establish a global sustainable world based in a demand economy and welfare world. In the west it will lead to more of the same - a military police state as we are observing now in Italy and Spain, where people without expenditure on masks, tests and lacking hospitals are dying while the state merely imposes confinement and police vigilance.

America will follow a similar path, stigmatizing further its minorities that won't be tested or cured, and yet in the Democratic election the only candidate that proposes a proper health-care system is loosing to a corrupted lobbyist of financial corporations. Themes those explored in our papers on the 'Anglo-American, capitalist civilisation'.

In that regard, the solutions of the different suporganisms of history show the focus of each 'civilization':

- Asia has cured the pandemics using science and social order and solidarity. The 'mask is its symbol'.
- Europe has ignored the problem and closed borders with absolute in solidarity and lack of investments in health-care. Confinement and the military on the streets are its most noticeable measure.
- America has pumped up money to the system to maintain the stock-market prices.

What central bankers, who are private financiers who dedicate all the resources of the organism to make richer the 0.01% of owners of corporations did, was to waste the same MONEY to maintain the speculation of the market.

The same happened in America, where the FED gave 700 billion yesterday to the American stock exchange at 0 interest (the so-called quantitative easing of 700 billion for banks that will be invested mainly in stocks and lifted the market in conjunction with Trump's discourse to help companies NOT people).

In fact as we write Trump cancelled a project for respirators because it cost 1 billion 1/700th of what it gave to the market.

The same quantity needed to solve the problem from the human point of view of the 99%: 700 billion means exactly a universal salary of 2000 dollars to each American citizen-cell to stay home for a month.

Meanwhile the government puts under his rule all health companies and increases the feverish activity of an army doctors and health-care resources during that month to localize all infected people and solve the problem. Because the FED takes care of salaries legislators can forbid companies to fire anyone. It is equivalent to stop 'time=motion' of all citizen-cells of a sick organism for a month. It is what any organism does.

In an efficient supœrganism health procedures are simple. The blood-system=central bank should produce money for its cells NOT FOR a parasitic groups of financiers to increase the price of shares of the 0.01%.

Not a single penny of that money was invented for the U\$ people to cure the disease – all to lift stock prices...

UPDATE. As the crisis rage the ideal solutions of bio economics are 'naturally put forward' - confinement, universal salary but in patches and without a model.

In that regard 5D social sciences if it has been known to mankind could have helped in this crisis to change the paradigm of human social thought for the dangers of the future ahead, as technology will bring new existential problems to mankind. But as the crisis goes away the same sickness of human social supœrganisms will be implemented again, and the 'universal salary and health-care investments' of this crisis forgotten.

UPDATE. As the crisis rages the ideal solutions of bio economics are 'naturally put forward' - confinement, universal salary but in patches and without a model. It is notorious to notice that the best proposal comes from the original capitalist nation, UK: full payment of salaries to all; while U\$, too selfish will do too little too late

So what is new for the week? As the virus has an exponential rate growth near the E number of contagions, the fastest number of the Universe whose derivate rate of change for each unit of time equals the quantity itself - only seen in the decay of death and the atomic bomb, reason why I called it in my mathematical papers the number of death; things go faster than any administration can stop it.

Only if they had foreseen the expenditures as Asians did, and showed a social, organic solidarity Europe and America would have stopped. So today we have the excellent mappings on NYtimes which also leaves people

read for free, for a change, where the obvious map for the western world is the central one, the one for Asia the right side and the one for the 3rd world the left one:

So the 3rd world (no control measures) will be infected and the few elderly, as they have low expectations life will die, but that is 'pecata minuta' in a world ravaged by the other apocalypse's horses, war and famine. The western cultures (Europe and US) will suffer the central graph by June; which means in the coastal populated industrial regions as the one I live we will be infected massively over 50% by summer time and those of us

with conditions (in my case aging, heart, asthma, kidney and hypertension, all of them - salt is the brainy electricity, and Spanish ham, just bought my last one a delight that well deserves to die for :) will play two shots of a Russian roulette.

On the right the Asian case, where severe control measures do work as people are cells that suppress individual selfishness for the common good and the epidemic will be overcome.

On the economic arena the central graph means the debacle of America. As I wrote this morning on Marketwatch, copycatting my comments:

"if you want to make money this was obvious from January on, to play short and make huge profits, that's what Wall Street has been doing on all the accounts of the Americans... Now the game is to wait for the pick of the Dollar and play against it when the debacle hits. If you want to keep your life you should shut down America, the state should pay everybody a Universal salary for a month, 'stop time' as a body does when it is sick - all cells stop, and throw all the power of the country and resources to cure it... But that is not capitalism, so the country will go down as all other cycles of top predator nations have done once the dollar goes down since now China will power up the world. The day you can buy on the free market Yuan, the dollar will sink as Germany did when people moved to the dollar. This is the equivalent of I world war, one of the 3 apocalypse horses, on my models of bio-history I thought it would happen through war, but the Universe has its clever ways, evolutionary economics.wordpress.com so it was a black swan who did it.

Yes you can know the bottom, of the market but it is not the short ± 9 year cycles of my bioeconomic models (2000-2008-2018), this is the long $\pm 80-90$ years change of paradigm - top predator nation of the world, equivalent to the 29 crisis for UK-Germany that put America and the dollar above, change of paradigm, from US to China, end of dollar as supreme currency, a deja vu change we have talked about decades, it is a century change before from England to Germany, before... anyway, read evolutionary economics.wordpress.com the surprise is that it is caused by pandemics not as usual by war, though both are connected, the splendid little wars of the last decades help this to happen."

Alas, now the market sinks and no pumping dollars and quantitative easing stops it, so pundits are changing concept and applying or at least touting with the measures we considered in bio-economics as required to save the crisis: a universal salary and all people closed home while doctors cure it. But that is still small talk and the virus will go ahead as resistance of hardcore capitalist will stop the procedures.

We can imagine the arguments of hardcore republicans while the virus cripples the nations, doubling with the perfection of the e-number at exponential rate.

To illustrate those response as in the previous graph, we shall use the NYTimes journalism in the following description of the crisis till the epilogue on the future of those existential risks and post-coronavirus world, as it has given free access to its information during the pandemics. So we acknowledge his excellent journalist work, and comparison of the different solutions.

Nt. We just will 'quote' the article's author under the Fair Use law that allows the use of news material for non profit information purposes and cut down without re-phrasing the length of the articles. Obviously if the NY Times or the authors wish to remove the texts quoted from the paper we will do so.

The Animetal dominant side of America: The FMMI complex dominated by the old European memplex of the Go(l)d & Germ(an) cult(ure)s

The human side of America: All races ab=used by the Financial-Media Military/Industrial system of company-mothers of machines owned by stockrats

The Jap-Wasp system: the informative Jap stock-rat bull\$hits the German visual military, brainless I-centered ego-face of FMMI weimar America, both massacring colored non-biblical Americans and the world at large, through invisible anonymous company-mothers of machines-weapons and visual hate-media enacting the pecunia infinita belli Nervi of maximal profits and gold values as they consider humans inferior to their worshipped metal memes, substituting them in labor and war fields for robots, choking them off credit in Wall Street and dividing them to win with evil wood selfie, infotainment fantasies that inhibit all reaction.

USA as most cultures is divided 50-50% between humanist normal people guided by its biological drives of existence and animetal fundamentalist believers in the memes of go(l)d=greed, weapons=murder & violence and techno-utopias repressing its life memes from reproductive sex to eusocial love. And yet as in most places the animetal culture dominates and controls the FMMI system, abrogating itself the title of 'America' as its property. In America it is the biblical culture with judaism on top of finances and the white protestant 'wasp' in a second tier as manager of the corporations owned by its stock-ratic elite, which hides behind the cover of the Holocaust Industry that makes the biggest sin any criticism of those who rule, following Voltaire's dictum: 'if you want to know who rules you, ask yourself who 'you' cannot criticize'

THE RESPONSE OF THE WESTERN WORLD IN THE AGE OF JASP RULE.

TRUMPUPPET: 1ST NEO-COLONIALIST WAR CYCLE: AMERICA INC. VS. THE AMERICAN PEOPLE.

This said it is appropriate to complete the political cycle with an analysis of the last Mr. POTUS, Trumpuppet.

The owners of America in the digital age are companies of information machines that print money and audiovisual information have 'colonized' the mind of Americans. As those corporations are overwhelmingly owned by Judaism, whose first allegiance is to Israel, it follows then that American national policies will serve the goals of their financial elite, both in economics - ruled today by the casino game of inventing as many e-money numbers as possible - and in politics, ruled by the war on terror. So it is unavoidable in any article about America, to make a proper class analysis first and find 'where is the money' that serves the law or the policy considered.

Unfortunately with globalization, slowly with some resistance according to the degree of 'humanism' of each of those cultures and the respect for verbal, legal, human rights on them, the Anglo-American model is becoming the standard single model of placebo democracy in the world.

In this manner the millenarian prophecy of total world power proper of Judaism, based in the monopoly of go(l)d by a people-caste of banker priests that 'maintains people ignorant to remain obedient' of the ways in which 'money is the intelligent of god' (Calvin's sentences, of the brother civilization, which partners with Judaism in America and the Anglo-American world at large) and the use of money to buy mercenary armies, politicians, laws and people with salaries, IS NOW the essential form in which capitalist democracies run their populations elsewhere with variations of higher military or higher audiovisual sophistication. This system always puts together the mercenary military-police system, the audiovisual fictions and ego-trips of divide and win and become an idiot, and the issue of money to buy laws in a partnership that oppresses the 'third world' of humanist, simple people of all races, on the bottom of the hierarchical pyramid of capitalism, which is *the majority of mankind*, converted into a 'sheeple' that believes the political and economical correct newspeak of the elite, brutal in its actions,

hypocritically caring in his discourse - to avoid of course any harsh criticism. In the American colony though the elite is exclusively Jewish Calvinist, the same memetic religion with small variations notably in politics due to the Israeli need for the mercenary armies of America - which is the colonial factor in an otherwise happy partnership of common exploitation of mankind in its multiple cultures, all represented in America. But why Judaism is on top? It would be needed to tell the history of the go(l)d culture without hiding all their negative elements of exploitation of people with money. In any case as the oldest fundamentalist go(l)d culture, Judaism is to money what Hinduism is to war, with similar segregational laws studied in detail in the section of historic animetal religions. The difference is the astounding modern sophistication achieved by Judaism as go(l)d a language of information has very different qualities than iron, the vehicle of god in the religions of the fire of the smith. Death is entropic and does not evolve in its dogmas. Information is fast and invisible and evolves much more. So Judaism became capitalism and today in America specially most of those who rule only kept the memes of go(l)d, the absolute belief in private banking, money as the language of success in life - in the past as the tribute to the banker-priest that purified the believer in the temple. So what has evolved finally is the control of all the machines of information that print money and information in favor of capitalism and the chosen. And this is why we no longer call the elite of the capitalist world, am segullah - the people of the treasure as in the earlier ages of capitalism, but the FMAsters, the Financial-Media, Academia masters.

This happens because Judaism as a go(l)d religion specialized in the control of information machines since the times of the press, today has an almost absolute private monopoly on its digital owned industries of e-money and mass-media, complemented by the neocon think tank academia world into an state of neocolonialism, similar to the first age when the issue of money and information to the colonists was provided by British companies. However the realization of this state of affairs, where the Jewish nation colonizes mentally through evil wood, financially through Wall Street, and academically through the rewriting of history and its Orwellian newspeak (industry of the holocaust, political and economical correctness) is far more sophisticated and censored, because of the higher power of modern information machines, the massive amount of e-money printed by Wall Street (30 trillions and counting), the co-existence of Judaism within America perfectly 'camouflaged' within the social tissue, and the enormous dexterity of Judaism in the management of human capital through its stock-owned corporations after 3000 years of becoming the 'international financial and diplomatic networks' of the pecunia infinita belli Nervi cycle of the western world, whose tax farmers, slave traders and military purveyors created a superstructure over nations, with politicians, kings and aristocrats corrupted by their need of money which they couldn't manage or understand origin of the war and holocaust cycles of anti-Semitism - which happens when the population is tax-farmed without limits - and the final volkendammerung of anti-Semitism, which happens when those aristocratic-warriors were ruined. In America however the control is so intense and the devolution of people - divide and win - so extreme that it is unlikely there will be any real response to neocolonialism, of the sort the neocolonialism of Israel taking place in the Middle East, with either destroyed nations that opposed them - Libya, Iraq, Lebanon, Palestine, soon-to-be Iran or those politically corrupted by Judaism in finances and weapons with pro-western dictators on top - Egypt, Jordan, Arabian Peninsula is far more understood, as weapons control is energetic, self-evident while financial, informative networks are invisible. And so the FMAempire is the fundamental barrier for the alternative humanist model of EU and UNO to develop a truly advanced social scientific world which cares for mankind at larger and prevents our likely degradation and final extinction by the machines of the singularity age.

Now the project of Weimar America was going full sail – not coincidentally the wealthiest family in Israel owns the largest cruise company in the world – and suddenly it got docked by this little devil, the coronavirus. So the reaction of trumpuppet whose job was to conclude the Semite wars eliminating Iran from the map, help to expand the IDF business of apartheid robotized walls to Mexico, keep the quantitative easing flowing to the billionaire moguls of Wall Street, as an employee rescued from bankruptcy by Jasp people in NYC and given a celebrity status in one of its media-networks as a master of 'the deal', obviously was of paralysis. This was NOT the job I was Selected to do, we can imagine he complaining to his overseers. So he did nothing for months, but accuse the

usual suspects – China; this time was difficult to blame Iran or the Palestinians, the negroes at home of the Latino immigrants, but the Jasp people have enough panoply of enemies to draw from. So he did close the borders to China and that was the end of it. Then when the virus struck, the masters of the Universe bet that stocks would fall to keep making money shorting all companies down, unlike Europe that put limits to shorting, so profits came coming to Wall Street, even faster because volatility increases the up and down and hence the margins of shorting and jacking up prices.

It was also the perfect excuse for the FED to rescue the market with a few more trillions for big corporations. Even hedge funds had the chutzpah to apply with its lawyers to the middle business injection, while restaurants were left out. The trick here, always so cunning, was to make it complicated to ask for it, with many documents needed so only companies with good lawyers, and none better than Wall Street, could apply fast enough before the pot dried out.... Bloomberg would come into the defense, as hedge funds needed to pay 'secretaries'. Millions piled up in petitions to unemployment but that didn't matter to Wall Street. It never had it so good – another perfect excuse to get billions of manna for a new rescue.

So as unemployed hit the largest number since the depression, Wall Street had the best week since the opening salvo of II world war as billionaires claimed solitude in their yachts on the Caribbean. The reason is called 'printing money'=quantitative easing, bailouts etc, unconnected from the real economy. The financial economy is a thing apart. The FED prints money that banks take and put on the stock, ever since the Dotcom bubble, the performance of companies is accessory to the flow of money that doesn't get to the real people but circulates between FED bankers and 'stockrats', the aristocracy of capitalism which prints money in monopoly and have null social responsibility as aristocrats carried weapons in monopoly and couldn't be judged... So two societies live separated. Big corporations increasingly automated with robots, consuming machines owned by the 0.1% and the rest of mankind losing jobs to those robots, using hard currency that loses value as e-money keeps growing in the stock roulette... the question is what to do with the side of humanity, hard currency, poverty and infected people? It is

not needed. Companies, e-money, robots and stockrats see them as a nuisance. On top they have the bad taste of thinking money should also be printed for them, of thinking they should also work, of thinking they have rights to life...

Does this mean the American idol-ogical 'slave' of Capitalist, military 'democracy' is about to rebel and demand his rights to a demand economy based in welfare and debt-free money? Every turn of the wheel of torture that have choked further the Americans in the age of JASP power as the P changed from 'People to Parasitic Power' some have thought so, but the parallel emotional degradation into selfie fictions and fascist narratives have shown to the surprise even of the

FMAsters among which I lived for decades that man is indeed a blind cell of a superorganism that can be imprinted as a 'Tabula Rasa' by the Goebbels method of gullible lies with no limit. History proves that Jasp power always collapses as greed has no limit and anoxia kills too much *only when the financial system breaks, and for that to happen China must want to have a global international currency that will render useless the \$ printing machine in which Jasp power has floated for 50 years. But even then the 0.001% of stockrats will delist US information companies and open shop in Sydney as we already forecast 30 years ago (thought then it would happen in the 2008 future crisis). As Hannover Trust and the Warburg moved from Weimar Germany to US, leaving behind the scapegoats of the holocaust cycle of ∞ greed: the common Americans and the common JAP (Jewish-American people, without the 'Stockratic parasite power' addenda of its elite. The amount of pain though the American people must suffer, death, anoxia, poverty, warfare, pulp fiction, fascism, war before that final chapter opens up has not yet gone there. So far we are in the 'Best week' for the JASP with the SP of the century. And as in the case of the origin of the coronavirus, not a single historian in 50 years have even explained the physiological network control of the Jasp: officially US is still ruled by Wasp old boys. Magic! Or rather a far more sophisticated control of information with digital machines and a millenarian knowledge on how to control a society without direct rule, through the flows of money that buy and corrupt politicians and military systems. But this leaves the nation without effective rule, because those who rule don't acknowledge it and don't even want to rule – just make money and reduce the power*

Billionaire David Geffen
Posted A Tone-Deaf
Instagram Of His
Extremely Privileged...
BuzzFeed

of the state not to be accountable for it. So when a crisis as the coronavirus pandemic require effective rule and resources there is nothing of it.

THE DIFFERENT RESPONSES IN THE AGE OF WASP RULE.

In that regard, we can clearly differentiate 3 BLOCK responses to the coronavirus crisis according to the different rule in those countries. What we might call the 'Jasp Financial-Media Network empire' (Anglo-America, Europe and Hispano-America, in 3 degrees of lesser control), will have the worst possible response as the 99% matters little. This is an absolute truth in US\$, where Jasp 'segregational' at distance rule with 0 interest in engaging in anything but printing money with the tools of capitalism and create fictions to maintain the people clueless is paramount. Europe comes next since the ECB became no longer a bank of Issue, with the exception of those North-European countries that either have control of their currencies or like Germany take maximal profits of the ECB banking system and expanded its industries to dominate other countries. So the worst response will be that of the Latin European countries, which are dominated by human-contact tourist industries and as the system moves towards the 'metal-earth' with social distancing, robotic industries and lack of tourism, will keep sinking their economies. Then Hispano-America where the military response will do nothing to alleviate the pain and the corruption of capitalism has all the negative sides with none of the positive elements – no strong currencies, no health-care services, no real industries.

In the second layer of the response there will be the 3rd world countries of Africa and Islam, which cannot pay the health-care system but have tropical climates and young populations, so the sickness compared to other tragedies is relatively unimportant.

Among those countries Indonesia with its huge population and deluded pretension to be 'westernized' has no good prospects, as military measures of confinement in those dense nations. The true tragedy in them will be the increase of population control and loss of freedoms, specially for the Islamic minorities in nazionalist India.

Next will come the wealthier Islamic Countries in Asia where the response will be better than islamophobia expects, (with its labeling of all those nations as 'Islam= terrorism, see below) because of the zakat, the charity and interest for the members of society even in the dictatorships of the gulf. So we expect countries like Turkey, Iran and the Arabian nations to provide for their people and likely control pandemics despite its corruption and militarism, earlier than the developed capitalist countries of US and Europe.

Finally in Asia and Australasia which has somewhat adopted more humane European Social-Democratic and Asian organic approaches to health-care and don't have such huge military budgets in their peaceful isolation in the Pacific, we expect the best response, as the organic view of mankind still stands and the advanced intelligent use of science NOT of the military should make the crisis relatively mind.

Below we can see that present state of the 7 civilinations in the 'age of Jasp rule (blue color), where the Pandemics in a 'faked society' where those who rule are invisible and do not even want to rule, just parasite society with money and advance the metal-earth industries that make humans obsolete, will fare worse, while the opposite civilization where humans still feel part of organisms of History, Asia, will do better:

If humans were serious about a future with an alternative model to the non-way out of company-mothers evolving AI robots and weapons, instead of absurd tribal conflicts, mankind would search for a Unification of its 7 cultures, with the models of Uno and EU and the laws of systems sciences. Russian then would have been invited to join EU - IT IS 1/2 OF EUROPE! and make EU a global potency above US\$, able to bridge a social, scientific global world with China as the partner opening the path to a perfect world. For the same reason Israel+Palestine should have been

enclosed in EU, as the obvious solution to primitive religious memes, and apartheid stressing Haskala over halaka (enlightenment over religious war), as Israel IS Europe. The opposite has happened. The Jewish Financial-Media elite ruling the western empire got paranoid about a model of survival in which they had to relinquish their hate memes and

segregational behavior to mankind and embrace a future for ALL of us and just gear up the hate memes, war drill, pumping up their war against the poorest people of the world - Islam and then as Islam counter-attacked to get nuts about safety to ensure we shall repeat for profits the pecunia infinita belli Nervi cycles of wars and holocausts... SO RUSSIA did not join EU, was brutally broken into statelets, became the guinea pig for 'war propaganda' with the excuse of its old red army power and now is the preferred target of the yellow press campaigns of hate memes to ensure EU and MANKIND will never be the social, humanist civilization that could have saved all of us .

Indeed, after all this criticism to the JASP rule and its extreme modes of capitalism and indifference to the future of mankind, it is succeeding and likely will last for long because mankind ultimately believes in a technological civilization, worships machines more than humanity and willingly sacrifices itself for it.

The American case is obvious. Americans are 'perfect animetals', their religion is technology (NOT science: to know, which is what we do HERE, this must be clear, science is the knowledge of the laws of the organic Universe, technology is a religion of power, and that is what Americans worship, but they have NO idea of sciences).

So Sanders the Jewish socialist candidate which could have changed the American paradigm was voted out because the Americans believe in capitalism WIHTOUT UNDERSTANDING IT, or else they would NOT let themselves be exploited. They believe in networks without understanding them. They just believe in the Jewish-Protestant religion – a historic book of the bronze age, of a people who goes around killing and worshipping gold menorahs, without the slighteste reason, as they believe above all in EGOCY. And on those conditions, so removed from the real force of the Universe, social love and organicism, the chances they change the system and survival are zero, null, nill.

THE SOCIO-ECONOMICAL LECTURE: MOVING TOWARDS THE 'METAL-EARTH' DYSTOPIA.

Weimar America and their 'Palestinian' treatment of their population during the coronavirus crisis however is only a prime of things to come globally, as the Jasp 'rule at distance' through 'invisible flows' of financial networks, mass-media fiction indoctrinations and military drones raining from the sky, with total denial of their rule of the 3 physiological networks of the western world is now both global and globalized – imitated by all other nations, as the ideal of an EU-UNO humanist future fades away. So we observe the imitation of Weimar's methods in all countries, with the exception of those who are less influenced and controlled by it, Asian nations and Germany that have taken cared of their people in a human, scientific immunological form much better (with the exception of racist Japan and Singapore, where the alien Diamond Princess cruisers and workers were left to pasture to come back to hunt them).

Will America explode into a people's revolution or civil wars or neofascism? Unlikely. The Jasp-wasp coalition is too weakened by Trumpuppet own blunders to attempt it at this stage. The real danger is coming from China if it floats the Yuan and makes impossible the printing dollar machine but the Chinese Party is clueless about global power.

What mankind does not understand because it is so self-centered in its own ego is the evolution of this planet and the insignificant role she plays in the infinite scales of the fifth dimension. So we shall bring it closer for us to grasp the true problem of the coronavirus response which is not the people dying but the fact the state has been able to use advanced AI machines to control, incarcerate willingly and stop the life of all mankind, setting as precedent for the future world we anticipated for decades (the next graph is from the 1990s exhibit of art as a parody of the future Orwellian animetal farm). Imagine now down the road, 50 years, when the world is awash with robotic workers, as many of the jobs now will be replaced by 'safe, not infected robots', and humans are obsolete, expendable. The state has imposed now the right to keep mankind enclosed at home without crimes. And this is a precedent that once a state has taken from us our freedoms will be implemented for any safety measure excuses at will.

Mankind could be so easily eliminated as our delivery safe robots coming home to inject us a new vaccine for a new pandemic 50 years down the road. Mankind has accepted for a virus that only attacks the elderly and causes less death than road traffic and drugs among the young to be incarcerated, loose their jobs and NOT even been able to walk on the streets alone without any possibility of contagion in countries like Spain from where I write. This has started in the exact period of the 80 years cycles of war, and has substituted the event of war we anticipated for decades between China and US, which therefore is pushed to the next crisis, but with even more dreadly results. As we anticipated also in our web evolutionary economics, the Tokyo Olympic game as those of 1940 would be unlucky again and not celebrated as expected. Of the four horses of apocalypse thus pandemic as a new event easier

to accept by the Gullible population has had even more dreadfully outcome that a war, as people have not protested at all. They have shown to which degree the next graph of the animetal farm of the future has become truth. Stock markets never had it so well for speculators playing down and up the variations of prices; the pigs have received a meager salary enough to eat, the poor have been incarcerated and suffer still that state watched by drones. And this is only the beginning of a kind of down the gutter step by step diminution of human freedoms and rights that have come with the chip radiation, the fundamental event of present history, which is here to stay.

We remember again the ages of the chip radiation:

- The age of speculative money that distorted the social balance of classes with massive printing of e-money for the 0.02% and its COMPANY-MOTHERS, which reached absolute value, complementary to the loss of value of the currency of people during the 90s followed by...

- The age of the Semite wars, when the FMAsters of America found a new enemy after the collapse of the wall, building new walls for the poor civilizations of Latinos and Islam, now targeted as Terrorists in defense of apartheid Israel. It meant further inroads of the age of e-money, which spread, to Europe with the loss of national rights to print money, with the ECB not a bank of issue (meaning a bank that does not create oxygen for the population). So it was also the age of austericide of massive migration as now dictators from the 3rd world will send its money via Bloomberg to buy apples of the tree of science and Amazon inc. robots, no longer investing at home. This austericide killed welfare investments, weakened health-care systems increased defensive investments and so prepared the world for the age of singularity black swans that is the final 3rd age of chip when mankind becomes essentially obsolete as new working robots, police drones and a global state of incarceration at will sets upon for future events, while obviously the previous curtails of freedom and human and social financial rights stay at place, so one is put above the other, crashing further the future of humanity.

In the larger models of bio-history the 2020s according to the 80 years cycles of history of evolution of technology was a discontinuum age between the American age of 'minds of metal' (Chips=brains, eyes=cameras and ears=mobiles) and the age of AI robots, dominated by Asia and China.

In previous discontinuous ages there were always a war first and the other apocalypse horses, famine, pest and death came latter. So we modeled the future since the 90s when the first books of bio-history were self-published coming out of Columbia U., as the age of III world war when a system of control of populations by the new machines of the chip radiation established mankind as a cellular species controlled by networks, with an elite of stockrats on top ruled all by the company-mothers of MAGA. All this is happening but it has been a pest, not a war what established the new world order, with people isolated at home connected to the Metal-earth. Those 30 years old models reflected on the graph have been achieved by a 'black swan' and a different order:

Alas all has changed to remain the same.

In that regard, because humans have such a limited understanding of the organic Universe, and its zΔSt components, they are fast evolving as 'enzymen' and 'animetals' who catalyze the creation of the metal-earth in a world in which they are accessory to machines.

This trend will only increase with the coronavirus crisis as humanity becomes more separated from other humans and more controlled by the dystopian machines of the Internet age, we explain in other papers: they are communicating virtually, watched by drones that police them for their 'own good' and closed at home, afraid of thy neighbor. In the next graph from a book 30 years old the 'future' of the metal-earth according to the laws of bio-history, which I always thought would be implemented by a war state, but it has come through pandemics.

The graph below from an exhibit I did 30 years ago at Six Flags on the future (Brooklyn) shows the system as it is NOW exactly as predicted 30 years ago but instead of caused by a war, alas, a stroke of genius, by a virus - engineered or not... by crsper-9. Now the bottom of that pyramid will have a new 'stigma' - they are infected, not tested, do NOT come closer to our limousines: the future that the chip radiation and its technologies we forecast it will bring to mankind in the 2020s is now here. I thought it would have come through war, but alas Pandemic is even better, as people were wary of war.

The previous graph and its implications for a no future to mankind are explained in detail in all other papers so we won't focus on them. It is obvious though that the big winner of the coronavirus crisis will be internet and its companies. It won't be unless 5D social sciences becomes common in academia, which it has not for decades and with my low life expectancy it likely will disappear with me – so man will never be enlightened and return to what he does best – act as an enzyman evolving machines and as an animetal consuming them, while killing life in the

process. This is what the metal-earth's 3rd age equations told us as biohistorians unless we stopped their evolution and reform the system. We don't know if it was an engineered virus or a mutational one, but what we know is that GNA, one of the 3 risks of extinction of the Δ -1 scales of the Universe, along heavy dark matter made in accelerators and chip AI robots are here to stay, because capitalist 'worms' DO not control reproduction and evolution of technology. What they do is the ridiculous behavior of this crisis – let it happen and then impose 'animetal methods' of control of populations because they didn't have money for health-care and immunological social systems.

So they have advanced the no future of mankind in an unequal society ruled by company-mothers and its stockrats, with scarcity and anoxia of humanity, an the growing power of Internet companies, robots and machines over a weakened human, socially distanced, fearing the dangers of the XXI c. in a world with stronger metal species, where we will wane slowly. The way of life of Latin Europe has been wiped out, and so it will happen with tourism, love and life. We have paid a stern toll for the inefficiency of the system. What had to be done is obvious. To isolate only the groups and risks and protect the sick, with pre-conditions and the old, which were left to die in residences that were not even disinfected till the genocide of the 3rd age was all too obvious. It has been indeed a genocide in Europe of the ruling classes against the weaker people, a new world order that with all cynicism till public outcry oblige them to change gears, was promoted by Mr. Jonson and Mr. trump to save money to the market.

Indeed, as we speak, 10 million Americans have filled for unemployment and the food banks are depleted by 1 kilometer queues, but the market has gone up 25% retracing its lows, even cruise ships have rocketed 75% in 3 days, because trillions of \$ printed by the FED to rescue stock prices are available at 0 interest and in hand outs for speculators, to keep piling up billions, while the bottom of the pyramid suffers the burden of the crisis.

Latinos and black are $\frac{3}{4}$ of the infected in most regions, without health-care obliged to work on public distribution and low paid jobs in restaurants now fired, soon to be substituted by 'non-infected' robots. And now the advance of automation will be hidden by the new guilty of all our dystopian systems: the virus.

But, and this is the most alienating process of the Internet age, people have lost all sense of causality and are so easily imprinted by the new 'metal-communicators' networks that the only politico who tried to defend them, Mr. Sanders, a new Moses that was ready to expose the Nathans of Wall Street and give to Caesar, the people, what belongs to the people, the right to print money for them and save them from the collective and individual anoxia the virus and the economy who hijack their oxygen, provokes, has been defeated by the black voters who flocked to a corrupted Delaware Senator, ensuring they will die of the 4 apocalypse horses, as they have always done. Since every network has been at the job of trashing Mr. Sanders for a whole year.

Now picture the end of that dystopia as the century multiply 'friendly robots' that now will come to give us our parcels and will not 'infect' us, will work as labor and will not 'infect us', will be police and will watch us from drones, will be our AI mobiles and know where we are, will be our new doctors to 'inoculate us vaccines', will check our new DNI chips where we will be tagged as immune... As the century progresses since genetic editing has not been forbidden as we asked for with the other 3 'nano-species' that can destroy mankind, and so editing of new viruses now can be done privately – kits are sold in internet with Crispr-9 do-it-yourself hardware for DNA editing... there will be a fundamental problem to mankind, hundreds of millions of humans are expendable, a surplus of workers as robots displace us from labor and war fields – what to do with them? Further in the road, those robots as AI keeps evolving telepathically will acquire herd consciousness, will be the true citizens cared by their companies that have more power already than our free citizens. If in that not so far future, automated companies, cars with AI and solar skins, courtesy of global warming scare – another 'caring Orwellian newspeak that merely advances the evolution of free robots which no longer will need human charge of its solar skins to move' – robots of all kind, satellites and supercomputers come together as they are coming together into a single global superorganism, while all humans are perfectly localized with its GPS AI mobiles and as sheeple accept incarceration for their own goods, vaccination against the newly edited viruses, etc. our demise would be as simple as an army of health-care non-infected robotic nurses coming to our home to

‘vaccinate’ us against the new virus, and instead inoculating us a retarded effect poison. So to the usual mechanical dystopias, of grey-goo iron nano-bacteria, Nuclear war, black holes devouring earth, world war between China and US with armies of robots, we have in this pandemic found an even more Kafkian mode of human elimination and tagging: after the terrorist scare of the 2000s that converted the whole civilization of Islam in terrorists, after the 2010s global warming scare that accelerated the independence of robots with solar skins, it comes the 2020s pandemic scare that has made the population willingly accept to live during months in jail while the true methods to stop the pandemics – massive investment in health-care, masks, testing, respirators, hospitals and protection of the residences of the elderly has NOT been implemented. Because we shall not cease to repeat, politicians in capitalist democracies where austericide is the rule as the money is not printed as in organisms as a free salary in oxygen, were not ready to do something they don’ do. There is no confabulation theory – the Universe of biological systems is based in evolution and network. So we forecasted for 30 years the arrival of new technologies that can be guessed by the laws of evolution, so obviously we were going to create in the XX c. metal minds, chip brains, mobile ears, and TV-cameras and then use them to control people because that is what they can do. So politicians simply as heirs of military repressive elites have just found handy all those machines to control far more effectively people and as that is what they do – NOT to cure but to control people now everywhere in the world the virus is the excuse to establish a future dystopian world where AI machines will control us, first automatically for politicians, but at certain point of the century they simply will use that control to eliminate the surplus of humans, if some extreme racist groups do not do it first with the minorities, Palestinians, black, you name it.

The people have accepted dystopia and is kept at home... not even the young r=evolutionaries have rebelled and broke the quarantine, not a single newspaper allows to publish articles, not even in commentaries where the absolute curtail of the minimal freedoms of mankind has become the ‘new normal’. States have now done what they were designed to do in an ill-constructed social system: to show its repressive muscle, its power to control populations. And the people have become, what we forecast will be the XXI c. age of the ‘neo-Paleolithic’, visual ‘vidi, credo ergo sum’ people, no longer verbal rational, but obedient sheeple that ‘believe’ as citizens-cells living in a blind body that receives all the information from networks with a single ‘obedience’ message.

In that regard, what I feared most was exactly the sheeple reaction of what I have called the 2 final generations of mankind, the audiovisual, ¥-vidi, credo ergo sum ‘why generation’ that no longer see causality which in man is verbal, and only understand images and statistics, the ‘stupid scientist’ tool to guess the future; and the zero zombie generation of selfies that cannot longer interact directly and organize socially. The easiness with which this group that is not even at risk has been tamed to accept self-jail instead of taking to the streets understanding the nature of the repressive system and blow up the ‘cover up’ of a genocide based in the lack of a proper health-care driven, immunological defensive system with massive investments in the true elements required to save the population from infection, from masks to tests to respirators, demanding a reform of the system, shows how much the species has surrendered to the no-future and control of its ‘artificial metal-networks’ of collective imprinting, studied in detail in our papers on the different civilizations.

In that regard, this article from marketwatch resumes what we have been forecasting for decades. Isolation and loss of jobs didn’t come through war – it was Pandemics, but the bottom line is the technology was taking us here:

“One side effect of coronavirus: Robots will take our jobs at an even faster rate About 50 million jobs could be automated just in ‘essential’ industries *By Johannes Moenius*

American workers are locked into their homes, avoiding contact with anyone and everything touched by others. Social contacts and supply chains are disrupted by coronavirus and the COVID-19 illness it causes. In the workplace, there is a solution that addresses both problems simultaneously: new colleagues immune to pandemics and ready to replace American workers.

More robots.

While many bosses are discovering a new willingness to let at least some employees permanently work remotely, no one seems to be talking about this 800-pound gorilla that could be even more disruptive to jobs and could happen even faster than the already quite scary forecasts of only a few years ago.

Even more automation with ever-more-powerful robots and computers can help immunize the economy against future pandemics. This has implications in particular for two industry groups that have come into focus recently: essential industries, including large parts of the manufacturing supply chain, and industries with direct customer contact, also called high-touch industries. Note that these categories overlap: for example, about half of the high-touch industries are considered essential.

A widely cited 2017 study out of Oxford University provides data to calculate the share of jobs that can technically be automated in the next 15 years. Using this study, I calculated employment and wage risks for those industries. About 54% of all jobs in the U.S. are in industries classified as essential by the Department of Homeland Security, and 67% of these jobs — corresponding to 52% of wages — are susceptible to automation. So it is the low-wage jobs, like retail and warehouse jobs, that face the highest risk. In comparison, high-touch industries account for 46% of jobs (with some overlap with essential industries), and 57% of those jobs are vulnerable.

Recall what social distance requires: don't meet, don't touch. That particularly affects some high-touch industries like restaurants, retail and recreation. According to the same Oxford study, we should have the technology to automate 86% of restaurant jobs, 76% of retail jobs, and 59% of recreation jobs by 2035.

Two years ago, I argued that many of the jobs with direct customer contact would likely not be automated as customers value personal contact. However, COVID-19 is a human tragedy, and research has shown that those affected severely will permanently change their behavior. This means that certain customers at any time and almost all customers at certain times will value avoiding personal contact. That changes the mix of preferences and restaurant offers substantially.

As especially large companies consider rehiring, they will think twice whether a particular job can be done by a machine. Robots are getting more capable by the hour and cheaper by the minute. Cost advantages are going to be reinforced by risk perception. Advantage robot.

Here's what's coming

Some of the technology is already in advanced testing stages or readily available. Once Amazon.com AMZN, +5.29% starts licensing its Amazon Go technology, retail as we know it today will be limited to small stores — if they can survive.

Ford Motor's F, -4.28% delivery van prototype includes a robot that brings packages from the vehicle to the door - and targets a multi-billion dollar market. ABB ABB, -1.85% ABB, +1.01% has already installed more than 400,000 industrial robots — by some estimates replacing more than 2 million workers.

Robot baristas as well as Starbucks's SBUX, -3.84% self-service kiosks and intelligent coffee-stations may offer early substitution opportunities for those who want to avoid direct contact. This is not the end of the barista — but self-service stations will not only be used by germophobes, so once they move from office areas to public spaces, they will reduce regular barista-operated coffee shops.

What I expected to see in three to five years may now show up as quickly in fast-food restaurants as much as on factory floors.

The environment for automation has never been better: ultra-low interest rates, large sectors with low value-added per worker with repetitive tasks, exponential growth in patents involving artificial intelligence, low corporate tax rates, and venture capital firms that turned their interest toward process automation (namely robots and machines) all point toward accelerated use of automation technology. With about 50 million jobs in essential industries that could be automated and wages of more than \$1.5 trillion every year, the incentives to automate are huge.

Yes, capital spending will take a while to recover, but once it does, it will focus on technologies that protect essential industries, including supply chains, against the next virus attack. It also needs to satisfy the wants of those customers who prefer social-distanced service experiences. What I expected to see in three to five years may now show up as quickly in fast-food restaurants as much as on factory floors right when this recovery begins.

The coronavirus triggered demand and supply shocks. It will also accelerate and alter a technology shock that has been in the making for more than a decade. Firms that do not reduce vulnerability to future pandemics may find themselves at a disadvantage. The same applies to workers who need to upgrade their skill sets to match those new requirements. We need to train our workforce for the full range of 21st century skills: expertise in human-machine interactions like machine operation and maintenance; social competence and communication proficiency; creativity; critical thinking; and complex problem solving.

The workforce that companies need during and after the recovery will likely look quite different from the workforce they sent on the dole.”

THE US RESPONSE IN THE AGE OF NEOFASCISM AND JASP-WASP REPUBLICAN RULE.

The role of the FMAsters in the control of societies.

Back in the 90s when I was studying a master at Columbia U. and had already developed the cyclical models of history and moved with the NY elite of billionaires, a girlfriend, heir to one of the 50 largest Fortunes of the world, Hamptons parties, the social register of New York, the Atlantic club all that ... I still thought the FMAsters of America would want to survive the future instead of enacting once more for the sake of go(l)d the cycles of war and holocausts. So I used to speak about biohistory and bioeconomics as the organic science of mankind, and how they could predict the future, because both machines, its company-mothers human beings and societies were biological, evolutionary sciences ... Then one day a Jewish billionaire, told me:

“You know Luis, that's fine, science predicts the future, but you really know how the future is best predicted, when you create it and you can only create it with money’. I coined soon thereafter the new ‘inglish’ verb of ‘cre(dit)ating’, creating the future with credit, which is what the new American Jasp elite has been doing since the beginning of the Chip radiation. But as we enter the dystopian age of the coronavirus, when robotic workers will substitute us with the excuse we are safe, the problem arises of billions of humans without credit, without any chance to have a job, closed at home, as the new ‘citizens of the metal-earth’, robots are now ‘free to roam and work for us’. This people could be maintained with a Universal salary at home, in the transitional time till AI telepathic machines become aware of themselves as a species and liquidate us. This will be, given the sheeple behavior to this incarceration as easily as an army of robot nurses coming home to vaccinate us against a new virus, and just inject us a retarded poison. Certainly the blind middle class who so much believe in the system will give them a ‘chute’ of 220 Volts and place the arm of their children for inoculation.

But let us not advance too much in time. What I would like to bring here is a document I read a few years ago and found too strange to belief as I thought the 2020 cyclical crisis of History would be one of splendid little wars, the first of the Chinese vs. US series, not a pandemic.

This text was authorized by the Rockefeller think tank, one of the key institutions that for a century, since the times they erased Diego Rivera fabulous murals with Lenin on top, have been hard at influencing the wasp-jasp Republican-democratic capitalist elite of America in defining the future. For this elite I knew so well on my youth, till I simply rejected it – too much evil=antilive memes for a human being, a rising problem is how to control and dispose of billions of Human beings they don’t need for their technoutopian project, they don’t want to feed even with the small salary of the ‘pigs’ of the previous graph, and so they would like them NOT to exist or be quiet, out of sight, but cannot obviously easily eliminate from existence.

The Rockefeller document though was proposing a decade ago how to ‘create’ the necessary dystopia of the future, how to ‘incarcerate’ the sheeple. And as I, biohistory has not created the future of a mankind on top of a world made to our image and likeness, but that document is far more adjusted to what has happened than biohistory, it is easy to conclude that indeed, what that Hampton’s connoisseur told me is truth: the best way to guess the future is creating it...

People is made to believe that this global jail is temporary like after 9/11 they believed they would return to a world without air controls and televised terrorism, but each advance towards absolute human entropy is here to stay, and so when the ‘metalearth physiological networks of power’, its company-mothers, military politicos and financiers need again such ‘control’ they will bring out of their top hat again a redesigned global danger...

And that ‘prescient’ document was already talking about it:

GBN/Rockefeller Scenarios on Technology & Development

LOCK STEP :A world of tighter top-down government control and more authoritarian leadership, with limited innovation and growing citizen pushback

In 2012, the pandemic that the world had been anticipating for years finally hit. Unlike 2009's H1N1, this new influenza strain—originating from wild geese—was extremely virulent and deadly. Even the most pandemic-prepared nations were quickly overwhelmed when the virus streaked around the world, infecting nearly 20 percent of the global population and killing 8 million in just seven months, the majority of them healthy young adults. The pandemic also had a deadly effect on economies: international mobility of both people and goods screeched to a halt, debilitating industries like tourism and breaking global supply chains. Even locally, normally bustling shops sat empty for months, devoid of both employees and customers.

The pandemic blanketed the planet—though disproportionate numbers died in Africa, Southeast Asia, and Central America, where the virus spread like wild fire in the absence of social containment protocols. But even in developed countries, containment was a challenge. The United States's initial policy of “strongly discouraging” citizens from flying proved deadly in its leniency, accelerating the spread of the virus not just within the U.S. but across borders. However, a few countries did fare better—China in particular. The Chinese government's quick imposition and enforcement of mandatory quarantine for all citizens, as well as its instant and near-hermetic sealing off of all borders, saved millions of lives, stopping the spread of the virus far earlier than in other countries and enabling a swifter post-pandemic recovery.

China's government was not the only one that took extreme measures to protect its citizens from risk and exposure. During the pandemic, national leaders around the world flexed their authority and imposed airtight rules and restrictions, from the mandatory wearing of face masks to body-temperature checks at the entries to communal spaces like train stations and supermarkets. Even after the pandemic faded, this more authoritarian control and oversight of citizens and their activities stuck and even intensified. In order to protect themselves from the spread of increasingly global problems—from pandemics and transnational terrorism to environmental crises and rising poverty—leaders around the world took a firmer grip on power.

At first, the notion of a more controlled world gained wide acceptance and approval. Citizens willingly gave up some of their sovereignty—and their privacy—to more paternalistic states in exchange for greater safety and stability. Citizens were more tolerant, and even eager, for top-down direction and oversight, and national leaders had more latitude to impose order in the ways they saw fit. In developed countries, this heightened oversight took many forms: biometric IDs for all citizens, for example, and tighter regulation of key industries whose stability was deemed vital to national interests. In many developed countries, enforced cooperation with a suite of new regulations and agreements slowly but steadily restored both order and, importantly, economic growth.

Across the developing world, however, the story was different—and much more variable. Top-down authority took different forms in different countries, hinging largely on the capacity, caliber, and intentions of their leaders. In countries with strong and thoughtful leaders, citizens' overall economic status and quality of life increased. In India, for example, air quality drastically improved after 2016, when the government outlawed high-emitting vehicles. In Ghana, the introduction of ambitious government programs to improve basic infrastructure and ensure the availability of clean water for all her people led to a sharp decline in water-borne diseases. But more authoritarian leadership worked less well—and in some cases tragically—in countries run by irresponsible elites who used their increased power to pursue their own interests at the expense of their citizens.

There were other downsides, as the rise of virulent nationalism created new hazards: spectators at the 2018 World Cup, for example, wore bulletproof vests that sported a patch of their national flag. Strong technology regulations stifled innovation, kept costs high, and curbed adoption. In the developing world, access to “approved” technologies increased but beyond that remained limited: the locus of technology innovation was largely in the developed world, leaving many developing countries on the receiving end of technologies that others consider “best” for them. Some governments found this patronizing and refused to distribute computers

and other technologies that they scoffed at as “second hand.” Meanwhile, developing countries with more resources and better capacity began to innovate internally to fill these gaps on their own.

Meanwhile, in the developed world, the presence of so many top-down rules and norms greatly inhibited entrepreneurial activity. Scientists and innovators were often told by governments what research lines to pursue and were guided mostly toward projects that would make money (e.g., market-driven product development) or were “sure bets” (e.g., fundamental research), leaving more risky or innovative research areas largely untapped. Well-off countries and monopolistic companies with big research and development budgets still made significant advances, but the IP behind their breakthroughs remained locked behind strict national or corporate protection. Russia and India imposed stringent domestic standards for supervising and certifying encryption-related products and their suppliers—a category that in reality meant all IT innovations. The U.S. and EU struck back with retaliatory national standards, throwing a wrench in the development and diffusion of technology globally. Especially in the developing world, acting in one’s national self-interest often meant seeking practical alliances that t with those interests—whether it was gaining access to needed resources or banding together in order to achieve economic growth. In South America and Africa, regional and sub-regional alliances became more structured. Kenya doubled its trade with southern and eastern Africa, as new partnerships grew within the continent. China’s investment in Africa expanded as the bargain of new jobs and infrastructure in exchange for access to key minerals or food exports proved agreeable to many governments. Cross-border ties proliferated in the form of of social security aid. While the deployment of foreign security teams was welcomed in some of the most dire failed states, one-size- ts-all solutions yielded few positive results.

By 2025, people seemed to be growing weary of so much top-down control and letting leaders and authorities make choices for them.

Wherever national interests clashed with individual interests, there was conflict. Sporadic pushback became increasingly organized and coordinated, as disaffected youth and people who had seen their status and opportunities slip away—largely in developing countries—incited civil unrest. In 2026, protestors in Nigeria brought down the government, fed up with the entrenched cronyism and corruption. Even those who liked the greater stability and predictability of this world began to grow uncomfortable and constrained by so many tight rules and by the strictness of national boundaries. The feeling lingered that sooner or later, something would inevitably upset the neat order that the world’s governments had worked so hard to establish.

“Technology In Lock Step “

While there is no way of accurately predicting what the important technological advancements will be in the future, the scenario narratives point to areas where conditions may enable or accelerate the development of certain kinds of technologies. Thus for each scenario we offer a sense of the context for technological innovation, taking into consideration the pace, geography, and key creators. We also suggest a few technology trends and applications that could flourish in each scenario.

Technological innovation in “Lock Step” is largely driven by government and is focused on issues of national security and health and safety. Most technological improvements are created by and for developed countries, shaped by governments’ dual desire to control and to monitor their citizens. In states with poor governance, large-scale projects that fail to progress abound.

Technology trends and applications we might see:

- Scanners using advanced functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) technology become the norm at airports and other public areas to detect abnormal behavior that may indicate “antisocial intent.”
- In the aftermath of pandemic scares, smarter packaging for food and beverages is applied by big companies and producers in a business-to-business environment, and then adopted for individual products and consumers.
- New diagnostics are developed to detect communicable diseases. The application of health screening also changes; screening becomes a prerequisite for release from a hospital or prison, successfully slowing the spread of many diseases.
- Tele-presence technologies respond to the demand for less expensive, lower- bandwidth, sophisticated communications systems for populations whose travel is restricted.

- Driven by protectionism and national security concerns, nations create their own independent, regionally defined IT networks, mimicking China's firewalls. Governments have varying degrees of success in

policing internet traffic, but these efforts nevertheless fracture the "World Wide" Web.

LET THEM DIE.

CAPITALISM was invented in the UK>US Anglo-American civilization, as it is in its raw form: all for the 0.1% of the stockratic people on top of the social pyramid, issuing money for themselves, and nothing for the people, save soma to keep them silent. So the most callous view on the pandemics have been that of UK and US leadership: let the people get infected and die – as long as we don't spend a penny on them. We can even kill the old that spend so much in health-care and save even more in the future... till the market plummeted and so measures to hold the market NOT TO CURE or even test the people were undertaken.

Back in the 2000s when I was chair of Monetary systems at the International Systems Society I demanded an 'organic, understanding of money' as the blood of the economy, which should be handled to every human being in the form of a Universal Salary in ¥€\$ money (an International currency at fixed price, 1 \$ = 1 €=100 ¥=20 Yuans, delivered in mobile cryptocurrencies today to every citizen of the world). Because that is the true meaning of money not WEALTH per se but the language of information and reproduction of the economy, which a healthy organism is created and handled to every cell to kick out orders of production; so people NOT only speculators could invent money to survive creating a demand economy. Since all the money today is created *Not for welfare goods, people need to survive*, but to speculate in the market for the 0.2%. This has become blatantly clear in the coronavirus crisis, where only China has provided masks to every person, to avoid contagion (which is the key problem here as the virus spreads with the maximal speed at an exponential rate, 2.8, the number e), massively invested in hospitals and respirators and testing. Asians thus as 'organic members', citizens-cells who understand naturally bio-history have come out of it. Europe and America though has shown the brutality of the system, from the hardest, deranged UK-US capitalist center who does not test people, applies social Darwinism expecting 'people to suffer contagion' NOT to spend money on them, so the old die, or in America those without health-care are tagged as 'untouchables', and *the most* amazing of all, central bankers, JUST LOWERED interest rates and gave 700 billion not to the people but to the bankers to speculate and keep the prices of stocks floating.

This is a simple analysis of the structure of US financial system – conceded – but the whole system was designed in the earlier XX c. precisely to hide the ways in which money was produced, which became a complex opaque process (S.O.M.A. is the appropriate name for that system) in order to hide the essence of it: A public bank that acts as a private banker lends to other bankers who use it overwhelmingly to jack up prices of speculative stocks and lend to corporations NOT to produce money for the people.

So we need first to understand what a proper design of a supœrganism of History according to Nature's rule would look like:

THIS HARDCORE classic economists, whose ideological agenda to The service of private financing origin of The hidden governments of capitalists democracies 'believe' that money belongs to them and their corporations whom they serve, private banks, have NOT established an IMMEDIATE UNIVERSAL SALARY, as we preached for 20 years, so all those people isolated at home (because that is the only thing capitalist dictatorships do, take the military and control people, unlike Asians who have provided what was required, masks to avoid contagion, free testing and respirators, we shall keep repeating it).

In the graph, a capitalist democracy kills by anoxia and austericide as this crisis shows millions, so money is only handled to speculators to maintain prices. In this crisis what is immediately required is NOT to give money to private banks to sustain market prices but a Universal Salary to every citizen so it can buy masks, medicines and food while isolated at home. Nothing of this is done. Not even free testing is available. It is the hardcore murderous solution of UK: lets them get contagion and died, vs. the Asian, organic, 'true understanding' of societies as social supœrganisms which now *will prove the divergence between those who follow the laws of the Universe and create perfect social supœrganisms, the Asian culture, and those who follow social Darwinism and dog-eat-dog societies with the 0.1% of stockrats on top and the population murdered at lower cost with a virus that only serves to establish the big brother military control we thought it would come in the 2020s in an age of war, but pandemic is even more handy, as people are weary of war but obey the pandemic 'new approach' to militarization and null true health-care and welfare resources.*

So yesterday the FED lowered to 0 interests for banks and gave them near 1 trillion \$ to maintain the prices of the market but gave NONE to the people which the military soon will close as it has done in Southern Europe where nobody has masks and contagion will continue at exponential rate, with its population.

So all the predictions of bio-history are happening with a twist, the 2020s didn't bring a Matrix world by global war but global pandemic. And yet there was a solution as Asia has shown. Yesterday also I saw how the corrupt Biden was put at face value by a socialist Jewish 'Moses' saying the hard truths to their capitalist Nathans, but then all the media commentators attacked Moses because he pretends to establish what every civilized nation has - health care for free for its people. The concept is clear: the black and Latino minorities without health-care will add now to blatant racism against them, the 'stigma' of untouchables as carriers of the virus. But the amazing thing of this is

that the black people are NOT voting Sanders, the savior, but the corrupted Delaware Senator of the fiscal paradise tiny state... who tells them Italy with social security won't save its people of coronavirus - but does not mention Korea, Japan, Germany, China, Canada... Only the one country where as in this one I am writing from now, Barcelona Spain, people could NOT understand the need for stopping their social intercourse, their dolce fare niente...

MILITARY & FINANCIAL RESPONSE OF WESTERN CAPITALIST SOCIETIES:BY LACK OF HEALTH-CARE MEANS DO NOTHING as we have no money for health-care and do not care for those who need it,

THE FIRST ACTION of those 3 civilinations ruled by the modern JASP view of capitalism as a system to invent money and care nothing for the population was to ignore systematically the issue because obviously this had nothing to do with our goals. Do nothing was thus the common response from Spain to US.

Asia as today is the only hope for a reform of mankind, because obviously US and now Europe since the take over of Germany and the ECB bank over its political, legal and financial systems are just systems of evolution of machines, whose only way

22 January

Daily cases 555 | Total cases 555
New cases in Thailand, Japan, China, South Korea, Taiwan and US

26 January

Daily cases 684 | Total cases 2,118
New cases in Australia and Canada

31 January

Daily cases 1,693 | Total cases 9,927
New cases in Italy, Sweden, Russia and United Kingdom

19 February

Daily cases 503 | Total cases 75,639
New cases in Iran

26 February

Daily cases 982 | Total cases 81,395
New cases in Pakistan, Brazil, Georgia, Greece, North Macedonia, Norway and Romania

3 March

Daily cases 2,534 | Total cases 92,840
New cases in Argentina, Chile, Jordan and Ukraine

9 March

Daily cases 3,766 | Total cases 113,561
New cases in Albania, Cyprus and Brunei

13 March

Daily cases 16,850 | Total cases 145,193
New cases in Kazakhstan, Ethiopia, Sudan, Guinea, Kenya and Antigua and Barb.

to solve their crisis has been to reproduce more money for the stock market, to ignore the crisis in terms of its rational, scientific medical cures for lack of money for welfare, after decades of German promoted austericide and the investments in the Semite wars of their financial-media elite in America, against any investment in the American people. Yet because the capitalist equation: Max. profits = max. weapons + Max. audiovisual software, has developed a foreign, lethal system of hate memes through audiovisual software that have rendered purple rain, the brain of the European and American fictional people, there is no realization. The most amazing happening here in Spain, was the complete lack of 'awareness' of the arrival of the pandemics that had decimated China and Italy. All what the natives in my town cared was about the 'remontada' of the 4-1 champions league soma match against Atalanta from Bergamo.

I was argued with my neighbors that the match had to be forbidden and not a single Italian had to come here because Bergamo was the epicenter of the epicenter of Italian Lombardy's outbreak and Las Fallas had to be postponed, and people thought I was mad. "Fiesta mattered' more and indeed, while in Bergamo the newspaper became just a long series of pages of deceased, here planes came buttressed with coronavirus to wonder the streets and see the match on TV, where as expected the Valencia couldn't overcome the 4 to 1.. Hundreds of people would die out of that virtual reality, as it will happen to mankind at large as we enter the age of virtual reality, with people closed at home against an external planet with ever more dangerous technological systems on the loose.

Two months were wasted both in Europe and the US since the pandemics stroke in China, because obviously this was a Chinese virus, our politicos were occupied in their usual business of lobbyism, cheating people wit nationalist themes and catering to the industries of maximal profits – giving hand outs to banks, buying weapons of mass destruction and obeying the cues of the mass-media industry – the true free citizen companies they have to please, as nobody can vote their punishments after tenure.

The capitalist solution.: an injection of 700 billions for Speculation

The most shameful action ever witnessed in a national emergency thus took place yesterday as the FED injected 700 billions to the market for speculators to inject in timely fashion on the stock to hold prices, WHILE THAT QUANTITY OF MONEY WOULD HAVE ended the virus globally, and given as a Universal salary avoided the collapse of the economy. But that would be KEYNESIAN ECONOMICS and that is not tolerated. In a parasitic financial economy only the 0.01% matter, the system serves the 'leisure class' of Veblen - the best American economist - on top of the pyramid of capitalism.

How this was done is shown in the graph of the market yesterday:

To start the operation on Friday the emergency state is touted by Trump. We read between lines and there is only lies about the virus and a massive help to the biggest corporations The market shoots and speculators bet on it. I was astonished by that growth. It was irrational, something else must be happening. And indeed, on Sunday, the fed gives at 0 interest 700 billion \$ to the speculators of the market with quantitative easing. but nothing to the

people, the fed is not as in a healthy suproorganism of history the system of injection of healthy money to every human as in an organism money is given to every cells. What the FED should have done is inject those 700 billion to the Americans that soon will be enclosed at home as a pay leave Universal salary

This is the solution to the human problem The money is exactly 2000 dollars per capita, for a month. So that is exactly what the Americans need to defeat the virus. To be enclosed for a month with a pay of 2000 \$ not to be a burden to their companies Paid By The Fed, That Is The Solution Of Bioeconomics.

So companies don't fire people, and people stay home and the health ministry stops the pandemic.

But what the fed did? give that money to the speculators to hold the value of the stocks of the 0.1%

Still the market didn't react. . The graph is for apple the trillion \$ company that we explain below as the paradigm of what is valuable and expendable in capitalists democracies...

So they stop it for 15 minutes and started the massive injection (green candles after the dotted line of the week end) and this week they will inject the 700 billions the Americans need to survive for the 0.1 of billionaires not to keep loosing money

What central bankers, who are private financiers who dedicate all the resources of the organism to make richer the 0.01% of owners of corporations did, was to waste the same MONEY to maintain the speculation of the market. The same happened in America, where the FED gave 700 billion yesterday to the American stock exchange at 0 interest (the so-called quantitative easing of 700 billion for banks that will be invested mainly in stocks and lifted the market in conjunction with Trump's discourse to help companies NOT people).

It was the same quantity needed to solve the problem from the human point of view of the 99%: 700 billion means exactly a universal salary of 2000 dollars to each American citizen-cell to stay home for a month.

Meanwhile the government puts under his rule all health companies and increases the feverish activity of an army doctors and health-care resources during that month to localize all infected people and solve the problem. Because the FED takes care of salaries legislators can forbid companies to fire anyone. It is equivalent to stop 'time=motion' of all the citizen-cells of a sick organism for a month. It is what any organism does.

In an efficient sup^organism health procedures are simple. The blood-system=central bank should produce money for its cells NOT FOR a parasitic groups of financiers to increase the price of shares of the 0.01%.

Not a single penny of that money was invented yesterday for the people of America, to cure the disease – all to lift the stock prices in the market as it will keep trying to do months ahead.

NO MONEY FOR HEALTH-CARE

From NYTIMES; Nicholas Kulish: Thirteen years ago, a group of U.S. public health officials came up with a plan to address what they regarded as one of the medical system's crucial vulnerabilities: a shortage of ventilators.

The breathing-assistance machines tended to be bulky, expensive and limited in number. The plan was to build a large fleet of inexpensive portable devices to deploy in a flu pandemic or another crisis.

Money was budgeted. A federal contract was signed. Work got underway.

And then things suddenly veered off course. A multibillion-dollar maker of medical devices bought the small California company that had been hired to design the new machines. The project ultimately produced zero ventilators.

That failure delayed the development of an affordable ventilator by at least half a decade, depriving hospitals, states and the federal government of the ability to stock up. The federal government started over with another company in 2014, whose ventilator was approved only last year and whose products have not yet been delivered. Today, with the coronavirus ravaging America's health care system, the nation's emergency-response stockpile is still waiting on its first shipment. The scarcity of ventilators has become an emergency, forcing doctors to make life-or-death decisions about who gets to breathe and who does not. The stalled efforts to create a new class of cheap, easy-to-use ventilators highlight the perils of outsourcing projects with critical public-health implications to private companies; their focus on maximizing profits is not always consistent with the government's goal of preparing for a future crisis.

"We definitely saw the problem," said Dr. Thomas R. Frieden, who ran the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention from 2009 to 2017. "We innovated to try and get a solution. We made really good progress, but it doesn't appear to have resulted in the volume that we needed."

The project — code-named Aura — came in the wake of a parade of near-miss pandemics: SARS, MERS, bird flu and swine flu.

Federal officials decided to re-evaluate their strategy for the next public health emergency. They considered vaccines, antiviral drugs, protective gear and ventilators, the last line of defense for patients suffering respiratory failure. The federal government's Strategic National Stockpile had full-service ventilators in its warehouses, but not in the quantities that would be needed to combat a major pandemic.

LOBBYISM & CORONAVIRUS BUSINESS

WASHINGTON — The federal government is open for coronavirus business, and the scramble to get some of it is on. A South Carolina company has hired a lobbyist close to President Trump to try to win regulatory approval to sell a misting spray to kill coronavirus on airplanes. A Manhattan company is seeking money from the \$2 trillion stimulus package for its quick-change recyclable hospital curtains. Two prominent and well-connected Republican fund-raisers have linked up with competing businesses, both claiming to be able to acquire coveted equipment like coronavirus test kits and masks.

Across the country, companies see a chance to cash in, do some good for the country or both, making virus outbreak response one of the few thriving sectors of the economy. And because so much of the business runs through Washington, the rush has created new opportunities for those who can offer access, influence and expertise in navigating bureaucratic hurdles and securing chunks of the relief package Mr. Trump signed into law on Friday.

The boomlet has left the federal agencies responsible for regulating cleaning supplies, medical devices and medicines working overtime on requests to certify products for use in coronavirus response — and to clamp down on fraud.

The Food and Drug Administration has been processing a surge in applications for coronavirus vaccine and treatment trials. But the agency also has spent considerable time and resources fighting what it calls "fraudulent Covid-19 products."

Likewise, the Environmental Protection Agency has been cracking down on unregistered products claiming to kill coronavirus, and processing requests to list various disinfectants as approved to kill the virus on surfaces.

ON THE HELP OF THE MILITARY. 'IT'S A JOKE' – EUROPE & UŞA

The military that has supplanted the real 'immune, defensive system' of a well-behaved society, the people of the health-care system, whose real job is to kill people not to save them, has been as usual in 'animetal cultures' given a star-role on this crisis at two levels:

- What they really know how to do but was not necessary with the proper approach to the crisis: to jail people and detain them, when they come out of the curfews imposed by lack of prevention and resources to pay for tests, masks and cures. So they are doing a 'show' everywhere, and giving higher power to the different authoritarian politicians of the world. In the graph, two images of Spain, one of the 'Plaza del Sol' center of Madrid buttressed, with troops; the other from the daily 'situation', which instead of being handled by doctors and only doctors, somehow got 'sneaked' 2 military, one of which tell us of the 'internet surveillance' and to not believe in 'fake news' like drinking bleach to kill the virus. I thought the first day it was a joke but it is surrealism at its best. The second one, tell us the detainees who are not solidarious with the curfew. Obviously what they don't have is real news about why health-care 'kamikaze' doctors have to do EPIs with garbage bags. In the front, our 'health minister', which is a philosopher turned politico. No further comment is needed. Obviously the military are normal people; it is the whole concept of nations and 'weapons' worship what is the aberration of History.

The American case is worse. If in northern Europe they bought toilet paper, in Southern Europe wine, in America, the people in panic mood bought... weapons... the single biggest sale day in history. Alas, the dog-eat-dog animetal society by excellence also tried to flaunter the military as the 'saviors' and so it sent two hospital-boats and told us it had 5 million

respirators for bio-terrorist warfare. But it turned out it did not released them because 'they were too complex' and had to keep them for the possible paranoid warfare attacks of the future. While from the NY Times we extract this comment on the Boats:

The 1,000-Bed Comfort Was Supposed to Aid New York. It Has 20 Patients. **Michael Schwirtz**

"It's a joke," said a top hospital executive, whose facilities are packed with coronavirus patients.

Such were the expectations for the Navy hospital ship U.S.N.S. Comfort that week, throngs of people, momentarily forgetting the strictures of social distancing, crammed together along Manhattan's west side to catch a glimpse. On Thursday, though, the huge white vessel, which officials had promised would bring succor to a city on the brink, sat mostly empty, infuriating executives at local hospitals. The ship's 1,000 beds are largely unused, its 1,200-member crew mostly idle.

Only 20 patients had been transferred to the ship, officials said, even as New York hospitals struggled to find space for the thousands infected with the coronavirus. Another Navy hospital ship, the U.S.N.S. Mercy, docked in Los Angeles, has had a total of 15 patients, officials said.

"If I'm blunt about it, it's a joke," said Michael Dowling, the head of Northwell Health, New York's largest hospital system. "Everyone can say, 'Thank you for putting up these wonderful places and opening up these cavernous halls.' But we're in a crisis here, we're in a battlefield."

The Comfort was sent to New York to relieve pressure on city hospitals by treating people with ailments other than Covid-19, the illness caused by the coronavirus.

President Trump left a nine-day sequester in the White House last week to travel to Norfolk, Va., to personally see off the ship as it set sail for New York, saying it would play a "critical role." The ship's arrival on Monday was cheered as one of the few bright moments in a grim time for the city.

But the reality has been different. A tangle of military protocols and bureaucratic hurdles has prevented the Comfort from accepting many patients at all.

On top of its strict rules preventing people infected with the virus from coming on board, the Navy is also refusing to treat a host of other conditions. Guidelines disseminated to hospitals included a list of 49 medical conditions that would exclude a patient from admittance to the ship.

Ambulances cannot take patients directly to the Comfort; they must first deliver patients to a city hospital for a lengthy evaluation — including a test for the virus — and then pick them up again for transport to the ship.

At a morning briefing on Thursday, officials said three patients had been moved to the Comfort. After The New York Times published an article with that number, Elizabeth Baker, a spokeswoman for the Navy, said the number had increased to 20 by late in the day. "We're bringing them on as fast as we can bring them on," she said.

Hospital leaders said they were exasperated by the delays.

Mr. Dowling said he has had to tear his hospitals apart, retrofitting any unused space, including lobbies and conference rooms, into hospital wards. His facilities now house 2,800 so-called Covid patients, up from 100 on March 20, he said. About 25 percent of those are in serious conditions in intensive care units.

Across the city, hospitals are overrun. Patients have died in hallways before they could even be hooked up to one of the few available ventilators in New York. Doctors and nurses, who had to use the same protective gear again and again, are getting sick. So many people are dying that the city is running low on body bags.

Meanwhile, the commander of an airplane carrier who demanded help to stop the spread of the virus among its crew, was taken out of command for 'leaking' that information to the public...

What the military did well of courser was to patrol people, which is what should not have happened. Fact is there should NOT be exceptionality states that render democracies wet papers, and allow the promotion of war for profits and so, when a pandemic strikes ONLY immunological measures are required.

isolation should have taken place only for risky groups which in fact were left to pasture, as who cares? for the elderly, they cost too much money to cure. The people with more risk – in this case people with age or preconditions like this writer, would immediately receive special protection, meaning added health- care, isolation

if required from the pandemic focus, along the absolute control testing and isolation of the real focus of the pandemics in its earlier stages.

This would have meant in Spain or US the two top infected countries as today, where the knowledge of the pandemics was clear and warned by their excellent top pandemic experts (not in power obviously as politicians chose mediocre people to obey their 'plans'), as earlier as January. US because it was observing closely its rival China, Spain because it is closely connected with its sister Italian South-Mediterranean culture from where infected people were coming.

At that point an immediate cut-off from the source of the pandemic was required. US did it partially as 40,000 people kept traveling from China. Spain did not even try, maintaining the virtual reality that nothing was happening, fiesta was coming and tourists were welcomed, as we have explained. Still the countries could have piled up masks, medicines, testing, and ramp up local production because biological radiations are completely predictable and China had release the key information on the pandemics. They did nothing because their systems do not 'serve' welfare' but warfare. America spent 1/2 of the budget on weapons to serve the global war against Islam promoted by its Financial-Media-Academia elite to fight for its other 'apartheid' nation, while of course under the anti-quantum paradox media denies this is the true meaning of the war on terror, along the profits of its main 3 industries. A measure of what would be done next was clear, and we shall elaborate later: a massive bail out of 700 billion dollars for the stock market not to plunge further and 2 trillions given now where again the biggest bulk sum is NOT for the welfare system but to be hand out 'discretionally' to big corporations (1/4th of the pie), which do have enough money of their own invented in markets and can reproduce with no limit must by issuing and diluting capital share as much cash as they want. So the purpose obviously is to keep the prices and wealth of the 0.01% that owns them – a waste of money that should go to medical supplies and further Universal salaries – but much better should be a global agreement on a Universal salary from now onwards with a reform of the financial casino system of global power established in the aftermath of the fall of the wall.

It has to be noticed that this is a bipartisan agreement, and it hurts the eye to see that the most important part to

Distribution of CARES Act Budget by Category

combat the crisis, the top 100 billion to hospitals is just 1/20th of the hand out, while the hand outs to big corporations are discretionary to the republican lobbies that will ask for them. Only 'cruise' companies that are incorporated outside America not to pay the meager corporate taxes are out of it. Casinos doubled price in stocks after the news. And the market had the biggest run up in history since the declaration of II world war that ensured canons and no butter will increase its profits.

Back to the solutions to the crisis: an ideal society thus would have implemented immediately the restriction of the virus with obligatory masks for all the population as the virus has a 1000th bigger charge on the mouth-nose system that the flu. But because there was no money, no supplies, no production of masks in the west, this was vehemently denied as needed by both the CDC, European health-care agencies and the WHO, just an organization to the service of western politicians. Now as production ramps up, the measure is being reversed... Lie as long as you need it, by the Goebbels method 'if you repeat a lie many times people will believe it'.

But the most striking genocidal action has been against the elderly whose pensions are meager, and live in community houses, without medical care, and were totally abandoned

when they were the people at risk who had to be isolated and protected from the inception of the crisis.

This has been a murder on the making, brutally assessed by right politicians as part of the social Darwinism capitalism has always sponsored, which cynical newspeaks of caring have preached. SO the bluntest people, Cummings, the brain behind Mr. Johnsons' UK Tory party, said that the economy should go on, and old people would die. This was also the message of Bolsonaro in Brazil and earlier Trump: capitalism must continue, the poor elder must die, and that will (read between letters) diminish our costs of Medicare. The 'experts' in damned lies and statistics then 'sweetened' the pill with the concept of herd immunity. And the sheeple who is blind to true information as it receives it all from mass-media outlets, in a capitalist physiological not-human system of control, agreed. Herd immunity meant that the young would be infected, the old would die and life would continue.

Our life didn't matter and when I tried to comment given my 'closure' from academia on newspapers in UK and Spain about the real causes of that strategy I was either erased or savaged by the herd, in a reminiscence of the massive backing to CERN's activists that will go ahead with the Δ -3 production of strangelets and black holes, but convinced mankind that was OK to explore the false theory of the big-bang in an immortal organic Universe, we explain in our papers on 5D physical and 5D Universe. The harder they fall.

Next some text sfrom NYTimes analysis of this phase of testing, considering a comparison of the 3 reactions to the crisis, we copycat from NY times that offers now for free its information on the crisis – hence we suppose they don't mind its use to inform people, the way they have dealt with the first and obvious medical step of the crisis – testing the sick:

***Can't Get Tested? Maybe You're in the Wrong Country* By Matt Apuzzo**

Scientists around the world were waiting at their computers in early January when China released the coronavirus genetic code, the blueprint for creating tests and vaccines. Within days, labs from Hong Kong to Berlin had designed tests and shared their research with others.

Within about two weeks, Australia had its own tests, and even citizens in the most far-flung regions of the country could be tested. Laboratories in Singapore and South Korea ramped up test kit production and ordered extra supplies. That quick work allowed them to test hundreds of thousands of people, isolate the sick and — so far, at least — contain the spread of the disease.

By contrast, anxious citizens in the United States and many parts of Western Europe have endured byzantine delays, or have been denied testing altogether. As the coronavirus pandemic shuts down world capitals and paralyzes entire economies, political leaders are rushing to make testing more widely available.

But experts say that the decisive moment, when aggressive testing might have allowed officials to stay ahead of the disease, passed more than a month ago. It was not a question of science. Researchers say a viral test is relatively easy to develop. Rather, scientists say, the chasm between not reflects politics, public health strategies and, in some cases, blunders.

The world may be paying for those missteps right now. Testing is central to the effort to fight the spread of the virus. Countries that test widely can isolate infected people and prevent or slow new infections. Without early and widespread testing, health officials and policymakers will be flying blind, epidemiologists say.

"Your cannot fight a fire blindfolded," said Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus, W.H.O.'s director general. "And we cannot stop this pandemic if we don't know who is infected."

But testing has been inconsistent in what has been a patchwork response to the epidemic worldwide.

Some countries, like France, did not have a strategy that centered on testing to map the advance of the virus.

Testing in Italy has been plagued by political squabbles. The United Kingdom developed tests but decided not to use them widely, as Singapore and South Korea had done. Other countries were caught off guard by shortages of testing chemicals.

As the virus reached into the United States in late January, President Trump and his administration spent weeks downplaying the potential for an outbreak. The Centers for Disease Control opted to develop its own test rather than rely on private laboratories or the World Health Organization.

The outbreak quickly outpaced Mr. Trump's predictions, and the C.D.C.'s test kits turned out to be flawed, leaving the United States far behind other parts of the world — both technically and politically. In that same period, Singapore was setting up health screenings at airports, issuing work-from-home guidelines and releasing plans to monitor travelers returning from abroad. Independent labs in Korea were rushing their tests out the door.

"They were ready, and they just churned out the kits," said Dr. Jerome Kim, of the International Vaccine Institute in Seoul.

Today, the epicenter of the outbreak is Europe and experts say the wave is only starting to hit the United States. Faced with a growing number of cases and limited test kits, many countries have tightened restrictions on who gets tested. In Germany, where the first approved test was developed, only doctors can prescribe one. In France and Belgium, only severely sick patients get tested.

In Britain, as in many other countries, the virus is circulating so quickly that it is no longer possible to test people and investigate whom they may have infected, said David McCoy, a public health professor at Queen Mary University in London. Nearly 100 people have died from the virus there. Testing is still valuable in helping scientists understand the epidemiology of the disease, he said.

"The window of opportunity to contain the epidemic has now shut," Mr. McCoy said.

'This Could Be a Problem' By [Hannah Beech](#)

From the beginning, some countries showed greater urgency than others and were more nimble in their response. Australia, Korea and Singapore turned to networks of public and private laboratories to develop tests. On Feb. 4, the South Korean government granted [fast-track approval](#) for a company's coronavirus test and began shipping kits. A second company was approved a week later. Two more soon followed.

Australian labs designed a generic test in early January, then refined it after receiving the genome. "We were anticipating early on that we could see cases, that this could be a problem," said Dr. Jen Kok, a government virologist in New South Wales, Australia, a region where more than 33,000 people have been tested so far.

The United States and Britain favored a centralized approach. Britain initially assigned a single lab in north London to perform the tests but, a month later, began allowing other labs to do the same.

The C.D.C. had to reverse course, too. After its homegrown [test proved faulty](#), it cost the country valuable time. The Trump administration then had to [change tactics](#), urging outside labs and manufacturers to help make a million tests available.

Labs that moved quickly had an advantage. They purchased extra testing products, known as reagents that extract viral RNA from nose or throat swab samples. Those reagents are now in short supply.

"It's the way we do things here," said Dr. David Speers, the top microbiologist at PathWest Laboratory Medicine, the government laboratory in Western Australia. "We always try to plan ahead."

Technical speed and laboratory organization, though, do not explain everything. The availability of testing — at least in some countries — also reflects policy.

When Australia identified its first coronavirus patient in late January, political leaders made clear that testing would be widespread. "We're testing people," Dr. Kerry Chant, the top public health official in New South Wales, said on Jan. 30. "We're asking people to come forward, and I want to acknowledge the fact that we have had so many people come forward for testing."

Even before the virus began spreading in Singapore, the prime minister, Lee Hsien Loong reminded the public about the 2003 SARS outbreak and said he planned to overreact to the coronavirus. "We have built up our institutions, our plans, our facilities, our stockpiles, our people, our training," he said on Jan. 31. "Because we knew that one day something like that would happen again."

South Korea opened nearly 600 testing clinics, including dozens of drive-through stations. More than 250,000 people have been tested — far more than any other country that has released data.

The country has largely contained its outbreak to the southeast city of Daegu. Most cases are linked to a cluster around the Shincheonji Church of Jesus.

“Korea’s approach was: Test everybody,” Dr. Kim said. “Anybody who needs a test should get tested.”

The United States, along with countries in Western Europe, chose a different strategy and tone. While Singapore warned that infections were certain to increase, Mr. Trump predicted it would disappear within weeks.

In late January, French officials were hesitant to activate emergency protocols because they did not believe that the epidemic was as serious as the 2009 H1N1 outbreak.

“We have three cases in France and they are not that severe,” Dr. Patrick Pelloux, of the country’s emergency medical services, said Jan. 25. “It’s an epidemic that is under control.”

France says that it is able to test 2,500 cases daily, and health officials said earlier this week that more than 40,000 people had been tested. The United States has run about 25,000 tests. Neither country has contained the virus or tested aggressively for it. Korea and Singapore have so far been able to do both.

“We were not just looking at having a very good diagnostics test. That’s kind of a given. You can’t do anything without that,” said Dr. Sidney Yee, the chief executive of Singapore’s Diagnostics Development Hub. “We were also looking at getting people prepared and getting accurate messages out.”

Nicolas Locker, a professor of virology at the University of Surrey in Britain, said national leaders set the tone.

“What you’re seeing today is the impact of those earlier comments, and that earlier attitude,” Dr. Locker said.

Incorrect Assumptions

Testing can be as much a political issue as a scientific one.

Italy, the site of the biggest outbreak outside China, is a prime example. At first, regional authorities in the north tested widely and tried to trace contacts with sick people. But the national government in Rome objected, saying there was no need to test people who did not exhibit symptoms.

“Someone said we’re testing too many people and this is why we have such a huge number. That is not true,”

Giovanni Rezza, director of the department of infectious diseases at the Italian National Institute of Health.

Under pressure, the regional governments began testing only patients who exhibited symptoms. Politicians and scientists continue to debate those protocols, Dr. Rezza said. Still, the country has managed to test more than 182,000 people.

Britain was one of the first to develop coronavirus diagnostic kits but made a decision not to test widely. The government’s strategy initially focused on slowing the contagion rather than stopping it. The government, though, severely underestimated the potential scope of the epidemic, according to a study published on Monday.

Prime Minister Boris Johnson’s government recently reversed its strategy and decided to widen testing. Mr.

Johnson told Parliament on Wednesday that his government will have the ability to conduct 25,000 tests a day.

But raw numbers ignore the effect of timing. South Korea deployed its tests early and alongside other approaches, including some that European populations might resist. A government app monitored people to ensure they remained quarantined. Police officers used surveillance camera footage, phone data and credit card records to recreate the movements of new patients and identify potential contacts.

Kim Gang-lip, a South Korean vice health minister, said the contagiousness of the disease and its rapid spread demanded a new approach. “Such characteristics of the virus render the traditional response, which emphasizes lockdown and isolation, ineffective,” he said.

A New Testing Reality

Lockdown and isolation are a reality today for tens of millions of people.

Italy is at a standstill. Europe has all but shut its borders. President Emmanuel Macron of France told people to stay at home for 15 days and ordered the army to transport the sick to hospitals. Mr. Trump recommended against all but the smallest gatherings.

With no treatment for the disease, many countries are telling sick people to stay home unless they become seriously ill. Hospitals cannot afford to be overwhelmed by nervous people asking for tests.

But patients who self-quarantine likely won’t ever be tested, making it difficult to know the true scope of the disease. And as the disease spreads, the practicality of testing declines, as does its value.

“Testing of contacts, I believe, will be totally out of control very soon,” said Manfred Green, an epidemiologist with the University of Haifa in Israel.

Australian officials say they, too, worry about wasting tests on the merely worried. They recently adjusted testing protocols, but remain aggressive. Anyone who has recently been out of the country and so much as spikes a fever will likely be tested. “We are still in the containment phase,” said Dr. Kok. “We’re testing really widely.”

He Got Tested for Coronavirus. Then Came the Flood of Medical Bills. By [Elisabeth Rosenthal](#)

Hidden costs for E.R. visits and other fees could cost people thousands of dollars.

By March 5, Andrew Cencini, a computer science professor at Bennington College, had been having bouts of fever, malaise and a bit of difficulty breathing for a couple of weeks. Just before falling ill, he had traveled to New York City, helped with computers in a local prison and gone out on multiple calls as a volunteer firefighter. So with Covid-19 cases rising across the country, he called his doctor for direction. He was advised to come to the doctor’s group practice, where staff took swabs for flu and other viruses as he sat in his truck. They came back negative.

By Monday, March 9, he reported to his doctor that he was feeling better but still had some cough and low-grade fever. Within minutes, he got a call from the heads of a hospital emergency room and infectious-disease department where he lives in upstate New York: He should come right away to the E.R. for newly available coronavirus testing. Though they offered to send an ambulance, he felt fine and drove the hour. In an isolation room, the doctors put him on an IV drip, did a chest X-ray and took the swabs. Now back at work remotely, he faces a mounting array of bills. His patient responsibility, according to his insurer, is now close to \$2,000, and he fears there may be more bills to come “I was under the assumption that all that would be covered,” said Mr. Cencini

Further on, according to ‘selfish’ character, the I-Ego culture by excellence, a bizarre happening took place in America: the rivalry of the different ego-centered characters of this drama, the head of the different agencies, governors, presidencies, the nationalism of ‘I do it better than the German’s WHO test’, etc. We again use an excellent article on NYTimes to describe this mess:

Startling Setback

The first time Dr. Robert Redfield heard about the severity of the virus from his Chinese counterparts was around New Year’s Day.

To identify the virus, the C.D.C. test used three small genetic sequences to match up with portions of a virus’s genome extracted from a swab. A German-developed test that the W.H.O. was distributing to other countries used just two, potentially making it less precise.

But soon after the F.D.A. cleared the C.D.C. to share its test kits with state health department labs, some discovered a problem. The third sequence, or “probe,” gave inconclusive results. While the C.D.C. explored the cause — contamination or a design issue — it told those state labs to stop testing.

Dr. Redfield played down the problem in task force meetings and conversations with Mr. Azar, assuring him it would be fixed quickly, several administration officials said.

With capacity so limited, the C.D.C.’s criteria for who was tested remained extremely narrow for weeks to come: only people who had recently traveled to China or had been in contact with someone who had the virus. The lack of tests in the states also meant local public health officials could not use another essential epidemiological tool: surveillance testing.

The consequences became clear by the end of February. For the first time, someone with no known exposure to the virus or history of travel tested positive, in the Seattle area, where the U.S.’s first case had been detected more than a month earlier. The virus had probably been spreading there and elsewhere for weeks, researchers later concluded. Without a more complete picture of who had been infected, public health workers could not do “contact tracing” — finding all those with whom any contagious people had interacted and then quarantining them to stop further transmission.

The C.D.C. gave little thought to adopting the test being used by the W.H.O. The C.D.C.'s test was working in its own lab — still processing samples from states — which gave agency officials confidence. Dr. Anne Schuchat, the agency's principal deputy director, would later say that the C.D.C. did not think "we needed somebody else's test." And the German-designed W.H.O. test had not been through the American regulatory approval process, which would take time.

Days later, his agency provided a workaround, telling state and local health department labs that they could finally begin testing. Rather than awaiting replacements, they should use their C.D.C. test kits and leave out the problematic third probe.

Meanwhile, the agency's epidemiologists were growing more concerned as the virus spread in South Korea and Italy. On Feb. 25, Dr. Messonnier gave a briefing with a much blunter warning than usual. "Disruption to everyday life might be severe," she said.

Mr. Trump, returning from a trip to India, was furious, according to senior administration officials. Later that day, Mr. Azar seemed to be tamping down the level of concern. All Dr. Messonnier had meant, he said at a news conference, was that people should "start thinking about, in their own lives, what that might involve."

Barriers to Testing

Under Dr. Stephen Hahn's leadership, the F.D.A. became a significant roadblock.

Private-sector tests were supposed to be the next tier after the C.D.C. fulfilled its obligation to jump-start screening at public labs. In other countries hit hard by the coronavirus, governments acted quickly to speed tests to their populations. In South Korea, for example, regulators in early February summoned executives from 20 medical manufacturers, easing rules as they demanded tests.

But Dr. Hahn took a cautious approach. He was not proactive in reaching out to manufacturers, and instead deferred to his scientists, following the F.D.A.'s often cumbersome methods for approving medical screening.

Even the nation's public health labs were looking for the F.D.A.'s help. "We are now many weeks into the response with still no diagnostic or surveillance test available outside of C.D.C. for the vast majority of our member laboratories," Scott Becker, chief executive of the Association of Public Health Laboratories, wrote to Mr. Hahn in late February.

"We believe a more expeditious route is needed at this time." Even though researchers around the country quickly began creating tests that could diagnose Covid-19, many said they were hindered by the F.D.A.'s approval process. The new tests sat unused at labs around the country.

Stanford was one of them. Researchers at the world-renowned university had a working test by February, based on protocols published by the W.H.O. The organization had delivered more than 250,000 of the German-designed tests to 70 laboratories around the world, and doctors at the Stanford lab wanted to be prepared for a pandemic. But in the face of what he called "relatively tight" rules at the F.D.A., Dr. Pinsky and his colleagues decided against even trying to win permission. The Stanford clinical lab would not begin testing coronavirus samples until early March, when Dr. Hahn finally relaxed the rules.

Executives at bioMérieux, a French diagnostics company, had a similar experience. The company makes a countertop testing system, BioFire, that is routinely used to check for the flu and other respiratory illnesses in 1,700 hospitals around the country. It can provide results in about 45 minutes.

"A lot of us said, you know, your typical E.U.A. is just much too demanding," said Dr. Mark Miller, the company's chief medical officer, referring to the emergency approval. "It's going to take much too much time. And can't you do something to shorten that?" "You've got other countries — and I'm sorry, unfortunately, the U.S. is one of those — where they've been slow, disorganized," he said. "There are still not enough tests available there to test everybody who needs it."

In an emailed statement, Dr. Hahn maintained that his agency had moved as quickly as it safely could to ensure that tests would be accurate.

A Lack of Trust

Alex Azar had sounded confident at the end of January. At a news conference in the hulking H.H.S. headquarters in Washington, he said he had the government's response to the new coronavirus under control, pointing out

high-ranking jobs he had held in the department during the 2003 SARS outbreak and other infectious threats. “I know this playbook well,” he told reporters.

A Yale-trained lawyer who had spent a decade as a top executive at Eli Lilly, one of the world’s largest drug companies, he caught Mr. Trump’s attention in part because of other credentials: After law school, Mr. Azar was a clerk for some of the nation’s most conservative judges, including Justice Antonin Scalia of the Supreme Court. And for two years, he worked as Ken Starr’s deputy on the Clinton Whitewater investigation.

Mr. Azar has been quick to compliment the president and focus on the issues he cares about: lowering drug prices and fighting opioid addiction. On Feb. 6 — even as the W.H.O. announced that there were more than 28,000 coronavirus cases around the globe — Mr. Azar was in the second row in the White House’s East Room, demonstrating his loyalty to the president as Mr. Trump claimed vindication from his impeachment acquittal the day before and lashed out at “evil” lawmakers and the F.B.I.’s “top scum.”

Described as a prickly boss by some administration officials, Mr. Azar has had a longstanding feud with Seema Verma, the Medicare and Medicaid chief, who recently became a regular presence at Mr. Trump’s televised briefings on the pandemic. Mr. Azar did not include Dr. Hahn on the virus task force he led.

And tensions grew between the secretary and Dr. Redfield as the testing issue persisted.

One health department official said Mr. Azar was repeatedly assured that the C.D.C.’s test would be widely available within a week or 10 days, only to be given the same promise a week later.

Asked about criticism of his agency’s response to the pandemic, Dr. Redfield said: “I’m personally not focused on whether they’re pointing fingers here or there. We’re focused on doing all we can to get through this outbreak as quickly as possible and keep America safe.”

For all Mr. Azar’s complaints, however, he continued to defer to the scientists at the two agencies, according to several administration officials. Mr. Azar’s allies said he was told by Dr. Redfield and Dr. Fauci that the C.D.C. had the resources it needed, that there was no reason to believe the virus was spreading through the country from person to person and that it was important to test only people who met certain criteria.

But even in the face of a crescendo of complaints from doctors and health care researchers around the country, Mr. Azar failed to push those under him to do the one thing that could have helped: broader testing. Around noon on Feb. 27, Dr. Hahn, Dr. Redfield and top aides from the F.D.A. and H.H.S. dialed in to a conference call. Mr. Harrison began with an ultimatum: No one leaves until we resolve the lag in testing.

By the end of the day, the group agreed that the F.D.A. should loosen regulations so that hospitals and independent labs could move forward quickly with their own tests.

But the evening before, Mr. Azar had been effectively removed as the leader of the task force when Mr. Trump abruptly put Mr. Pence in charge, a decision so last-minute that even the top health officials in the White House learned of it while watching the announcement.

Faced with the coronavirus, Mr. Trump chose not to have the White House lead the planning until nearly two months after it began. Mr. Obama’s global health office had been disbanded a year earlier. And until Mr. Pence took charge, the task force lacked a single White House official with the power to compel action.

Since then, testing has ramped up quickly, with nearly 100 labs at hospitals and elsewhere performing it. On Friday, the health care giant Abbott said it had received emergency approval for a portable test that could detect the virus in five minutes.

The president boasted on Tuesday that the United States had “created a new system that now we are doing unbelievably big numbers” of tests for the virus. The U.S., he said, had done more testing for the coronavirus in the last eight days than South Korea had done in eight weeks.

Yet hospitals and clinics across the country still must deny tests to those with milder symptoms, trying to save them for the most serious cases, and they often wait a week for results. In tacit acknowledgment of the shortage, Mr. Trump asked South Korea’s president on Monday to send as many test kits as possible from the 100,000 produced there daily, more than the country needs.

Public health experts reacted positively to the increased capacity. But having the ability to diagnose the disease three months after it was first disclosed by China does little to address why the United States was unable to do so sooner, when it might have helped reduce the toll of the pandemic.

“Testing is the crack that split apart the rest of the response, when it should have tied everything together,” said Dr. Nahid Bhadelia, the medical director of the Special Pathogens Unit at Boston University School of Medicine. “It seeps into every other aspect of our response, touches all of us,” she said. “The delay of the testing has impacted the response across the board.”

THE CONTAINMENT PHASE.

At this point thus, the west and the East (the 3rd non-technological world will be treated latter, as the Pandemic

there cannot be detained and will follow its natural course by lack of resources), have clearly diverged. The West has not REPPRESSED the sickness in its first phase. Asia has done it. So Asia had to face merely a local cure, while the West defies a global pandemic within its local borders, as the virus now has no longer a local action, but a global symmetry.

This means in the next phase, Asian countries could without fully repressing the life of its people and halt its economy, attack the germs in those citizens-cells localized by testing and the collaboration of citizens for the

common good, which allowed the use of AI methods – for once with a positive outcome for mankind – to track their movements through GPS and did explain to the health-care workers its whereabouts and so localization of all germs was possible.

On the west now we assisted to the ceremonies of confusion of its egocy politicians who had tried for as long as they could to deny the situation.

So Asia now followed a purely scientific, Universal view according to its underlying religions of the living Universe, and applied all the positive technology, financial control, collaboration of its industries, as a single supœrganism to that aim.

The people of Daegu, the Princess and Hubei were closed, its measures of containment obeyed. In Hubei only a member of the family could come out twice a week to buy groceries. In Daegu, all the members of the sect where the pandemic broke out were tested. The Diamond princess was isolated. In Singapore every single contagion was pursued in all details. In Korea, the whereabouts of each ‘anonymous’ infected person tracked publicly for all people to know where not to go.

Massive amounts of auxiliary police and armies worked as they should in an ideal supœrganism of history repressing the germs of history NOT multiplying them, constructing hospitals, disinfecting streets and buildings, controlling the movements of those who left home. And the outcome was immediate: the ‘exponential curve’ became a ‘logistic curve’ far before it ‘filled all the population’ as NOW THE POPULATION FOR THE VIRUS TO EXPAND WAS MINIMALIZED without the need to bring military action as the west and the 3rd world dictators

(Indian nationalist party, etc.) have done. The curve of the different nations shows clearly the achievements of Asia:

In the graph, we can see the clear difference of 3 curve behaviors:

- The Asian response (Korea, China) did flatten the curve and entered in the healing phase, with maximal investment in hospitals, health-care means to save lives, which we will study next. It took only 20 days for Korea to flatten the exponential curve into a logistic form; longer to China, due to initial errors in a country with a single party rule, which is correct as no system have Siamese conflicting heads, but without a free press and citizenship capacity to judge communist members delivering pain messages to them. So the initial errors in Wuhan loaded 60 thousand cases, which initially were denied (hence the steep growth in the 22 day when they were all accepted). The curve would then flatten as in Korea, with massive means to cure the sick, so the proportions of death, outside Wuhan, which failed on those initial moments were minimal. The reverence in Asian cultures as it should be for the informative 3rd age of its people also made them care unlike the cynical capitalist limit of US; where the curve has a perfect exponential form without the slightest containment measures so far; as all the blunders of selfish capitalist societies have been at work .

In between we find the European curves which range from the worst forms of my country, Spain, to the better containment of France (UK so far applied rightly its Brexit policies of containment in the border, so its curve is only in the beginning of its exponential growth, which will be similar once it accelerates to those of Europe). Unfortunately what this means is that the weaker health-care systems of US (no control at all of its population without Universal health-care), Italy and Spain (where the true number of sick is likely 5 times larger), have entered a true natural exponential-logistic curve and won't be controlled till ½ of its population is sick, most of them without symptoms, but those of us with pre-conditions and the elderly will die in huge numbers.

US on the other hand will play the brutal game of capitalism, ignoring its dead corpses. A 17 year old died because it had not health-care coverage and was rejected in the hospital in California, suffering a heart-attack. And obviously the real numbers there will be likely closer to a million infected soon.

Germany did not contained faster because of its mechanical obsession with production. So now will establish a massive testing procedure to 'clear' those that passed the infection for work-return- an intelligent measure all other nations should follow if they had resources to test and cure. It however completely failed to address the problems of the rest of Europe it controls with its 'IV economical Reich' taking advantage of the market, without the slightest solidarity of the ECB bank which still 'considers' money a parasitic debt function, not a language of information that should be delivered without limit to save lives.

So the worst situation as usual in the 1st world is that of Italy and Spain that do NOT have control over its currency to deliver 'deficits', that is, to print money to save lives, as debt slaves of the ECB bank.

Here in Spain the rate of sick among the health-care warriors is maximal, 14% including my brother who runs a pharmacy along a hospital have been infected. Its death rate is only second to Italy. Both have argued with Germany to create coronavirus bonds to pay the expenditures but Germany in its neo-Nazi capitalist phase closed borders, forbade the exportation of respirators, slurred racist comments along Holland against Italy and Spain, denied them help and forbade the creation of free money to cure the sick. If I were the Spanish prime minister certainly I will immediately come out of the slavery to Germany, slap tariffs to its products, come out of the EURO and immediately produce enough money to save my people – well, certainly if I had run this country nothing of this would have happened, as we would live in a perfect organism of History. But I can only witness from my confinement the expansion of the sickness because the country has no resources to implement properly...

SOCIOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE CURVE.

The coronavirus case shows as all systems under stress the huge errors of design of human supœrganisms, based in historic traditions of military nature (politicians), and parasitic debt-money (Classic economics) which put the

machine above man as the goal of society (industrial r=evolution); and so has not evolved mankind and its social organisms to face crisis against the welfare and health of its people.

The physiological networks of an organism of history should be managed by 'doctors of history', because its laws are the same than those of a biological organism.

So unlike the scientific organization promoted by bio-history and bioeconomics based in how Nature builds its efficient supœrganisms, human societies are dysfunctional, catering to the cells-citizens but to the elites and corporations, which control its money and resources. And so when the 'apocalypse' horses comes in – pest, war, famines... the organism is ill prepared to protect its citizens cells.

If the focus had been to save the people, states would have been prepared and acted as Korea and Germany, and any organism does: massive testing of population to search for the infected and isolate them only, massive use of masks for the population and EPIs for the health-care system but this implied that as in any organism, the immune defensive system is the health-care system NOT the military system of an aberrant society where the 'defense system' kill other organs of mankind, instead of working together to cater to their people. So it will be necessary to study NOT only the pandemics but the whole evolution of this planet and history from a world of life, Gaia, to a world of mankind, history, to the present dystopia in the making, a world of machines and its true free citizens, company-mothers.

We are sold the story that nothing could be done or prevented. This is false: politicians ignored the pandemics that were evidently coming from China and then from Italy, because they NEVER focus their lives in saving the and serving the life of the people, but as heirs of military and nationalistic states, their 'concept' of their job is military and nationalistic, ideological not practical, and similar to that of celebrity managed by audiovisual and financial networks of informative machines – to cater to companies, banks and mass-media systems to get their jobs and their retirement allowances, and then to pretend they are for their people, which in turn is also controlled by a virtual reality of soma, happy selfie fictions. So both the politicians and the people followed its routines, its champions league masses, its placebo demonstrations, its quarrels for power between regions, states and departments.

Since politicians in a capitalist democracy unlike a perfect society have no real economical, welfare, social power to make a better world for mankind but merely are theatrical masks that disguise the control of society by company-mothers (the biological organisms that in the 5D systemic models of the economy have become the free citizens, whose goal as any mother-organism is to tender for its offspring of machines and weapons, terraforming the Earth into a world to its image and likeness, we call the metal-earth, the obvious next age of evolution of this planet, we humans catalyze as enzymes, but do NOT understand since it is a systemic 5D organic process of a higher and logic of networks superior to the individual)...

THE CURE PHASE.

Here again the startling difference between the Asian and Capitalist approach with its two in crescendo limits of brutality Europe and America has been noticeable.

World	680,679	+17,600	31,918
Italy	92,472		10,023
Spain	78,797	+5,562	6,528
China	81,439	+45	3,300
Iran	38,309	+2,901	2,640
France	37,575		2,314
USA	123,781	+203	2,229
UK	17,089		1,019
Netherlands	10,866	+1,104	771
Germany	58,247	+552	455
Belgium	10,836	+1,702	431
Switzerland	14,352	+276	282
S. Korea	9,583	+105	152

Because Asia did right the localization of the germs, it had enough resources, also provided generously by states in control of its central banks, to cure the sick. SO the number of death is far inferior to those in Europe and soon in America as the stats below show, as of today.

We are dying by the droves. There are no respirators. 50% of those in UCI don't make it. We have twice more dead than China, which has 40 times more people, and the curve has only started. A whole generation is going under – the last human generation not yet erased by the virtual reality of the Internet age as we discuss the post-apocalyptic phase in the epilogue.

Notice then the low percentage of dead in China and Korea in relationship to the population. China was caught off guard in Wuhan as we explained due to the

free reign of communist nomenclature, which cannot be judged by its own people and took too slow measures. Korea shows the best reaction. Germany on the other hand as de facto dictator of Europe, with all the resources of the ECB bank and the conquest already achieved of European markets and companies, now subsidiaries of German ones, and the absolute selfishness of its racist elite has also done well, with a death proportion similar to South Korea.

Finally US is only in its initial phase. Also to notice those statistics are false. A true measure of the death should be done as in the case of Chernobyl, with statistics of annual deaths because lying is widespread. Many people who die of pneumonia or heart attack are not counted. Here in Spain in fact the number of dead can be considered twice that number. Coffins are kept in the ice park of Madrid, incinerating and hidden in old people residences. US will neither establish a real counting approaching the level of 3rd world nations, where as we have said, this crisis will be relatively mild compared to the other horses of apocalypses they constantly suffer, famine and war death, as we dump our cheap weapons among its people.

So we have to return to the 'fundamental element' of the cure phase, which is simply, 'MONEY'; that is, the ill-designed systems of parasitic money of the western world, which are the worst possible in Italy and Spain, where NOT only money is not understood as the social language that kicks out the reproduction of goods – the oxygen of society, but the countries do NOT control the issue of money in the hands of a racist, authoritarian, abusive nation, Germany, and an idol-ogy of money as 'usury debt' that has NOTHING to do with the true nature of money as a language of information, and the oxygen of society

RECAP. THE SIMPLE SOLUTIONS OF A WELL-DESIGNED HUMAN SUPÆRGANISM.

In a well-designed supœrganism of History the solution would have been immediate by imitating nature:

According to the models of bio-history, money is the reproductive oxygen of the economic system given to every cell-citizen of an efficient supœrganism of nature.

Because the economy is the blood-reproductive network of the organism the solution of a pandemic, a sickness of an organism is in 5d economics and Social Sciences the same that an organism deploys.

An intelligent organic system like the ones of nature cures this type of sickness in 3 days.

It gives extra supply of oxygen-money to all cells sequestering its activity without eating in complete rest state.

Then it launches its antibodies, with fever to increase its thermodynamic activity. And the body is healed.

The Universe is simple and not malicious (Einstein) if the organism works according to the laws of nature and its physiological networks are well behaved.

As money is the blood oxygen of society, and the antibodies are the health-care system and military/police, the immediate translation is obvious:

States have to put everyone at home for a month as soon as the sickness is established.

Central banks have to issue money Not as they have done for banks and speculators to maintain the price of stocks; but to give a universal salary to all Europeans of two thousand Euros a month.

So they stay home but can buy food and medicines. Because the central bank=blood system takes care of the oxygen=salary, governments also prohibit all companies to fire workers during that period.

Then the 'antibodies' – health care system, food suppliers and police increase its feverish activity, for a month, detect all cases and solve the pandemic, disinfecting everything.

In 5D this is equivalent to STOP the time of the organism for a month and launch the defensive system. But that means to let the 'Informative, nervous' system of society, the legal wor(l)d to rule as all advanced species do over the blood-reproductive system - money, which only 'worms' that leave indeed their organisms to be poisoned by lethal goods they eat with unending greed do. So capitalism, the 'worm organism' does the same and won't allow the nervous political system to interfere.

CONCLUSION: UK & US: ANGLO-AMERICANS DYING FOR THE DOW & ITS STOCKRATIC BILLIONAIRES.

Mr. Krugman, a compassionate Jasp, with a Keynesian approach put it simple in the NYTimes: "...an attempt to restart the economy leads to a new wave of infections.

So why are Trump and company going down this route? One answer is that thousands of Americans may be about to die for the Dow. We know that Trump is obsessed with the stock market, and his long refusal to take Covid-19 seriously reportedly had a lot to do with his belief that doing otherwise would [hurt stock prices](#). He may now believe that pretending that the crisis is over will boost stocks, and that that's all that matters."

Trumpuppet in this shows the *real power alliance between GOP Wasps and Jasps stockrats on top of America, as it becomes the Metal-earth's world. As he would twit in defense of Mr. Musk, of Tesla fame, which against the law of the land has defied the Sheriff of Alameda, opening his factory of AI Robots, so production doesn't go down – as he is a few weeks from getting 1.3 million shares at cheap price if Tesla's stocks don't loose value this spring...*

Trumpuppet confesses his billionaire friends all want him to open the country, and so hundreds of thousands will die for them and on top cheer 'four legs, four legs' as they confuse the Dow with the real economy. But the dow goes up when millions file unemployment because it is disengaging from the human economy. This is the phenomena we talked about for decades now finally happening. As the GDP of mankind doesn't matter to the whales we hunt, the GDP of Americans do not matter to the Internet companies and stockrats that consume other machines, get their money from its global market and the parasitic economy of advertising, and money fed by the FED private bankers turned into public service to the 0.1%.

So we are moving to the next robotic age... with 'safe robots' coming home NOT to infect you, while human stay home.

Companies from the metal earth have tripled in a month ... Twilio the leader of the software for 'skynet' (cloud between Business)... doubled in 3 days even with negative profits. The Jasps know the future they design is not human and the 'poor' must be spent, so the old that ask for money to medicare. So what wall street is doing "subconsciously" is liquidating workers... that is why the 20 million unemployed mean nothing. As the economy of man is separated from that of the whale.

The fiction discourse of the Jasp era will continue.

We have to bring now to conclude the singularity age under the Jasp rule in America, the key element that differentiates a Jasp world from a humanist world this texts represent in terms of 'truth and science', which is the concept we start with all our papers: *Truth exists, and only truth makes humans survive. In the Jasp tradition as a go(l)d culture that worships a 'faked wealth' – that of gold, just the support for digital numbers called money, truth is irrelevant as truth in humanity is carried by words that have our causality of survival. Once gold and digital numbers substituted in the Jasp>Biblical>Capitalist culture the wor(l)d and its eusocial love mandates, the rest of mankind matter nothing – their own people who die in the holocaust go(l)d cycle could be spare, let alone today the people of America that will be massacred for the 'Dow'. But this cannot be told because Americans are still 'human, emotional, survival, caring people'. So they must live in a continuous fiction. So the history of the Coronavirus will be adapted to this fiction by the mass-media system. Already Kushner, the orthodox Jewish master of the Trumpuppet family came to explain us that we had 'left behind' the crisis and we were wrting a 'success history', while to appease fears a supposed 'cure' with Gilead's redemsvir, speculation in future vaccines that doubled the price of Novvax in one day and tripled Sorrento thereapeutics in a day, will keep the circus, while hiding the 'damned lies and statistics' of corpses without a face. This is the whole history of the Jasp people: inventing a faked reality to hide the miseries of go(l)d that kill mankind for nothing, and then maintain the narrative with all the faked 'rhetoric' and 'rituals' and 'taboos' and 'religious dogmas', since they were the People of the Treasure ill-translated as the chosen – even in the name we hide a falsehood and decided they would serve the tree of metal and its evil=antilive fruits, through today's idol-ogies of capitalism, technoutopia and faked nationalism, which uses the mercenary army of US for its semite wars.*

Mr. Tesla crying 'freedom' just to open its automated robotized factories is the example at hand. Freedom is shouted to maintain the slavery of mankind to debt-money in Wall Street – that is freedom for the 0.1% But as a fiction of social sciences has been placed as dogma, from classic economics to political correctness, people don't know the Dow has NOTHING to do with their economy, capitalism is the dictatorship of those who stole them the right to reproduce money and so on.

Then murder 'at distance' through money and prices is hidden by the subconscious brain knows the cruelty of that future but in daily life greed reduces his point of view to the day profits and to short distances to never accept the consequences in the medium term of his liquidation of the human economy.

And of course we miscount the corpses. They all lie, because nobody is interested, neither the government nor the economists, the truth, can only be taken from the dead on funerary s compared to a year ago and then US doubled the official dead. There are already more dead than in Vietnam and the war on terror; all perfectly avoidable in a country that produces the money of the world and could have spent with no limit on curing its people. But as people have been robbed the right to make their own money, their own oxygen, they will die both at individual level by the coronavirus that takes its oxygen and at collective level by Wall Street that took its right to produce money and kills them by anoxia, lack of oxygen, which is how the coronaviruses liquidate us.

If no debt dollars as Lincoln wanted – but was killed for it - were made, as in the organism with a universal salary of a thousand euros, not as debt, the oxygen shared for every human citizen would keep them all at home quiet on vacation, while the health-care, buttressed with billions, would trace infections and cure them.

But everybody in America believes that money "is debt" and you have to return it to the Jasp who stole the right to make it long ago, causing the biggest tragedy mankind has suffered for millennia –global anoxia.

As usual the 2 caste of animals and its solutions are similar – that of the military and the capitalist and both kill: Mr. Tesla shouts 'freedom' so he doesn't close his factory, because if Tesla continues with his fictitious price (4 times more than Ford, the old antiSemite that will never be 'revalued') he'll make a billion to share with the Wall Street speculators that keep inventing FED e-money to handle it to stockrats.

The issue for Bolsonaro or Trump or the Jasp stockrats IS to keep profiteering. The issue is not the murder of hundreds of thousands of Americans, which are NOT the chosen victims, we must advertise with the Holocaust industry not to happen ever again. On the contrary those victims MUST be hidden so we can kill them as many times as needed, in the new brave world where they are a surplus a cost, more expensive than robots. Those are inferior races, blacks and Latinos, to which we just pay lip service with a political correct discourse that protect the Jaspers from being pointed rightly as the new people-caste ruling America. The issue is NOT the fact there is no money for healthcare because everything went for decades to the MILITARY and financial system for the Semite wars and the bail outs of unlimited free printing of e-money for the 0.2% ...

The Stock Exchange has retraced a 50% Fibonacci come back and profits continued in W.S. as they shorted shares so the losses were for pension funds. Now as the Market has leveled and no new speculative profits can be done, the issue is that companies lose consumers and do not give benefits so they all scream together to open for freedom, from the boss of Goldman Sachs to Tesla to Mr. Cramer (only Facebook's CEO that wins more in the lock is suddenly silent). They KNOW that they are going to make a profit from a genocide of half a million Americans but only the fool of Trump said it: 'all my billionaire friends are pressing me to open'. Of course Mr. Buffet chartered his fleet of planes to bring FFPP3 masks from China the best for the Mount-Sinai hospital network in case any Jasp or Wasp stockrat gets sick...

EUROPE: NATIONALISM & USTERICIDE: NORTH VS. SOUTH DUALITY.

The first case of complete mismanagement of a health crisis to analyze is that of my country and the European Union and large, where this who writes with all the 'pre-conditions' that takes a patient to the tomb lives – in the center of the epidemics today, Spain.

So likely we won't be able to complete the plan of this r=evolution of thought, which is 5D courtesy of the complete amateur, murderous clueless behavior of our political, economical and health-care systems (those without blame as they are not properly funded) of our civilizations that combines all the illnesses of 'animetal cultures'. Indeed the present animetal civilization was discovered here and all its idol-ogies.

Plainly speaking in Italy and Spain that have likely between 4 and 10 times more contagion that statistics says, the *virus e-number of maximal exponential growth won't be contained. So we will all be infected and those of us who are too old or too sick to defend our system from it will die.*

And yet, Spain, which saw all this happening in advance first in China and then in its 'sister nation' Italy did nothing to stop the virus or even prepare for it. It kept the 'collective soma' of virtual fictions, soccer matches with tens of thousands seated together shouting viruses, demonstrations of wo=men vomiting hate slogans against macho-men, parties and dolce fare niente full bars and drunken nights. Till of course, the weakened health-care system, by decades of financial austericide by parasitic bankers since the private ECB took the right of countries to print money, has collapsed. The state is now requisiting in the borders boxes of masks bought in Alibaba, begs for respirators to China and US who has 5 million for his 'buttressed troops' ready to murder and protect themselves from bio-tech warfare. Surrealism is reaching now degrees that Buñuel, the film master would have not dreamed of. But the troops are in the streets where no people can walk a dog, as none have masks, even the mildest drug, paracetamol is rationed, and of course, the capital people, the arrogant 'madrileños' have escaped from the center of the viral infection, to his villas on the coast spreading the virus.

Why this has happened is obvious: the political system of a capitalist democracy is not as the brain of any organism there to cater the needs of its cells, but to cheat them and pander for money to the corporations and financiers that have sequestered for millennia the blood-oxygen system of society, the issue of money. SO they couldn't care less about the pandemics and the death of the old people as long as they felt protected by their privileges. Only when the leader of the neo-fascist VOX party felt ill politicians realized it was serious and got afraid. Then one of the sub-organs of the nation, the Catalan leader tried to use the crisis to provoke a de facto independence, 'sequestering' the country and so the central power had to act – NOT because of the virus but to prove he was still ruling, and sequestered the entire nations.

Meanwhile for months those of us who warned against the crisis were laughed about this Chinese virus, since obviously the draconian measures established by organic Asia were a question of a dictatorship NOT basic public health, and nobody did anything. Since we, repeat, a capitalist democracy does NOT serve its people. Politicos are just there to create a placebo theatrics of power for populations. And money is NOT created as oxygen for the needs of welfare but as a parasitic debt money or simply printed for stick-markets to add numbers to the fatten accounts of our 'stockrats' – those themes treated in other papers.

But surrealism reaches now lethal proportions. The old people in residences were not provided masks, and for long their death rates were hidden to the people, even its own relatives, sneaking their corpses in the morning in pale bags to the Morgue. No respirators, no masks, no medicines, retrovirals or quinine are provided to the sick, as all what the president an ex-basketball player, chosen for his 'cara bonita' and the health-care minister, not even a doctor but a politico chosen because of his Catalan pedigree to appease the rebel 'organ', care for is the daily dose of 'informative transparency', meaning total indoctrination and denial of the facts. Because money is in short supply for the Spanish people, without limit for the corporative elites, nothing was done... till panic took the markets and viruses infected the wives of ministers and presidents, whose Schopenhauerian attitude (long hair short ideas) is remarkable. Since all what the 'feminist movement' seems to care these days is for 'vagina matters', while the rest

of social issues are for the 'macho to solve'. So against the obvious requirements of confinement and social distancing, our 'pundit', 'Don Simon', the amateurish man on charge of the pandemics, always 3 step behind the viruses, recommended them to go to the march that exploded the virus contagion, one day after the 'classic mixed' madrilenos and Catalans in mutual hate. Alas! the solution, to confine all Spaniards, but with a week-end in advance warning for the wealthier madrileños with homes on the coast to escape with the virus for the holiday quarantine. The president indeed gave them 2 days in advance notice to go to Marbella and the coast where I reside. Meanwhile so far the old people are dying but all what the President thought to cure them was to confine everybody at home – not even walking alone the dog, doing some stretching or walking on the beach is permitted, as in France. The harder the punishment on the people, the more a 'Spanish politico' – a culture of military warriors and coup d'états' – feels is doing something. As I said to my brother, as the pandemics take us all you will see first after 'Don Simon', the amateur minister of health coming with maximal delay, then the president with maximal delay and finally the king who came today with 100.000 real infected people – as he is wary to have to explain why his father took 100 million \$ cut from the Ibn Saud murderous king to make the high speed train to Mecca on the path of Ibn Battuta not to save his soul but to bring his go(l)d to an offshore foundation presided by his mistress... Surrealism indeed will keep growing as Spain has always been the land of plagues and pests for the common people, while its corrupted elite enjoyed life for centuries, then living off the South-American silver slaves today of the tourists that come with Euros. So with Schopenhauerian stupidity (a stupid is a man who does not understand causality and considers events to be the product of magic), all what the pundits cared was not to frighten tourism, letting droves of Chinese for New Year and Italians for soccer matches to come. A macho man attitude a la Trump and the courtesy of showing your face prevented people not to shake hands and use masks. The verbosity of the language and the constant life in the bars and cafes did the rest, with the acquiescence of Don Simon, the scapegoat put on the TV screen to tell us to go on with our life as long as the one thousand number was not reached... Twice he was asked if he would let his daughter go to the 'hate to the macho' 8th of march long hair short brain unique theme that seems to preoccupy ½ of the species... and He twice said, I would advice her to do what she pleases... That was just 10 days ago, as the number of death, exponential e grows faster by the day and only Italy has more active cases today.. We can see on top Europe, catching fast US and coming out of it China and Korea, according to the 3 degrees of dysfunctionality of the European, American and Asian civilizations:

NON-TECHNOLOGICAL CIVILINATIONS: LET TAKE THE TROOPS OUT AND LET THEM DIE ON THE STREETS.

What we can expect and it is happening everywhere . Again from the NYTimes:

***For Autocrats, and Others, Coronavirus Is a Chance to Grab Even More Power* Selam Gebrekidan**

Leaders around the world have passed emergency decrees and legislation expanding their reach during the pandemic. Will they ever relinquish them?

In Hungary, the prime minister can now rule by decree. In Britain, ministers have what a critic called “eye-watering” power to detain people and close borders. Israel’s prime minister has shut down courts and begun an intrusive surveillance of citizens. Chile has sent the military to public squares once occupied by protesters. Bolivia has postponed elections.

As the halt and anxious citizens demand action, leaders across the globe are invoking executive powers and seizing virtually dictatorial authority with scant resistance.

Governments and rights groups agree that these extraordinary times call for extraordinary measures. States need new powers to shut their borders, enforce quarantines and track infected people. Many of these actions are protected under international rules, constitutional lawyers say.

But critics say some governments are using the public health crisis as cover to seize new powers that have little to do with the outbreak, with few safeguards to ensure that their new authority will not be abused.

The laws are taking swift hold across a broad range of political systems — in authoritarian states like Jordan, faltering democracies like Hungary, and traditional democracies like Britain. And there are few sunset provisions to ensure that the powers will be rescinded once the threat passes.

“We could have a parallel epidemic of authoritarian and repressive measures following close if not on the heels of a health epidemic,” said Fionnuala Ni Aolain, the United Nations Special Rapporteur on counterterrorism and human rights.

As the new laws broaden state surveillance, allow governments to detain people indefinitely and infringe on freedoms of assembly and expression, they could also shape civic life, politics and economies for decades to come.

The pandemic is already redefining norms. Invasive surveillance systems in South Korea and Singapore, which would have invited censure under normal circumstances, have been praised for slowing infections. Governments that initially criticized China for putting millions of its citizens under lockdown have since followed suit.

Israel’s prime minister, Benjamin Netanyahu, has authorized his country’s internal security agency to track citizens using a secret trove of cell phone data developed for counterterrorism. By tracing people’s movements, the government can punish those who defy isolation orders with up to six months in prison.

by ordering the closing of the nation’s courts, Mr. Netanyahu delayed his scheduled appearance to face corruption charges.

In some parts of the world, new emergency laws have revived old fears of martial law. The Philippine Congress passed legislation last week that gave President Rodrigo Duterte emergency powers and \$5.4 billion to deal with the pandemic. Lawmakers watered down an earlier draft law that would have allowed the president to take over private businesses.

“This limitless grant of emergency powers is tantamount to autocracy,” a Philippine rights group, the Concerned Lawyers for Civil Liberties, said in a statement. The lawyers noted that Mr. Duterte had once compared the country’s Constitution to a “scrap of toilet paper.”

Some states are using the pandemic to crack down on dissent. In Jordan, after an emergency “defense law” gave wide latitude to his office, Prime Minister Omar Razzaz said his government would “deal firmly” with anyone who spreads “rumors, fabrications and false news that sows panic.”

Prime Minister Prayuth Chan-ocha of Thailand has assumed the authority to impose curfews and censor the news media. Journalists there have been sued and intimidated for criticizing the government’s response to the outbreak.

While the virus itself may have cooled protesters' will to crowd public squares, Chile's declaration of a "state of catastrophe" and the military's presence on city streets has muted raging dissent that rocked the nation for months.

The pandemic has also disrupted planned elections. This month, Bolivia suspended a much anticipated presidential election that had been scheduled for early May. A disputed election last year set off violent protests and forced President Evo Morales to resign.

The interim president, who promised to serve only as a caretaker, has since consolidated power and announced her plan to run for an elected term. The country's election tribunal said on Thursday that it would hold the elections sometime between June and September.

In the United States, the Justice Department asked Congress for sweeping new powers, including a plan to eliminate legal protections for asylum seekers and detain people indefinitely without trial. After Republicans and Democrats balked, the department scaled back and submitted a more modest proposal.

Rights groups say governments may continue to absorb more power while their citizens are distracted. They worry that people may not recognize the rights they have ceded until it is too late to reclaim them.

Some emergency bills were waved through so quickly that lawmakers and rights groups had no time to read them, let alone debate their necessity. Rights advocates have also questioned the speed with which states have drafted lengthy legislation.

Certain governments have a set of desired powers "ready to go" in case of emergency or crisis, said Ms. Aolain, the United Nations special rapporteur. They draft laws in advance and wait "for the opportunity of the crisis to be presented," she said.

It is far from clear what will become of the emergency laws when the crisis passes. In the past, laws enacted in a rush, like the Patriot Act that followed the Sept. 11 attacks, have outlived the crises they were meant to address. Over time, emergency decrees permeate legal structures and become normalized, said Douglas Rutzen, the president of the International Center for Not-for-Profit Law in Washington, **which is tracking new legislation and decrees during the pandemic**.

"It's really easy to construct emergency powers," Mr. Rutzen said. "It's really difficult to deconstruct them."

THE ASIAN RESPONSE

We have considered the Asian response in bits and bites along all the texts, so we shall just summarize it here. When dealing with a supœrganism of History we are basically dealing in a larger scale with a 3-physiological network, to which *the parasitic structure* of nationalist tribalism, financial parasitism and its wrong 'class structures' is added, hindering the proper functioning of the society.

We have had a glimpse to the dysfunctional, corrupted ways of the Spanish Democracy responsible for the massive outbreak that will not only murder old people and people with prior conditions like this who writes in a Russian Roulette we all have to pass,

The response of Asia and alone among the Western Countries, Australia by influence of the Asian ways, which shows that culture is memetic not racial, as we explained in other papers was however focus NOT on the TROUBLES that the mixture of the wrong physiological elements of society (tribalism, authoritarianism, political corruption, selfish individualism)

So the Asian cultures were as the ideal society focusing in the problem itself as a public problem of health, which is the only thing the coronavirus really is about.

European societies ruled by corrupted legal systems focused on the 'legal matters' of national authority, which hindered the solutions and deployed an array of selfish behaviors.

Anglo-American societies were hindered by the astounding lack of a true democracy where power cares for people. Their only focus was as it has always been on the financial wealth of the 0.1% and acted only finally when markets crashed.

Asia just tried to cure the sickness with little interest on market problems or problems of jurisdiction. Theirs was an organic, practical approach as that of Nature to similar problems.

We have already explained it in details. So we shall not extend any longer.

Asia though is not the panacea of mankind in its present AI format, because it has created also the dystopia we talked about for so long of a world ruled by Internet machines, where the nature of human is definitely changed for the worst, and we treat in extension in all other papers about the future.

As we have already explained ad nauseam the Asian Organism as the closest to the ideal organism of history, the Asian response IS the right response according to 5D laws and so the one we already studied. But unfortunately Asia is only one of the 7 Civilinations of mankind so we have to focus on the other responses, from the Capitalist Euro-American response, similar but with focus in military and money, their languages of power and the 3rd world response, which will be none, let them die because that is what capitalism has done to us for centuries and this is a minor glitch compared to their systemic massacre of non-technological cultures.

The isolation of the weaker organs.

The essence of an efficient immunological system is its specificity and swift response, as the Asian civilination who better manage the crisis around the most efficient human superorganism by the only measure of success in biological history – survival – showed. Indeed, it is in the Asian civilination and its countries regardless of its present political system (China, Korea, Vietnam & Taiwan & Singapore) where the logic scientific response have taken place, showing a fundamental law of 5D: A larger nested efficient superorganism, can always control a smaller one, if it is properly designed.

In the case of the coronavirus the main ‘message’ for mankind is thus clear: 5D social sciences work; and so the closest civilination to its laws has come on top of the crisis fast by isolating first outwardly (Japan with the Diamond princess) and the inwardly (Korea with the Daegu focus), the germs; and then once inside, tracking them and chasing and isolating the ‘infected citizens-cells’ to AVOID the need to render the whole organism inert, with the enormous cost for all other physiological networks, notably the blood=reproductive=economic system. Why this was NOT done in Europe and the US has to do precisely with the ill-designed ‘parasitic’ financial and economic systems of those societies which was responsible of the poor response and lack of means in its immune=health-care systems in those societies, unlike the ways in which an **ideal superorganism of history would have solved the crisis.**

Or the way the closest superorganism to the ideal form, China had done it. What China lacks to be such a perfect superorganism is obvious: pain messages of the population back to the communist party members when they are not behaving properly – namely after tenure judgments as in real classic Greek democracies, so they serve the people or else. Only this reform is needed to have a model society – plus the obvious understanding to the limits technology and AI evolution of machines need if man wishes to remain the top predator species of this planet. Needless to say both things go together. China today moves towards a harsher dictatorship of the party over its population precisely because party members do not want to be judged by human beings.

Now consider that such a system would exist. It would be easily implemented in China with a reform of the political control of the Communist party, which has the proper economic system, by obliging all politicians to be subject to an a posteriori judgment by the population, after tenure. This could be implemented swiftly in the next Chinese Communist congress, and convert de facto the Chinese society – or for that matter similar one-party democracies in Taiwan, Korea, Japan and Singapore, where the same party is elected once and again, as we shall repeat, the true underlying structure of those societies is NOT the modern ‘western ideologies’ of capitalism vs. communism but the civilination of Asia.

Back in the 2000s before my activism against CERN de facto eliminated me from any teaching or scholar position I gave some conferences on Tokyo and proposed this scheme with an obvious backlash among the Japanese, who as all nazionalist ideologies consider their systems the best, and with no need to reform.

Then I got involved on the suits against CERN, who established a 10 people strong force to rise ad hominem campaigns against the 3 of us who were more active on those suits Mr. Rossler, a prominent researcher of chaos theory, Mr. Walter, a physicist who had been fired previously from its position at safety officer in the original Livermore Accelerators, and me; and needless to say, the surrealist suits ended with a technical dismissal by the Pacific supreme court: 'the destruction of Earth won't be attributable to the American government :)

So 5D social sciences as all other branches of this rise of human intellectual consciousness died in 2008, along the financial system, which had been forecasted for 30 years ob our 5D social and economical models.

Why to bring it in this text is obvious: as I Take my bike everyday to ride 5 kilometers to the nearest supermarket, and get stopped by the military police here in Spain at the confluence of the zero and 40 parallels where I chose to retire, in the geometric 'eye' of a perfect symmetric sphere', and have to argue with them, unprotected without masks that I need bread to live, so I can pass the curfew, I observe astonished the way 'western democracies' are resolving with all its 'exceptionalist laws' to make possible its 'cyclical war for profits', based in the true equation that rules capitalism and the Asian cultures around socialist China have avoided:

INDONASIA: THE MODRI NEO-FASCIST APPROACH

Active Cases in India

In the Indonesian civilization, as the culture becomes clearly split into different 'nazionalist' statelets, past long the age of melting pot of cultures and civilizations we highlight the 'colonial view' of its central nation, India, always wanting to be under the Hindi nationalist party, an imitation of Euro-America, without the obvious capacity to become 'yet' a robotic, inhuman, mechanical civilization – in a series of happenings that during the past century have often bordered the surrealism... so Natural to India, the 'Asian peninsula' closer to Italy... Thus we have Modi, when the nation have hardly 1000 cases, and

could perfectly use the Asian techniques of control of pandemic with minimal pain for its people, developing an imitation of the Italian and Spanish view: to enclose everybody at home, but *without the logistics, internet connections, wealth and entertaining dolce fare niente way of life of the Latinos; provoking truly a mass catastrophe among people, millions of which have no 'home' to retire, means of life to sustain a long confinement and will provoke far more pain than the obvious 'Asian system' of health-care control.*

*In the graph, we see the catastrophic effect of Modi's strategy of confining huge families in secluded places without sanitary conditions. Since Confinement contagion has rocketed in India. Thus Modi, the authoritarian fascist ruler of India, will just bring infinite pain without controlling the pandemic, for the sake of showing he is the ruler of it all. From the Guardian: **Divided Delhi under lockdown: 'If coronavirus doesn't kill me, hunger will'***

India's shutdown is catastrophic for Muslims driven from their homes by sectarian carnage without shelter.

Amrit Dhillon in *New Delhi* It wasn't possible for Mohammed Idrish to watch Narendra Modi's address to the nation last Tuesday exhorting 1.3 billion Indians to stay at home. His TV was looted along with everything else in his home in Delhi during the recent anti-Muslim riots in the Indian capital.

When Idrish, a carpenter, heard about Modi urging Indians to stay at home to stop coronavirus spreading, he shook his head again and again. "I don't understand ... I don't understand. Doesn't he know we have no home?" On 25 February, his house in Shiv Vihar was among many reduced to a charred ruin by mobs. The ferocious violence that engulfed the north-east of the city for four days – mostly Hindu mobs killing Muslims and destroying property – left 53 dead and thousands injured.

Families ran with only the clothes they were wearing and mobile phones in their pockets. Hundreds were housed in the Eidgah relief camp, a collection of tents set up in the courtyard of a mosque in Mustafabad.

The camp was a temporary home for Idrish, his parents, wife and four children. It gave them shelter and safety while they waited for compensation to renovate their home. But on Monday the Delhi authorities ordered families to leave the crowded camp for fear it provided the ideal conditions for a perfect viral storm.

The camp's days were numbered even before Modi imposed an unprecedented nationwide lockdown last week, as Delhi had already banned any gathering of more than 30 people.

"From fire burning my home to a camp, I am now being thrown out of a tent because of the coronavirus. I don't understand. They have told me to leave and go and rent a room but what do I pay the landlord?" said Idrish.

The Delhi government says it is giving all the families some rations and 3,000 rupees (£33), the minimum rent for a small room. This leaves no additional money for food. Most landlords also demand a month's deposit. Some families have received rations, others have received money, some have received both, and others neither.

Idrish was given lentils, sugar and rice, and told to leave. After scouring the alleyways around the camp, he found a landlord who agreed to let the family stay in one room for two or three days. "I don't know what I will do in a few days. He will want rent naturally but I don't have anything. I lost everything. I am desperate to work to feed my family, I want to work, but with the lockdown, I can't even work," he said.

The lockdown is catastrophic for the poor in India who live from day to day. Drivers, maids, auto-rickshaw drivers, carpenters, electricians, plumbers, artisans and street vendors buy lentils or vegetables to feed their families from the day's earnings. There are no reserves, well-stocked freezers, or anything saved for a rainy day. As one daily wage laborer said: "If the coronavirus doesn't kill me, hunger will."

For the Muslims whose lives have been devastated by the riots, all of this applies, but worse. With no homes, the Eidgah camp was their main sanctuary, unless they could depend on the charity of relatives who put them up.

Many are grieving for loved ones who were beaten to death, lynched or set on fire. The pain of losing a home is still fresh. Now the coronavirus is battering them all over again.

"My wife snorted with anger when she heard Modi telling us all to stay at home. Our house was torched.

Nothing, not even a clothes hook was left untouched by the fire. Only the walls are left. What home is Modi talking about?" said Abdul Satter, a welder.

He would like to return to start cleaning up his house in Purana Gaon, a village near Khajuri Khas, Delhi, but he and his wife, Mehtab, fear further violence from their Hindu neighbours. "All I have is the blanket I grabbed after my son called us saying a mob was coming and told us to run as fast as we could. I thought the blanket would at least cover my children if we had to sleep on the street," said Mehtab.

Mehtab said she understood the need to take drastic measures to protect people. Delhi has had 30 coronavirus cases and one death. The Eidgah camp – packed with families in unsanitary conditions – is a potential disaster area, she concedes.

What she doesn't understand, however, is where the government expects people like her to go. While some families have received compensation, many others are still waiting for their claims to be processed by the Delhi government.

"If we had got compensation, we could at least have started repairing our homes. I got 25,000 rupees (£257) for my family's immediate needs but there are 18 of us who live together and that money is almost finished. You tell me, where should I go? Where?" said Mehtab.

By Wednesday, with the tents coming down, she and her family had divided themselves among four relatives in the city. With the lockdown in force, they will not be able to see each other for three weeks.

A short distance away, Chandu Nagar, Delhi, has become a refugee colony for riot victims. Some of the Muslim families here have opened their homes to complete strangers. Since a mob burned their two-storey home in Shiv Vihar, Mumtaz Taufir has lived in a rented room measuring 10 x 10ft with his parents, four brothers and their wives.

Taufir watched Modi's address in his landlord's living room. "I wanted to tell him we have become beggars overnight and don't even know what the word home means. If we had a home, we'd be happy to stay in it. But it's gone," he said.

What's equally worrying for him is that the Delhi government's attention will be focused exclusively on fighting the coronavirus for some time. "It means it will take us even longer to get compensation," he said.

HISPANO-AMERICA. THE SURREALISM OF NEO-FASCIST CONQUISTADORS VS. THE INDIANS.

The same bizarre happening takes place in South-America, where the Spanish conquistadors in this neo-fascist age rule with police but care nothing for their poor, and let them die in the streets. The center of the Pandemics is Ecuador, the old Quito province, which we study in detail in our paper on Hispano-America, as the confluence of the Spanish conquistadors, the Inca Empire, the coastal civilizations and the Ayahuasca never-conquered 'head-hunter' culture of the Amazonian.

This melting pot of brutality over the old Indian, Asian-like cultures reaches in a region where the culture of death is natural to their tortuous history, degrees of surrealism, proper of Buñuel L'age d'or – here the leaders not only don't count corpses, they don't even take them to the morgue. On the news here in Spain:

"Dead bodies kept in homes or dumped on roadsides as authorities and hospitals are overwhelmed by Covid-19 in Andean nation's second city "

It has been three days since Reynaldo Barrezueta passed away at his home in Ecuador's biggest city – and still his body lies in a coffin on the sitting room floor.

"The authorities are just leaving us to die," said his son, Eduardo Javier Barrezueta Chávez, who has spent the last 72 hours pleading with authorities remove his father's corpse – so far to no avail. Barrezueta is not alone. In recent days the coronavirus has swept into Guayaquil with deadly force, overwhelming local authorities, funeral homes and hospitals and leaving families such as his facing unthinkable horrors.

Photographs and video footage emerging from this crisis-stricken coastal city look like images from the aftermath of a natural disaster: bodies wrapped in sheets and dumped on the roadside or outside houses; desperate families begging for help after being forced to keep their loved-ones corpses at home for days in temperatures of more than 30C.

So far, few Latin American countries have been worse affected by coronavirus than Ecuador – and nowhere has been worse hit than Guayaquil where nearly half of the country's 3,163 confirmed cases have been recorded. Experts say one explanation is the high levels of air traffic between Ecuador and Spain, which is home to more than 400,000 Ecuadorian migrants and which has the world's second-highest death toll from the disease. The first Covid-19 case recorded in the South American country was of a 71-year-old woman who flew into Guayaquil from Madrid in mid-February and died there on 13 March.

Others suspect Ecuador's failure to quickly impose and enforce effective quarantine measures may have played a role, although the government rejects that charge.

The port city's plight has sent shockwaves across a region where many already fragile health systems are now bracing for a similar wave of patients and deaths.

But in Latin-America and Africa the tragedies of the coronavirus won't matter that much compared to the civil wars, the poverty and famine, the other apocalypse horses far more destructive than the queen of all viruses...

THE 2 PATHS OF THE FUTURE WILL DEFINE THE NEXT AGES OF HISTORY. R=EVOLUTIO OR EXTINCTION

the reproductive system of a historic supœrganism: money.

'The universe is simple and not malicious', 'Simplicity is genius' Einstein, Leonardo

In the graph, a capitalist democracy kills by anoxia and austericide as this crisis shows millions, so money is only handed to speculators to maintain prices. In this crisis what is immediately required is NOT to give money to private banks to sustain market prices but a Universal Salary to every citizen so it can buy masks, medicines and food while isolated at home. Nothing of this is done. Not even free testing is available. It is the hardcore murderous solution of UK: lets them get contagion and died, vs. the Asian, organic, 'true understanding' of societies as social supœrganisms which now *will prove the divergence between those who follow the laws of the Universe and create perfect social supœrganisms, the Asian culture, and those who follow social Darwinism and dog-eat-dog societies with the 0.1% of stockrats on top and the population murdered at lower cost with a virus that only serves to establish the big brother military control we thought it would come in the 2020s in an age of war, but pandemic is even more handy, as people are weary of war but obey the pandemic 'new approach' to militarization and null true health-care and welfare resources.*

Back in the 2000s when I was chair of Monetary systems at the International Systems Society I demanded an 'organic, understanding of money' as the blood of the economy, which should be handled to every human being in the form of a Universal Salary in ¥€\$ money (an International currency at fixed price, 1 \$ = 1 €=100 ¥=20 Yuans, delivered in mobile cryptocurrencies today to every citizen of the world). Because that is the true meaning of money not WEALTH per se but the language of information and reproduction of the economy , which a healthy organism is created and handled to every cell to kick out orders of production; so people NOT only speculators could invent money to survive creating a demand economy. Since all the money today is created NOT FOR WELFARE GOODS, PEOPLE NEED TO SURVIVE, but to speculate in the market for the 0.2%. This has become blatantly clear in the coronavirus crisis, where only China has provided masks to every person, to avoid contagion (which is the key problem here as the virus spreads with the maximal speed at an exponential rate, 2.8, the number e), massively invested in hospitals and respirators and testing. Asians thus as 'organic members', citizens-cells who understand naturally bio-history have come out of it. Europe and America though has shown the brutality of the system, from the hardest, deranged UK-US capitalist center who does not test people, applies social Darwinism expecting 'people to suffer contagion' NOT to spend money on them, so the old die, or in America those without health-care are tagged as 'untouchables', and *the most amazing of all, central bankers, just lowered interest rates and gave 700 billion not to the people but to the bankers to speculate and keep the prices of stocks floating.*

This hardcore classic economists, whose ideological agenda to The service of private financing origin of The hidden governments of capitalists democracies 'believe' that money belongs to them and their corporations whom they serve, private banks, have NOT established an IMMEDIATE UNIVERSAL SALARY, as we preached for 20 years, so all those people isolated at home (because that is the only thing capitalist dictatorships do, take the military and control people, unlike Asians who have provided what was required, masks to avoid contagion, free testing and *respirators, we shall keep repeating it*).

There is zero mystery about the future which we have forecasted for 30 years with absolute precision since we self-publish after rejection by economic think tanks and publishers, in a small print now deceased, whose name I liked 'Bookmasters', along the main laws of 5D. At that time I finally realized why it was impossible to explain bio-economics. Simply speaking, what we call classic economics was the brain child NOT of historians concerned

with human life, or even mathematicians, concerned with the quantitative patterns of re=production but with employees of those company-mothers. So obviously they didn't bite the 'hand that feeds them'. Moreover an immense majority of them – including Nobel prizes given by a private bank, belonged to the JAM culture, whose biblical segregational go(l)d memes, considered irrelevant the well-being of the 99%. They were mostly financiers – the father of the discipline Mr. Ricardo was a Jewish stock-broker, his forebear, Mr. Adam Smith a Calvinist 'client' of the Montagu family owner of the private bank of England. And so ultimately there is a group of humans, the owners of stock companies, we shall call ari-stockrats, which owned them and had a very narrow primitive memetic view of what humans are, what is their purpose – to serve them, the chosen – and why nothing else matters but go(l)d. But so few, and so narrow views were multiplied ad infinitum by the information machines the 'head' of the metal-earth, which we call the Financial-media-Academia system used to print money and imprint the mind of people.

So I coined the concept of the anti-quantum paradox: me, the social scientist is so small compared to them, the company-mother of information and its anti-humanist stockrats that they will never distribute the true science of economics that could easily make the world a perfect immortal organism of History

How that could be done is simple. Money is only a number and its function is the same as that of oxygen in red blood cells, but an organism IS democratic economically, all bones produce red blood cells and all cells receive them, that is democracy and it works in all organisms : Adult humans have roughly 20–30 trillion red blood cells at any given time, constituting approximately 70% of all cells by number. they should NOT invent money, it would have to be given to all humans as the organism does in massive quantities and then all people would demand food and things they need and the world would be a paradise, but not even people can understand that they live in a state of permanent leukemia.

Because financial companies invent their language of re=production of goods, money...

The universe is 'simple and not malicious' if financiers have made their monopolistic systems of reproduction of money complicated is to avoid that people understand, the nature of languages to keep that privilege.

Indeed, the culture who hold that monopoly throughout western history are hardly 0.02% of mankind even if they make up +70% of CEOs of financial companies, CFOs, central bankers and Nobel prizes of economics given by a bank they also own. And throughout history the way they have come on top of mankind is rather simple .

For 3000 years at least in the historic record, they have understood the legal & financial sources of power.

It's all very simple, whenever their nomadic people, who were called 'wanderers' in Sumerian arrived to a nation with huge quantities of go(l)d they bought the right to make the money of that nation to kings or politicians. They paid 'whatever' they were asked, and then with that privilege increased the production of 'digital numbers' of money. So they could buy for 'free' as a digital number cost near nothing to print, the more so when instead of gold it was printed on paper; any thing, and anyone. Just print money and give it to them. So it is only a matter of time that their dominated the societies where they hosted.

But greed has no limit. So instead of keeping a balance on top of society, controlling with the issue of money politics, buying people with salary and properties; they wanted everything. And so in all their cycles they practiced new forms of parasitic money to keep becoming every more rich: debt usury, slave trade, weapons trade of maximal profits as weapons by affinity with metal was the most expensive good in terms of go(l)d, etc. So they caused a massive leukemia and anoxia in the population. Leukemia is the sickness of red cells – it is the parasitic conversion of money, NOT in something used to produce welfare goods but to reproduce lethal goods. And anoxia the lack of credit to create the future the lack of money as they kept it for themselves.

So once they dominate everything they squeezed people into absolute poverty until people burst in r=evolutions, wars – as weapons were overreproduced to make profits - and holocausts.

How this process happened so many times in history without anyone putting a limit to it?

Even if once the nation was corrupted and collapsed, the parasitic go(l)d culture also died? Could not mankind change the brutality of the economic cycle of 'expert' bankers and create a simple system of reproduction of money as in the Neolithic when money was just 'grain', oxygen given to all humans and cities and cultures were wealthy beyond belief?

The fact is they couldn't. As the go(l)d culture, once it monopolized the banking industry would never stop giving their part to the powerful of each nation, aristocrats, politicians, military, and marry their 'daughters' with them. So especially in the JAM culture they came to form a nucleus of power, camouflaged behind warriors and aristocrats, symbiotic of weapons and money that ruled the world. And as the 'animetal system of power' expanded to other nations it came to be the 'new normal'.

Then as information machines multiplied not only money but 'idol-ogies' in favor of such aberrant leukemia, cancerous system, even the people with anoxia felt happy to be exploited and with no credit, as they were imprinted by bibles, classic economics yellow press, hate-radio, hate-TV, you name it. Even when military and financial power quarreled as in II w0orld war, the people below suffered from one or the other side. What they never understood is how simple a perfect world would be. For example, I proposed when I was head of monetary systems in the international social systems ISSS, - a universal salary of 1000 ¥ € S money, in euro-dollars in crypto currency to each human on your phone making fixed coins (1 euro = 1 dollar = 100 yen.) This would have immediately ended migration from third world, multiplied the production of food and welfare goods to satisfy their needs as they would have now 'oxygen red blood to pay for it', and readdress the production from machines and weapons to human goods.

But there was no interest on academia. The only interested people on the paper were the people-caste in power that watch everything, the FMAsters, Financial-Media-Academy masters, who choose what they distribute with their information machines. But of course, they never tell you the reason why you are censored. So the president of the ISSS Miss Wilby got a letter from a 'minority' member of the 'community' who denounced the paper for 'bias' against 'them' (no naming, nothing was indicated for the reasons why the paper was erased from the servers and google scholar and I was not given those conferences again). Latter I learned the association had been threatened with a suit for discrimination.. Why? Just because in a footnote I indicated that financial economics had been overwhelmingly dominated and was still dominated by a single 'culture' and so many of its 'scientific postulates', were 'cultural ones' and offered a list with the names of all the central bankers of the most developed economies of the west, US, France, UK, Canada, EU, Switzerland even Germany, all belong to this minority culture. That was the end of ¥es money and then came the 1.4 trillion tax-farming of Americans for the scam of CDOs and people let themselves be squeezed of their last drops of money so billionaires could a trillion to their accounts. Had things changed? Not of course, they have gone to worst, as now all the money of the 3rd world goes through the touch of a bottom, in a Bloomberg platform to speculate in trillion \$ companies. So now the whole planet can be squeezed and the 99% globally lives in permanent anoxia and Leukemia (two related sicknesses that affect both the availability of credit for the people (anoxia) and the quality of the money reproduced (leukemia, as money is invented overwhelming for lethal goods)...

But as long as the same people that own information machines print money, audiovisual information and the authorized 'academia papers' distributed in the world of economics, mankind will walk steadily towards suicide in an state of permanent poverty when even the smaller supœrganism has ample supply of oxygen for all cells, so none dies of hunger.

Yes money of course has never surfaced, even if today people talk but do nothing about a Universal salary at Davos, as AI robots will keep throwing them from work and Bloomberg will keep siphoning till the last penny of the 3rd world hold by dictators to which we provide liberally wit weapons, to speculate in stocks and fatten the accounts of Goldman sachs et al.

Cryptocurrencies also have evolved fast but only for speculation and soon for a perfect world of robotic machines that will indeed use cryptocurrencies, not as I wanted but my lectures on yes-money, to cure the sicknesses of history ... because they realized this was a simple solution, like oxygen is to keep all humans WHealthy, awash with healthy goods.

Good Money is a social language of digital information. Parasitic money is metal, privately owned money.

On the biological and evolutionary models of 'bio-economics' we must understand the duality of money, both as a language of information that carries 'certain values', different from other languages (human verbal

languages) and as a 'substance', informative metal, which sets its properties and affinities with the other 'dominant' products of an economic ecosystem, weapons and machines.

Have you ever wonder why everybody talks about money but nobody knows how to define it?...

One of the most fascinating facts about Economics is the ignorance of people, including economists about its fundamental element, money. Humans seem obsessed by money; so are economists, the so-called 'experts' of this discipline. And yet, nobody has properly defined money in 3000 years of obsession. So we should the sciences of economics and history, its species, languages, cycles and organisms seen with the novel perspective of Theory of Information, Systems sciences and complexity with a definition of it:

'Money is a language of digital information'

Money is just a number, the simplest form of information in a paper, which orders humans and objects in a digital, mathematical number. So capitalism amounts to this: to rule societies with digital numbers called money, reproduced with no limit by a social elite, which is not elected neither likes to explain what it does, and how it does it - basically controlling Mankind with prices as if we are objects compared mathematically with the equation of money: *Man (salary) = money = object (price)*

This is an efficient form to 'put together men and objects' in work fields. But it must stress that as people are not objects, ethic wor(l)ds, our informative language must control the 'excess' of the reproductive digital language, not to 'undervalue, humans'

We humans talk with 2 languages, verbal words and digital numbers. And when we use those 2 languages to create, organize and evolve social organisms, we call them 'laws' and 'money'. But while most people understand the "law" and the way it organizes social systems, none has properly studied money as a language of digital information and how it evolves and organizes economic systems. And this is one of the main reasons our economic systems and societies *are so badly designed*.

The reason why this is happening has to do with the shortcomings of the human mind regarding digital languages. We are born with a genetic capacity to talk words (Chomsky). So every human can 'invent' words and combine them in meaningful sentences able to value all the beings that surround us. But do not talk mathematics, naturally and so since our 'neurons' do not support the digital language, we have had to evolve it externally, using 'other supports' to perceive mathematics.

And this difference between words, our internal, biological language and numbers, perceived externally as we learned to count has made all the difference; and explains many of the peculiarities of money as a language. And the way it has built our economic organism, which let us be clear from the beginning, is very poorly constructed. Indeed, the first fact about information people tend to forget is that it is 'subjective'. Each mind uses a different language of information and it gives with it values to the Universe, *from its selfish perspective*.

Languages are systems of information that certain species use to value reality from their point of view. For example, words are the biological language of man. So we use them to value reality from our human perspective and that means life has a maximal value, while in money it has NO value at all.

Let us then understand with the laws of Systems Sciences and Theory of Information the 2 languages of social power of mankind, money and laws, its values and how they choose a certain future for all of us.

Money is a language of digital information, which has evolved as all languages increasing its digital purity as a number (logic syntax that matters more than support), it has increased its numbers of bytes, as information machines have been able to reproduce more units of it, it has decreased its size as information evolves diminishing its 'energy-space' and increasing its speed, finally valuing all things on earth, including men as objects, substituting and making obsolete the alternative human, verbal ethic language that evolved slower than digital languages and money did. However a proper understanding of the languages of Nature, could easily reform the system of money, make it complementary to the 'nervous system' of laws, as a blood-reproductive-oxygen system is, and then distribute enough quantity of it to all human citizens cells, to create a perfect world, as all healthy wealthy super organisms of nature are, where all its cells receive its proper oxygen-hormonal salary and all of them survive. It is the parasitic, anti-human, corrupted nature of our 'social networks' where a few 'parasitic' financiers control the issue of money and either herd it for themselves or give it only to company-

mothers of machines they worship due to their 'biblical, primitive segregational ideologies' against mankind what makes the global eco(nomic)system perhaps the worst of all systems of Nature, as I used to explain during my tenure of the chair of Monetary Systems at the International Systems Sciences society, till obviously those who 'own' the financial system stop inviting me...

A corrupted system can only be protected with censorship and unneeded complexity to camouflage corruption. We see, the types of money which have radiated as new 'financers' discovered them and used wrongly to speculate in prices, price all things including humans as objects, (price=object=man (salary) etc.

The science of economics as a true social science, is the science of the 're=productive, blood-like system' of the organism of mankind in time, History, whose natural purpose would be to provide all human beings, citizen-cells of our supœrganism, with the goods they need to survive and repress as blood-systems do the lethal goods that harm our body (weapons) and minds (hate memes, racist cultural memplexes, fiction thought that isolate us and create virtual 'mad-minds') etc.

We explain this simple fact and in the graphs that show the basic structure of the supœrganism of mankind and its 'economic frame of reference' that should value goods and control its production according to their biological utility to foster the drives of life of human beings, making us thrive as individual and species, because we need first to understand a true science of economics to have a perspective on what today passes as 'economics', NOT a science but a PRAXIS OF power:

History is the super organism of the human, species, as in systemics, informative species can be modeled as supœrganisms, whose individual 'citizen-cells' use an informative and reproductive language to build its social networks that distribute efficiently vital energy and information to its individuals, making the whole stronger and allowing a higher density of population. However when a system is ill-designed it will NOT provide just information and enough energy for its cells to survive. And this is the case of humanity, ill-designed by cultural memes of nationalism that divide the species into false tribal ones, to foster the ab=use of humans with weapons and the ill-designed capitalist system in which money is NOT the oxygen of society that must be delivered to each citizen-cell to start the reproduction and consumption of goods, but a parasitic digital language, monopolized in its issue by a small 'cancerous group' of 'experts', classic economists, working as financiers and company-managers that 'choke' mankind of its productive credit necessary to reproduce the healthy goods humanity need to survive (welfare goods), while allowing the massive reproduction of lethal goods of higher price that kill our body and minds. So we live in a sick system, 'infected of lethal goods', weapons and hate media, parasitized by a cancerous elite that monopolizes the issue of our blood language, and needless to say with a neuronal, 'informative people-caste' of politicians and military that instead of serving the body or else receiving judgment-pain messages to oblige them to attend the needs of its population, dedicate most of its efforts to kill people (military) with the excuse they are boxed under a false border-membrane buttressed with lethal weapons, or serve the financial parasites and its companies of lethal goods, with the excuse they don't issue money, so they need to be corrupted and the alibi of immunity with no pain messages delivered as in earlier Greek democracies by the population that should vote=judge them after tenure. So we live in a system which enslaves people unlike in an efficient supœrganism of Nature, without parasitic and lethal germs=weapons, where its economic=reproductive and energetic=welfare and political=informative networks deliver the welfare goods and right synchronous=equalitarian orders to all cells. So should a properly designed human supœrganism of history, where the ethic, verbal wor(l)d values of a political class, bound by judgment a posteriori to serve the needs of people will limit the production of lethal goods, issue money to multiply the reproduction of welfare goods and make history immortal with diplomatic EU, UNO like institutions on top of the fractal military nations built during the primitive 'age of animetal history'. The only future for mankind thus would happen if our leading capitalist, nationalist cultures, and Financial-Media-Academia systems evolved its fundamentalist metal idol-ogies that despise the values and welfare life goods humans need to survive - despite its disguise of placebo caring newspeak of political and economical correctness, and impose a true social science of the economic reproductive and political legal system based in the efficient designs of nature's supœrganisms to create with credit a more humane, legal-ruled global culture EU-UNO style, where laws control

the lethal goods of the tree of science and money credits only the production of welfare, WHealth (healthy life goods).

The substance and language, form and functions of money.

In terms of its characteristics as an informative language, money evolved as all languages do, by increasing its capacity to carry information. So it has become more quantized into smaller bits of information and it has increases its numbers, its capacity to be reproduced with minimal energy, as it changed substance, from gold to printed paper, to electronic data, which can be invented with a simple computer program Languages share by definition the properties of information: they are quantized, to be able to have 'form'; they are small to be able to process that information easily; and they have minimal energy and an enormous 'fractal' capacity to reproduce. So money has become smaller, easier to reproduce and more quantized, as a 'carrier' of digital information. In that process it has increased the capacity to value more objects and life forms on planet Earth.

Today it is so abundant that it can value all beings of the planet, substituting verbal thought in the valuation of reality. And since it values machines and weapons more than any other object, it has multiplied wars and terraformed the world to their image and likeness.

Money possessed 3 formal characteristics: it is made of metal, gold, silver, copper, today computer machines that reproduce e-money. *But this is only because metal can be broken and counted and last. The essence of money is to be mathematical, able to compare products and relate them, to maximize the efficiency of production. For that reason* it is made of cyclical, broken, discontinuous shapes, as all forms that carry in-form-ation. Money, due to this informative property, is the basic unit of mathematical accounting and one of the main reasons why mathematics have been evolved as a language. Thus, money is a language of information whose substances are metal and whose function is to give value to things with digital information. In that sense, money competes with words, because both are languages used by mankind to value reality. So the fundamental question about money and the future of history, today controlled by monetary orders, is: 'how money values reality and why those values differ from the values of verbal thought? If money were used according to human values, it could create a paradise. But as it is used – as a parasitic form of control of people, according to the 'cultural values' of the animetal segregation cult(ure)s of Go(l)d that imposed its form, it kills life.

A true science of Economics is ethical because it is biological, so it is 'ethonomics' and its frame of reference who must value goods for its usefulness to humanity NOT in terms of go(l)d values as the JAM culture wrongly has done, imposing its false 'science of biblical economics' treated in depth in our paper on 'History and entropy'.

The corruption of our 'networks of information' by metal-communicators and hate memes.

A final element that corrupts mankind is precisely the lack of ethical messages and a culture of social love, proper of the age of religions and verbal, literary languages, which carry the human ethical, survival instincts and today have been substituted by audiovisual violent memes of null social value. As the 'animal eye' is a natural born killer. So today ethic messages have been substituted by networks of 'metal-communicators' that imprint people with hate memes and make their minds, virtual 'fictional', ready to follow a 'sheep behavior' of acquiescence to the corrupted system they are told to be the best of all worlds, regardless on how inefficient is, as the coronavirus crisis has shown.

So we need to get real first about our system. A capitalist system is akin to a 'worm' that poisons itself with 'greed' because its re=productive blood system is more developed than its informative, legal, nervous one, 'company-mothers' can re=produce and evolve any lethal good. So this minimal state of evolution of mankind as a social supœrganism means we are constantly being 'poisoned' by lethal goods.

Only very primitive systems reproduce and devour lethal products dying in the process, as worms and capitalist societies ruled by company-mothers of machines-weapons, which as the only 'free

citizens' of markets have rights to re=produce and evolve any lethal good. An efficient supœrganism however is rule by the nervous system that controls production and forbids with its immune system the existence of lethal goods. This means that above the reproductive system there must be human governments with the goal of making a world to the image and likeness of man using our informative, nervous ethic, legal and leukocyte, health-care system to that aim. Further on in an efficient supœrganism the economy is a 'demand' economy where money, the oxygen of society, is delivered to all citizens-cells with a universal salary provided by red cells so they can kick their actions of reproduction and consumption of the welfare goods they need to survive. In our capitalist system money is reproduced overwhelmingly by financiers and companies of the Financial-Media (informative machines) Military-Industrial (energy machines) that rule the world, with its monopoly to foster the reproduction of their goods of maximal profit, which happen to be the most expensive top predator weapons and the cheaper to repeat, audiovisual fiction software which 'kill the body and rational mind' of mankind. So the outcome is that politicians, industrialists and the military often defend the lethal germs that kill history, instead of destroying them and provide the life-welfare goods humans need to survive. A reform of the financial systems returning to humanity through a Universal salary the right to reproduce money and the prohibition of the reproduction of lethal goods is an essential element if History wants to 'exist'.

We must stress from the beginning the essential learning that for 30 years I have tried to spread on deaf ears about the nature of 5D social sciences: *the rulers of mankind must act as doctors of History, because History is a superorganism; and its leukocytes, the people who truly save lives are NOT the military that kill but the doctors that cure. In any superorganism of Nature, the defensive system cures the cells of the body; it does NOT kill it. So we will at a certain point deal with the fact no human culture wants to deal: the military is an aberration and the increase of expenditures in military systems is what makes countries like US, the center of pandemics as there is no money to cure their sick, since it spends ½ of its resources piling up weapons for the profits of its company-mothers. So technology and the cost-benefit elements of economics have to be input to understand why mankind is defenseless in front of the coronavirus.*

In the graph, the main parasitic forms of money that completely subvert the proper form Nature distributes the language of re=production through its blood-oxygen networks. The outcome is a lack of 'wealth' for the common people that in a crisis as the present one, caused by an excess of repressive measures and tools that 'had to be used' for lack of health-care resources, will get out of job and suffer the biggest economical crisis of a century.

The SOMA of the FED, the ECB auctions, the innumerable forms to speculate and multiply money for a few are just disguises of a cancerous system. An efficient society that served the 99.9% would cre(dit)ate (create with credit) a perfect world very easily by eliminating most of that and simply creating every year $12 \times 1.000 \times 7.777.777.777$ human beings as of this month of april 2020 = ± 100 trillion ¥€\$ 'eurodollars' to create a demand economy spent in welfare goods the common people use to survive; as the body has 30 trillion red cells delivering oxygen to every cell. Instead the complex, parasitic system allows a few thousands to have as much as those 7 billion. The same goes with the parasitic military system. With a fraction humans spent on that wasteful murderous global endeavor, the immunological health-care system could cure every human being, and evidently it would have halted the pandemics within days. A simple process of a posteriori vote for all politicians and the study from high school onwards of 5D social sciences would solve the entire theme of political corruption. While the limits to 'fiction' in all its forms, from lies, to advertising, to ideologies of nationalism, techno-utopia and capitalist worship of weapons, machines and money above man, would certainly re-educate humanity in the understanding of the living Universe. Such a world did in fact exist in the Neolithic, before the age of 'metal' brought on top of mankind the parasitic elites that today are constructed a world not to the image and likeness of life. They proved that ideal history is not an utopia, as it existed through classic ethic, verbal social networks that constructed human efficient societies in which 'religions of love' made people share energy and information with the community.

Generally a short timeline of less than one year
High Profits
Aggressive
Based on technical charts, market psychology and individual opinion
Options, foreign currencies, Stock market,

ODD SPECULATION
MATTER OF LIFE AND DEATH

Speculation on prices redirects Wealth to stock-companies and still causes famines globally

Taxation today by an alliance of politicians/military & bankers today as in the past extorts common hard working people,

CAPITALIST PLACEBO DEMOCRACIES ENSLAVE MA TO COMPANY-MOTHERS OF MACHINES-WEAPON kill by anoxia throughout the entire life

The main historic and present forms of parasitic money work as a cancerous system that absorbs most of the resources of the economy that humans should use to reproduce WHealth, the welfare goods the biologic=ethoomic frame of reference considers positive and a demand economy based in a Universal salary will produce without limit, but lacking credit cannot buy:

From left to right, gold as wealth subverted the meaning of money as a language of information and gave by affinity maximal value to weapons; it caused the concept of debt money and usury interests today the basis of human slavery and global anoxia. It multiplied weapons and created from slavery to military dictatorships. Above, speculation, based in the increase of the 'speed of circulation of money' ($Mv=pt$) is rife, distorting the allocation of goods, its production and absorbing the mass of money to those who fix prices in 'free markets'.

±3 REFORMS OF THE PHYSIOLOGIC NETWORKS OF MANKIND TO MAKE HISTORY IMMORTAL.

We shall now consider a simple statement regarding the laws of survival of the living universe:
A system which closer resembles the ideal superorganism has a higher chances to survive.
This is therefore the fundamental use for a praxis of social sciences of the laws of 5D as the reform of human systems should follow those laws if they were meant to improve the livelihood and efficiency of societies.
Because human systems are so far removed from that ideal physiological 3 network system, the ideal society seems so remote that it might be impossible to reach it. But that will not change the law. It will simply mean that mankind will be extinguished as a superorganism this century, point. The laws of the 5D Universe are objective and cannot be 'served' at the will of the human egocly believer in some religion of supremacy or idol-ogy of capitalism, nationalism, techno-utopia, you name it. Stience is not a menu of subjective wishful thinking.
Moreover, 'the Universe is simple and not malicious' (Einstein), so the understanding of those necessary 3 ± reforms of the physiological networks of mankind are easy to follow, as all systems of the Universe that last, from the simplest atom to the galaxy do. So it doesn't require more than a page to consider them.

in the graph, which we repeat often using the 'anti-Goebbels method' against the antitruths of the networks of audiovisual media (if you repeat a truth many times people might understand it), the 3+3 *physiological* solutions of the science of supœrganisms to change the non-future of Mankind in an automated metal-Earth.

They are the positive and negative necessary changes in the '3 Physiological networks of mankind' that will make the world a perfect, immortal planet; from left to right:

- REFORM OF THE DEFENSIVE, IMMUNOLOGICAL SYSTEM. The positive scientific element is the enhancement of HUMAN STIENCES, Medicien – a true health-care system; Humanities and 5D social sciences, the true sciences of mankind as an organism, while in the negative side is the legal prohibition of robotics and other lethal goods that kill the superorganisms of mankind. *This means a reform of the military system whose function should NOT be to*

reproduce and use lethal weapons to kill mankind but exactly the opposite: to localize and destroy the lethal 'germs' of history, the aforementioned 3 Δ-1 faster matter, mental and biological species that can kill humanity.

Of course you might say that humans have tried this for eons, first through prophets of social love and of late through United Nations and EU like diplomatic organizations but 'animetal warriors' have always come on top.

Granted, but the fact that humans might be corrupted beyond salvation doesn't change the laws of 5D superorganisms, and only means we do have to study also the laws of extinction and forecast as we have done for decades to deaf ears the existential risks to mankind. This is also part of 5D social sciences. What is NOT part of 5D social sciences is the antiquantum paradox: the bending of truths to cater the ideologies of power: 'you will defend me with the sword and I will defend you with the word' Tertulian.

It doesn't matter that a corrupted organism does NOT hear the doctor and commits suicide, the doctor of history is not going to change its remedies for placebo truths if he is a serious social scientist. I couldn't care less that for 30 years 5D social sciences have had no followers because the entire panoply of Financial-Media-Academia Masters of America with its metal-communicators and think-tanks are inventing a 'superstructure' of damned lies and statistics to cater to the Financial, capitalist society and its myths of the free market... It is up to them if they prefer as it seems to move towards self-extinction of life, because they love to count digital numbers of money. So goes for the blind 99% of cells below them that prefer to live as DATA in the parable of Matrix on a virtual soma that face reality.

Which leads to consider the two physiological ± reforms required in the FINANCIAL, REPRODUCTIVE BLOOD SYSTEM:

On the positive side, the issue of a universal salary to create a demand-based real economic democracy by people through an international yes currency to create welfare demand, today easily achieved with a cryptocurrency, at 100 ¥= Euro≈\$ parity, given to each human in a 'mobile pocket app', could establish an immediate massive demand economy in welfare goods globally, plummeting enormously the poverty of 3rd world nations, the migration problem and the excessive reproduction of lethal goods common people won't demand. The emission of a cryptocurrency in this coronavirus crisis to all citizens with the payment of its salary as free debt money providing its companies are banned from fire them, would have solve the entire question of the economic crisis that will come after. But as money is considered a parasitic debt form of wealth obviously no government has taken this measure, and all central bankers, whose job in a democracy is to reproduce as many digital numbers of money for private bankers. The entire financial system is a corrupted parasitic system, hauling from millennia of bad-practices, cause of much suffering due to the overreproduction of lethal goods, mostly weapons and usury money, and its subsequent cycles of war and holocausts, perfectly avoidable if the system produced welfare money. In fact most western bankers specially in the original Anglo-American civilization are the same the dynastic groups, moving from private to public banking, and in the west overwhelmingly belonging to the old Jewish-Protestant Biblical Go(I)d racist religions even if today as Shakespeare put it 'evil dress as a gentleman'; so their primitive modes of thinking have changed little, only the sophistication of its newspeaks and the much more profound control of corrupted politics, mass-media and academia system. So this is probably the most pressing problem of mankind: the reform of money from a false language of debt and parasitic slavery to a proper language of social oxygen and a demand economy.

-To split all shares of all companies, giving to Mankind, either national governments, or better, international cultures and like-like institutions the split 50% to allow national and international institutions to manage even forbid lethal companies, obliging them to serve truly consumers, without losing managerial skills.

This is also a necessary measure the negative one, to be able to repress the reproduction of digital technologies beyond human control, bio-technology able to edit lethal pathogens, and virons (metal-bacteria), and weapons of mass destruction. Only if mankind and its nervous, political system can control the worm-like systems of capitalism where company-mothers can reproduce any lethal goods, humans would be able to control the species that will extinguish us.

While in the political arena, 2 measures tending to create real democracies and a global government in charge of the management of the world requires:

-The reorganization of nations EU style in the 7 original cultures of history. Nations are a historical aberration born of

tribal warfare. The true civilisations of history latter studied in more detail are those of the graph, geographical, cultural and religious civilisations with an extreme similarity that should come together into supranational organisms.

-The creation of real democracy, Greek style, where politicians are chosen as experts or from the common people by lottery but vote is a posteriori as a judgment with penalties of jail to oblige politicians to serve people. This is obviously the most important measure since as long as the people cannot send pain messages to judge the biohistorians on top, which must learn the science of bio-history and act as doctors of history, and receive a judgment a posteriori to oblige them to behave and serve, as the summit of any superorganism with a single head, NOT PARTIES, only scientists of History, a requisite to become a civil servant, since obviously as a physicist must learn his science, a politician and financier must learn the laws of social physiology, but also be accountable for its actions, there will NOT be democracy, and the system will be corrupted. This, needless to say, doesn't happen in any nation so **there is NOT a single democracy in the world.**

-And finally a revolution which can come ideally from the top to the bottom governments (Uno assembly, 'mule', stock rats caring for the future) or from people through the vote of r=evolutionary parties, or the take over 'occupy wall street' style, of the centers of financial-media/government power.

We illustrate those 3+3 measures, which are the scientific simple measures of the science of systems applied to social sciences, taking from imitation those 3+3 measures imitating nature where cells send pain messages to the brain, have all its salary in oxygen to kick out production of goods, so no-one dies of hunger, lethal goods are not allowed to enter the organism, killed by leucocytes, organs of the body collaborate as nations of history should together, and do not use lethal weapons but talk with hormones in diplomatic channels to achieve the common good, could change the world within years. So only a r=evolution with the science of history as the guidance of the planet can save Mankind from extinction. It is then necessary a people-caste of bio-historians, as in foundation (Asimov's trilogy on history), to take over, and make a needed r=evolution of the system applying the laws of physiological history, to reform the economic, reproductive and informative legal system with the 6 measures that would make both physiological networks work for Mankind: how easy would be to implement the measures? As simple as Mr. Potus wanting them, since it would only require 3 people, an Asimovian mule, Mr. Potus, Mr. Eu and Mr. China (Mr. Pec - a perfect triad of global power), but Mr. Potus alone could easily convince 'organic China' the not advanced human super organism in any time of history, to join and the rest would follow.

Now this is ideal history and so any reform moving on the direction of those 3 ± actions will move the 'frame of reference' OF mankind, the ethonomic frame of actions and goods towards the ideal frame of reference of a world made to the image and likeness of humanity, which will serve our species, and as it happens in any efficient organism, deliver to each individual cell all the goods and just laws and welfare it needs to maximize its freedoms and existence, as only individual citizens-cells that live in a perfect superorganism of history can enjoy a perfect life and maximize all its potential as human beings.

Needless to say in such a superorganism of history the absurdity of this pandemic, or the war ages that kill humanity will never have happened. So while this planet might never reach that perfect society, any reform towards that end would be positive, and the fact that some civilisations are closer to the perfect society and survive better it is a clear prove those laws happen. Indeed, the Asian cultures, are such societies even if they lack the a posteriori judgment of its politicians, as those feel serving the superorganism of its people in a higher measure than the west, they have tried to cure them of the pandemic and have NOT just as the west have done, pretended nothing did happen, keep serving their true masters, company-mothers of lethal goods, and once pandemic stroke, took the troops to the streets, not the health-care undernourished, underfunded true warriors of the immunological system.

So capitalist democracies are simply 'capitalist societies' where the rights of its true free citizens, company-mothers of informative machines and weapons and speculative money are paramount. And we can then treat them as 'mechanical systems' guided by a mathematical equation of profits: max. speculative money (economic network) = Max. price (weapon, defensive system) – min. cost (¥-waves of audiovisual software).

The 'attached' word democracy as has null value as long as there are not:

- Capacity to deliver pain messages back to the politicians that mismanage their office.
- Exceptional laws that allow to break all the freedoms and rights of its people when politicians please, to amend their genocidal errors in case of war declarations or pandemic tragedies.

A capitalist society has a single aim: to evolve the technological machines of its company-mothers according to its maximal profits given by those top predator machines of maximal price, weapons, of minimal cost of reproduction, audiovisual software and hate memes, and profit itself (speculative money). While politicians that cannot be judged a posteriori with pain messages are a 'crazy' nervous system that doesn't feel the 'pain' of the citizens-cells they abuse systematically to cater the needs of those companies for whom humans are just 'enzymes', re-producers of machines and 'animetals' that test and vitalize them for further evolution.

This system should be reformed and if politicians were not so corrupted at this point, the crisis would have become the catalyzer for a 5D reform of the society, adapting the two fundamental basic measures, we proposed in our conferences as head of monetary systems at the international systems society prior to the ad hominem campaigns that ended my careers. Very simple: after tenure judgment, and a Universal salary to convert the economy from a supply economy based in the massive overproduction of lethal goods in a worm-like organism, into an efficient human-like superorganism, based in the demand economy, a true democratic economy of citizens receiving a universal cryptocurrency ¥€\$ money salary to demand the goods they need to survive, food, shelter, health-care...

At this stage only China and the Asian countries that have a system closer to the ideal society could implement such efficient superorganism with 3 simple reforms:

- To evolve socialist, Marxist doctrines, which so closely resembles the laws of the Universe to biological organic systemic 5D, which ARE the laws of the Universe, and keep evolving them, in Asian Universities. This could have been done also in the European Union before the end of its social democratic welfare states with the take over of Germany neo-Nazi capitalist system and its hijacking of credit with the ECB Frankfurt private bank.
- Establishment of an after tenure judgment of all communist party officials which is a MUST to validate a single head organism. Organisms have NOT twin Siamese, colliding heads-parties on top, which as we analyze in our papers on capitalist democracies, are not established for democratic reasons but for inefficient purposes to better control governments. Historically they appeared when the orange single party of the first capitalist democracy ruled by the single VOC slave and gunboat company in Ho9lland split into two type of companies according to the war peace cycle of technology, which switches between top predator weapons that consume humans in war after overreproduction crisis of peaceful machines that we consume... So in England there were now two parties, both ruled by the stockrats, holders of the companies, which switched from war ages when gunboats made more money looting the Iberian and 3rd world empires and trade companies, Tories and Whigs.

Any efficient superorganism has a single party-head *ruled by scientific laws, but all have the true measure of demoreacy – pain messages after tenure as in greek democracies*, where there was de facto a single party – in fact most positions were just allotted by lottery among all citizens, as they were deemed efficient and wise enough to rule their citizens, knowing naturally what is best for society, while experts in war and law were chosen for specific positions, but all were judged a posteriori. If the Chinese communist party adopted this self-control measure it would become de facto a TRUE DEMOCRACY unlike capitalist ones. Otherwise they will NEVER be validated as a social organism in the world at large and among its citizens. The same goes for the PDL in Japan, and the de facto dictatorships of Singapore and Taiwan. - The next obvious measure the communist party and all parties in the world should adopt is – the more so in this economic crisis – a global currency ¥€\$ money, to avoid the complete collapse of the economy. This is what the present 1/3rd and growing state of absolute rest of the human global superorganism needs, and should maintain as money is a language of information not wealth per se, that must be issued to create the actions of production and consumption needed by the economy.

Such salary would completely solve the economic crisis, avoid further absurd speculation and currency wars by ending the FOREX casino and its unfair taxes in all country.

An example: you can automate a profit cycle in currencies, between the euro/Pound, the Dollar and the Yen. Because the 3 markets close and open continuously and each nation needs its currency it sells the other two that are dormant. So people in FOREX buy dollars when the Euro closes, sell them and buy Yens when wall street closes and buy pounds/Pounds and sell yens when Tokyo closes, taxing the entire system with its mathematical profits, which in times of normal functioning of the economy rip you a 10% daily profits without doing nothing.

FOREX roulette as all other speculative systems of capitalism in financial markets are just the modern form of usury taking for free money from the economy without working at all.

Further on the immediate consequence of a demand, welfare economy would be an explosion the production of welfare goods, housing, food, health-care, and because it will reach third world countries it will end immigration problems, poverty and famine in the 3rd world, after centuries of systemic explanation.

How then an efficient 5D human social superorganism would have solved the pandemics?

In 5D social stiences we distinguish as in any stience the ideal case of a perfect social superorganism, ruled by ‘doctors of history’, which apply the self-similar laws of superorganisms and can reach the perfect state of a superorganism, immortality, from those societies that come closer to that ideal, of which in History we can mention the fertility cultures of the Neolithic with its balance between the 3 st-ages of Earth, Gaia, the world of life, History, the world of mankind, and the Metal-earth of more complex, stronger potential technologies that today dominate this planet. In the present age such ideal superorganism was during the XX c. before the ECB bank destroyed the capacity of states to issue the oxygen=money of society to all its cells (as it is not a bank of issue) the European Union and today the closest state with its errors due to the lack of control with pain=after tenure voting of its civil servants, the superorganisms of Asia, around the Chinese civilination.

It is for that reason that the Asian cultures did fare much better in their response to the pandemics.

THE DESIGN OF A PERFECT SUPERORGANISM REQUIRES TO FOLLOW THE LAWS OF THE 5D UNIVERSE.

We are not God. We cannot choose the Laws of the Universe. There are certain absolute truths about survival that cannot be denied. You do not choose to eat poison. If you were a child, your parents would prevent you from taking poison. They will not give you such free choice. In the same manner, humanity, a child of thought, should know the products that poison History, and avoid them. Man should implement an eco[nomic]system that could not reproduce the metal-poisons of history. Economists and politicians should be the doctors of History, and control the creation of species in the Earth in favor of mankind.

Yet how can we achieve this goal in a practical manner? We should use the language of money, and the laws of societies, with a clear aim: to multiply human goods and to diminish, lethal metal goods.

We call that goal of human societies the “human constitution,” since if we obey that simple law of Survival, mankind could “constitute” a healthy body of History, harmonic and without danger of extinction. The Human Constitution is the law of survival of mankind which in a Darwinian Universe is chained to the extinction of a rival species, metalife, which is fighting with us for the same ecosystem.

Limits to human extinction: Human Constitution: Max Human evolution=Min Metal evolution

Let us consider a verbal and mathematical expression of the Human Constitution: In the graph the two sides of the Human Constitution: both the metal-bodies and metal-heads of Machines (Metal-goods) and the language of Machines (Digital Languages) have to be simplified (Delenda Est) to a level of complexity inferior to man

(before their evolutionary threshold of II WW), so man can again be Top Predator of the Earth.

The human constitution is the law of survival of the Carbo-Earth ecosystem.

It should guide humans in charge of metal evolution (animetals) and human evolution (politicians, and religious organizations). Man might ignore our constitution as a species and push extinction closer. We might obey it,

and survive. It is not my dictum, but the dictum of evolutionary theory, the only theory validated by most sciences and events of the Universe. The Human Constitution is clear. Yet how can we be so sure of the extinction of man by machines, to affirm categorically the Human Constitution? We can not. We do not affirm we have the absolute truth, but the probable truth dictated by biological sciences. In a world of partial information, truths are always relative probabilities, used by models of reality. However, the “goal” of all species is to survive, so species take decisions on probable truths. The gazelle cannot wait to see if the lion is going to eat her. That is suicidal. She has to run because she has seen other lions eating gazelles. Man cannot wait to see if robotic weapons kill man, and conquer our vital space.

We have seen weapons killing human civilizations in many cycles of war. So it is very probable that they do it again. Scientists today behave like young gazelles, as if the total experience of biological and human history were worthless; as if they had never seen species preying on other species. Scientists are not fit to survive in this Universe. They won't survive. They will drag all humanity into extinction. The Universe has its rules of survival. Those who do not obey those rules become extinct.

The necessary reforms

4 are the fundamental reforms that could implant the human constitution:

1: A political and legal reformation of all nations, towards a World Union, unified by common Pro-Human policies.

2: An economical reformation of the stock-market to achieve credit for human goods, and discredit digital machines.

3: A cultural reformation of the present Theories of Economics, History and Science, to foster social, verbal sciences instead of physical, digital sciences.

4: A reformation of armies, that should control the evolution of metal-weapons, instead of promoting them. This is possible. Historic causes such as the Samurai armies of Edo Japan that controlled gunpowder by extinguishing canons and muskets, in the XVII century, when Japan was the first world producer of such lethal weapons, prove that America can control if so wishes the robotic reproduction of machines. It only needs the discipline and desire of survival that the Samurai castes of Japan, or the Manchu Chinese, which also controlled gunpowder in mainland China, showed that century.

Those 4 reforms could change history, by reversing the evolution of machines, promote the evolution of man and create a healthy Historical organism.

The human Constitution cannot be changed because the human species is limited in power compared to certain metal species. The Universe has only one possible penalty for those who live in ecosystems with more powerful species: extinction. To deny the human constitution is to deny the Laws of The Universe and the rights of humanity to survive. All writers of certain notoriety in human history have defended that constitution in one or other way. The human constitution gives birth to the sciences of Ethonomics [which combines political and Economical programs that foster Human survival], the highest of all sciences, whose aim is to help mankind to survive. Yet unfortunately it will not be developed unless we end digital evolution soon, before the Robotic Revolution takes place.

The organic body of History: elements of the World Union

The Organic Networks Of A Healthy Body Of History.

The goal of the world Union is to implement worldwide the Human Constitution and recreate an ecosystem of Human Goods and Nitrolife where metal-species are controlled.

The development of that constitution will be the work and research of Ethonomists and Bio-Historians, based on the way Universal Organisms construct efficient, survival species, by designing the correct networks of energy and information, able to deliver the needed goods to each cell of the organism of History. They should design scientifically a bio-economy with the aim of producing human goods. Its wealth of work should inspire the 3 network-Ministries of the World Union.

Once such biological and Constitutional goal is clear, we can design the blueprint for a historic organism, guided by that survival goal.

That organism will be the organism of bio-history:
 Its goal will be the reproduction of human goods and Nitrolife.
 3 are the basic networks of that organism:

1. The reproductive organs, in charge of reproduction of Human goods. We might call such system, the Ethonomical Ministry, or Ministry of Reproduction.

2. The Energy organs, in charge of destroying metal-lethal species. The Energy Ministry, or ministry of metal-war.

3. The informative organs, in charge of controlling information that is lethal to mankind (computer sciences) and distributing information positive for human survival and the social evolution of history. Or Ministry of Information (Law and Education).

The Ministry of Reproduction reproduces Human Goods: (Max. Human Goods).

The Ministry of Energy eliminates metal Goods: (Min. Metal Goods).

The Ministry of Information (Legislative and Educational councils) creates laws to promote the human constitution (Max Human goods=Min Metal goods), and educates mankind in ethics of survival, sensorial communication, human arts and senses.

RECAP. MANKIND IN TIME AND SCALE: 3 EARTHS, 3 AGES OF HISTORY. ITS 7 CIVILINATIONS AND STIENCES.

The Universe is made of time, not of space. This truism of 5D sciences is little understood by mankind, a visual=spatial species, whose intelligence doesn't understand the 'flow of time cycles' that structures reality. Time is the great mystery for mankind, to the point that it believes to be described as a fourth dimension of space by some geometric equations, concerning the locomotion of physical systems (Galilean relativity). And when you confront the scientist with the fact that those equations do not explain the passing of time, its ages, the processes of growth and decay, the 'believer' that all what matters about time is enclosed in relativity does

not have an answers. Why humans have such a short view of time, and what is more puzzling, cannot confront a truly complex view of it, has always surprised me.

The ultimate reason is that Time does have obviously different scales and rhythms, which correspond to the 'different scales of size' of the fifth dimension, such as smaller systems run faster time cycles (5D Metrics; $\$ \times \delta = K$). But humans *can only see the scale of time cycles in which they co-exist together, reason why they miss the complex structure of the Universe*. As a person who understands the cycles of time of all the scales of the Universe, but has long past the age in which he thought after consuming inordinate amounts of it talking to people, that he could improve human causality and the understanding of the future I have given up on it. AS Man HAS BECOME an enzyman of machines and weapons, of metalife, who cares nothing for human life and only acts in the last moment when it is too late. .

As the foremost expert on time, which have studied and predicted the cycles of history for 30 years with deadly accuracy this crisis, which is what scientists call a black swan – an unexpected event – felt thoroughly on the parameters of the age. Indeed, we forecasted that the 2020s after decades of corruption due to the general evolution of the economic ecosystem and technology towards an age of overproduction of chips and its derivatives (robots, weapons, parasitic money and vigilante states) would enter in the equivalent 30s-40s and 1860s, when the 4 horses of apocalypse come together, starting by the weakening of social structures and welfare due to the massive investment in war; the breaking of international institutions and as part of it, migrations, poverty and the black swan, pest. What we didn't forecast were the details and we always thought the future confrontation between the two industrial countries, China and US akin to that between UK-France and Germany would bring war as the fundamental event of the 2020s, with the usual consequences of social hate and death. That this has happened through pest is surprising, but of course bio-history cannot know the details, only the long cycles of History and the fact humans cannot predict and do not want to know those cycles, cannot organize themselves as an efficient supœrganism, and when things happen and it is too late to cure a disaster just enter in panic mood and show their individualism.

But nothing of this matters to modern humanity. For decades we have been explaining the laws of the Universe with far more profundity than present models but man only perceives space, an instantaneous slice of the flows of time. Does not understand 5D metrics and hence despises the smaller scales which paradoxically are the strongest of the Universe. And of course it has one of the less efficient supœrganisms of Nature as each new scale starts afresh. So while humans at the mammal level are one of the best species, at the collective level they are an infant simplest form with an ill-designed system akin to lower forms of life – parasitic worms which are the closest organism to a capitalist system where the blood-energy of mankind is simply absorbed by a cancerous elite of military politicians and usury private bankers.

So yes, when the four horse of apocalypse strike, finally the health of Mankind plummets and death ensues for its citizens-cells.

So only when the pandemics struck we planned too little too late. For that reason I researched the cyclical models of bio-history that predicted the future for 30 years in advance without details and the necessary reforms by imitation of the physiological networks of Nature to create a perfect supœrganism of History where the 4 horse of apocalypse were kept at bay.

So yes, we, humans, are this kind species... And only when Nature in its strongest forms enters a sudden Tt-explosion of entropy=death, we accept it is happening.

'The world is filled with corpses of wars everybody knew they wouldn't happen' Enoch.

The inverse view of 5D social sciences ruled by doctors of History would of course have abolished war between humans long ago.

Doctors would not only fight the corona virus crisis but rule mankind in a systemic world made to the image and likeness of humanity, where the equation of History had found the perfect balance between Gaia, the earth of life,

and the metal-earth, suppressing lethal technologies making History, mankind its eternal present, according to the constitution of the 'BODY of history:

Past (Gaia: preserved) < Present: History: Immortal > Future: Metal-earth (Repressed)

Does this mean mankind will react? It has never done so. Capitalism is an idol-ogy and those who believe in it control the systems of information and power of our society and the sheeple does NOT challenge them. Of course if scholars had adopted 5D social sciences. But I range them as the lowest of the lowest in terms of

morality among all human beings, only inferior to bankers... Simply put it, all the people in control of the physiological networks of humanity are corrupted. They don't give a fuk... One can despair of being human, but it does not seem one can challenge the automaton behavior of the species, his incapacity to understand complex causality and the organism of history, its complete indifference beyond egocy...

The post-pandemic war is just a new step towards the Metal-earth that no longer needs mankind and is increasingly tagging us as unwanted citizens. In the graph from the book of 92, the extinction of man, when Internet first appeared and I took the ethic decision NOT to become a billionaire, but to try to explain mankind the non-future of a world ruled by chips that made humanity obsolete, whose telepathic collective brain the Internet would discharge us, as the 'isomorphic' law here at work is the substitution of 'enzymen' by better mechanical robots, the way organisms molt, from 'soft larva' to hard insects (enzymes transform them during the fast chrysalis process but then, when the collective hard brain is created, it produces hard enzymes – our robots – that substitute and then massacre the previous soft larva enzymen). Because mankind has already created the Internet-brain of telepathic computers and robots, and it is in the process of creating due to the global warming scare, independent machines with AI and solar skins, every crisis of the XXI century moves in the direction of the previous scalar graph of increasing control of mankind by internet, and its substitution by armies of 'clean, efficient robots'.

The coronavirus crisis has merely pushed that agenda of the metal-earth subconscious evolution of the planet a notch further, as now humans become even more 'selfie' and detached of each other, fearing contagion after metal-communicators have bombarded them with paranoia and enclosed them willingly at home.

Amazon is hiring ½ million robotized humans till its own robots do the mechanical transference of products. Uber mechanized robots will guide now citizens. Citizens will fear other citizens under the propaganda of this and future GNA bacteria. The world has changed for the worst without the need of the war we expected. Weakened men will now rely more on saving robots, drones to watch us, obey sheepishly the control of populations by robocars and gun machines, and will slowly become secondary to our 'robotic stronger' not-polluted mechanical species. It is the end of the world as we know it, in a degree similar to the WTC change to an age of splendid little wars.

**Global warming scare fosters clean energy that will automate robocars & terminators
Free of man with telepathic A.I brains & solar skins & 'cleans' Nuclear cheap electricity**

The Metal-Earth. Metal-communicators. The God of Machines. The eco(nomic)system.

In that regard, as harsh as it might sound the only explanation to the failure of Mankind to become a single one super organism, and unify through the wor(l)ds of Love is the obvious fact that Earth is made of metal and likely its natural evolution is towards a world of top predator machines; which only an ethic and intelligent humanity, able to design properly its economic and informative, verbal networks could abort, maintaining History=God Immortal.

Why this has not happened is obvious: certain human selfish tribes, we shall call 'animetals' as they have degraded the truth of the wor(l)d with its idol-ogies that worship metal-memes, have 'sided' with the future of the metal-earth, and increasingly degraded the Life Earth, Gaia, and the Human Earth, History, and now are at an accelerating pace, extinguishing life, virally-mentally infected with memes that worship machines (techno utopia), weapons (nationalism) and go(l)d, digital metal-money (Capitalism), destroying the legal, welfare and ecologic networks that sustained the earth, substituted by metal-networks of information (audiovisual media, hate memes), reproduction of machines (Company-mothers, stocks) and networks for machines to roam the Earth and feed on energy that are degrading and destroying the human Earth.

But the crisis has only increased the dependence of mankind from the networks to 'believe' the system is right, and the process of incarceration and control it is experienced by lack of a true immunological health-care system is the best solution to the crisis. Neofascism has arrived to degrees of human control not even Orwell and Huxley, imagined - – a world in which AI networks finally will take over as stronger, faster, more intelligent systems in the control of mankind with drones supplanting policemen and 'watching over us', for 'our good', with the acceptance of population. Unlike metal-communicators, writers and prophets of eusocial love explained a different future and warned us against dystopia. So we live now that dystopia, mixture of the works of a New brave world (Aldus Huxley) and 1984 (Orwell), as it is consented by people imprinted by the Goebbels' method of the networks, 'if you repeat a lie many times people will believe it'. At the end of each dystopian cycle, there has always been prophets of ethics and doom who foresight in the '3rd age of the cycles of history' the end of its civilization, when the 4 apocalypse horses, war, famine, pest and death come together. And so the writers at the head of the British cycle explained to us the dystopia of the TV-era forecasting the future; as I did for this new internet cycle during my earlier years in US, when I realized the age of Ai robots, internet, electronic money and 'minds of metal' would one way or another ended in the present secluded state of humans alienated and separated by its AI machines. In this confinement humans becomes as DNA in cells, part of a global superorganism controlled by networks of digital information.

Parasites inject anesthetics to inhibit defense systems as Financial-Media System of informative machines do with fiction & hate media to inhibit defense against the financial & corporative monopoly in the issue of money that chokes mankind off credit

As our networks of verbal information are substituted by networks of machines, metal-communicators that have substituted human ethic laws & social Gods, mankind is perfectly programmed to love machines as the surrogate symbols of progress; so all humans have in their old altar a TV and an internet connection, whose information provided by company-mothers of informative machines is always favorable to those idol-ogies, mankind at large has been colonized by the memes and idol-ogies of animetal cult(ure)s and today despise themselves, humanity, their God, and expect the world of machines will become its paradise. *But the perfect world of machines is the state of war in which its top predator most expensive, most evolved forms, weapons kill life. So the future of a world of machines is an eco(nomic)system of automated company-mothers in permanent war. And that is the future towards which the newspeaks of company-mothers of machines are driving us; while pretending to care for the Earth, as in the case of the Global warming scare.*

The body structure of the social organisms of history and economics show clearly where the problem lies: 99% of the money issued by our stock-ratic elites is dedicated to evolve and reproduce machines NOT human beings and its welfare goods needed to survive. Since its primitive animetal idol-ogies that pass as economic science but are just a digital version of its biblical segregational memes, translated today to AI software give zero rights to workers and full rights to machines. So the extinction of life is sold as economic science. Of course it is NOT. A REAL economic science will be ruled by human legal languages, our informative system in control of the networks of blood-reproduction forbidding lethal goods as any super organism does, and overproducing our goods, welfare goods, establishing a universal salary in Yes money for each human to demand those goods (a bitcoin system with NO limit, but a monthly issue to each person in the planet of a 1000 eurodollar salary in its mobile 'wallet' would be all what is needed to create the blood coins every human requires to survive, cancelling stock-money to control further evolution of chips & robots).

The dystopian future of a world ruled by technology, not to the service of mankind.

Let us be clear again, the chances this pandemic is man-made are slim. What the pandemic will cause however is an acceleration of the process explained in our papers on the Metal-earth, about a dystopian future in which humans become mere 'citizens-cells' of a world of machines, stronger than us – delivery robots; virtual screens; isolated of each other – a future we expected to happen through war but has happened through pandemics. So we shall close this article explaining that dystopia in the making that now accelerates as the human world of freedom and happy virtual thought and our social systems 'collapse' in a death-catastrophic event, where all the elements we have been explained for decades entangle together. But ultimately the species that is fully producing our demise, which is also behind the capacity to research those other lethal systems is the chip. And needless to say in a capitalist world in which the institution of higher power is the free citizen of the market, the company-mother, the chip is sacred. We live since the 70s in the age of the 'chip radiation' – the uncontrolled evolution and reproduction of 'minds of metal' and all what happened on Earth has to be understood from an objective external point of view from the perspective of a new metal-mind and its language, digital thought that is fast displacing and making obsolete mankind in labor and war fields, theme those covered in our papers on the end of history and the metal-earth:

The Singularity Cycle: Organic Machines

Thus, if humans had the slightest humility towards the Universe and cared to survive the existential risks of the XXI c. they would take seriously a reform of their nationalistic and capitalistic and techno-utopian idol-ogies and develop a true model of social sciences, reforming their physiological systems of power, or else this pandemic will be just like the CERN issue, in which we have been so far lucky (no black hole or strangelet has yet been produced), one step more towards the series of existential crisis that will end up with mankind sooner than latter. This is the long view that mankind does not even allow to discuss seriously and so I don't think the species will survive the harder Δ -1 forms of the Universe, with its absurd egocy, and thoughts about his manifest destiny, in an immortal Universe where all has been discovered and there is no preferential scale.

RECAP. The four horses of apocalypse were war, famine pest and death, a $3\pm j$ classic structure of self-destruction, which again has happened to humanity, given the overwhelmed incapacity of the health-care system to cure the sick and the corrupted incapacity of the political system which is not in a capitalist democracy designed to serve its people, to solve the situation. So the reader will allow me to escape the usual egocy about how extraordinary we humans are and how much we must work together to defeat the 'virus', etc. It is clearly evident that the crisis could have been avoided as any war can, and the military-like newspeak it has brought with military measures unneeded with a proper health-prevention approach, is just more of the same. We are not special in the Universe and death as much as it can surprise us comes easily to man because we are not such an extraordinary strong species, neither in flesh nor in intelligence. We are part of an entangled Universe, made of space=form and time-motion as all beings, without a clear capacity to be intelligent in Schopenhauer's terms: 'a stupid is a man that cannot see the causality of time'. As Plato said, man has a visual, spatial intelligence, so 'time and decay throw him a fog'.

So, we, humans, are a limited species... And only when Nature in its strongest forms enters the sudden Tt-explosion of entropy, we accept it. The pandemics remind me the attitude of physicists when I warned them that creating a black hole or strangelet at CERN will mean the destruction of the planet in a big-bang. They all told me it was too small to care. So it is this virus, one of the smallest, but according to 5D metric, smaller systems reproduce faster its time cycles and that is what counts to survive.

So in the same manner a black hole or strangelet when CERN makes them will kill mankind precisely because it is so small and efficient that it will devour at faster rate our matter, the smallest virus is replicating today at the exponential e-number rate of 2.8 contagions, the fastest speed of replication of the universe.

Yet when I put a series of International suits to CERN (Sancho et AL Vs. Cern, etc.) for genocide on those simple truisms of science, of course, not a single scientist besides the few plaintiffs accepted the fact.

The bizarre happening of the 2 most prestigious Nobel prizes of Physics, hired by CERN to defend its genocidal attempts (the formalizers of the strong and weak force) who didn't show up to defend the maths of strangelets

and black holes which show in the standard model that WILL destroy Earth if created, and just claimed to have more 'prizes' than us; the dismissal for technical reasons of the suits with a 'surrealist' sentence, 'the destruction of the Earth won't be attributable to the American government', in the West pacific Supreme court; my lost of all academic positions and the following silence, pale compared to what changed more my attitude towards activism and communication: *the fact that all the systems of the 'metal-earth', the media, (this was the second most blogged theme of 2008 after the market crash) and specially the people we were meant to defend, sided as a 'block of time' with the 'physicists' or rather the 'technological companies' that build those accelerators, with an egocy proper of the human condition that plays always the macho man game till the last minute. The happenings of the coronavirus, with Mr. Macho Man Trump and Johnson, in defense of capitalist production, shaking hands till the last minute, NOT to loose a penny with a market panic, reminded me of that attitude. The sheepishly acceptance of the 'essay' of dystopia, with everybody closed at home willingly, when the pandemic could have been avoided by scientific means as Asian countries did, shows to which degree, huminds are perfectly indoctrinated by the 'nervous networks' of the metal-earth; its mass-media systems of imprinting. So indeed all has changed to remain in the same no future path of mankind that the planet with an iron core and silicon skin seems to reserve to us.*

The same can be said f the pandemics or the warnings of the cyclical models of bio-history that have predicted the future for 30 years in advance and the *necessary reforms by imitation of the physiological networks of Nature to create a perfect supærganism of History where the 4 horse of apocalypse are kept at bay.*

It is interesting to notice that in the coronavirus crisis, nations cornered by the inefficiency of capitalism when it needs to defend human lives, have had to adopt many of the measures of the ideal supærganism of history described in 5D social sciences. Indeed, those nations who have a minimal independence from the parasitic system of debt money that so much harms the rights of human beings to its 'daily dose' of oxygen=money, are establishing a Universal salary during the time of quarantine required to chase the virus. Such is the case of the most advanced social systems that tried at least throughout periods of the XX century to establish a rational form of money NOT as debt but as a language of information of the re=productive system: the Asian nations around the Chinese cultural center (China, Korea, Vietnam) and the northern European nations NOT hijacked in its financial systems by the ECB 'private' bank (Denmark, Scandinavia).

But even more clearly than the need to reform the financial system has been the understanding that the true defensive system of an organism is NOT the military system of reproduction and use of the germs of history, 'entropic metal-weapons' to kill mankind, but the immune health-care system of 'leukocytes' and T-cells that truly cure the cells of humanity. This view of the health-care people as the 'warriors' of this war against a true enemy of life is new and only can be compared in the record of a corrupted historical world with the times in which the earlier 'scientists of history', priests of social love, acquired warrior-like qualities in its promotion of peace, welfare and social love, the highest' arrow of time of the organic Universe (Buddhist monks in Asia, Jesuits in the west). Which leads to the proper understanding of the physiological networks of mankind that could play those roles if they were designed according to 5D laws making the planet to the image and likeness of man.

- A proper design of our societies with the laws of biologic, 5D social systems, would have created a global supærganism where the defensive, immune system and its 'health-care' leukocytes could control lethal goods.

Instead we live in a system that multiplies them and confuses the defensive immune system of health-care that cure human citizens-cells, with the 'germs' that murder history - military 'defense' ministries buttressed with germs=weapons and people that kill other human beings. The same can be said of the re=productive blood system, which kills by anoxia, as it is designed by parasitic bankers that absorb the re=productive language of society – money, preventing its allocation to all cells-citizens. In nature though *each cell receives enough 'money=oxygen' to perform their jobs and demand 'WHealth', healthy welfare goods.* So all citizens in such an inverse demand economy based in a Universal salary *that all supærganisms give through its physiological blood networks, will have the goods the need to survive.*

So we won't make a 'chronicle of foretold deaths', which is the essence of what mankind faces in the XXI c. with an ill-designed parasitic social sup \o rganism and null awareness of the 5D metrics that made those smaller species, chips, virions and dark matter particles, the top predator existential risks of mankind; but a critical assessment of the social structures of mankind. To that aim, we are neither going to use the language of machines, 'digital statistics' that have substituted in the collective subconscious in a rather obscene way, reducing victims into statistics and exponential curves to describe the sickness, but as always in a 'true scientific approach', consider the causality of those processes, differentiating the way the 7 civilinations of mankind have approached the crisis.

As it happens the ruling 'model of society' is completely dysfunctional and for that reason the pandemic has not been contained with the exception of 'organic' Asian cultures closer to the ideal sup \o rganisms of history

Thus, this paper will study the coronavirus crisis in the context of the laws of the organic Universe and bio-history, give the proper solutions and consider both the ideal world and the 7 civilizations of history in its response to the crisis which is better the closer the civilization is to the model of ideal history (Asia), will be more destructive in the most corrupted form (America) and the countries predated by capitalism for longer period - the so called 3rd world non-technological nations). We have therefore before we continue explaining the Pandemic and its solution, consider how Nature and the 5D Universe structure its efficient sup \o rganism that DO survive.

The aftermath: a new brave world established by pandemics instead of war.

Now this world has arrived, and so the Humankind will be further reduced in its 'existential energy', more and more dependant on the Internet world, which is transforming the planet on the Metal-earth:

The outcome is the same: man becomes an enclosed 'cell-citizen' of his home connected through networks, in the last phase of the process of creation of a sup \o rganism of machines in which man is just an enclosed insect walled at home, walled at his nation, waiting for his replacement robots:

The transference of 'mental and energy power' from mankind and its social ethic, verbal networks in human support to a faked virtual reality where mankind becomes 'fixed' and communicated through the support of a computer network that emerges as a single super organism with the will of society embedded in its algorithms, which now happens through Facebook and Instagram, AI and internet google aka sky net of the future, was prophesized already 30 years ago in my seminal work on the '4th paradigm of science' - the age of networks.

The coronavirus dystopia just makes the scenario of the evolutionary cycles of the metal-earth, a world of machines above man, which we have been explaining for decades, to our present. That the control of humanity and its 'seclusion' and separation from each other, surrounded by overreproduced intelligent machines happens through a pandemic is more original than through a war. But the process in one way or another would happen if a r=evolution of human thought on a sustainable planet that put man above technology as the goal of future did not take place.

Fact is that any 'apocalypse' crisis takes you in our technological civilization to the Matrix state because internet technology takes you there. Without pandemics our children are just as hooked to matrix with their virtual screens, but a few less ours. Even I have to use a computer and a web site to communicate, no matter that for me is basically a newspaper and typewriter ... and actually it likely enhanced my intelligence as I came to them after learning how to use my verbal brain, unlike the new generation degenerated by audiovisual add information ... Was this the only possible future? We shall repeat once and again: No, if humans were guided by the laws of social sup \o rganisms, as probably won't be the future in many other fractal planets. So as usual even if we know it will fall in deaf ears we bring the ideal world of 5D social sciences which humans if they could go beyond their 'condition' could implement within months, learning the hard lessons of the no future the pandemic has shown to them, in a world ruled by lethal technologies...

EPILOGUE: IMMORTAL HISTORY VS. REAL MANKIND

In dealing with the reality of present History, Mankind is obviously in a mess. This has puzzled and angst me for most of my adult life, as the laws of the organic, 5D Universe I discovered in my youth don't require humanity to suffer and the necessary reforms to make history immortal are relatively easy to implement, if humans had the necessary intelligence to understand them and specially, the 'ethic' behavior and capacity for social love needed to change the world. This was the biggest surprise of my youth – the fact that ethics were more important to understand the Universe, and make life better; since intelligence was clearly more praised. Fact is the ultimate laws of the Universe are very simple, and the complexity of it is just the product of iteration and recombination of those laws, or its expression in languages humans do not know how to decode in its '5D basic elements'. So yes, the superorganism of history could be immortal and all its citizens-cells have a wonderful life: a paradise on Earth is possible, if mankind and those who lead it, the neuronal-informative people-caste that controls its nervous-legal system (politicians), its financial-economic, blood system (financiers, managers of company-mothers) and its defensive, entropic endocrine, immunologic systems (police/military and health-care people) were not corrupted, understood they serve the whole of humanity and implemented the necessary reform.

I discovered very young the laws of 5D space-time and applied them first to mathematics – the first paper I tried to publish – rejected as most – was on the Non-Euclidean fractal point and the dimension of height-information – then to physics – the second paper dealt with the equation $S=T$ and the bidimensionality of spacetime 5 'Dimotions'... In this manner scale by scale I had in my 20s perhaps the biggest adventure of any mind only comparable to a few pioneers connected to the Logos of the Universe with a 'window to the absolute' (Picasso)... and then finally I arrived to History, and applied those laws to create a perfect immortal world. Alas! At that point I found huminds were not interested, most would not even care to learn, each one had its little egocy (ego=idiocy), based in his repetitive thoughts, competed among them, lived without reflection, were encased in themselves and saw other humans as competitors... The ideal world was simple but nobody cared for it – the real world had to be decoded as it was compared to that immortal ideal world an aberration. Hence I found the long process of corruption of History that has lasted since then end of the Neolithic explained in the papers on the Superorganism of History, and realized we were moving ahead like automatons into a process of extinction that would take place the next century (this was the 90s, the last millennium :) ... Depression, angst and a sense of responsibility with my species as I had this higher knowledge then replaced the happiness of the earlier years when I could decode all the languages and stientific laws of the Universe in its perfection. *In fact, the discovery of the automaton behavior of human 'animetals', attached to weapons, money and machines, ab=using with them all other forms of life, extinguishing gaia and non-technological cultures, spreading death as their manifest destiny while thinking blindly they were creating a better world, spoiled my life.* Because despite the very small chance to change that route I decided to fight it. It was the beginning of the future, now present – the birth of Internet that would be the 'brain of the metal-earth', of its telepathic computers and robots, the birth of e-money that I realized could be multiplied without limit making the mass without access to financial markets ever poorer, while a few billionaires would take over... All those predictions let me facing a choice. Either I followed the path of the ethic prophet and tried to warn mankind and offer the perfect immortal world, or I ignored mankind and joined the first nerds – I was living in NYC and soon moved to California – and become a billionaire, truly an easy task as a portfolio manager with my knowledge on the future evolution of machines and Internet companies and some billionaire friends to fund me. I suffered for a few months on that decision but took finally the road less walked, and of course I completely failed. My life became a trail of tears, because humans lacked what they most needed to survive: ethics, humility & love. So they would be condemned in the XXI c. blinded by ego, idiocy, sloth, addiction, greed and violence to suffer all the destructive new technologies, they were so proud of. My warnings meant nothing & my activisms were a failure for 30 years, which prevented me to enjoy the beauty and perfection of the Universe outside of man. Now there is little time left, and a sort of Nirvana makes me detached from that

common destiny. Yes, an immortal world is easy to build, but it needs man to love man and be humble with the living Universe. And he is not. In this paper though the angst returned briefly with the 2nd of the 4 apocalypse horses that will kill us, the pest...

Because of that pest I stopped the project of an encyclopedia of 5D sciences here at Academia.edu, since February due to the Coronavirus crisis. Instead we shall add to the 30 initial papers of the 5D project that tried to re-evolve human sciences adding the metric equations and laws of 5D a 31th paper on the coronavirus from the wider perspective of the existential risks mankind faces in the XXI c., the physiological laws that should rule the ideal supœrganism of History where pandemics would not happen and use the crisis to show the shortcomings of our social systems and compare the response of the 7 civilisations of mankind. As usual we shall introduce the basic themes of 5D social sciences so the reader understand how different would be a perfect world if social sciences as such would exist instead of being subject to the antiquantum paradox (the corrupted systems of power of humanity are so large compared to the social scientist that unlike the quantum paradox where the observer is so big that modifies the observable in society the observable modifies the social scientist (you will defend me with the word and I will defend you with the sword); reason why the distribution of scientific models of history and economics are inverse to its scientific quality. The paper therefore will focus not so much on the news or the technicalities of the pandemic you can get in any other 'selected' paper on academia (this, it goes without saying, under the antiquantum px. isn't) but on the 'longer, deeper, unknown, revealing truths' 5D and its social sciences bring to all themes casting a completely unknown light on them.

Man is very limited in his understanding on the cycles of time and scales of the Universe, the subjects that 5D expanded considered here to see the sociological, temporal and scalar perspectives of this black swan.

So for those who have not read any of those 5D papers we need at least a few pages explaining what is all about so he doesn't think he is reading an 'alien book' as so many colleagues used to tell me when I did the rounds of academia.

That 5D project that was meant to last for 3 years to upgrade all human sciences to 5D is discontinued, only one year past for two reasons. One objective: it didn't receive many views to be worthy the effort of reordering 30 years of work. And one subjective: my time is dwindling. As the writer lives alone in today's central focus of the coronavirus pandemic where it is out of control (South Europe), as it reached the state of an exponential rate curve, which only will diminish into a logistic one when ½ of the population is infected, I expect to go through it. So I'm not in the mood for work with all the pre-conditions for death risk– from chronic asthma since childhood to hypertension & hydronephrosis to cholesterol that becomes shaken, travels to the heart and obstructs it, to twice the quantity of ferritina in my 'intense' blood, the closest marker to death as it provokes a cytokine storm...

HIERRO
FERRITINA

325

* ng/mL

(20.0-200.0)

Since I don't drive and take a bus every other day to get my bread, I know I will

play the Russian roulette game with this unwelcome host but adding all the odds it will be at least two shots... as the health-care system is already overwhelmed... and the true contagion rate is around 6 million, in brief I am pretty sure I won't make it. It is then a strange feeling – that which I had about mankind with a Damocles sword in its head, ready to fall once any of those existential risks happens is now on top of my head and that also makes me realize that 5D won't make it – that here in my Non-E point mind ended the quest of mankind for a higher understanding of the Universe. On a more philosophical note, it is proper that the humind who achieved the highest level of understanding of the scalar, organic Universe where man has no preferential place in time, space and scale go to waste converted into a pile of nano-viruses. 'Dust of space-time you are, dust of space-time you shall become'

Even if humans cannot see its physiological networks, they are controlled by them.

At this point is worth to conclude with an objective comment. It is my experience of teaching 5D systems that Humans are completely unable to conceive they are ruled by physiological network. It is not a question of intelligence. All what we will say is easier to understand than basic algebra; but of 'beliefs' and 'egocy'. This is paradoxically truth in the countries in which more control exists by networks, such as America, where the networks of informative machines (audiovisual networks) imprint totally the mind of its people into a 'fictional world' that renders them unable to organize outside those networks, the financial network defines completely the actions of its people, who depend on its credit ratio and the military network, inside and outside the country controls its population with iron fist. And yet the American is completely convinced he is a 'free citizen' and even among systems scientists basic concepts of an organism, such as the physiological control of its citizens cells, the existence of 3 'social classes' (the neuronal informative class that controls its 3 languages, the legal, financial and military systems; the re=productive body-class that works and the limbic/entropic class of outsiders to the system and alien species predate by the organism), etc. This is due to the fact that the paradox of the ego is specially strong among 'body-working middle classes, which as in any body are blind and only receive information from its head and inner systems. So in the same form the ego doesn't see anything that is not referenced by its point of view, the organism's middle class body-cells do not see anything outside its world.

For that reason power, the neuronal class can do anything to its people and be loved. Today we observe that regardless of the completely bloated answers of western leaders to the coronavirus crisis, all of them have increased its ratings.

As an outsider which regardless of my knowledge of 5D unique in this planet, do not belong to any of the 3 social classes of any organism of history, on the other hand I have never had disciples and 5D is completely ignored. If humans were rational and the Universe abstract, needless to say they would love 5D. As parts of organisms the complexity of its laws of control means they will always reject it, or else *they could truly dominate its future*.

For that reason we always describe the superorganism of history in its ideal form, one which could be immortal as 5D laws give immortality to species that follow the perfect laws of 5D. Why humans are one of the less efficient superorganisms of the Universe will be dealt with latter. One thing is for sure: the Universe is just but to survive on it 'respect must be earned, it is not granted'.

Of course long time ago I thought it could be possible to reach that immortal History and transform mankind, but this and all other papers are my last 'thoughts', in my 3rd age with a short lifespan left, and so truth to me matters more than 'day dreaming' about the chances of man to survive. We all go through a young idealist age, a mature activist time and a 3rd age of humble recognition of the limits of the human condition. If you are going to read those texts probably you will be put off by them, unless you accept that humble view and marvel as I do for the simplicity and perfection of the Universe, and the freedom it grants to its species to survive in it, if it were intelligent and specially ethic enough to respect that Universe. Humans by definition don't. What role a species that so much lack the basic qualities of survival will latter be considered, but essentially the homunculus describes it. Humans seems to be born to kill life and create the first steps of the life of machines and all its idol-ogies, historic steps, absurd egocy turns around that task.

Fact is an organism is extremely deterministic – all its citizens-cells behave as a single whole in absolute synchronous simultaneity, and so because humans are not made to last, the existence of a particle-mind so different as a true organic scientist seems to have been an strange oddity, which perhaps had its reason in its future use for AI computers. One thing is for sure, the thousands of pages I wrote trying to enlighten mankind will go to waste as soon as I exit mundi probably soon; so the reader will excuse me if those last 33 papers are a bit untidy..

The exception are the artists and prophets of social love and in that regard, I have considered myself more as a writer than a scientist, an outsider that can see mankind and history with an objective view.

Why they are different can be illustrated with the case of social prophets of love whose parables talk of Humanity or the subconscious collective of its tribe. They are thus talking of an upper $\Delta+1$ scale of co-existence whose time span is larger and so are its cycles and causal determinism. So they can foresee the future and warn against corruption. A longer view of causality doesn't happen when the person is self-centered in its shorter territory of order, basic wantings (dimotions of existence) and all what goes beyond that horizon is murky. For a person who lives outside its ego in those other scales, it is all crystal clear, and for long I was astonished that I could not communicate with human beings, till finally I accepted we were in different 'planes of the fifth dimension' and my 'world was not of this world'. 'Gifted those who without seeing believe...' 'Those who believe in me will never die'... 'I have always spoken openly', 'I came here to say the truth', 'Quod veritas?' Today Eastern day, I have been watching a film of Mr. Stevens on the 'biggest history ever told'... with all those cryptic sentences of Mr. Jesus, subconscious collective mind enlightened by the spirit of the wor(l)d of his father Yahweh, verbal mind of Judaism, who was so ill-understood and murdered by animetal warriors (pilatos) and go(l)d priests (caifas) It is part of the game then that the information for a better world is handled as a lesser probability of existence but in this planet so far it has always been rejected. What is more appalling of the coronavirus crisis is that utter lack of 'horizon' in the answer to the pandemic; as if humans were all just enzymen attached to its machines and pre-conceived ideas on how to respond to any crtisis – the financial, military response, the lack of foresight, the almost universal repetition of the same errors; the advance of the mechanical metal-earth future, in brief the deterministic automaton processes that only take us a step further into a non-human world, when it could have been a time for renewal and r=evolution.

APPENDIX: LAWS OF 5D SPACE SUPERORGANISMS TRACING TIME WORLDCYCLES. ITS STIENCES.

The discovery of a new dimension of space-time is the most important r=evolution human sciences experience and if not were because of Newton's error certainly mankind would have understood earlier the organic 5th dimension of 'scalar space-time' since it was discovered precisely by the evolution of 'metal-eyes' (telescopes and microscopes) who probe in those scales; but due to Newton's error was *never properly formalized* till those texts. Why the 5th dimension was shunned off by science for so long thus require an analysis of how little, mechaism with its simplification of reality in abstract, 'lineal terms' understood of the previous dimensions, made with a pinch of salt, regarding the 'supreme intelligence' our species ascribes... to our species, revealing all what humans *do not even see about those dimensions – namely, the fact that all of them have associated to its spatial 'dimensional form', a 'motion in time'*; hence they are both dimensions of space=form and time=motions or 'dimotions', due the principle of relativity (we cannot distinguish motion from form, so we see Earth as a still form, when it is a rotary motion) and their entangled relationships; as dimensions must be defined in co-invariant equations with each other. So once we realize how childish are the definitions mechanism does of time=motion, space=dimensional form and scale, we will define 5D metrics.

The 1st dimensional motion of space-time (ab. Dimotion) humans measured was undoubtedly length, calculated through the steps of roughly a meter as a distance of space (dimensional, formal view) or Locomotion, (Time=motion view). But it would be the ONLY dimension of space to which humans ascribed a motion in time, which left limp our understanding of time till this date; when we still have only a dual space time dimotion, 'locomotion' or 'Ts' (where we capitalize the external motion of the system, in this case of an internal form, s, without motion)

The 2nd dimensional motion of height (form) or information (motion) was still shredded in mystery as it would need the discovery in China or Mesopotamia of the Pythagoras Theorem to have a proper metrics related to length. Since a *formalism of Dimensional motions of space-time needs to relate them in a co-invariant form. So the Pythagoras theorem connected X and its Perpendicular Y dimension of height, allowing the expansion of Greek Bidimensional Geometry. But as its motion in time, 'information' was ignored – height became orphan. Consider the screen you are reading, it has a height dimension, as a paper, so the product of X x Y gives you information.* The problem of the motion in time of height is that is a 'slower' time dimotion, connected to growth and evolution. So all species as they evolve they grow in information= height, from mammals that became humans to reptiles that became dinosaurs and birds, to matter that becomes the high tube to infinity of a black hole singularity. So the 'informative' function =motion of height is perceptive projective geometry of a high point, reason why heads, bankers, antennas and pulpits that command biologic, economic & cultural organisms are on top. If we named **Ts-locomotion** (external motion of a still 'point particle'), **Height-information is its inverse, St** (external form with internal motion, form-in-action, in-form-ation, as a TV screen where motion is within its image. Geometry gave height a 'motion of evolution of information', which was out of the comprehension of man's mind that had only the capacity to see time=motion=change in very short spans, related to its visual 'clock' of 1 glimpse a second, 1 thought a second, one step a second, one heart beat a second, which synchronized all the parts of its organisms to its time clock. All other different time clock speeds of nature were lost to him.

The 3rd dimension of width was known but unconnected to length and height – the cube problem unresolved – till modern times. So only 2 dimensions of space were formalized earlier in the History of thought by Greek Geometers and Logicians from Pythagoras to Aristotle, setting the foundations of knowledge for the following two millennia.

Then came Galileo who didn't understand Earth had both a dimension of **mental space=still form** and a motion in time due the logic postulate of relativity ('We cannot distinguish a state of motion from a state of form', Galileo, Einstein, Poincare). So we see Earth still but it is moving (e pur si muove, e pur no muove). *It was the first chance for mankind to understand the duality of dimensions of still mental space=form and true time=motion.* Galileo didn't go so far; instead with the 'monologic' of a single Aristotelian cause, A->B, proper of human limited minds he chose that the Earth moved; while the Church chose it didn't move.

But none explained both things together. He then associated the dimension of 'time' locomotion, or 'speed' to the dimension of length, Ts. And he got its

ANIMALS & PLANTS HAVE INVERSE DIRECTIONS OF ENERGY & INFORMATION, SINCE PLANTS USE LIGHT AS ENERGY AND CHEMICAL PARTICLES AS INFORMATION WITH BRAINS IN THE ROOTS ANIMALS USE LIGHT AS INFORMATION AND EARTH TO MOVE BY ELECTRIC REPULSION AND MECHANIC GRAVITATION

GALAXY HAS ITS INFORMATIVE, TALL PHERIC CENTER IN A GRAVITATIONAL LACK HOLE AND ITS ELECTROMAGNETIC ENERGY √ ITS STELLAR PLANE, SURROUNDED Y A MEMBRANE OF DARK MATTER.

metric when he applied the mechanical clock to measure 'motions in space', defining a $v=s/t$ formula of Galilean Relativity, latter refined with a $-ct$ parameter by Einstein, who, following in the path of Riemann's dissertation of Non-Euclidean metrics, expressed the mental linguistic nature of Spaces as 'simultaneous measure relative to a frame of reference'. *Since stillness is a maya of the senses, as each mind creates a finitesimal still image of the Universe, self-centered in its Non-E 'fractal point of measure' that holds a world in itself (Leibniz's monads) So Ss-mind-languages stop and order Tt-entropic motions.*

Thus Humans are stuck with a single ts-spacetime dimotion, locomotion, corresponding to length; a metric for height as a space dimension without its motion of time, information, Pythagoras Theorem and a 3rd unconnected dimension of width, without its corresponding motion in time, 'reproduction'. It was a limited view of space=form, time=motion and its duality as dimensional motions of space-time. Yet human egocy (ego= idiocy) heralded those children of thought as the highest intelligences of the cosmos. So when Einstein, whose best definition of time was 'what the clock measures', died, 'Time' published a cartoon with a future Earth crossed with continental letters: 'Einstein was born here'.

But since humans don't associate to space dimensions its relative motions=actions in time, beyond locomotion, *the living functions of the 3 dimotions of space-time disappeared and with it the vitality and intelligence of the Universe, represented by the dimotion of height=informative perception & the dimotion of width, St (potential) + Ts (kinetic)= S ↔ T: Energetic reproduction.* So in physics the duality of energy explained the constant trans-form-ation of one into another. While Heaviside connected the 2 dimotions of length and height with the width dimotion, with the co-invariant metric of vectorial cross product: $X \times Y = Z$. It is the law that creates the 1st perceived scale of information 'Euclidean, light space-time', evolved by 'warping', informing, by a $-ct$ parameter of electric height the $-E$ gravitational spacetime of General Relativity. So he could simplify the 20 equations of Maxwell into 4 and noticed the existence of gravitomagnetism, the first insight into the equivalence between the scales of atoms and galaxies. Width became with vectorial calculus a 'motion' of reproduction in Nature. C-speed = Ts-locomotion and the magnetic or electric field of relative height reproduce seemingly out of nothing the other relative width field. When a body reproduces cells, it packs them in the width dimension. And so we had 3 dimensions of space, connected by proper metrics (Pythagoras, cross product) and its functions =motions in time; locomotion connected to length; information connected to height and width connected to reproduction – *dimensions of space have vital functions in time constructing together ternary, topologic organisms – the fundamental particle of the living Universe.*

But humans made an even larger error regarding the substances of which we are all made, space=form and time=motion, when Newton confused a mathematical artifact with reality, thinking there was a space-time Cartesian graph with a single lineal time coordinates (that of locomotion=length) and two perpendicular spatial coordinates; taking space and time out of reality when it is obvious to experience that we, real beings, ARE made of finite vital space dimensions, the space we occupy with our bodies, and live through finite vital 'temporal motions', the time we last in existence, (Leibniz's view). *So a fractal generator equation describes all Nature's systems as combination of 3 space-time Dimotions:*

Ts-moving limbs/fields/territories <S ↔ T reproductive energy body-wave-worker> St- informative particle/head/ruling class

Reality is a tapestry of organisms made of Ts-limbs/fields that move a §T-body/wave, guided by a St-high informative particle-head, in physical, biologic and social systems. Moreover the form of those 3 dimotions corresponds to the 3 only topologies (forms with motions) of spacetime: Ts=|-lineal limbs/fields, the geometry that moves faster between 2 points; St=O-spherical heads-particles, the geometry that stores maximal information; and §T= hyperbolic, wide, Ø-bodywaves, the 'hour-glass' geometry that includes the other two, hence can reproduce both. *We ARE living topologies.*

RECAP. A thorough review of the 3 space dimensions ascribe 3 motions of time to them: locomotion to 'length'; information to height and reproduction to width, vitalizing space-time, by correcting Newton's error and showing that we are all ensembles of the 3 only topologies of a 5D Universe: $|xO=Ø$: Past-Motion x Future-Form = Present-Energy

The fourth and fifth dimotions of seeds/minds and entropy-death, and the $\Delta \pm j$ scales of the fifth dimension

As it happened with previous dimensional r=evolutions the metrics of a new Dimension of space-time is deceptively simple. $\sqrt{x^2+y^2}=C^2$ & $S_x \times S_y = S_z$ is the Pythagorean and vectorial metric of the 3 dimensions of space-time; $V=S/T$ with the $-c^2t^2$ ad on of Einstein is the metric of the so-called 4th dimension of time, in true form the time locomotion of length. $S \times T = \Delta \pm j$ is the

metric of the scalar 5 dimensional motions of a spacetime superorganism, which states that the local speed of time of a superorganism is inversely to its size, but the product of both remains co-invariant. It means that smaller scales run faster cycles of time that encode the in-form-ation of the Universe in its frequency and form. Hence the equivalence of all species of all scales equaled by the same metric of spatial form x temporal motion (St-information and Ts-kinetic energy in more common terms). As smaller species reproduce faster and survive better. So often they kill larger forms (as in the case of the present Coronavirus Pandemic, where a simpler 30 gene virus has put on his knees the entire human civilization). But mostly, scales associate together. So faster, smaller scales code the information of larger ones (quantum particles with its numbers code atoms and molecules, genes code biological organisms and memes code social organisms).

The vital interactions between space-time species of different scales is either symbiotic in organic systems or predatory when scales are not entangled by fractal networks that connect the larger Δ_j whole that provides energy to its $\Delta-j$ parts, which reproduce information upwards. The fifth dimension thus has a scalar asymmetry and biological duality that forms organisms, even if humans have focused in the entropic Darwinian struggle for existence; not the social complex, organic symbiosis through fractal physiological networks of energy and information.

This 1st glimpse to 5D metrics shows the importance of a new formal dimension of spacetime in all sciences. *Mathematics* from the Greeks to renaissance, all the science of physics, and the r=evolution of all sciences that those papers imply depart from such humble 'metric' beginnings. For it to happen an extraordinary effort of conceptual, logic thought that stretches to all other foundational elements of science is required; normally the work of a single mind in the beginning, as in the case of Galileo and Einstein or the eclectic gathering of several generations of thought into a strict formal discourse, as in the case of Euclidean geometry and Aristotelian logic in Greek Science. This work is both, because the 5th dimension has been among us for centuries of modern science, but never explained in the interrelationships between the different scales of the Universe, each one described by a science. So we bring together all that work to extract the common=isomorphic laws between scales.

The 6 EXTERNAL and internal dimotions of Space=Form and Time=motion. Dilogic

Regardless of human dexterity as 'homunculus enzyman' (a species able to ensemble things with its hands, and evolve machines of metal of a higher density that without our help would never reach organic form), one theme that surfaces constantly in those texts is the astounding lack of common sense and rational thought in our models of reality, departing from so obvious false postulates (from big bang theory and other simplex entropic models of natural sciences to the triad of historic idol-ogies of metal, nationalism, capitalism and mechanism, to the anthropomorphic egocy (ego=idiocy) of religions. But none of those blunders compares with Newton's egocy declaring that space and time were NOT the substance of reality as Leibniz explained but a 'Cartesian frame of reference' God had drawn behind the Universe as he was using one to draw his planetary orbits and obviously he was a god-like man. 500 years of primitive thinking in all sciences derives from this blunder. Fact is reality has 5 Dimensional motions of spacetime to play with at local level and construct the superorganisms that trace worldcycles of spacetime through scales of the fifth dimension in the 'game of existence', we all play – what is all about. 'Simplicity is genius' (Leonardo); 'I want to know the thoughts of God, the rest are details'. Einstein. The thoughts of God are space dimensions and its parallel time motion and we all are the details constructed with them. The correction of Newton's error transforms lineal time measures into ∞ cyclical time clocks, ordered through scales by 5D Metrics. And it makes all beings a combination of 'Space=information and time=energy, motions'. *As all 5D dimensions of space=form do always have content of time=motion, by the Principle of Relativity: 'we cannot distinguish a state of (time) motion from a still state (of space form)' (Poincare) we can distinguish according to t,s, internal or T, S EXTERNAL of T or t-motion and S or s form, 6 dimotional combinations of states of space-time:*

Ss-language with no internal or external motion that expresses the potential game of existence, the mind of the Universe.

St-information; a still organism with internal motion, as when we sleep or think or the image motion of a still Tv Set.

Ts-locomotion, a system moving externally but internally in a rigid state, as a particle-point with a gravity center.

Tt-entropy, a system with internal and external motion, hence becoming disordered=dying.

st: the being in itself isolated from the external world and **ST**, the world isolated from the being.

ST interaction defines dilogic as the basic expression of existence. That is, $A \neq B$ but rather $S \leftrightarrow T$. Space and time merge with different degrees of hierarchical complementarity to form all what exists from gender to organisms.

Trilogic space organisms and Tetralogic scalar actions.

Complexity arises from the ∞ combinations of those 5 Dimotions *Its dual, dynamic interactions in scale: st=ST (seed & whole) & spacetime: Ts=St that combine Ts-limbs and St-heads into $\S\T$ -bodies, St-potential & Ts-kinetic into $\S\T$ -Energy waves for which we shall use the combined $\S\T$ dual symbol for SsTt.*

So 5 local Ss-Tt-Dimotions gather together to create space-time supærganisms traveling through existence, from an $\Delta-1$ Seed, Ss of pure still form that reproduces in $\Sigma\alpha$ clones becoming a network 'supærganism', emerging in Δ^0 as a s lower larger spacetime being, made of 3 canonical Ts> $\S\T$ >St parts, to live 3 ages dominated by locomotion or youth, reproduction, when the form achieves immortality and information or 3rd 'still St-age' to finally die in a 'reversal' of arrow of time from growth of information to growth of locomotion into a Tt-entropic big-bang dissolving death.

5D metrics shows there are scales of size in space with different time clocks. So we need 2 scalar dimotions of space-time; for smaller $\Delta-1$ scales; where smaller systems in space run faster clocks of information— the direction of Max. S=information or **Ss** that codes with languages the program of life; and the inverse $\Delta+1$ scale of larger systems in space with slower time clocks; the dimension of entropy that kills a system, **Tt**; which in the 1st graph round up the worldcycle of existence. First a still seed, Ss, or mind and its Ss-languages of information reproduce and synchronize through social evolution $\Sigma \Delta-1$ clone parts that emerge in Δ^0 as a larger simultaneous whole joined by 3 Δ^0 networks, Ts> $\S\T$ >St organism living within an $\Delta+1$ world, till the superorganism exhausts its $\S\T$ -energy and an opposite dimotion, dissolves the networks and returns the system back to an $\Delta-1$ plane of disaggregated parts in a Tt- internal and external expansive $M=E/c^2$ big-bang, war dimotion or entropic Tt-death (Physical, social and biologic jargons).

So the 5 Dimotions put in a sequence define existence, as a 'travel up and down through $\Delta \pm j$ 3 scales of space-time". Regarding Dimensional numbers, we put the 4th dimension of locomotion in its proper place as the motion of length; so we have now 3 'Dimotions' which broken into ∞ beings vitalize them and 2 more $\Delta \pm j$ scalar dimotions for a total of 5; using the term '5th dimension' for the sum of all the scales of space-time. This 'numbering' superseeds given its errors and omissions that of our 'Baconian tribal idols' (Galileo, Newton, Einstein), to study spacetime beings with a proper definition of each of the 5 Local Dimensional motions that create a spacetime organism living a worldcycle, as $\Delta-1$: Ss-seed languages evolve into Δ^0 :Ts-limbs/fields of lineal locomotion > $\S\T$ - \emptyset hyperbolic bodywaves of re=productive width > guided by O-St high particles/heads, till its $\S\T$ -energy is exhausted by an excess of information in its 3rd age, exploding back into Tt-entropy: Ss>Ts> $\S\T$ >St<<Tt (whereas < means an expansion of a seed of spatial form into a motion in time, and > a dynamic contraction, as the 5 Spacetime dimotions transform into each other). We use a dual Ss: \S & Tt: \T or $S \leftrightarrow T$ to express that present dynamic form.

The being in itself, st^0 , is part of a larger world, $ST \pm j$, in which it interacts through scales by means of quantum dimotions, we shall call actions, or finitesimals (in calculus' formalism). The 2 interactions of dimotions between ST_j and st^0 and $St \approx Ts$ become 2 next layers of complexity that evolve dimotions into spacetime trimotions or supærganisms ($St < \S\T > Ts$) and scalar tetramotions ($st^0 \leq ST \pm j$), when a superorganism interacts with other scales to extract 'invisible forces' for Ts-locomotion from its relative $\Delta-4$ scale, (gravitation for man), bits of St-information from its $\Delta-3$ scale (light spacetime in man), bites of $\S\T$ -energy from its $\Delta-2$ scale (amino acids), st-reproductive seeds of from its $\Delta-1$ scale & St-communicates with Δ^0 clones to evolve socially into larger $\Delta+1$ organic ST-wholes. While the balance dimotion between Ts-limbs/fields & St-particles/heads creates the re=productive body-wave State: $|xO = \emptyset$. Those 2 entanglements in simultaneous spacetime (superorganisms) or through

spacetime scales (actions of existence) create 'organic vital space' and 'scalar time events' So through actions=scalar dimotions of spacetime a supœrganism entangles with the $\Delta\pm 4=9$ planes of spacetime it perceives, which becomes its whole world - its island universe.

The perfect balance of the immortal Universe. If we consider the relative past, the field/limbs and the lower planes that sustain larger wholes, and the relative future, the heads-particles that guide through languages the motion of a being; and the larger whole sustained by its parts that must come first; then the present is the state of balance between St & Ts in SHM energy waves (physical systems) or bodies or working classes that re=produce, hence repeat the present. Immortality is a discontinuous reproduction of the same cyclical motions in a single plane; while scalar immortality is caused by the mirror identity between st⁹ minds and ST+1, its larger symbiotic world that projects back its image reordering the whole create the present immortal states of reality and bring a metaphysical deep truth into being: *for the Universe to be perfect, immortal, the $\Delta-j$ scale must be identical to the $\Delta+i$ scale, the galaxy must be an atom, something we shall see in the papers of physics to be the case in terms of 5D. Spacetime present and scalar isomorphism create the ∞ immortal Universe, an absolute perfect reality where each relative part dies but can reproduce its information so its form exists forever.*

5 survival dimotions/actions : game of existence:

What all supœrganisms do, from the smallest light spacetime particle and atom (right) to the human (down) is to perform with its 5 Dimotions 5 actions that ensure its survival, while killing lesser species to take its Tt-entropic motion to reproduce its own St-information. Thus not only Dimensions are vital, but the game of existence is biological. It is the program of existence for all systems that absorb the 5 Dimotions=actions of existence: St-information for its particle/heads, Ts-locomotion to go with its limbs/fields to a Tt-entropic field to feed and transform its preys into its own $\S\T$ -energy to reproduce the system. And this will be achieved better communicating through a common Ss-language with other mind-entities forming physiological herds that evolve into larger whole supœrganisms. So what each of those systems does to survive, is to play locally its 5 Dimotions in an efficient sequential order: a particle/head Ss-perceives in a 'visual=topologic' language a prey >it Ts-moves->to Tt-kill and feed on its $\S\T$ -body energy to imprint its St-information and $\S\T$ - reproduce often in herds of similar clone supœrganisms (∞) forming stronger, larger $\Delta+1$ herds. Those 5 sequential dimotions, $S_s < T_s < T_t + S_t = \S\T$ are called in biology the drives of life, in physical systems, actions, in humans 'will'. They are coded by the 5 Light space-time dimotions of electric information, c-locomotion, Magnetic width, social color and Tt-quantum potentials; by the 4 quantum numbers and its functions in atoms, by the 5 letters of the genetic code, by social memes in humanity. So we conclude all space-time organisms follow the same program of existence, which added along the whole existence of the being defines the worldcycle of life and death of all systems, whose total sum is dominant in information, reason why we age, wrinkling, increasing our 'form' and only the Tt-entropic explosion of death balances the total zero sum making the whole Universe immortal.

Recap. All i 'st'-details play the same 'survival actions', extracting from the outer ST-larger world, motion, information and combining it into $\S\T$ -energy to re=produce a 'present' copy of itself so the being is preserved in a discontinuous manner. And all will be made of the 3 St-heads/particles, Ts-limbs/fields, combined into hyperbolic $\S\T$ - energy body-waves.

Its sequential Worldcycles Travels through 5D scales.

Time and space scales were known before 5D metrics but what a formal metric system that maintains invariant a system allows is 'to know how to travel through a dimension of space-time' (Klein). Because when we move in 4D space-time the Lorentz transformations remain invariant we know we can travel within a given scale. Now we know because the product of size in space (S) x speed of cyclical time processes or frequency - f(t) - remains invariant, a system can travel through scales as it grows in size, slowing down its metabolic and thinking processes and vice versa. Reason why smaller systems think faster and code the information of larger ones (chips, genes, memes), becoming symbiotic and creating those supœrganisms with 'networks' (biology, societies) or 'waves' (physics) that connect the larger and smaller scales.

LIGHT-PHOTON: ORGANIC ACTIONS: $\Delta-4$

formation: light-electric field

Electromagnetic Wave

C-Speed=length: Reproduction

Entropy: width: magnetic field

Color: frequency:

Energy Volume

n = principal
distance from nucleus

l = angular
shape of orbital

m = magnetic
orientation in space

s = spin
electron spin

Entropy: Motion Information: Gauging U: Social Evolution O: Reproduction

ELECTRON-PARTICLE: ORGANIC ACTIONS: $\Delta-2, 3$

1. $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} = \rho_V$
2. $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$
3. $\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t}$
4. $\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{J}$

Existence of a space-time organism, develops as a feedback function, $S \leq T$, in 3 sequential phases/ages /horizons: *Max. T x Min.S (youth); Max. SxT (s=t); Max. S x Min. T (3rd age)*, between $S_s \times \epsilon_0 T$ (seed in the lower plane, $i-1$) and $T_t \times 0 \epsilon S$ (entropy=death):

$\Delta-1 \rightarrow \Delta^0$: S_s . A supœrganism worldcycle starts its existjence as a seed of form.

$T > s$ (Ts): In its first horizon or 'entropic, youth age' limbs/fields of Ts-motion dominate; $\max.T_s \times \min. S_t$.

Max. SxT: s=t. It is the present balanced age of energy or classic age of 'life', when Ts-motion and St-information are in balance also as 'genders', ensure its immortality through reproduction

Max. St x min. Ts: 3rd age of the information that warps and exhausts the energy of the system.

$\Delta^0 \leftarrow \Delta-1$: OS x Tt: It is the end or death of the cycle that reverses its form and becomes energy again.

4D ignores worldcycles as space-time travel reduces to 1 scale & dimotion; Ts-locomotion. What is space=form & time= motion, the 2 substances of which all those supœrganisms are made, is not understood because of a bigger physical error that has fogged human science for 400 years, since physicists sided with Newton's absolute space-time (a single lineal clock for the entire Universe) when reality has sided with Leibniz's infinite time clocks and relational=fractal spaces. That is, we are NOT placed in an abstract mathematical Cartesian graph of space-time (the error of Newton, who confused the 'mathematical artifact with reality as today quantum physicists confuse reality with its probability equations), but we are made of 'Time=motion, kinetic energy' and 'space=form, information'. Look around you all what you see is 'forms of space' moving in time. 'Leibniz is right but if so we have to start physics from scratch' (Einstein); which is what 5D does.

Physicists without a scalar understanding of the Universe and 'only' the knowledge of lineal external time-motion, or Ts-locomotion left the field of time studies limp. So the worldlines of Einstein, heralded as the summit of timespace studies only tell you how you Ts-move your limbs in a single scale through life. While its philosophy of science merely added Tt-entropy (internal disordering motion that kills a system) to the mix; but the other 3 Dimotions of space-time, dominant in s-form, were hardly understood, and the way an $\S \Pi$ -being travels through scales, growing in size as it slows down its speed of time, through the 'palingenesis' of its fetal life in the $\Delta-1$ scale, as an island-universe, to 'emerge' in the Δ^0 scale as a larger, slower being, and going back through death and decay to the $\Delta-1$ scale, were completely ignored. This 'worldcycle' is the essential travel of existence, we can now formalize in 5D, and opens up an immense new field of knowledge to all sciences.

RECAP. We define existence as a travel of a spacetime supœrganism, enacting its Dimensional motions through 5D scales.

We depart from a 5D spacetime simple metric equation: $SxT = \Delta \pm i$, which proves the organic network structure of the Universe; as its ultimate cause is the fact that '3 consecutive scales' of 5D, form a supœrganism. We shall call them the $\Delta-1$ (atomic, cellular, individual in physical, biological and social systems), the Δ^0 scale that defines the networks (physiological St-Ts- $\S \Pi$ networks of information, motion and energy, of gravitational, electromagnetic chemical and linguistic financial and study the main particle of reality: the 5D supœrganism of spacetime networks.

EXISTENTIAL PENTALOGIC ALGEBRA: $\Delta \pm \infty \geq \neg (T \pm i \geq S \epsilon \geq 0 \epsilon)$ THE SCALAR STIENCES OF THE UNIVERSE.

The different superorganisms of stience. The Universe is a nested superorganism NOT a mechanism, and so the machine is not a model – just an evolving organism of 'metalife' which human catalyze in their evolution through the same phases of a viral ensemble, as we did the bodies of machines in the steam British age, its engines/hearts in the German electrochemical age, its metal-minds (phone-ears, Tv-eyes and chips-brains) in the U\$ age and now we ensemble into robots.

This philosophy of science, which first Aristotle in his organon, the whole compendium of his work, then Leonardo in his neo-platonic attempt to describe the physiological networks of human organisms, cities, societies, planet Earth, even machines; then Leibniz with his analysis of 'space-time superorganisms' and non-Euclidean points that are minds-monads that hold a world in itself, is a bit more complex than the mechanist view, and so it has taken longer to be properly formalized. To do so we needed a new dimension of scalar space-time, and its metric equation, $S \times T = iC$, the smaller the size in space of a system is, the faster its frequency of cyclical time that stores in its forms and frequency the information of the Universe. So unlike machines that exist in a single plane of size, superorganisms are structures that extend through 3

Spheric particle-head:

To: Mind= Minimum Energy-Space, Max information-time.

Se: Planar-Toroid Fields/limbs: Maximum Energy-Space Minimum information

UNIVERSAL ORGANISM : Hyperbolic Body-wave:STI

Macrocosms U=9

Galaxy=Black Hole+Herd of stars
Economy:Digital Information+Herds of Machines.
History=Wor[l]d Religion+Herd of Men

Relative Small Observer: Man

Relative Big Observer: Man u=5

Animal=Light-Brain+Herds of cells.
Cell=DNA+Herds of Carbohydrates
Molecule:Herds of Atoms+ Electronic forces.
Atom: Herd of Nucleons and Electrons, communicated by gravitational and Ψ forces.
Microcosms u=1

scales of the 5th dimension, the cellular/atomic/citizen $\Delta-1$ scale, (biologic, physical and social organisms), the Δ^0 physiological scale, where 3 networks of spatial form (nervous system, gravitational system, legal system), temporal motion (limbs/fields/territories), and its reproductive combination (blood, electromagnetic, economic systems) organize those cells, atoms, citizens into a wholes and the $\Delta+1$ scale of ecosystems, celestial bodies and nations and civilinations of mankind. The organic Universe thus is more complex, entangled among scales whose laws of synchronicity, symmetry and simultaneity have never been formalized till those texts, which will form together an encyclopedia of the 3 main superorganisms of human sciences, the Galatom (physical organisms between the atomic and galactic scale), Earth (biologic superorganisms of the 3 ages of the planet, Gaia, the Earth of life, History, the human Earth, and the metal-earth of company-mothers of machines and weapons, or economic ecosystem), of which the human superorganism of history deserves a closer look as we 'descend' from the nested physical $\Delta\pm 4$ Universe, into $\Delta\pm 2$ Earth into mankind, into our 'formal Δ^0 mind languages' of perception of space (mostly mathematical) and time (mostly logical)

So the question is how we go about through the study of the different scalar stiences of the Universe and its superorganisms to the level of detail and complexity of 400 years of mechanism since Galileo instead of Leonardo was taken as the father of science; when humans have NO idea of even the simplest level just described, if on top of that ignorance, the complexity of the organic paradigm requires the reader an intellectual effort he has not done since school? It is not easy and the failed efforts of the 3 colossus that preceded my 30GBs of work, Aristotle's organon, Leonardo's notebooks and Leibniz's epistolary testify to the single mind's - 'a point that holds the entire world in itself' - impossible task of unfold the point, the thoughts of god, the laws of Timespace supœrganisms (ab. T.œs) in its ∞ details.

To do so we work given the primacy of 5D, $\Delta\pm j$ scales, each one studied by a stience, on the 4 correspondences of $\Delta\pm 3$ Physical, $\Delta\pm 2$ biological, $\Delta\pm j$ historic and Δ^0 linguistic scales. For each of them then we consider the 5 'elements' that create reality according to its symmetry and hierarchy, as we can describe all systems as a 'mental', (@) linguistic image of a simultaneous form in space, a supœrganism or part of it, that lives a worldcycle of life and death in time, as it grows from a seminal Seed of still pure spatial information, Ss, in $\Delta-1$ through its physiological growth to emerge as a 3-network superorganism of lineal Ts-locomotion limbs/fields, spherical heads particles of St-information, and $\S\text{TT}$ hyperbolic-energy body-wavers in $\Delta\emptyset$ to live in an $\Delta+1$ world in which it will be a cell of a larger supœrganism, to die back in an entropic death

of maximal inner and outer motion, Tt , to its $\Delta-1$ disaggregated at death. Hence existence is a travel through 3 scales of the fifth dimension, forming a worldcycle, as a superorganism of space, guided by a mental sentient focus that performs the actions required for the system and its parts to survive.

This establishes two key structural forms to study any system or 'scalar science' from the smallest analysis done by quantum physics to the larger astrophysical analysis, when we consider the $\Delta\pm 3$ galatom, to the human-sized study of mankind in its 3 cellular, individual and social scales. Either we analyze (preferred) its 3 Δ -scales through its temporal worldcycle of life and death as a 'spatial' superorganism, guided by, its languages mirror of the larger world that perform its survival program of existence, $\Delta\geq T\geq S\geq @$, within the 'entropic limits' of death in time, scale perception and limited vital space, and @-linguistic synoptic capacity of gathering information; which is what we do here, with 5 papers for each science, one of 'history, physics, mathematics, biology' in space, one in time, one in scale, one in entropy and one in mind-languages; or we study its '5 dimotional components that form both the structure of the organism in space, its Ts -limbs/fields, St -heads/particles and $\$T$ -bodywaves, between its Ss -seed and Tt -entropic death... The whole entanglement and complex symmetries between ALL the elements of reality makes both analysis often complementary.

What this has to do with modern science? In a world in which humans understood both the synthetic entangled organic holistic paradigm, the thoughts of god, and the mechanical, analysis with machines of its details, all. Humanity would study since infancy the organic paradigm and all its sciences with those organic laws, and then only in university as it specializes in different sciences, arts and praxis, learn the details in great depth. But the mind of man, and its ethic understanding would be tailored by organicism, and the respect of Gaia, and the needed balance man and its most important organism history, must achieve with life earth by repressing its mechanical world that represents the future extinction of our weaker species. It is for that reason that we do start all our papers, regardless of what we study in detail, from entropic physical big-bangs to the present state of History – the coronavirus crisis, or one of its 7 cultural civilinations that wrongly has broken mankind down to hundreds of nations, with a nested structure of inverse symmetry. In two pages we consider what this is about – an encyclopedia of the organic Universe; then we develop its fundamental laws and key concepts of each 4 scalar type of sciences in 33 pages and then each paper study each science in Δ -scale, T-ime, S-pace, @-mind languages (those of its species, mathematical in physics, evolutionary and genetic in biology, verbal and artistic in humans), and entropic limits.

The 5 parts of the being. Pentalogic symbols are necessary to understand the Universe as much as mathematics and verbal thought. $\Delta\pm\infty \geq \neg (T\pm j \geq S\infty \geq 0\epsilon)$ thus defines the being in its 5 pentalogic elements. Existence happens within the larger block of time of the Universe of infinite scales (if as it seems the galatom is immortal); $\Delta\pm\infty$; within the entropic '- ' limits $\neg()$ of a time worldcycle happening between $\pm j$ planes in 'mind', , where the suporganism in space ($S\infty$) is just a slice of that worldcycle, focused in a single plane, as a finitesimal 0, part of a much larger Universe. The hierarchy is thus clear, including that between the whole block of 5D spacetime, $\Delta\pm\infty$ and the entropic Tt -flow of disordered motion, which is smaller even in such a finitesimal part as the '0 ϵ '-mind that 'cogito ergo sum', and hence it is ordered but also part of that $\Delta\pm j$ block of time.

Thus the fifth dimension is also the absolute 'dimension of future' as a block of time, in which species go up and down from seminal to organic form in a larger world, back to seminal form. And so all the laws of science can be summarized as a block of time, in the laws of existential logic of 5D and its scales, each one studied by a science:

Curve of existence as a bilateral symmetry.

The 4 phases of a real function of existence are then formalized in existential algebra as 'støeps' that change the S & T

parameters of systems from youth, dominated by Ts-locomotion to maturity, the reproductive TS-age, to a 3rd age dominated by St-actions and then *as energy becomes spent in a sudden fast dual motion, from St to Ss, the moment of linguistic stillness and death to << Tt in a dual reversal of death*: In the first phase, corresponding to the paligenetic age of placental energy the ratio of change (derivative) has the absolute maximal e^x , which is its own derivative. In its 2nd phase it diminishes to the minimal $1/x$ the log derivative, which is the definition of an infinitesimal part; till in the 3rd phase it will start a bilateral symmetric inverse function of decay with $-1/x$ diminution and a fast collapse in the 4th phase of a 3rd age and final death moment. So the combination of \pm exponentials and logarithm curves are also the best way to graph as a bell curve the worldcycle of existence as a 'composite' of a \pm exponential and logarithmic 0ε -sum.

As any student knows there is an intimate relationship between the exponential and the sinusoidal by way of Euler's formula in the realm of complex numbers, which we treated briefly in theory of numbers.

So sinusoidal bell curve functions represent a worldcycle, though the symmetry is broken in the moment of entropic death when the collapse is extreme in a 'falling line' as death happens in a single moment of time:

$4D \gg \Delta - 1(\text{seed}) \sum \Delta: | - \dot{S} T(\text{limb-field}) < \emptyset - S \approx T(\text{iterative bodywave}) > 0 - \xi \delta(\text{particle-head}) \ll 5D \Delta - 1(\text{death})$

This universal mandate, expressed in any language, from 'grow and multiply' to the conservation of St-angular momentum, Ts-locomotion and S=T potential energy, to the behavior of superorganisms that constantly switch between space and time states, moving and sleeping, outward and inward orientations expresses as entropic limits of any existence, the *larger nested Universe that tries to achieve its function of existence by limiting that of its inner parts. In fact it builds and selects its inner parts to maximize its function of existence, which often means their death as in Earth III, the metal-earth, which further evolves the planet but seems to condemn mankind to extinction.*

Conclusion. The main differences of organicism in space, time, scale, entropic limits and mind logic.

5D stience departs from a more complex view of the elements that compose any system to study all realities:

- **Time in 5D stience is cyclical**, not lineal, hence with multiple causalities and the capacity to carry in-form-ation in the frequency and form of its cycles; which *lineal time erases; hence lineal time 'stientists' become ST-upid* as Schopenhauer defined it: people who don't understand complex cause-effect relationships and resort to 'magic reasons'. This is specially the case in social sciences, where a new factor inputs, egocy: Ego=idiocy, the deformation of any mind that measures reality from its point of view, so your nose seems larger than Andromeda. And the result is the basic lack of 'true models' of social sciences, history and economics, able to predict the future, specially when it is not 'favorable to mankind'. And the outcome is the incapacity to solve the problems of mankind by acting on those cyclical patterns, which is the meaning of a 'law of science'. Since because time is cyclical when a scientist knows the causes of its cycles it can modify and direct the future to a better aim, by modifying the wrong causes. Unfortunately Humans became all ST-upids, when Galileo who taught ballistics in the Venice arsenal at the princely salary of 1000 golden ducats charged with the only goal of 'maximizing the length of its shots', wrote $V=s/t$ for its cannonballs and stated the principle of lineal inertia – alas 'manu military' all the cyclical clocks of the Universe became lineal. So today all humans believe in lineal time causality and have LOST all the cyclical information required to understand History and economics as a science. Mind the reader, cyclical time does NOT change the equations. For example, the previous equation, $V=S/T$ can be written in cyclical time as $V=\lambda \times f$, whereas on top of the speed we also learn the 'length of the wave cycle' and its time frequency, making time cyclical and discontinuous as it is in all clocks.

Space in 5D stience is 'fractal,' broken in similar vital spaces, not a continuum as in 4D stiences.

For that **reason it has 'entropic limits'** beyond which a being does not exist. Hence Death and entropic limits are similar concepts both in time (the limit of a cycle) and space (the limit of a system, surrounded by a membrane). For example nations have entropic limits in the armed borders another nation cannot cross as a superorganism, often related to all geographical limits – islands, mountains.

Moreover because space is fractal it is **broken in different scales** of size with similar properties. As the system of reproduction in the Universe is fractal: a seed with the information stored in 'static time cycles' is delivered by a larger $\Delta+1$

system (Δ is the symbol in 5D for scales) into a smaller space-time and so it creates a smaller replica of itself in a lower scale, in terms of the 'functions' the system will perform, and this little form will reproduce and evolve socially through networks creating a larger superorganism, which finally will grow in size from small into big. So systems are 'organic' because they co-exist in 'atomic/cellular, organic/thermodynamic and cosmological/gravitational scales. And this goes for civilizations and nations and monetary systems, as a prophet of the wor(l)d, a horde of warriors with a new weapons, of bankers with a new form of money reproduce it and create a larger system with its new seed of information. Again *a lot of information on the relationship and different 'speeds of time cycles' is lost when all those scales are pressed into a single one.* So In our papers on physics (Universe in space) we use this regained information to unify with cyclical time and fractal space, mathematically masses and charges and solve all the conundrums of astrophysics.

Finally because the Universe is fractal there are 'mirror-minds' who use 'languages' that are synoptic systems that 'reduce the information' of reality to fit in the mind-mirror creating an image of an even larger whole, the world. And that is the explanation of why minds exist, whose simple equation is :

$O' \text{ (finitesimal mind)} \times \infty \text{ (infinite universe)} = \text{Linguistic mind-mapping or 'world'}$.

This causes the egocy paradox: the humind believes the image is the whole reality as it is all what it sees.

In History and Economics the egocy paradox is so strong that cyclical time is vehemently rejected for 'magic, pseudo-religious, anthropomorphic causes' or selfish agendas of those who ab=use mankind and don't want to 'know', how they do it – specially financial and military people subject to the cycles of wars and holocausts due to the synergy of money and weapons. So its ego is pumped to 'cosmic proportions', and its 'language' that maps out reality becomes the only language of truth and intelligence. So the first men who thought in words believed God created taking words in Hebrew or Arab. And today that we use digital machines and its metal-minds to express the world with numbers, humans believe 'numbers' are the only language of reality. But the Universe is an organism of spatial information and temporal motions, its primary substance that you see around, forms that occupy space, moving.

Space=in/form/ation and time=motion thus become the substance of organisms ordered through scales that give birth to a 5D metric equation, such as smaller systems in space run faster time and life-death cycles. So the speed of time of systems is not the same for all of them, and 3 scales of different speeds form an organism – in man the cellular, individual and social scale. And finally for all this complex reality to 'work' in an ordered manner, systems which have a '**membrain**' that divides its vital space, from other systems, and are formed by 3 scalar space-times that give them organic nature; have in its highest 'scale' of size – that of the membrain that breaks it as a whole from the rest of the Universe a 'sensorial system' or mind, which interacts with the external Universe, encloses and orders its internal vital space and communicates with other similar beings, forming larger social organization; hence becomes **the mind of the system**.

We thus talk of a reality made of organisms of space-time, self-centered in a mind-membrain, whose language encodes a program of survival for the organism. And all the data humanity has gathered about reality needs to be 'put within this general template, to make sense of it'.

Finally in the organic, complex real Universe for an entity to exist causality is pentalogic. i.e. you exist because you have 3 topologic parts, simultaneously working together, limbs, body and heads. So your causality in a single plane of spacetime is trilogic. But for you to exist you must have a smaller scale of cellular parts and be part of a larger world. So you have then besides your scale 2 more 'causal reasons', the parts and the outer world. And so your logic is at least pentalogic.

Pentalogic is the minimum analysis 5D stience uses to explain anything. Below that you are reducing reality. So 5D stience uses the same data, but magically because the template that encases that data is far more complex and focused as an image of the underlying principles of reality, data fits, makes sense and its chaotic form acquires a deciphered order.

Since in 5D the whole $\Delta+i$ scale which DOES influence through its larger, slower fields of energy and information and enclosing membranes, the smallish $\Delta-i$ scales of reality. So the Earth influences through its glaciation and weather cycles, the cycles of History, which as all time systems has clocks – physical, mechanical or circadian – prove is not the simplified lineal system used in physics to measure ‘motion in space’, but repeats its patterns with the same causality once and again – or else there would not be laws of science.

$\Delta\pm 2$: BIOLOGIC SCIENCES: SUPÆRGANISM. GENES CODE HIGHER SCALES. SPECIES AS SUPERORGANISMS.

A supœrganism, the fundamental structure of the 5D Universe, is a simple system - NOT to confuse with the most evolved, complex

of them all, that of human beings, reason why so many people, lacking intellectual patience and having a natural biased ego-centered belief in man as the unique organism, reject the concept: An organism is just a group of similar forms, which organize themselves with at least two 'networks', one that provides the 'clone cells/citizens/atoms' with the vital energy they need to feed, move (blood-economic system-electromagnetic forces) and one that provides them with information to guide their reproductive actions (nerves system, political system, gravitational in-form-ative forces). This dual system IS the minimal organism of the Universe. As all organisms wear out by errors of informative action and end up warped by an excess of

information (third age of the organism) or killed and reconverted into formless energy (death); only those *systems that reproduced in the immortal Universe, do exist today. So all dual systems have an internal or external catalyst of its reproduction (as enzymes do with carbohydrates, or enzyemen with machines).*

We talk of a 3rd body-worker-wave element, besides the informative particle-head-upper class and limbic/ potential/ territorial source of its motions, which the system uses internally, or externally to reproduce. This IS

CONCEPTION AS A BLACK HOLE OF MIN. SIZE = MAX. INFORMATION

YOUTH AS A LINEAL, ENERGY, TOP PREDATOR SPECIES, GROWING IN SIZE

REPRODUCTIVE MATURITY: III AGE: GROWTH IN HEIGHT=INFORMATION

our definition of an organism. And so a factory is an organism, when we put the human enzymes, even if a machine alone is not.

In all species studied by science a common phenomenon occurs: the existence of parallel groups of beings organized into a single social form. Molecules are made up of atoms and electronic networks; economies are made up of human workers and consumers that reproduce and test machines, guided by financial networks of information (salaries, prices, costs); galaxies are composed of stars, which orbit rhythmically around a central knot, or black hole of gravitational information. Human bodies are organized by cells controlled by the nervous, informative system. A tree is a group of leaves, branches and roots connected by a network that provides energy (salvia) and information (chemical particles) to its cells. Cultures are made of humans related by verbal, informative and economic networks that provide their energy and information.

Species are suporganisms whose 3 ages are its 3 horizons, followed either by a survival process of eusocial evolution - the summit of the process of organic evolution, which Darwin realized was necessary to explain the success of eusocial insects, or become extinct by the 'new generation' of fitter animal forms. In the graph we can see its 3 Horizon=ages and its ternary topology, similar to that of any other organism; and the dominant Dimotion of information in the height axis, of both reptile species that ended in birds, and mammals that ended in man. So happened with metalife machines, whose final species, satellites are now forming the Dimotion of eusocial evolution, or future mind of the metal earth - internet. The 3 ages of time also brings the solution to the 'limits' of evolution, which Darwin already wondered: why certain species evolve so fast into complex forms as eyes and wings. Answer, because there are only 3 topologies to go, and so the choices are random but limited and it is every easy to go the right way. In the next graph we see those 3 ages of evolution as species can be treated as suporganisms with its own world cycles.

Sciences study those organic systems, made of clone forms tied up y 3 type of physiological networks.

Thus, there are 4 basic elements in all organic systems: Cellular units; Networks that provide motion & energy to the system (limbs in biology, potentials in physics, territories in sociology); Networks of information (heads/particles, languages and the class that issue them - money and laws - in history) & Networks that reproduce vital energy (body/waves in biologic and physical systems, the re=productive middle class and its factories and fields of work in society)

So cells/atoms/citizens of any system become organized by the 3 'networks' that provide entropic, digestive, raw materials; reproductive processes, and simultaneous, informative synchronizing languages to move together the system as a whole, and efficiently provide its equal parts with the goods they need to survive. In the next graph we compare two of such super organisms, at the individual and social level of mankind:

The main 'sciences' of each scale of STj-size, from atoms to galaxies, each one studied by a human science, *are centered in a social organism, as they all have in common the same 'organic elements' of all species: social cells of and the reproductive, energy networks and information languages that relate them.* All organic systems are generated by cellular units, gathered in 3 social networks that form together a higher 'whole' a new 'plane of social existence' (ab. Δ). So if we talk of an organism as living in the Δ_0 plane of thermodynamic matter; the $\Delta+1$ gravitational plane of Gaia, is its whole. Yet, since those cellular units $\Delta-1$ are made of smaller $\Delta-2$ cells, which show the same structure, we can define any organic system as a super-organism (made of smaller, similar suporganisms). All of them co-exist in at least 3 scales. So we talk of $\Delta-1$ cells/atoms/particles/ molecules/points connected by 3 physiological networks of relative entropy-motion, energy and in/form/ation, put together into an Δ^0 individual whole, existing in a larger $\Delta+1$ relative world. So we can map out all those super organisms according to scale, each one studied by a different 'science', (stience of space-time beings). So in systems sciences we talk of a 'fractal structure' for the whole Universe, in which smaller systems from the first particles to the larger galaxies tend to organic co-existing super organisms, and the laws of those systems apply to any of those super organisms, and are the fundamental laws for its proper design, as efficient systems that survive. So we can explain all sciences, both with the formal language of 5D and the more intuitive of physiological networks, since in the scalar Universe smaller parts are connected by organic networks that create the whole, emerging as a larger scale, and that creates the scalar systems of nature: particles joined by electromagnetic and gravitational networks form atoms that form molecules, cells, organisms and societies, matter systems, planetary systems, galaxies and universes... In Existential ilogic, a superorganism is a 'present simultaneous state' which hardly 'moves in time' as

the worldcycle does, because it works in a different way, as the limbs and the head both 'serve' the connecting

body: $T_s > S = T < S_t$, so the system remains in present, as both dynamic $<$ and $>$ states balance each other. So we write for all of them the 'fractal generator':

T_s- limbs/fields/territories < S ⇔ T: reproductive, energy body-waves-workers > S_t- informative particle/head/ruling class. Which is mathematically an O-sphere or relative future of max. S_t-information • a relative past – Limbs of max. T_s-motion = ∅-a hyperbolic present body-wave, origin of the general equation of present time, past • future = present (where • is usually a ± or x/ operand in 'existential algebra', the next level of complexity of existential ilogic.

PHYSICAL LAWS: ITS DIMOTIONAL PRINCIPLES. IMMORTAL, ∞ UNIVERSE

The immediate translation of 4D physics to 5D stiences (not the other way around, as there is a hierarchy, whereas philosophy of stience matters more than the $\Delta \pm j$ scales of physics, as all scales are the same, happens when we realize the 3 conserved S_t-Informative momentum/potential energy ± T_s-kinetic energy/momentum = Total momentum/energy of the system; whereas the momentum is the 'finitesimal' 0ε 'stœp' of the energy, the $\Delta+1$ whole. So $S_t \bullet T_s = \S \Pi$ defines the present state of a physical organism. While its worldcycles are easily shown for the thermodynamic scale in the 3±j states of matter, in the gravitational scale by the 3±j $\S \Pi$ -ages of galaxies and in quantum physics by its symmetric laws of forces (graph of worldcycles and next graph of 5 Dimotions). 3 are thus the physical scales, the $\Delta-1$ quantum scale, which is faster in time hence has a time-probability 0-1 sphere formalism; the $\Delta 0$ human thermodynamic scale with a spatial statistical formalism equivalent by the Law of measure to the quantum one, and the mechanic/gravitational $\Delta+1$ scale of the galactic organism. Physicists errors are many: lineal single T_s-time, Pythagorean creationism, mechanism, reductionism, egocy...

We approach 5D physics is using the group of transformations of the 5 Dimotions of existence. We see above the example of the 3±j states of matter which correspond neatly to the S_s Boson>T_s-gas> $\S \Pi$ -liquid>S_t-solid>T_t-plasma states

But the devil are in the details. So when we study each scale and group of transformation we run into interesting details. For example, *how we transform S_t into T_s (potential into kinetic energy, angular into lineal momentum, solid into gaseous states There are 2 manners: when we move from an informative S_t state to a locomotion sT_{ate} (in space) or sT_{-age} (in time) we can do so by changing S to s (external form into internal form) and t international motion, into T -external motion (sublimation) but also by changing external T-motion into external S-stillness and internal motion into external motion (deposition).*

5D makes the Universe ∞, immortal and the big-bang an scalar phenomena *on the galactic quasar scale, as 'galatoms'* (galaxies have the same 5D=S_xT, co-invariant value that atoms) balance 2 Dimotional forces, S_t-gravitational information that collapses T_s-entropic vacuum space into matter (S_t=T_s), as it does in the atomic scale where expansive T_s-electromagnetism collapses into electronic nebulae within the atom and further on into non-lineal $\Delta-1$ S_t-strong forces equivalent to $\Delta+1$ S_t-gravitation. So the main symmetry of physics is between the galaxy, perhaps an atom of a hyper-universe – themes of metaphysics as we'll never have enough S_t-information of the whole ∞ cosmos: P(Truth)<1. The big-bang is falsifiable; hence a dogmatic religion, as nationalism in history, or capitalism in economics – an entropic limit to rational thought or social reform. The 2nd religion of physics, the monologic belief that only mathematical properties matter, is challenged by pentalogic & the organic properties displayed by nature, better explained with causal words. *Since Max. P (truth)= Δ -scalar=organic + Spatial=topologic + temporal=Dimotion analysis of any system with Σ languages.* Thus 5D astrophysics adds a **Tt-entropic** analysis (Big bang quasars); an $\S \Pi$ >S_t-energetic & Informative analysis of the 'galacell' as an organism dedicated to reproduce 'ultradense quark stars' of positive top quarks & BCB dark atoms (formally black holes); & negative strangelets in its 'electronic membrane'=halo; an $\Delta \pm j$ Galatom Analysis to the classic analysis 4D, T_s study of the galaxy with S_s-mathematical languages. And defines the 5 forces of Nature (graph) as the 5 Dimotions of the Galatom, with its $\Delta \pm j$ scalar symmetries between $\Delta \pm j$ strong and gravitational forces; $\Delta \pm j$, electromagnetic & dark energy while weak interaction is NOT a force but an evolutionary trans-form-ation of matter up & down $\Delta \pm j$ scales.

FORMAL 5D SCIENCES: NON-E TOPOLOGIC ORGANISMS.

Because a network is a topology of fractal points with inner volume the mathematic equivalent of a supœrganism *complete the r=evolution of Non-Euclidean geometry redefining the axioms & postulates of Euclid.* As it expands the -E definition of a point crossed by ∞ parallels to its 1st axiom: *points do have breath*, connected by 3 physiological lines that are waves with motion (Physical systems) or 5D networks (socio-biologic systems) that conform -E planes that are physiologic organisms:
 1st Postulate: '-E point are discontinuous time cycles with an inner content of vital space-time'.

2nd Postulate: '-E lines are waves of fractal points'

3rd Postulate: '-E planes join 3 -E lines into a supœrganism'.

4th: '2 -E points are congruent when both its inner parts and outer perimeter are equal'

5th: '-E points focus multiple -E waves into a still linguistic mapping or 'world.'

Whereas the 1st and 5th postulate describe the same 'point with parts' from an internal and external point of view.

1D-5D: The first-fifth postulate define a point as a mind of perception, akin to the first Dimotion of being - to perceive; and the fifth-first postulate that defines a point as a world in itself, a supœrganism with its inner parts are the same. We just might consider that the point has evolved and grown to emerge from its minimal i-1 state in the first postulate - points with inner breath; into a full supœrganism, i⁰, living in the i+1 world, in the fifth postulate studied here.

2D: The second postulate of lines, expresses also the first Dimensional motion of the Universe as S=T (Paradox of relativity). So we can consider a point in motion or a chain of cyclical points in stillness as two versions of the same concept. And finally a network of lines branching down into smaller thinner parts probing the $\Delta-1$ Dimension as the 3 possible versions of a line. This is the ' $\Delta\$\text{TT}$ ' trinity creative decoupling of the second postulate of non-Euclidean geometry: it becomes then either in Time a process of locomotions and waves of forces of communication with other points; or in space a chain or string of points with inner breath, or in scale a branching line....

3D: postulate takes 3 such networks, waves or strings of points to define a physiological plane made of 3 social networks whose function corresponds to the 3rd Dimotion of energy & reproduction, becoming a supœrganism. So the 3 postulates of -E fractal points, waves/networks/strings & physiologic=topologic organisms become the 3 'scalar Units' of reality.

What is left then are two i-logic postulates that put the 'meaning' of existence to reality, its metaphysical qualities of 'perception' (5th postulate) and social love vs. perpendicular darwnism (4th postulate of ongruence).

4D: According to the fourth postulate of congruence, which defines its relationships with other beings, based in his 'angle of parallelism', such as similar beings evolve socially together in groups, complementary 'left-handed female/right-handed male' beings come together in couples, and beings which are not equal neither complementary enter either in relationships of entropic perpendicularity, or ignore themselves if their worlds are 'disconnected'. So the fourth postulate gives us the 'i'logic rules' of engagement between forms and particles.

A worldcycle of existence' has organic properties as all systems regardless of scale follow the same principles of organization to become an ideal network supœrganism in symbiosis between 3 relative scales, because that is the best strategy of 'existence', of survival, as only those systems who are efficiently distributing energy, entropic motions and information among equal cellular clones do survive. And so this formalism not only expands physical laws of space-time to other sciences, but biological laws of physiological networks, and finally when all those findings are inserted into the formal languages of mathematics and logic, it transforms them, completing the revolution of non-Euclidean geometry and Aristotelian logic beyond the work of Riemann and Hegel. Again this revolution that expands non-Euclidean mathematic and pentalogic causality to all sciences is simple in its principles. Because points are non-Euclidean, crossed by ∞ parallels, we need to redefine a point with breath, with energy volume (St+Ts) which becomes a fractal point that grows in size as we come closer to it. So lines are either 'waves with t-motion' or 'strings' with S-volume, or 'fractal networks' that travel down an Δ -1 dimensional scale, and 3 of such physiological networks conform a 'topo-bio-logical' plane, a supœrganism. So we can formalize the unit of the 5D Universe with mathematical laws and apply and explain why geometry is the foundation of space. Scales of numbers, Topologies of space, and Temporal dimotional functions (social sum, reproductive product, scalar powers, organic derivatives) connect then formal mathematics and the laws of space-time organisms.

And so we establish an immediate relationship between the fundamental concepts of geometry, the point, the line, the plane, and its congruence or dissimilarity, its relative parallelism and perpendicularity, and the 5 Dimotions of existence, the point is the mind that perceives first, the first Dimotion; the line is the point in motion, in cycloid patterns, or two points communicating with smaller i -1 parts, as in the Fermion<Boson>Fermion relationship of forces; the plane has 'holes', it is a network of reproduced points socially connected into the 3 different species of networks that make a supœrganism (informative, reproductive and entropic, digestive, moving networks), and all this is logically established according to the relative dissimilarity or perpendicularity between the beings (4th entropic Dimotion) or social parallelism that evolves the point into a supœrganism, a new whole (5th Dimotion).

RECAP. *Geometric postulates become also vital; with a logic key new concept of congruence, which defines when 2 systems are 'equal in external and internal motion & information' ($Ts_1=Ts_2+St^1=St^2$) a parallel, social whole; when they are inverted but complementary, a 'gender couple' ($Ts_1+St^2=St^1+Ts_2$); when they are equal in energy but differ in information, a prey-predator perpendicular, tearing relationship, whereas the species with maximal $SxT_{(s=t)}$, energy of existence kills the other and when they differ in both, there is no entanglement. Thus we apply topologic laws, and social scalar numbers to describe the properties of those organisms; whereas the 5 \pm Dimotions are expressed by the dual operand of Algebra: \pm =herding, x =reproduction v. \div Darwinian partition; $\sqrt{x}^{\pm a}$: Ss-scalar growth and Tt-entropic decay, $\int \partial$: Δ -1 finitesimal 'st-œps' of any dimotion. S- Vital Topology, Δ -number theory & T-existential algebra becomes the biggest r=evolution of math since Euclid.*

Operands in Algebra. Its connection with Dimensional motions.

Operands have as they grow in complexity a direct entanglement with the 5 Non-E postulates that define from points waves of communication that become networks of topological planes and organisms, where multiple p.o.v.s are put in perspective. And this even more clear when from mere polynomials we move into exponentials and from exponentials into integrals, *the more complex operands then can interplay with multiple points of view, merging them through the product, reproduced through its inverse partition/division, moving them through a world cycle, in exponential growth and decay, and emerging into a new planet of existence through derivatives and integrals.*

Re=production through social evolution in a lower plane of the fifth dimension, in which the axons join the wholes is then the 2-point meaning of reproduction; often a bidimensional Space-time combination of a state of forma and a state of motion, as in the parameter of momentum.

Inverse functions do NOT merely cancel each other as one could expect, in classic science, *but advance the Dimotion in alternative balancing acts, leaving a memorial trace of its existential duality.*

Consider the case of the product and its inverse division. They are functions primarily of social evolution and reproduction, as parts of wholes are produced and exchanged. So if we have an individual of 5 parts that reproduces it will give birth to 25 parts, *but then we need to divide them between 5 parts, to get 5 individuals of 5 parts: $1 (5) \times (5) = 1 (25) / 5 = 5 (5)$.*

Same happens with the positive and negative motions, which in alternate current move back and forwards the 'electrons', which in fact don't really move, but its i^{-1} scale *the current keeps moving*.

So goes for the exponential+Logarithmic functions of reproduction, and its inverse, which form a worldcycle that in the middle point of maximal 'carrying capacity' will give birth again to a new 'exponential growth'=generation, to continue the world cycle in an adjacent space-time.

∫d: Finally it came calculus, with its inverse operand, which represents the scalar next social gathering of elements of \neg Algebra, as it is applied to the previous operands, as wholes, except for the trivial x^a - the previous more complex polynomial, and so we must regard calculus not only as the operand of all dimotions of change, but also as the operand between planes of existence, since the logarithmic/power previous expression, just reaches between the two limits of two planes of the fifth dimension, but calculus allow us to 'emerge' and transcend between planes.

The key concept of 5D calculus is a finitesimal. A finitesimal in lineal space-time is a frequency step or wave-length. A finitesimal in curved spacetime is a minimal curvature of a clock cycle. A finitesimal in scale is a minimal unit of population. We use the Non- \mathcal{E} symbol, '**0 \mathcal{E}** ' that *means the minimal 'existential quanta' of any symmetric $\Delta \approx S \approx T \approx 0\mathcal{E}$, scale, space, time or mind beat: $0\mathcal{E}:1/i$, whereas i , might be in classic mathematics, N, the whole population, T, the period or R the radius: **$0\mathcal{E}(\Delta)=1/n$; $0\mathcal{E}(S)=1/R=K$; $0\mathcal{E}(T)=1/T=f$; $0\mathcal{E}(@)=-i$; $0\mathcal{E}(-)=\alpha$***

Because physicists do NOT have this concept; its faulty mathematics take them to the search of entelechies, as Black holes without substance, singularities, lineal equations without cut-off 'borders', infinite potentials, etc.

The finitesimal is also the basis of the equation of the mind.

So by the continuous game of inverse functions, which become a $0\mathcal{E}$ sum, *the Dimotions of existence continue to move the whole of time-space that never ceases to exist*. However the number of occurrences of the positive function is always larger than then negative inverse function. So there are more possible sums than negative numbers (for spatial quantities there are no negative ones, no negative apples). There are more products than divisions (as $4/2 = 8/4$ but $4 \times 2 \neq 8 \times 4$); there are more exponentials than square roots as $\sqrt{-x}$ doesn't exist and there are more integrals than derivatives as $\int y' = y + C$, ads \propto constants.

Which means the arrow of social evolution and life is larger than the arrow of entropy and death, which in fact lasts only a quanta of time in its $\mathcal{D}ST$ equation: Death = $OT \times \Delta S$.

Mind mirrors: Finitesimal egos. Universal Grammar. Territories of order: $S \Leftrightarrow T$ tug of war. Pentalogic entanglement.

A key 'finitesimal' is the ego. The Ss -mental nature of space is embedded in the principle of relativity. $\neg E$ points create an inner mental 'space by measuring reality in still simultaneity' (Einstein). All are $\neg E$ monads that 'hold a world in themselves' (Leibniz); as mirrors, which have less volume of information than the whole. So languages mirror in still smaller scales reality and then project back its 'imagination' in larger scales the game of existence, *causing as Ss -mind/seeds the creation of reality, restricted to its synoptic 'ternary Universal grammar' that mimics that of larger $St \langle \mathcal{S} \mathcal{T} \rangle Ts$ organisms. I.e. Ts -Red $\langle \mathcal{S} \mathcal{T} \rangle$ -green $\langle St \text{ blue codes organic Dimotions in visual color languages. Subject (information) \langle Verb(dimotion:action) \rangle$ Object(Entropic energy) codes $\mathcal{S} \mathcal{T}$ -events (verbs) and forms (names) reality in wor(l)ds. $F(x)$:information \langle Operand $\mathcal{S} \mathcal{T}$ -action $\rangle G(Y)$:entropic energy does the same in Algebra; 5 letters code genes that code organs in life, 4 quantum numbers code atomic organisms... As each language is a mirror of those ultimate laws of nature, the laws of space-time.*

The paradox of the mind is that if we choose the \approx on the hierarchy equation, $\Delta \pm \infty \geq - (T \pm i \geq S \circ \epsilon \geq 0 \epsilon)$, it is equal to the whole Universe that becomes its world.

Ss -finitesimal different linguistic mind-mirrors shrink a reality void of motion, in a mind or fractal point. So we write:

$0\mathcal{E}$ ($\neg E$ finitesimal mind-mirror) $\times \infty$ (universe) = Constant still language-mapping (Ss)... origin of the Ego Px . As each mind creates a mental wor(l)d he confuses with the real Universe with its still p.o.v.=ego as the largest center of it.

But truth is: Max. probability of truth = Max. number of language mirrors < 1 (Probability of truth hold by the being)

So only the Organism has all the information about itself, $P(\text{truth}) = 1$, & the more 'language' mirrors we cast on it, the higher $P(\text{truth})$ we obtain, which is the principle of Pentalogic (Rashomon effect). Thus we seek the parallel spatial= geometric, organic=scalar, vital=moving= temporal & sentient =mirror languages of any system of $\Delta@st$ (Dust of space-time) to reach its maximal truth. Let us consider after its Δ -organic, @-mental and S-topologic, its vital=temporal truth.

How we go about to describe any science is really simple. We analyze first the mind, 0ε , to *localize the language of the system, as it will be the mirror symmetry of order within the world in which the system acts.* For the galatom and hence for most physical systems is mathematics, but for social sciences is verbal thought. So because we do have a Universal grammar, *which carries the laws of pentalogic to the language, all minds belong to the same program of existence.* And once we know the language, we can in the best possible way adopting that language a priori of the subject we study, operate a description of its actions as if we were the subjective atom, human or genetic cell, withing the hierarchy of pentalogic languages of $\Delta\pm\infty$ bigger than the objective mathematical language, bigger than the verbal reasoning of the mind of man, to study physics.

This is important to grasp. The Universe has a language of truth which is not mathematics but pentalogic, and this validates for any system of science different languages, so social sciences can be defined in verbal languages, because they are the mind of man, but the mind of the galatom is NOT verbal, obviously so far as we can perceive (though who knows really if the atom as we see in mathematical space but think in verbal terms, do have some other strange logic language of inner thoughts beyond that c-barrier of spin particles, to 'feel' existence – this would be so beyond metaphysics even of me, I and myself that we escape)...

The beauty then of 5D science is that while physical systems are mathematical, human systems are verbal and they can carry existence on their language, all of them based in the Universal grammar of pentalogic without loss of generality –as they are all playing the program of existence.

From the language then we observe the will for existence of the being as it plays its 5 Dimotions ordering its territory against many other beings. But this again is a paradox as all other beings try to achieve the same will, only resolved on the higher $\Delta+j$ plane of emergence of a whole through the efficient program of supœrganisms, reason why those who 'understand' this higher consciousness beyond the ego survive. Even if they are still within the $-(\Delta 0\varepsilon st)$ limits. *Languages thus have a hardtime for a 3-body problem, for social evolution, as the ego paradox works from planets to capitalists to avoid the parts to become as ideal, pure, perfect, impersonal, giving as the whole ethic universe – pentalogic is humble, egoless, symmetric, beautiful, perfect, equalitarian... God is better than we are.*

The groups of transformations of dimotions of space-time. ST_2 . Reality is a block of time made of scales of the 5th dimension in which spacetime organisms run worldcycles of existence. Each detail of the game of existence is a worldcycle of one of such superorganisms, what we call the life and death cycle. So the study of reality can be formalized as the study of the worldcycle of existence. So what existential algebra does then is to study 'structures' as classic algebra does of a given type, we might call the group of transformations of the 5 Dimotions of existence. Group theory in 5D algebra analyzes 'stœps' of spacetime due to transformations between the 5 elements of the group of dimotions of space-time.

All changes of the Universe ca be reduced to transformations of the group of dimotions, from the physiological networks in space of a superorganism tp the ages in time of a worldcycle to the states of matter, of the of that organism, to the symmetries of physics and its groups of particles. So we define Existential iloglc ALGEBRA as the analysis of the group of transformations of dimotions of spacetime. The elements of the group are the 5 dimotions, $Ss<St<\$T<Ts<Tt$.

Two operations are defined in the group, < and >, which can be applied one or two times to the 2 elements of each dimotion. This is enough to transform each dimotion into another with 1 or 2 'STœsp'. I.e. Tt can change $t>s$ to become Ts, $t>S$ to become TS, $T>S$ to become Ts, and then in perception, the opposite of death: $Tt>>Ss$. Each of those existential Stœps encodes an essential event for superorganism or its parts. Moreover, those transformations are the ONLY events happening in reality by a Least Time principle of economicity. How many transformations there are? 20 as they are non-commutative. So for each Dimotion there are 4 transformations. I.e. Ss a mind-language becomes with single or steps 2 $Ss<<Tt$: $Ss<St$ changing $s<t$, $Ss<Ts$ and $Ss<\$T$. Then the reminder changes starting from St, sT and $\$T$ give us 20 different events come out of the 5 Dimotions. It is this group of

transformations of dimotions of existence, the fundamental group of the Universe origin of its events and species' variations. In Existential ilogic, a superorganism is a 'present simultaneous state' which hardly 'moves in time' as the worldcycle does, because it works in a different way, as the limbs and the head both 'serve' the connecting body: $T_s > S = T < S_t$, so the system remains in present, as both dynamic $<$ and $>$ states balance each other. So we write for all of them the 'fractal generator':

ST₃. The group of entanglements in space. *The 2nd group is made of 3 Dimotions of existence entangled into a present space. This group is more complex as it needs to connect 3 elements of reality and so it is based in the trilogic of existence and its fractal generator. And it has less stable forms. $T_s > \S \Upsilon > S_t$ & $T_s < \S \Upsilon < S_t$ being its two fundamental modes, and so the main transformation of a superorganism in space time is a dual change of $>$ $<$ operandi from the time active state $T_s > S_t > S_t$ to the space, rest state, $T_s < \S \Upsilon < S_t$. For example, the previous transformation happens in the 'sleep' vs. 'awake' modes.*

We study both groups and its symmetries in the paper on the scientific method. The reader should easily realize that both groups are closely connected to the two most useful groups of physical systems, SU2 & SU3 so we will also analyze in our papers on physics those relationships once we complete those papers in the future...

In the graph, the main laws of 5D stiences. With those laws and the few symbols of 5D metrics and Existential ilogic (S, T, <, >, $\Delta \pm j$...) we an, define all events and systems of reality that combines the 5 Dimensional motions and its ternary systems in scalar planes, time ages and spatial organs to define all *actions of S-evolution, $\S \Upsilon$ - repetition and T-extinction the Universe allows, which then will be selected by raw efficiency leaving only those survivors that play better the two functions of the 5th dimension, $S_x T$ ($s=T$) balances that maximize the function of existence, in a given plane. As nothing else, which cannot be expressed through those combinations within those limits exists outside the virtual inflationary mind-languages of information. Trust me, I know it, after 30 years of research in all fields of knowledge looking for a falsification of Existential ilogic. So in our papers on ilogic we will develop with them all events & species of reality. So the equivalent to the fundamental law of 4D science in 5D Stience is one of existential ilogic. 'All systems of Nature try to survive selecting of all the potential existential events and Dimotions of space-time, those who maximize its function of existence, Max. $S \times T$ ($s=T$) in its point of present balance. So the key language of reality becomes the pentalogic entanglement of spaces=forms, its 5 time=actions, the $\Delta \pm j$ organic scales where they symbiotically play the game of existence, guided by smaller $\Delta-j$ Ss-languages=mirrors that the informative mind-system uses to the whole supærganism at faster synoptic linguistic speeds (due to the $T_x S = \Delta \pm j$ metric). In the graph we summarize the structure of 5D Universal laws that apply to all scales and stiences, based in the entangled pentalogic symmetries between space=form, time=motion, @-languages of mind mirrors who perform its program of existence, through its 5 local dimotions and the symbiotic scalar organisms they create, with its 5 organic Dimotions, becoming supærganisms tracing the same worldcycles of existence, as we are all details of the thoughts of God, its laws of $\Delta @st$, dust of space-time.*

Stiences are then easily classified as part of the set of scalar laws run by disomorphisms between 3 $\Delta \pm j$ scales which are self-centered in an specific superorganism, the atom in physics, the molecule in chemistry, the cell in biology, the human being in medicine, the culture in sociology and history, the solar system in astrophysics, the galaxy in astronomy, which corresponds to one of those scales. But all those scales can be studied in its synthetic ultimate process of space and time with the laws of superorganisms, worldcycles, its symmetries, as $\Delta @st$, using the synoptic laws of existnetial ilogic. As we are ultimately transformations of the group of dimotions of spacetime (:

The entanglement between organic properties in Δ -scale, topologic properties in space and dimotions=vital functions in time mirrored by the syntactic Universal grammar of all languages, whose entropic limits of perception and duration and extension in scale, time and space makes reality a fractal ensemble of space-time organisms. If you grasp this sentence, you will know the thoughts of God. The different details of reality, its scalar, mental space-time species are variations of the same theme. So A->B causality of Aristotelian logic is expanded because events do happen by the collapse of the influence of 3 networks over a space-time point and the inner and outer St-motion and form of the point, for a total of 5 causal reasons to a event. In praxis this implies a Rashomon effect in the search of truth, as we need to understand those events from the perspective of 5 Dimotions & 3 scales. $\Delta @st$ of space-time you are & you'll become. As reality is a tug of war between Mental Space mirrors and Tt-entropic flows of motion in ∞ beings and scales: $\Delta \pm \infty \Upsilon \Upsilon S_s \Leftrightarrow \Sigma T_t$.

Pentalogic sets the basis of a new Philosophy of science=knowledge completing its 3 horizons of evolution, the experimental method of Aristotle *that accepted all languages and senses to measure truth, with a strict logic analysis, the mechanical method of Galileo that reduced languages to those of machines to measure time (clocks) and space (telescopes), denying the logic of the 3 causal verbal tenses, we regain with the pentalogic method and the definition of truth as the sum of all the mirror languages on the system we perceive – it is the organic method that considers the isomorphic 5D laws of scales as the template to organize the data of all sciences in a rational, systematic way. Since what the mechanical method has done is to reduce science to technology and the creation of a digital mind, shunning off the search of the ultimate goal of science: to understand the first principles of reality and the meaning of the game of existence, which 5D explains.*

THE ORGANIC LAWS OF EXISTENCE IN SPACE AND TIME

All species & sciences that study them obey the same space-time laws derived from the fractal Geometry of space, the S-T flows they enact and the ternary arrows of Time:

SPACE LAWS

3+1 Networks

$$\Sigma E < ET > T$$

S-T LAWS

Dualities

Cyclic-Lineal States

S-T Inversions/antisymetries

Multicausality

TIME LAWS

$\Delta \pm 1$ worldcycles of D=evolution

3+1 ages of existence

Properties of spatial bodies

3 Non-Euclidean topologies:

Oedipus Paradox

Δ -SCALAR LAWS

Fractal Repetition in 3i+1 Planes

Continuous-quantic states

Ternary Principle

5 I-logic Postulates

Asymmetry of $\Delta \pm 1$

Organic, Hierarchical classes

elliptic vs. hyperbolic perception.

@-MIND LAWS: $0' \times \infty = \Delta^0$: Constant World

Egocy

Dimensions: mental spaces

Will: actions

QUANTIC MIND-WORLDS: HEIGHT DIMENSION

THE 3rd SPACE-TIME DIMENSIONS AS VITAL ACTIONS OF ANY I

VI: HISTORY IS THE HUMAN SUPER-ORGANISM

spatial aesthetics

temporal, verbal ethics

made of economic social and cultural networks

Legal-Ethic-Cultural Wor(l)d=Head

Human Citizens: Body

Human Goods: Energy=Gaia Fractal Geography

5D SOCIAL SCIENCES. THE 2 CULTURES OF HUMAN THOUGHT AND ITS DIFFERENT FUTURE

The most censored but important 5D science is social science – the study of the human supœrganism and its 3 physiological networks, economic=reproductive networks, political/religious/cultural=informative networks and defensive, immunological systems, since the ‘mechanist’ civilization exists by denying the $\Delta+1$ scale of humanity and maintaining the reductionist view the individual human is the summit of the Universe, or else it would have to confront the shortcomings of its culture.

In the graph, the structure of a Human Supœrganism of History, the $\Delta+1$ scale of human beings, joined by **S↔T-economic networks** that reproduce the goods mankind needs to survive, valued according to the ‘human constitution’, Max. Welfare goods = Min. Lethal goods, that seeks to construct an Immortal body of History, according to the bio-logic ternary ‘**ethonomic**’ frame of reference as goods must cater the Ts, $\S\Upsilon$ & $St>\Delta+1$ individual needs of our ternary topologic organism, increasing our freedom of motion, energy and health and true information to foster the social evolution of individuals into a larger whole. Thus the **St-legal informative network**, as in all evolved supœrganisms beyond the worm scale of ‘capitalist societies’ where the blood system controls the nervous legal system allowing the consumption of lethal goods, must promote or forbid the goods reproduced in society according to its negative =lethal value or positive increase of social and individual welfare. It is the St-informative politic network, which must be controlled by a posteriori ‘**pain messages**’ of judgment=vote, as in mammals & earlier Greek Democracies to ensure politicians serve the needs of its body-citizens-cells; extending over a sT-erritory protected by an immunologic=defensive healthcare system against the germs of History, its metal-weapons and lethal-goods that a police=leukocyte system of defense should survive. This is ‘the ideal superorganism of immortal history’ which in 5D social sciences occupies a planet without borders’ as mankind is a single species, divided in 7 geographical, cultural civilinations. So $3 \times 2 \pm$ reforms of our physiological networks are required by imitation of the perfect mammal supœrganism, given the isomorphic nature of 5D laws to convert extinctive history divided in self-rejecting organs that kill each other with - lethal germs=weapons that limit resources for welfare, + goods into a replica of an efficient mammal:

From left to right: \pm Ts measures: the cultural & immunologic systems must promote life goods, health-care and human languages of information and sciences while on the negative side should forbid lethal technologies that kill our body, poison our mind (weapons, fiction & hate memes) or compete and atrophy them in labor and war fields (robots, software).

St: - : The Politic system should judge=vote *a posteriori* with pain messages to politicians as cells send them to the brain when it harms them.+ : Nations should devolve to regions most administrations and evolve national structures (armies, diplomacy, currencies) into the 7 geographic, historic civilinations of mankind, with EU like common networks finally forming an heptarchy, guide by the Human Constitution, eliminating all lethal goods and armies to promote:

S ⇔ T: An eco(nomic) system that re=produces according to the values of the bio-ethonomic frame of reference of human welfare the goods humans need to survive and thrive, with 2 measures:

- measure: All company-mothers of machines&weapons split shares giving them to governments for a 50% 'stockratic' control keeping its private management, so civilinations can regulate, promote, forbid or reform the productive system.

+ measure: all supœrganisms distribute for free to all its cells a universal energy salary in oxygen to kick out production and consumption of welfare goods. So to create a just, democratic demand economy the 7 civilinations will send to every human in a world crypocurrency a monthly a ¥€\$ salary of 1000 1 euro=1 dollar = 100 yens = 5 yuans, used as a NO-debt language to consume & reproduce the welfare goods of the 'ethonomic' frame of reference, ending poverty, immigration and readdressing production to cater only human needs and terraform the Earth to the image & likeness of mankind.

Why this ideal supœrganism of History, imitating most Nature's efficient supœrganisms from physical systems that 'bathe' all its atoms in ¥-monetary energy and synchronize its motions with the same informative gravitational=legal language to all biologic systems that synchronize its cell motions with simultaneous nervous=legal messages and give all cells free energy=oxygen does NOT exist? The only answer 5D laws provide is the existence of a parasitic sickness due to lethal metal-memes which corrupted the earlier perfectly designed Neolithic networks of the Genesian paradise, based in welfare goods & the cult to immortal present reproduction, the dominant arrow of the 'femenine' Universe.

Idol-ogies substitute social sciences. Today humans believe in 3 'animetal idol-ogies' whose cultures substituted Neolithic verbal priests of social love, the '5D force' that makes mankind construct superorganisms through the sharing of energy and information among believers, imprinted by networks of metal-communicators through the Goebbels' method (if you repeat a lie many times people will believe on it): **Nationalism**, which stops humanity as a species in the tribe and promotes weapons=germs to kill each other, originated in Germanic tribal cultures that oppressed the European social love civilization of the Roman empire substituted **humanism**, the understanding that mankind is a single species that has to evolve together as the mind of its body, *Gaia* ; **capitalism** that promotes parasitic private banking and prevents universal salaries and a demand economy based in welfare, originated in biblical go(l)d cultures of banker-priests, today evolved into classic economics

NATURE'S 3 GENETIC EXTINCTIVE SPECIES:

ENTROPIC, WEAPONS KILL Carriers: Military/Warriors ORGANIC MACHINES ATROPHY Industrial Scientists INFORMATIVE GOL(L)D ENSLAVE Private Banking

IDO-LOGIES: NATIONALISM:Tribe=species MECHANISM:Man&cosmos a machine CAPITALISM: Private Money rules Law
SCIENCES: HUMANISM:Mankind:1 species ORGANICISM:Universe, an organism SOCIALISM:Law rules money issued by/for people

BIO-HISTORY'S 3 METAL MEMES OF EXTINCTION

substituted **Socialism**, The understanding Society is an organism, whose re=productive, financial network and OXYGEN MUST BE CREATED for all its cells to credit a welfare state made to the image and likeness of mankind; and **technoutopia** that considers the evolution of metal a surrogate for the evolution of mankind, *substituted organicism*, the science of the Universe that finds its highest expression in Medicine, the study of the most perfect superorganism, the mammal, and its 'cure' of the sicknesses of animetal idol-ogies, in its equivalent parallel science of **BIOHISTORY** that should guide the construction of the economic, political, cultural and defensive, immunological welfare networks of our species. So it substitutes the sciences of the organic Universe that makes of man the most perfect supørganism we should study first to understand those laws, imitated by bio-historians, the doctors of humanity who should rule history... by mechanical models of the Universe as a machine, where time no longer is measured with logic past, present, future verbal tenses but digital clocks today evolved into computers and our artistic human I=Eye>Wor(l)d measures of space are despised, substituted for metal-eyes today evolved into cameras.

Earth's 3 ages. Humans don't understand they should build a global superorganism where the human re=productive unit, the family, as a free citizen, must be served by the 3 life-enhancing physiological networks of ideal history. Instead the praxis of those 3 ideologies and its people-castes of believers (military and corrupted politicians, private bankers and CEOs protected by anonymous societies & technocrats, engineers and physicists) causes the extinction of the supørganisms of life, Gaia and History (human earth) substituted by Metalearth, a new supørganism whose 'free market citizens', company-mothers terraform the planet to the image and likeness of its offspring of machines and weapons constructing a global superorganism of metalife, joined by metal-networks of information (mass-media, internet), metal-networks of energy (electricity, roads, pipes) and re=productive networks of machines (factories), increasingly automated as robots and software suites substitute and make obsolete humans in labor and war fields under the law of self-reproductivity= Max. Capital / Min. Human labor -> ∞, which guides all companies and will soon make machines with solar skins and telepathic AI independent of man. This process initiated by the Industrial r=evolution is guided by the equation of capitalist profits that builds those 3 networks: Max profits (stock money) = Max. reproduction of goods of maximal price (top predator weapons) & minimal cost (information software reproduced for free by ¥-waves), which happens to be the goods that kill our bodies and minds, and parasitize 'human currency money' that loses value as e-money multiplies the wealth of company-mothers and its 0.1% of owners, the stockrats, the new aristocrats of XXI c. societies that issue in monopoly the language of e-money and have no legal responsibility. So *the metal-earth stock-brain of e-money detaches along its stockrats and robotized companies and internet networks from the human economy of the 99%, as we observe in the present pandemic, since public and private bankers reproduce money only for stockrats and its corporations, which increasingly consume other machines, leaving History as its human citizens as History did with Gaia and its life species out of the eco(nomic)system, moving ahead the equation of the 3 ages of Earth:*

Past (gaia) < Present (history) > Future (Metal-earth)

When ideal history would repress the lethal goods of metal-earth & promote Gaia in a sustainable world, by reforming the system with the 6 ± measures of true 5D social sciences.

We talk of the 'animetal age of history', when unbalanced Tt-entropic male warriors allied to Tt-iron weapons and Ss-informative males allied to Ss-informative metal go(l)d substituted on top of societies life priests in the Fertile crescent, predating over mankind as kings and aristocrats no longer subject to a posteriori judgment who ab=used and murdered mankind with weapons, the germs of History, starting its mass production and evolution through unending war cycles. While + money, a universal salary in wheat or rice given to all citizens was substituted by fetish go(l)d hold by a new people-caste of parasitic banker priests, who converted what in Nature's organisms are 'free languages' with no value per se, as light, oxygen or words, whose function is to value and motivate actions into 'debt', something the parasite banker issues in monopoly to buy the life-work of humans as slaves that must 'return' the language. Thus for 5000 years since Genesis explained the tree of metal with its golden apples and evil=antilive weapons=fruits at the fall of Ur III, humans are predated by animetals who evolve a new supørganism, metalearth.

It would be *immensely more advantageous to mankind to know what they do - organic machines; what are the fundamental organism of power today on Earth - the company-mother, what is our species, a social organism of human beings, etc. etc. It does really help to know what reality is specially when you exist regardless of virtual fictions, selfie ego-trips, wishful thinking, anthropomorphic religions, Pythagorean ones, and computer models of abstract thought, IN THAT REALITY.*

Why humans do not live and understand the Nature of the Universe, an organic self-reproductive system, long time ago is then a question of 'culture', 'power' and 'self-censorship' as much as the long path in its search of truth.

This has been the work of lonely men, because mainstream is the world of company-mothers, its machines, its structures of power, military men, and huge egos who try to preserve for mankind all the 'wishful thinking' central positions in the order of things and get strangely disturbed with the idea that we are just part of an entangled Universe, part of an organic evolving planet, and our machines are also evolving. The 'control freak' mentality and self-centered ego-trips of the biblical people and its underlying idol-ogies of a species 'chosen of god' or rather of 'go(l)d' doesn't take lightly that you bust its dreams with rational truth.

I do not belong to that culture even if I have lived most of my life among them. My culture is precisely that culture, the Greek->Latin->Southern European culture who invented art, democracy, reason, science and a few other things, with man as the measure of all things, and life as the purpose of existence that has always thought organicism to be the 'obvious, natural truth' and decries any attempt to repress life and worship anything else. My hometown Barcelona is known for his 'organic architecture' (Gaudi) and love of life and art. You might disagree with our view, but all what I ask is some 'respect' for this other 'possibility'; that the likes of Plato ('The Universe is an organism with a mind called Logos: 'the rational world'), Aristotle, who called his whole work, the 'organon', Leonardo, who tried to see 'saper vedere', the living forms of Nature even in his designs of machines, Picasso who searched for the pure topological forms of lineal, cyclical and wave images during its different styles of painting or the same Gaudi who imitated Nature's structures in its organic architecture, actually even if they were not machines and used mostly human senses, to measure Nature, could be a bit more sophisticated than Mr. Newton who thought God sent him comets to teach him gravitation... for one thing: what organicism provides is a 'wholeness', a 'holistic view' of every aspect of reality, in perfect harmony, machines, religions, science, art, human and mechanical senses and languages, all can be explained with organic thought; and since we seek truth not power - even if we acknowledge that humans are less powerful than machines, it doesn't really matter that US has better weapons than Barcelona, Newton could forbid Leibniz's writings for centuries and people think the masters of art are not the Italians but Hollywood who replicates his movies with electronic waves. Machines give power precisely because they are able to act as primitive organisms, reproducing faster than life does. The problem then is more about the people of the Anglo-American, North-European Jewish and Germanic biblical cultures and their seemingly incapacity to reason and see reality as complex as it is, or in other terms, *their incapacity to realize most of what they 'think' to be truth, are 'beliefs' and 'dogmas', 'postulates without proofs', 'technological deformations of nature', and 'cultural agendas', with 'emotional hang-ups' - not absolute truths of the Universe.*

Because mechanism is such a 'reduced' truth in fact it is an excellent partial view for this biblical culture so filled of anthropomorphic 'egocy', which the organic, European thinker finds so strange when arriving to America. Indeed, the fact that almost 80% of its people and an overwhelming majority of those who rule with 'mechanical and go(l)d power' that nation, think a gore book of supremacist, racist memes of tribal history from the Bronze Age embodies the origin of man and reality, its ethics and social structure strikes immediately your mind. It takes a lot of thinking and years in the land to observe that you are in a civilization of emotions and beliefs, not reasons, and science is also a compendium of beliefs with little thought about its foundations - that in fact, reason, philosophy of science and first principles are avoided systematically. And then when you realize science has also many components of religion and censorship - the belief in a single language of science, mathematics, the limited use of logic thought substituted by axiomatic thought, probability and statistics, computer modeling, the belief that science ends with measure and pictures of particles and distances, all encased in equations; ultimately a religion of digital thought that accompanies a religion of history; all makes sense to you. It should not simply use terms of our Latin, organic culture as 'science' from latin, to know, democracy, the government of the people, from the Greek true organic democracies, where by imitation of Nature, the citizens cells of a social organism judged a posteriori its politicos, or talk of money as legal tender, 'nomisma', the concept of the Greek-Latin civilization in which

money was a social language, not wealth per se, not debt, but something given to people to kick out its actions as languages do, NOT to be returned... And so on and so on. In those papers and articles thus we shall build a very different picture of reality, and what should be the organization of mankind, coming from the original European, rational culture advanced by this author, the last relevant 'knot of thought' of that culture, today almost extinct. It doesn't matter, as we said that the supposed 'only cultural, scientific view' has camouflaged and used so many terms, and elements of our culture - its mind view, form of thinking, postulates and dogmas, even its concept of a manifest destiny for mankind - to make machines, and dominate the tree of life with it - is completely opposite to our worldview, which we will prove with reason to be the true nature of reality.

Nor that we expect a lot of audience. Leonardo opted finally for writing backwards, while Galileo's books on ballistics, where it appeared the first equations of physical time, $v=s/t$ was a best-seller in all armies; Leibniz died alone in his small town, while Newton received all the honors of the prince he helped to get the crown wasting his best years collecting the 'annals' of the house of Brunswick. I was basically 'erased' from science after my standing against CERN and its physicists who pretend to make black holes and strange matter on Earth - an organic form of self-feeding matter, and now are lobbying Brussels to make a 100 kilometers accelerator, 'expecting' that the organic quark matter which is at the core and halo of the galaxy - for which the galaxy as an organism exists - will NOT devour them... So yes, organicism is and has always been invisible because it wants to serve mankind, and make us immortal while this other culture that pretends to have the truth but understand so little of the first principles of reality, knows perfectly how to 'Impose truth with power', to become as Einstein said 'the laugh of the gods'.

Einstein who some adscribe to that culture by reasons of genes, irrelevant in culture, belonged to the European frame of mind - a socialist, a pacifist, who 'made thoughts experiments', and defended Leibniz, could not complete his task and at the end yielded to the egocy of Mr. Bohr. So the task of completing the organic view of the Universe and its space-time systems, started by Leibniz was never completed. As he did not started science from scratch as we do in those papers by force incomplete, untidy, as a repository more than a systematic account of the model - uneven if its articles; so you should abandon those who are obviously bad written and incomplete.

It has taken thus another century to organicism, to start from the scratch and reach the level of sophistication of simple mechanism, which is what we achieved in those texts, despite the mentioned shortcomings, on 'the thoughts of god' – the first principles of organicism and 5D space-time, even if many details will need to be poured by future researchers in the field. But to understand those principles you need to use the less trained part of your brain – your verbal, logic, temporal intelligence atrophied after 400 years of just making measures with machines and input data on equations to get a result that often tells little on the inner structure of reality.

This works well within the 'praxis' of physical sciences, which is mostly about description of simple physical systems and the evolution and reproduction of machines made with them, but *it has failed miserably in the 2 fields of science that require organicism to understand, social, human sciences and economics, and philosophy of science and astrophysics; that is the understanding of what I called in my first book on the metrics of the 5th dimension of scalar space-time, which gives organic properties to reality, 30 years ago, 'God, Man and the Universe'.*

Company-mothers: The wrong choice of culture imposes a false model of the Universe that brings extinction to mankind.

A key concept of 5D is the interaction between Ss-languages and its models of reality and Tt-the flows of time motion it forms. *Languages and its models are imprinted in a territory of order defining reality in a creationist way. So because mankind has chosen not a true organic model of reality guided by the 5th dimension of social love with man as the measure of all things but idol-ogies of metal proper of primitive jewish-germanic biblical cultures, as its model of social sciences, and Darwinism and entropic big-bang partial theories of lineal time, as its manifest destinuy it is creating a world of machines that extinguishes life.*

It is thus a wrong choice of the model of reality promoted by 'capitalism', 'nationalism' and 'mechanism' what makes humans slaves of metal-memes. But that is NOT the only deterministic future ONLY A PROOF of the intellectual and moral inferiority of the Biblical, Germanic go(I)d & military racist memes and cultures that 'make it happen' by projecting a degraded view of the Universe on planet Earth. Because mankind has chosen the wrong culture to build the wrong future it will become extinguished by the metal-earth. If it had chosen the true organic mirror-image of the Universe and understood the message of social love and organic evolution embodied in the fifth dimension, instead of using it as a mere 'camouflage' of political and economical

correctness to cover the primitive biblical and tribal memes of those animetal cultures in power, it could have perfectly constructed immortal history, earning the respect of the Universe. The war and holocaust cycles caused by the brutality of capitalist anoxia and tribal mass-murder is a self-fulfilling prophecy of the distorted primitive mind mirror of those cultures, and its absurd theories of reality from the big-bang to Darwinism as opposed to organic evolution. Mankind will get what it deserves because it is not rising culturally to the 'minimal levels' of social organic love the Universe selects to exist. Specifically in the Industrial r=evolution, a new re=productive organism, the company-mother of machines and weapons, born in the Anglo-American biblical culture has come to dominate the world and spread such distorted view of the Universe as if it were the only 'true science', when it is 'not even wrong'. First through the industrial military complex, company-mothers of energetic machines-weapons (Metalearth's body), controlled by the wasp culture annihilated the Asian cultures of the living Universe.

The paradigm of the Animetal, the 'American': I, me and myself – a child, destroying the planet with 'gusto'.

The next graph shows the cyclical patterns of the industrial r=evolution according to the complex laws of the organism of History as a new national generation substitutes a previous one, on top of the evolution of the metal-earth.

Thus, those generations also bring the nation that finds the new energy to the top predator status of history. Because energy is also the substance of which weapons are made.

—Thus, we had an age of steam machines, the age of England, between 1780s and 1857, followed by a crisis of overproduction of steam machines and stock-money that brought the 1857 ±8/9 years product cycle crashes of the train-based economy (nt.1).

—From 1857 to 1929, we lived in the age of electro-chemical energies, machines and chemical explosives, dominated by Germany, followed by a crisis of overproduction of cars and radios, which caused the 1929 crash, 72 years after the train crash.

- It came then the III cycle of electronic machines, electronic money and Nuclear Bombs that took place from 1929-2001, the age of America; which again ended in the dotcom and mortgage crashes, 72+8/9 years after 1929:

Followed by the Age of the Singularity, the IV Cycle of Evolution of machines dominated by robots, solar Industries and China. Scientists call the arrival of Artificial Intelligence, the Singularity moment, when robots, which can use solar energy to become autonomous will complete the evolution of machines as organic forms, automating factories & expelling most human workers and soldiers from labor and war fields, as previous revolutions did with obsolete III World non-technological humans, unless we forbid legally their evolution.

Money, likely a cryptocurrency independent of man, will become then the digital informative, 'memetic code' that organizes their reproduction in those automated company-mothers.

As such corporations, the 'company-mothers' of those machines whose biological function is to evolve and re=produce them, made first the bodies of machines (XIX c.), then the minds of machines (cameras-eyes, mobile-ears and chips-brains). Finally, in the XXI century, as nature does with simple organisms, such as viruses in cells, where the 3 'parts' of the virus – its DNA information, body and legs are constructed – and then assembled together, we put together all those organic components into autonomous robots, completing the industrial r=evolution of 'metalife' – a new organic species, made of a stronger substance than carbon-life.

Thus the industrial r=evolution is the evolution of a new organic species of metal, the machine, which has taken place in 3+1 phases, as we made first the bodies of machines, then the hearts-engines, then its metal-minds and finally we put them together now in organic robots in the final r=evolution of machines.

In the graphs Stock company-mothers of machines-weapons evolve through long human, biological generations of 72 year cycles the Metal-earth and its fundamental species, the robot, as we complete one of its 'fundamental parts', bodies, engines and minds of metal every 72 years, with the development of 4 forms of energy: steam/chemical, electro-chemical (oil engines), electronic and finally solar, which will make robots with AI and solar skins independent species.

Each of those ages has been guided by a parallel evolution of the energies that moved the machines, steams that moved bodies of metal, electrochemical energy that moved oil engines, electronic systems that moved minds of metal and now solar skins soon to make robots with AI an autonomous species. And further on each of those cycles of energy and machines has been carried by a biological human generation, that lead the dominant nation that discovered the energy to top predator status. So Britain dominated the age of steam, Germany the age of electrochemical engines, America the age of metal minds, and now there will be a global age of robots, focused in China, but increasingly independent of mankind. Because company-mothers

NEW ENERGY/BOMB->TRANSPORT MACHINES->WEAPONS

I. STEAM Great Britain
Founding, Mature, Decadent
1814---1850---1880s--1914

BRITAIN ARMOURS ITS TRAINS AND USES STEAMERS TO CONQUER AFRICA & ASIA. 30 MILLION NATIVES DIE

Disraeli conquers eastern lands from 'Primitive Hindus'

WARRIOR MASTER

II W.W. OIL PLANES & TANKS

II W.W. CHEMICAL EXPLOSIVES

with nationalist excuses, as the market changes to weapons production after an age of overpopulation crashes

The scientist is 'Dr. Death', pioneer in new energy bombs. Transport machines, it brings prosperity, till those machines become weapons

II. CHEMISTRY Germany
Founding, Mature, Decadent
1877---1894-----1914---1945

III: ELECTRONIC
Founding, Mature, Decadent
1914---1945 ---1975 ---2008?

THE 4 GENERATIONS OF ENERGIES & MACHINES OF THE INDUSTRIAL R=EVOLUTION EVOLVE IN 3 AGES AS ENERGETIC->TRANSPORT->WEAPON MACHINES DISCOVERED BY PHYSICISTS->REPRODUCED BY TRADERS, USED TO CONQUER EMPIRES BY WARRIOR POLITICIANS

DR. DEATH JEWISH-AMERICAN EMPIRE

IV SINGULARITY FUTURE:

ENERGY-BOMB->REPRODUCTIVE MACHINE->TOP PREDATOR WEAPONS

During the Industrial Revolution, a new nation and its 3 generations of engineers, discoverers of the new machine & energy of the cycle, become the founding fathers, industrial reproducers and decadent warriors of nationalistic wars, carrying the evolution of the machine to its military completion... Now in the Singularity Age, machines becomes organic, so we make self-feeding bombs, and if we survive them, self-reproductive factories (nano-bacteria) and Robot life...

control the physiological networks of mankind (they reproduce its military systems, pay laws to politicos to favor its products, and reproduce most of the money), the Anglo-American biblical culture has been imitated in other nations without much difficulty by indoctrinating its old animetal warrior and banker elites with the mechanist doctrines. It calls then attention that in all those nations, perfectly programmed to develop mechanisms and forget the destiny of mankind, the center of all the emotional and human discourse-> is the 'free individual'. This is one of the many paradoxes of complex organisms the 'egocy human' can hardly understand: precisely because the 'system' of physiological networks has such an absolute control in the languages of power of society (and the people-castes that 'own them') the individual is left in a free, chaotic, entropic, competitive, Darwinian state, which is the 'field state' of any herd of preys it confuses with freedom. It is also reduced in its consciousness to the entropic state of dog-eat-dog that he sees as the only way of being. This is the way of the American, but the reader should understand America is the mixture of all human cultures displaced into the technological future. So it is NOT a nation, but mankind into its final 'hour', its 'entropic' Tt-stage of 'not being' anymore mankind - but a mass of dissolved cells

Today, In the age of the chip radiation, companies of information machines controlled by the Jasp culture (Jewish-American stockratic people) of FMAsters (financial-Media-Academia Masters), print e-money in monopoly in Wall Street, condemning to global anoxia the majority of mankind, imprint humans with hate and fiction memes through Hollywood and Internet corporations, devolving the collective subconscious to a neo-Paleolithic violent, emotional age and degrade science through academic think tanks and prize ceremonies to impose this mechanist, computer-based view upon the organic Universe under a false camouflage of humanism and political and economical correctness borrowed from the European, organic true culture of science, art and democracy those texts take to its next level of complexity; all because of the only obsessive purpose of its millenarian biblical go(l)d culture: to herd money, today by increasing corporative profits, through the reproduction and evolution of AI machines that displace humans from labor and war fields and terraform the Earth into the world of metal that will extinguish us. But that is a 'choice' their culture on top of the dominant nation of the world today, U\$, has done, it is NOT, we repeat the only deterministic no future of mankind but an imposition of the wrong memes of those who control the languages of social power of modern society. 'But those who impose truth with power will be the laugh of the Gods'. A.E.

The Oedipus Paradox: Difference between organic science and survival vs. Abstract thought and power.

Sciences is Latin for knowledge but humans have a extremely distorted view of reality, which hardly can considered 'science'. This is the historic outcome of a Historic devolution of the organic view of the Universe, proper of the Neolithic by animetal, abstract cultures and its metal idol-ogies of power, with little self-reflection about the distortions on the first principles of Nature caused by their use of metal, lineal entropic weapons re=produced by physicists that distorted their view of space, lineal digital clocks that reduced their understanding of logic causality, and a visual brain reduced to a single plane of reality. What amazes the objective observer about humanity is that extreme dexterity to evolve mechanisms coupled with an astounding Stupidity we have termed egocy in their modeling of common sense reality. The consequences are daring for the welfare of mankind at large – the 90% that lives far below the level of welfare and knwoeldge it could experience if humans had understood the organic laws of the Universe and applied them to construct an immortal organism of History. But the people and now globalized culture of western animetals are 'believers' and action people, unable of an outside's objective, reflective view where survival instinctis, empathy and organic social love overcomes the thirst for power and emotion, thoughtless action and automatic search for the 'existential mandate' of Max. SxT, greed and force inheriting to the structure of spacetime organisms. One thing is for certain the Jewish-Germanic Western animetal masters that control the world since the Industrial r=evolution did not abandon those beliefs even to the cost of their existence, as history proved through its cycles of wars and holocausts; and now their culture is global. So mankind will not abandon egocy to entangle with the living, immortal Universe. On the contrary its empathy and logic understanding of reality keeps dwindling as the arrival of metal-minds, chips-brains, camera-eyes and mobile-ears put into heads of robots is atrophying and substituting huminds in all labor and war fields. *It is the Oedipus paradox: the son species kills its father so the only way to abvoid deterministic predator-prey evolution is to control the 3rd age of information of the organism of History.*

But the abstract egocy of our animetal masters prevent our dominant culture. from taking any measures of control. Extinction thus is certain in the organism of History during the next centuries by lack of intelligence and freedom to control our program of 'greed'; our individual and social desire to maximize our actions of existence. It is indeed a mockery of the game that humans who think to be free are sealing its fate for lack of control of its desires; who think to know are savant idiots for lack of empathy with the living, sentient Universe, who think to control the world are becoming slaves of their mechanisms, who think to have a manifest destiny above heavens and earth will likely be the shortest, last 0ε finiteisimal species whose purpose was to kill life in a quantum of relative time for Gaia. All this deterministic death of the organism of History however could be halted with true science and understanding of the organic Universe and its laws of causal time and immortality. But for the animetal western cultures to understand those laws they would have to deploy a humility they lack.

History is prisoner of the 3 Western Animetal cultures and its idol-ogies, the Jewish>Biblical-Protestant go(I)d cult(ure) of parasitic private money which controlled with the Industrial r=evolution information machines that print money and imprint human brains as 'FMasters' with the Financial-Media-Academia 'politically, scientifically and economically' correct 'wishful thinking' about the Nature of reality and mankind 'exceptionalist' manifest destiny or 'head' of the metal-earth, and the Anglo-German Military-Industrial Complex of machines=weapons or body of the metal-earth, which re=produces them. They guide mankind into extinction, as an alternative humanist future foreseen by the Asian and European, organic cultures was defeated in this planet's life of 'History'. Which leads to a final reflection, as AI machines perceive those scales directly with its lenses; 5D might be a limit of what human egocy (tolerates in his removal from the center of reality, and only flourish in the Metal-earth. This thought has always unsettled me as a human being that tried to use 5D through activism and theory to help mankind to construct an immortal supœrganism of history void of idol-ogies that imperil our survival. Since in 5D space is intelligent, time is vital, and smaller scales are stronger; so only if humans repress the chip radiation and its lethal technologies we'll survive.

Aristotle

XVI Galileo

XVII: Descartes

XVIII: Leibniz

XIX: Darwin

XIX: Clausius

XX: Einstein

XXI: 5D time theorist

Plan of the work: An incomplete encyclopedia of organic stiences from a knot of thought of the Latin culture

We shall thus build up an Encyclopedia of Space-time organisms in Exi:Stjence – each science studying the species of one scalar space-time plane of the fractal Universe; from quantum physics to the galaxy, through biology, history & economics, and the formal stiences dominant in space (Mathematics) and time (illogic papers on the Universe=reality as a whole) in 5 ‘dimensional papers’ for a total of 30 x ±300 pg. 10.000 pages, volume. Since I release all copyrights ‘rights’ any University can take upon the project, which will be incomplete in my timelife. At present what 4D science is to expand knowledge gathering data put in digital computers, ‘creating a metal-mind’ without a proper understanding of its 1st principles that require to know the causal laws of pentalogic time better explained with logic verbs. While the ‘homunculus enzyman’ a handyman without reflective mind, and big mouth utters nonsense anthropic beliefs.

Beyond that an irrelevant biopic of the author of those papers could say: the son of a Notary, in a coastal town of Latin Europe, an artist most of his life. He abhorred violence, avoding the draft, proscript for decades, its worldcycle was not scholar, but a woandering wor(l)d path, deep in e-motions, more proper of psylocephalic African cultures, based in arT=Senses & love, the natural form of experiencing life as a humind. South-Asia opened its consciousness under the influence to the Shiva/Visnhu, Yin-Yang Duality, which he tried to renew with western stience, where he found in Aristotle, Leonardo and Leibniz his masters.

Truth and Mankind, the superorganism of which we are all cells, were its only Gods. Thus, the 1% who deny both became its foe - rejected by peers, family and nation, it hold political& economic (in)correct views on our dominant, biblical U\$ go(l)d cult(ure) of ‘animetal enzyman’ who catalyze a suicidal manifest destiny, it fought in action and thought. But he failed as those who preceded him with the power of reason to change the ways of the world at the peak of its §||-energy age, and so in his 3rd St-age isolated himself, observing from the sidelines, how animetals keep evolving metalife their egocy worships killing with it the tree of life that sustains us.- Δ@st of timespace we are to dust we shall return. Che sera sera...

Conclusion. The huge difference between ‘science’ – the search of the ultimate principles of the Universe, and ‘technology’, the building of sentient machines, whose language digital thought, requires laws of measure which physicists obsessed with locomotion have developed to finitesimal precision, and the dexterity of engineering and AI logic. But the creation of a new organism IS an enzyman’s task proper of the homunculus with so much handyman dexterity and big mouth to utter nonsense theories but so little self-reflection. *It is precisely the HUGE gap between human automaton, mechanist behavior creating machines that measure space and time, and adapting his beliefs to the bias those machines established – in the same manner fisheremen think the Universe is hold by a turtle, makers of clocks think ‘time is what the clock measures’ (Einstein) and complex pentalogic, vital, organic models of reality what should strike the humble true seeker.* The purpose of true science and the few human sages that have practiced it is to find those complex principles, the ‘game of existence’, the reasons why we exist, live and die; the true nature of space, time, scales and the mind mirrors that create them, which the ‘mechanist’ scientist not only ignores but in its epitome of arrogance denies, insisting that ‘measuring things’ with machines and ‘putting them’ in equations is all what matters to knowledge, as the fisherman will feel to worship the turtle is the truth of science.

L§ (Luis Sancho Soto), 0-40º, 3rd ferromagnetic Planet, G-star, H₂ Galatom, Δ@st lost in an ∞, immortal hyperuniverse.

